

LANDMARC

Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

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Changes with respect to the DoA	A key feature in this task and deliverable were the in-person workshops. The pandemic along with the need to synchronise with linked tasks and activities in other WPs resulted in delays and two iterations of changes to the approach between 2020 and 2022, but eventually the in-person workshops were held in 2023, with the content following closely the original plans. See Section 3 for details on deviations in approach.
Dissemination and uptake	Public

Short Summary of results

This report documents analysis and stakeholder engagement conducted at regional level for Africa, Asia, Europe and Latin America. A particular sub-region was chosen in each case, including East Africa, Southeast Asia, European Union, and the Amazon Treaty countries. The results provide a regional perspective on raising ambition for land-based carbon dioxide removal (CDR) and narratives as to how regional engagement can enhance global impact through land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs). Preparatory work involving literature reviews, surveys, interviews, and stakeholder consultations showed that although stakeholders have limited awareness of LMTs, they are aware of the wide range of social and environmental impacts of LMTs and tend to prefer nature-based LMTs over technology-based LMTs. At the same time, there is also recognition that in order to achieve global impact, the more novel LMTs that also involve significant infrastructure investment, namely BECCs, will be needed in some world regions when aiming for high climate ambition, i.e. to reach the 1.5° or 2°C targets of the Paris Agreement. During stakeholder workshops at which modelling/simulation results for each respective sub-region were presented, participants envisioned various mechanisms and pathways through breakout discussions on CDR/climate ambition and regional engagement. The stakeholder views were distilled into four sets of narratives, which, when taken together, describe the evolution of CDR/climate ambition and how regional engagement can facilitate such ambitions.

Evidence of accomplishment

This report itself and its annexes, and also: two surveys conducted during 2022-2023; approximately 80 interviews conducted during 2023; four online regional consultations held in Sept-Oct 2022; and four in-person/hybrid workshops held in Oct-Nov 2023.

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the European Union (EU), Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g. climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Executive summary

Land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) are currently the main contributors to carbon removal, which is critical for climate stabilisation in the long term. There is considerable heterogeneity in the socio-economic and environmental impacts of LMTs as well as the underlying requirements for deployment, replication and scaling up. This report provides a stakeholder-based perspective at the regional level in investigating how climate ambition for LMTs can be scaled up. In particular, we evaluate regional engagement for global impact from implementing LMTs across four world regions.

Preparatory activities were conducted through multiple channels or means, including literature review, stakeholder interviews and consultations, and stakeholder surveys. In the surveys and interviews, we queried respondents on the priorities, impacts and implementation of LMTs within their regional context. The results suggested a general awareness on impacts and trade-offs and a preference for nature-based LMTs rather than those requiring significant technology and infrastructure, i.e. BECCS.

These preparatory activities supported a common design for a workshop that included a number of features aimed at eliciting a broad perspective rather than an expert view, and we developed a background review document so as to allow participants to prepare for the workshop with a common understanding of the key issues for LMTs in their region. In addition to this background review, participants in each region also received the preliminary results of land use/climate modelling/simulation runs that were structured on the principle of two future scenarios along with the baseline case. These two scenarios were associated with the 1.5° and 2°C targets embodied in the UNFCCC Paris Agreement.

For the implementation of the in-person or hybrid workshops, a team in each region (all of whom were based in each of the respective regions), had facilitators and rapporteurs for multiple breakout groups so as to establish multiple perspectives from both an individual stakeholder view and from the small group interactive discussions, with each small group numbering between 5 and 8 and the total number of groups being either two or three. The two sets of breakout groups addressed separately the two dimensions of regional engagement and CDR/climate ambition.

The outputs from the workshops were used to create a set of narratives for each region that together provide a regional perspective on raising ambition for land-based carbon dioxide removal (CDR). The stakeholder views were distilled into four sets of narratives, which together describe the evolution of CDR/climate ambition and how regional engagement can facilitate such ambitions. and how regional engagement can enhance global impact through land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs).

Although the results are qualitative and do not have wide statistical relevance, considering the tremendous diversity of stakeholders and the LMTs of interest, the results nevertheless suggest linkages between regional engagement and climate ambition for CDR that are worth exploring further in consideration of the increasing pressure for climate response across all world regions to meet the climate stabilisation aims of the Paris Agreement.

1 Overview and objectives

This brief overview section provides the context and objectives for Deliverable D6.2, which is based mainly on Task 6.3. Among the five tasks in WP6, Task 6.3 on regional/continental engagement occupied the majority of the total person months in WP6. The considerable effort required was due to the labour-intensive nature of designing and implementing engagement and stakeholder consultation at regional levels instead of the national level where such engagements and consultations are much more common (with the partial exception of the EU). In LANDMARC, we define the regional level as transnational, i.e. geographical areas spanning multiple countries based on physical proximity and/or economic relations. Task 6.3 was designed to be well-integrated with the other WP6 tasks and several tasks within other WPs to the extent feasible and appropriate. This section therefore provides a short sketch of the relation with the other WPs and/or tasks, followed by the overall approach and objectives. Although WP6 operates at regional rather than national level, the national case studies (coordinated through WP2) provided inputs and shared some stakeholders, design features, and implementation approaches with the analysis and engagement conducted at regional level, based on those LMTs and stakeholders in the respective regions that had regional and/or international relevance, potential or significance.

1.1 Overview for WP6

The LANDMARC research program spans all scales from the local parcel level to the global scale in analysing land-use based mitigation technologies (LMT). WP6 addresses primarily the regional or continental level and the issue of scaling up from national level. The literature review (Task 6.1 and Deliverable D6.1) provided basic information on the applicability, barriers, and potential of LMTs across different regions, while the stakeholder repository (Task 6.2) facilitated the initial identification and characterisation of stakeholders who have knowledge at regional, continental and/or transnational levels. Based on the results from Task 6.1 and Task 6.2, the engagement actions and workshops (Task 6.3) provide the platform for stakeholder co-production of scaling scenarios of LMT portfolios (Task 6.4 and D6.3), including both qualitative storylines or narratives for each region and technical analysis using the LANDMARC modelling tools. Land-use modelling of the scenarios (LandSHIFT-G) coupled to earth-system modelling (EC-Earth3-CC) and modelling of techno/social-economics (E3ME) provide the analytical basis for scaling up LMTs, and linking across WPs 5, 6 and 7. Finally, the capacity gap analysis (Task 6.5 and Deliverable D6.4) identified barriers and opportunities to refine the LMT outlook and qualify achievable potentials within the context of LMT design and implementation across the respective regions. A key aim in linking across the tasks is to build up the analysis across the associated levels and regions for both the techno-economic and the socio-economic context.

1.2 Task 6.3 Objectives

LANDMARC case studies across the other WPs (2, 4, 5) are built up around local technical studies and national level case studies, whereas WP6 and especially Task 6.3 aims to provide a regional and/or continental perspective, i.e., some indication of how LMTs might be applied or scaled up in regional, transnational or continental context. The focus is primarily on investigating issues that impact LMT implementation and scaling, particularly those that cross national boundaries in various ways.

Alongside the background research, the task includes also synthesising and incorporating stakeholder perspectives rather than addressing in detail specific technical, biophysical, or socio-economic variables. The task aims to mediate between the LMT portfolio/scenario analysis developed in case studies at national/local level (WP4) and the results of global models (Task 6.4 and WP7) evaluating changes in LMT implementation and the implications for carbon sequestration and climate mitigation. Although the feedback from stakeholders at regional level is by necessity almost exclusively qualitative in that it should provide a regional and/or continental narrative, a secondary aim is also to use this qualitative information to make the land/climate modelling results more realistic. There is also an associated aim of transnational or intra-regional knowledge-sharing to consider innovation and learning opportunities in each region, which in turn contribute to global systems or platforms (Binz & Truffer, 2017) . Therefore, we can break down three sub-objectives:

- (1) Investigate stakeholder perspectives on LMT portfolios in a regional, transnational and/or continental context, in order to develop (for each region) a set of alternative **regional/continental narratives** for future development of LMTs..
- (2) Elicit regional/continental stakeholder views on priority and **feasibility of different LMTs to inform the configuration of alternative scenarios or pathways** in the coupled land-use modelling framework and fill gaps arising from the limited number and type of case studies.
- (3) **Engage stakeholders in discussions** at regional/continental level **for knowledge-sharing** on the deployment of LMT portfolios and the associated drivers and impacts.

These three objectives guide the implementation of Task 6.3. It will be important to keep in mind that this task has these three different and complementary aims.

1.3 Geographical scope and definition of regions

For the first (online) set of consultations or engagement actions (see Section 4.4), the geographical scope was broad, and included Africa, Asia, Latin America, and a global North consultation (Europe + Canada, due to the LANDMARC case studies). In this way it was possible to capture regional perspectives from some large countries that were not included as LANDMARC case studies (e.g. Brazil, India, China) as well as some sub-regions (e.g. West Africa) that differ significantly from other sub-regions within a given continent. More info is provided on these online consultations in section 4.4.

For the in-person/hybrid workshops(which ended up being about one year after the online consultations), a more nuanced approach was taken in choosing the region of focus. This approach allowed for more coherence compared to continental level, which is too large and diverse in economic and physical terms (especially in Africa and Asia). Based on initial literature review and consultations, we identified differences in regional priorities for different LMTs and/or approaches to carbon removal and land-based mitigation. We also considered the different agro-ecological zones across different regions and the climate science/policy context with respect to economic cooperation and regional engagement levels. For Europe, Africa and Asia, it was therefore appropriate to use the most relevant sub-region for economic cooperation. For Latin America, due to the strong focus on forest-related LMTs, we considered the countries of the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO), which is

an intergovernmental organization for cooperation on the Amazon river basin and rainforest. The country list is given in Annex D7: Regional-Country definitions.

- Europe: European Union (EU)
- Africa: East African Community (EAC)
- Asia: Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)
- Latin America: Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO)

The definition of different regions for the stakeholder workshops and the modelling needed to be consistent and coherent in terms of the overall framing of LMTs and their deployment or implementation. Therefore, when presenting results of the coupled model simulations (which are always global, to capture the physical climate interactions) we used the above regional definitions when discussing results. Thus, not all LANDMARC case studies could be fully included where they were outside the focus (e.g. Canada). However, relevant country and case study experiences from outside the region were considered in the workshop design where appropriate (e.g. Nepal for Asia) and also because of the big countries in each region (section 3.1.1). The details for regional context are provided in sections 6 and the details for workshop design and implementation in section 7.

1.4 Brief outline for this document/report

The remaining sections provide the full documentation, including approach, methods, preparatory activities, workshop design and results, with particular focus on Task 6.3, as follows:

- Section 2 provides the broad background on the approach, especially for stakeholder engagement.
- Section 3 provides an overview of deviations from the Grant Agreement, in terms of changes made to the approach, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and changes in other tasks or WPs.
- Section 4 details the consultations and related activities carried out in preparation for the regional workshops.
- Section 5 provides the background and conceptual framework for research design for the regional workshops, including the scope of regional/continental engagement actions and the regional analysis to be undertaken across the four regions.
- Section 6 provides a summary of background or inception material given to the participants of each of the regional workshops ahead of time to frame the expectations and discussions.
- Section 7 describes the design and implementation of the regional workshops.
- Section 8 provides a brief synthesis of the stakeholder inputs for the four regions.
- Section 9 gives the regional narratives/storylines that emerged from discussions and analysis.
- Section 10 explains limitations and provides conclusions and recommendations for research.

The annexes (see: LIST OF ANNEXES) for this report are extensive, due to the qualitative nature of this work and the need to address all regions. They are grouped into five sets (A, B, C, D, E), with each corresponding to a different phase or component, namely: Consultations, Regional Interviews, Inception/Background Reports, Regional Workshops, Big country reports.

2 Review on Stakeholder approaches

Many different forms of stakeholder engagement have been used in interdisciplinary research. Some approaches provide primarily one-way feedback to stakeholders whereas others aim for deep integration of stakeholders into the front end of the research process (see section 2.1). A full integration of stakeholders into the research process is generally viewed as research “co-production” or *transdisciplinary* research, which has been identified as important in research aiming at a “Just Transition” in achieving climate goals (Cronin et al., 2021).

For Task 6.3, a full co-production or transdisciplinary approach was outside the scope, budget, and proposal preparation process as it would require a pre-proposal phase with deep and extensive involvement of diverse stakeholders. We did, however, include and consult stakeholders during the preparation of the research proposal, thus accommodating the inclusion of some stakeholders’ perspectives, especially those drawn from partners’ previous/existing collaborations. Thus, the identification and incorporation of stakeholders into the research process is also the subject of each WP, accomplished at the case study level (mainly local and national) and then complemented at the regional level. More specifically, in the stakeholder engagement process in WP6, we incorporate stakeholder views in a consistent way at regional level to inform the overall results and thereby provide a coherent structure for stakeholder input and feedback that will be used to refine and/or improve the qualitative and quantitative analysis.

This section provides a brief and broad introductory literature review on participatory and stakeholder approaches, with particular reference to the regional and global stakeholder engagement in LANDMARC WP6 and Task 6.3. The literature review in Task 6.1 as well as the literature reviews for Tasks 6.3 and 6.5 have provided a rationale for the overall structure of the approach and provides the basis for the adaptations and updates made in the implementation of Task 6.3.

2.1 Participatory methods and knowledge co-production

The traditional science production model has been critiqued for failing to inform environmental management and decision making in an effective way, because it consciously separates science, policy, and society in ways that inhibit the use of science for problem solving (Djenontin & Meadow, 2018). In that model, the emphasis has been on scientists alone to identify an issue or problem, carry out the research and then deliver the knowledge to society (Norström et al., 2020). Interest in a knowledge co-production approach has sharply increased in climate sciences, climate change adaptation and broadly in environmental management and governance, since the traditional model is deemed to fall short when it comes to addressing wicked problems (Djenontin & Meadow, 2018; Norström et al., 2020; Salter et al., 2010; Villamor et al., 2022).

Knowledge co-production is part of an evolving cluster of participatory, transdisciplinary, and mission-oriented problem-solving research approaches, although their conceptualization and implementation are highly variable (Norström et al., 2020). All the methods of knowledge co-production in this cluster aim to increase the relevance and usability of science for society, to break down the unidirectional and linear traditional collaboration and participation structures, and to better address complex problems (Djenontin & Meadow, 2018; Norström et al., 2020).

One basic definition is provided by Norström et al. (2020): *'Iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future.'*

Djenontin & Meadow (2018) apply a similar definition borrowed from Lemos and Morehouse (2005) which does not mention the iterative element, but matches the elements of contributions by diverse stakeholders spanning the science–policy–society interface aiming to inform environmental decision-making.

The growing body of research on co-production of knowledge suggests that the driving force behind the success of the approach is the direct connection and collaboration between researchers and practitioners (whether policymakers or on-the-ground resource managers) (Djenontin & Meadow, 2018). Norström et al. (2020) state that for co-production of knowledge to be successful, it should be context-based, pluralistic, goal-oriented, and interactive. Other factors of importance identified through research are the inclusion of participation in the design of the research project, the systematic selection of stakeholders to ensure accurate representation, a high level of engagement, and a focus on tangible and timely results (Meadow et al., 2015). A research process that meaningfully includes diverse stakeholders and their knowledge base can contribute to equitable knowledge co-production (Lieu et al., 2023). Absence of or insufficient attention for any of the considerations that are crucial to a successful co-production, such as interaction between actors that remains superficial, can inhibit fruitful coproduction of knowledge (Meadow et al., 2015).

If the co-production process is successful, the generated knowledge can be more useful than that generated through the traditional scientific model, since it may be more acceptable to policy makers, more transparent and legitimate, easier to integrate with existing information, and tailored to relevant spatial and temporal scales (Meadow et al., 2015; Villamor et al., 2022).

Despite the accumulated knowledge and guidance, researchers and practitioners continue to struggle with the complexities involved with collaborative, multi-party, and transdisciplinary research (Kirchhoff et al., 2013), with some describing the approach as vague and ambiguous in practice and lacking empirical implementation strategies (Djenontin & Meadow, 2018). A considerable amount of time is needed not only in establishing such processes but also for self-reflection to determine how they can be effectively applied (Podestá et al., 2013). It is important that co-production efforts are fit-for-purpose, and that scientific analysis or modelling is not oversimplified for the sake of showing that stakeholders have been included. Furthermore, there are trade-offs in the process, since the process of model development is also quite time-consuming: it may be the case that increased efforts on measures of deep interest to stakeholders may not have significant effects on the key objective (i.e. carbon removal through LMTs), thus possibly diverting effort from other LMTs that have greater effect (see D6.3 for discussion on adjustments made to LMT modelling for WP6 in response to stakeholders).

Knowledge co-production and participatory approaches have become widespread and diverse practices in the environmental studies arena. A crucial point made by Meadow et al. (2015) is the importance of assessing which research questions require end-user perspectives to find a solution and which can rest on a linear-science model before engaging in participatory research activities. The study

then presents five approaches to collaborative research that can be used to structure a co-production process, known as action research, transdisciplinarity, rapid assessment process, Participatory Integrated Assessment (PIA), and boundary organizations. Each approach suits a different type of research or management question, decision-making context, and resources and skills available to contribute to the process of engagement. PIA is a problem-based research approach centred around the added value of direct stakeholder participation in assessment processes involving complex problems. For instance, in climate change assessment, PIA can help to overcome the lack of capacity to encompass many qualitative elements pertaining to society, culture, and policy of the computer models that account for biophysical processes. Additional arguments for PIA besides improving the quality of the outcomes are the right of stakeholders to participate in scientific processes, and the increased acceptance and uptake of co-produced results (Salter et al., 2010).

2.2 Application to LANDMARC stakeholder engagement

PIA is relevant for LANDMARC as it allows for a flexible selection of participants and the inclusion of diverse and wide-ranging stakeholders from policymakers to the general public, the integration of stakeholder knowledge in a mix of qualitative and quantitative exercises such as scenario-planning and modelling. In addition, PIA offers a multitude of participation mechanisms such as open meetings, workshops, focus groups, interviews, site visits etc. (Meadow et al., 2015; Villamor et al., 2022).

Scenarios are common components of PIAs and can be effective tools for summarising and synthesising scientific knowledge in a shape that can be used by policymakers. They help visualising the different aspects and connections of an environmental problem, as well as its large time and space scales (Alcamo et al., 2001; Salter et al., 2010; van Vliet & Kok, n.d.). Scenarios can be categorized as exploratory or anticipatory. Exploratory scenarios, or descriptive scenarios, start in the present and explore trends into the future. Anticipatory, normative, or prescriptive scenarios start with a set future outcome based on goals or targets and backcast to identify a pathway to that future (Alcamo et al., 2001; Salter et al., 2010). Within WP6, we expect a mixture of the two, as we need to anchor to the goals of the UNFCCC and Paris Agreement (anticipatory) but also explore different futures (Section 5 outlines the approach to workshops while LANDMARC D6.3 provides the modelling approach).

Environmental studies can benefit from using qualitative as well as quantitative scenarios. Using both qualitative and quantitative methodology in a single scenario exercise can allow to benefit from the different advantages that each approach offers. Generally, advantages of qualitative scenarios are that they are more easily understood and allow for the participation and contribution of a wide range of stakeholders and experts. Quantitative scenarios are beneficial since their output consists of numerical values that are sometimes necessary, and that the process of achieving a result is more comprehensible and reproducible. The Story and Simulation method recommends steps for obtaining and integrating mixed qualitative and quantitative information, covering the selection of participants, the first draft of scenarios, the iterative process of improvements, the quantification of qualitative information, and finally the distribution of final scenarios (Alcamo, 2008).

Combining quantitative and qualitative approaches, however, also presents a set of challenges related to the translation of qualitative information obtained from stakeholders into quantitative model input

data both on the technical question of parameters to be used, as well as the degree of stakeholder participation in this part of the process (Alcamo, 2008; Salter et al., 2010; van Vliet & Kok, n.d.; Villamor et al., 2022).

Van Vliet & Kok (n.d.) also raise the issue of scale. It is important for assessments to cover multiple scales due to the potential differences between different scales when it comes to drivers, processes, effects, and actors, as well as the relations and interactions between scales. However, well-developed formal approaches for linking scenarios across scales? are still missing. So far there are mostly examples of large/global scale scenarios downscaling to lower scales being subject to the risk of incorporating inconsistent information from smaller scales into larger scale storylines (van Vliet & Kok, n.d.). Hard-linking models is time-intensive, even as results are uncertain. Furthermore, obtaining a representative set of stakeholders is normally only feasible at quite small scales rather than across scales, and thus our approach here tends towards using qualitative stakeholder work to fill in evidence gaps.

2.3 Key attributes of LANDMARC Task 6.3 approach

The information elicited from LANDMARC stakeholders will directly shape the qualitative exploratory scenarios and also contribute indirectly, for selected aspects and components, to the modelling. As opposed to participatory modelling, this approach does not entail the direct participation of stakeholders in the construction and use of the model. Instead, participants provide feedback when presented with assumptions and initial outputs of the models, followed by discussions in which they can share further thoughts on assumptions, criteria, and indicators (Salter et al., 2010). Some examples of tools that are applied to structure and elicit information, and facilitate the quantification of storylines during interactive PIA stakeholder activities are Bayesian networks, causal loop diagrams, Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCM), and Multi Criteria Analysis (MCA) (Alcamo, 2008; van Vliet & Kok, n.d.; Villamor et al., 2022). It may also be feasible to use simpler tools or algorithms, since the sample sizes may be small and/or because of constraints in the identification and characterisation of stakeholders. Moreover, the discussion with stakeholders itself will need to be non-technical when the stakeholder group is diverse.

The LANDMARC Task 6.3 stakeholder engagement methodology is thus generally inspired by PIA And emphasises three of the key elements identified from the literature, , which were modified for the prevailing conditions:

- (1) **Iterative process:** particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic and the need to rely mostly on online engagement, it became necessary to have more than one consultation or engagement in a given region, especially since land-based mitigation is relatively new compared to rather well-established climate mitigation measures in other sectors such as energy. More time would be needed to identify and engage stakeholders, especially since input from other LANDMARC WPs/tasks is needed, and these tasks follow their own timeline and/or may also have been impacted and/or delayed.
- (2) **Diversity of stakeholders:** the approach in Task 6.3 needs to include a diverse group of stakeholders (e.g. land use managers, technology providers, industry experts, etc.) in addition

to experts/researchers. Otherwise, the exercise would be more like traditional scientific research to support land/climate modelling, which is not the primary purpose of Task 6.3. The diversity of stakeholders means that feedback from stakeholders does not feed directly into models, but rather provides qualitative descriptions, which would need to be further interpreted to be used in land/climate modelling.

- (3) Story and Simulation:** the “story” is elicited from stakeholders, consisting of a set of structured narratives for different LMT scenarios, along with the associated enablers and barriers of those scenarios. The largely qualitative feedback from stakeholders can nevertheless also be used to provide guidance for the coupled land/climate model, thereby addressing the “simulation” that complements the story or narrative.

LANDMARC stakeholders will thus contribute with mainly qualitative inputs to the creation of exploratory scenarios and thus indirectly improve the land/climate modelling through iterative interactions via diverse participation mechanisms and tools. The engagement of diverse stakeholders in scenario and narrative building in different world regions—combined with a methodology to translate some of these inputs into useful guidance for land-use modelling (given in greater detail in LANDMARC D6.3)—enhances LANDMARC results in several ways:

- The regional narratives or storylines have value as stand-alone research results in that they facilitate a comparative cross-regional and/or transnational view on LMTs;
- Stakeholder input can be structured to provide some guidance for the land/climate models so that these results better reflect the feasibility for scaling and deployment;
- The elicitation of stakeholder information on national to regional scaling contributes to ongoing policy processes that aim to enhance climate ambitions or improve climate actions;

The literature reviews conducted at national, regional and global level inform the overall approach, and thus the stakeholder input along with the results of the land/climate modelling provides a triangularisation of inputs, evidence and methods. The particular structure of the approach to Task 6.3 and how it evolved or deviated is provided in the next section.

3 Deviations in Task 6.3 and D6.2

In this section, we briefly explain the original approach (from the Grant Agreement) for Task 6.3, the updated approach, and any deviations in thematic, methodological, or geographical terms. We also enumerate methodological and thematic gaps that were identified either as a result of work within the task and WP6 or across multiple WPs.

1.1 Modifications/adaptations in overall approach

The original approach had three main components, briefly described below and depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.**

1. The first phase was to be preparatory, including literature and policy reviews, surveys/interviews, initial engagements, and receipt of information from national cases and land/climate modelling, which also needed to be interpreted and prepared in a way that is suitable for a diverse stakeholder audience.

2. The second phase was to be centred mainly around in-person regional workshops that developed regional narratives and elicited information to guide the land/climate modelling.
3. The third phase involved follow-up and feeding into global policy processes and analyses as feasible and appropriate.

The approach was adapted several times in substantive and logistical terms, between 2021 and 2023, and was subject to several delays, due to changing conditions, especially associated with the COVID-19 pandemic:

- Due to the pandemic and continuing uncertainty around in-person events, reliance on one in-person workshop for each region was deemed risky. As the pandemic deepened and in light of significant differences in vaccine availability across the different regions that needed to be covered in WP6 (Europe, Asia, Africa, Latin America), it was assumed that in-person workshops would have to be avoided altogether and that 2-3 online consultations would be used instead.
- Given the aim to elicit information from stakeholders that could provide guidance for the land/climate models, availability of the baseline model results could help to anchor the stakeholder elicitation process, and therefore Tasks 6.3 and 6.4 were to be better aligned, for the stakeholder and modelling processes, respectively. The timeline needed to be extended by several months to allow for this alignment without affecting other tasks and WPs.
- However, after the first online consultations during September-October 2022, the approach was re-evaluated. It was determined that in-person or hybrid workshops would be much more effective, due to the difficulty in attracting online participants, the need for more time for discussions to include the model results, and the need for more in-depth discussions (see the revised approach in Figure 2). As the pandemic restrictions eased by the end of 2022, it was decided to hold in-person or hybrid workshops during the second half of 2023.

Figure 1: Task 6.3 and WP6 original structure as planned in the Grant Agreement

Figure 2: Updated/modified structure/approach for Task 6.3 and WP6

The adapted approach effectively has six different components (see Figure 2) although there was some overlap in their implementation. The first five components are included in this deliverable whereas Component 6 includes various dissemination activities at cross-regional and global levels, in cooperation with ongoing activities and deliverables in WP7 that are to be completed during the final planned months (M43-M48) of LANDMARC. The dependence on information from other tasks arose from the national focus in case studies and modelling. The higher level (regional or continental) used information from the lower level (i.e., national case study results; therefore, where appropriate, the approach and timeline was also adjusted in some cases in line with changes in national case study efforts in WP 2 and WP5.

3.1 Thematic or methodological gaps or shortcomings

Thematic or methodological changes in the approach have been due to gaps or shortcomings partly identified with respect to certain characteristics mentioned in the GA. Other changes were made based on the knowledge gained during the first two years of LANDMARC within WP6 but also in relevant tasks associated with case studies in WP2 (stakeholder engagement), WP5 (national models scaling up), and global modelling in WP7. The main gaps or shortcomings identified are summarised below.

3.1.1 Big countries

One gap that was identified in the original LANDMARC approach (as represented in the Grant Agreement) was that, with the exception of Indonesia and Canada, case studies are located in countries

with relatively small land masses where the potential for land-based mitigation is quite modest. The implementation of LMT portfolios at the national level from these small countries will not significantly affect results at continental and/or global levels. With the current LANDMARC setup, the regional and global results from the coupled model will, therefore, not properly reflect the significant LMT implications of the world's "big countries" with respect to land and/or population. According to Roe et al. (2021), approximately ten countries account for more than half of the world's LMT potential. However, WP6 was not designed or expected to gather information at national level, nor was there effort allocated under other WPs to gather such information for countries beyond the LANDMARC case studies. Any additional effort in this regard is thus outside the scope of work for LANDMARC; but was considered useful to complement the storylines or narratives developed, and where feasible, to allow the regional and global modelling results to be more useful.

We therefore have done a limited analysis for a few countries with major land areas, including a review and interviews/inputs from stakeholders. We chose one country in each of the major regions of the global South (sub-Saharan Africa, Asia and Latin America) where the potential is concentrated: Brazil, China and the Democratic Republic of Congo. Results compiled or available for these countries are alluded to briefly in this report and are given or explained in more detail in:

Annex D7: Regional-Country definitions

Annex E: Big country reports. Another change in LANDMARC compared to the original proposal (though not falling under WP6) was the addition of Ukraine as a case study within WP2 and WP5, and since Ukraine has the largest potential for land-based mitigation in Europe, some input from analysis in Ukraine was considered within the European workshop. The results from these "big countries" thus served to complement the other analyses, albeit in a limited and qualitative manner that differed somewhat in each case.

3.1.2 Relation of case study LMTs to regional analysis

The national case studies were designed as "deep dives" into local and national LMTs but should also inform as far as possible the regional and continental perspectives. However, there are three shortcomings that arise in scaling from these national cases:

- (1) Some continents/regions (North America and South America) only had one case study country and it is by definition difficult to gain any transnational insights from one country.
- (2) Some of the chosen LMTs in case study countries may not be prioritised at the regional or continental level.
- (3) Some case study LMTs are not among those that can be analysed in the coupled model;

This last issue (3) is addressed by considering those LMTs for inclusion in the regional narrative or storyline where this is appropriate and especially if stakeholders feel that it is important for the region. However, the LMTs included in the qualitative narrative should not diverge too significantly from those used in the model as it would then become harder to incorporate the quantitative results to complement those narratives, i.e., the abovementioned approach (Section 2) of maintaining some alignment between the "story" and the "simulation." Another minor deviation from the GA was that there were no separate activities (consultations or workshops) for North America, as there was not a

sufficient basis (nor funding) for including the U.S. or other North American countries. For (1) and (2), some effort has been made to complement with other information, but compared to the many person-months behind a national case study, the information will naturally be quite limited.

3.1.3 Analysing the regional LMT policy/stakeholder context

With the exception of the European Union, the multilateral climate regime is built almost exclusively on national frameworks and policies. There are comparatively few “continental” policy discussions about climate actions or policies in general and/or for LMTs in particular, for that matter. There are, however, some efforts of regional actions, regional learning and regional capacity building. Furthermore, intra-regional trade for LMT-related commodities and/or technologies is likely to have more significant implications for LMT portfolios or scenarios than international trade for goods and services not connected to land sectors (Zapata et al., 2022). There are a variety of reasons for this difference, including the bulkiness of biomass and inputs for agriculture and forestry, compared to higher value-added products and services in international markets.

Another reason that LMTs differ from mitigation in non-land sectors is that land and biomass mitigation actions tend to be more heterogeneous than actions in industrial and energy sectors where technologies are more uniform and portable. Regional economic cooperation as a means to support greater climate ambition fits well with the notion of regional engagement that improves, facilitates or upscales the deployment or implementation of LMTs. Moreover, regional cooperation on climate goals as well as linking with SDGs may lead to several co-benefits in terms of economic gains, increased security or improved knowledge sharing. Connecting the regional perspective to climate policy processes requires taking advantage of various opportunities for aligning regional stakeholder engagement processes to regional economic bodies (analogous to EU). The regional and transnational coordination bodies of UN and international organisations were valuable as both participants in engagement actions and recipients of findings, as discussed further in the next sections.

4 Preparatory activities for regional workshops

This section provides information on the inputs to the regional workshops carried out under Task 6.3, divided according to various components (Review, Consolidation, Consultations) as noted in Figure 2.

4.1 Review

This component included five different types of reviews:

- (i) Review of relevant literature on stakeholder engagement methods;
- (ii) Incorporation of the findings from the Literature review on LMT potentials, costs and barriers that was conducted in Task 6.1;
- (iii) Review on policy processes and institutions for regional stakeholder engagement;
- (iv) Review or identification of key stakeholders associated with relevant policy processes and institutions (alongside Task 6.2 that creates a stakeholder repository);
- (v) Capacity gaps literature review for Task 6.5? (and Deliverable 6.4)

These reviews established the basis for the overall approach and the structure for elicitation of key data from stakeholders. The findings from the literature review thus formed the basis on which surveys, interview questions, and discussion themes were then built.

The literature review for capacity needs/gaps ultimately included 48 articles (the majority of them peer-reviewed) discussing capacity gaps in the efforts for scaling up LMTs around the world. We used key word searches on google scholar (examples include 'agroforestry + capacity' or 'biochar + capacity + gap') pertaining to our chosen LMTs and the snowballing technique, i.e., where one source led to another to identify appropriate journal articles and grey literature.

Using the results from Task 6.2, we also conducted initial background analysis and short interviews or engagements to consider the different types of stakeholders and their differing perspectives, with special emphasis on the replication and/or scaling up of LMTs from local and national levels to regional and global levels. The results of these engagements are reflected in the enhanced Stakeholder repository (not released publicly due to GDPR rules) and in the subsequent regional interview choices and design (see Annex B: Regional Interviews). The aim was to obtain the most representative group for each of the four regions: (Africa, Asia, Nordic/North, and Latin America). There were also practical considerations in terms of giving emphasis to the case study countries and then aiming to complement these with regional actors.

4.2 Consolidation

In this second component, the results of the reviews were consolidated, and two surveys were designed and implemented. The first was the capacity gaps survey (Task 6.5, D6.4). The second was a pre-consultation survey that aimed to assess the state of knowledge across the stakeholder groups and regions in advance of the consultations.

4.2.1 Capacity gaps survey and interviews

The survey was conducted online between November 2021 and February 2022 and was anonymous unless specified otherwise by the respondents. Follow-up interviews of 30 to 60 minutes with non-anonymous respondents were scheduled after the survey was completed. From 22 survey questions in total, 8 were open-ended questions, while the rest were closed questions. Open questions were used so that respondents have the freedom to elaborate on some topics, but also clarify the reasons behind their answers to the closed questions. We ran a test session of the survey to ensure that the survey would be easy to answer by potential respondents. The respondents were asked to rank the capacity gaps and LMTs in terms of importance for their region. The scale was 1 (most important) to 10 (least important for capacity gaps). We then calculated the mean ranking and the standard deviation of the ranking responses. The survey was first sent to a selected number of experts knowledgeable about LMTs. Then, we used the extended LANDMARC network to increase the potential number of responses. In total, we received 64 responses.

After completion of the survey, 16 follow-up interviews were performed by the research team. The interviews were centred around questions that were exploring stakeholder views on preliminary survey results, as part of our triangulation approach. The interviewees were asked whether they agree

with the survey results and if not, to explain why and whether they have other perspectives on it. Additionally, interviewees were asked to provide their views on LMTs that could be most feasible and environmentally and economically attractive for adopters and private sector providers. Furthermore, other questions explored financing potential as well as the role that carbon markets could play for supporting expansion of LMTs. Transparent regulations and skills that might be lacking as capacity gaps were also discussed from the perspective of each of the LMTs and regions the interviewees were most knowledgeable about. In total, the interview protocol included 10 questions.

Deliverable D6.4 provides all the information relevant for the capacity gaps/needs survey. A journal article based on the deliverable was published in 2023 (Bößner et al., 2023).

4.2.2 Pre-consultation survey

An online survey (see Annex A1: Pre-consultation survey) was carried out with stakeholders prior to the regional consultations. This survey aimed to both familiarize the stakeholders with concepts that would be discussed in the workshops and also to provide initial long-term perspectives to stakeholders, inviting them to envisage the future for LMTs until 2050 and beyond.

Stakeholders were contacted and invited to the first round of regional consultations between May and August 2022. When invitations were sent out, participants also were requested to fill in the online survey. The online survey had the following key characteristics and aims:

- The first part aimed to understand the geographical knowledge of respondents, i.e. which country and region they knew most about, and they would be answering the survey for. It also focused on the respondents' knowledge about LMTs and the importance of six criteria for each LMT for their region:
 1. CO₂ removal potential
 2. climate risk exposure and permanence
 3. biodiversity and ecosystem services
 4. socio-economic impacts
 5. capacity for implementation
 6. public acceptance and citizen participation
- The second part of the survey asked respondents to rate the potential (or lack thereof) of each LMT against the six criteria mentioned above on a scale from 1 to 5, looking at the period from today until 2050.
- The third part of the survey asked respondents to rate the potential (or lack thereof) of each LMT against the six criteria mentioned above on a scale from 1 to 5, looking at the period from 2050 until 2100.
- Respondents were asked to provide any additional comments for each period of time, from today until 2050 and from 2050 until 2100.

The survey was translated into Spanish for the Latin American respondents. Respondent statistics are given in Table 1 in Section 4.4 and the full results in Annex A2: Pre-consultation survey results.

4.3 Summary of key survey results

This section highlights some of the initial findings and trends that could be identified through the survey results. The detailed results and some discussion are provided in Annex A2: Pre-consultation survey results and Annex A3: Pre-consultation survey results discussion, respectively.

The element that was generally considered to be crucial when it comes to the success of LMTs in the different regions, is the socio-economic impact of the development of any given LMT. The other factors that were considered rather important by most respondents were biodiversity and ecosystem services impacts, as well as the capacity for implementation and administration. Respondents generally indicated that elements such as CO₂ removal (CDR) potential, climate risk exposure and permanence potential, as well as public acceptance and citizen participation were also important, but the view that these are important to a lesser extent was slightly more common among respondents.

Afforestation/reforestation came out on top of the LMT list when respondents assessed cost-effective CDR. When it came to biochar, agroforestry, and organic agriculture, a larger share of respondents thought that potential to be lower. BECCS was deemed to have a good cost-effective CDR potential, but a larger share of respondents indicated not being knowledgeable about this technology.

Respondents' views on permanence of carbon capture reflected findings from literature, with afforestation/reforestation, and agroforestry offering the highest permanence potential, organic agriculture the lowest, and uncertainty with regard to the permanence potential of BECCS and biochar.

While all surveyed LMTs were generally considered to benefit the economy and society, BECCS and afforestation/reforestation were indicated to pose potential biodiversity and ecosystem services risks.

The relatively strong technological character and high infrastructural investment cost of technologies such as BECCS and biochar was reflected in respondents' answers about current capacity and institutional support, rating these technologies lower in terms of capacity for deployment. BECCS was singled out when it comes to public acceptance, as the only LMT with significantly limited acceptance.

Finally, respondents highlighted the fact that there is a large element of uncertainty that comes with projecting scenarios about the development of LMTs on a timescale of multiple decennia into the future. This was particularly the case for questions aimed at the more distant period 2050-2100, but was also mentioned for the period present-2050. Evaluations of the importance or impact of different elements regarding the LMTs or their potential were similar for both periods of time.

4.4 Stakeholder Consultation Approach

The consultations focused on identifying stakeholder views on LMT priorities across various criteria, drawing on the survey results and insights from national case studies. The continental engagements and/or workshops were planned to be held in Latin America, sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia and Europe. The regional/continental consultations had the following objectives:

- To place the national and local case studies within a regional or continental perspective;

- To elicit stakeholder feedback with respect to regional potential (both mitigation and permanence potential) of LMTs, regional barriers as well as regional opportunities for successful LMT implementation and scaling;
- To provide some initial ideas for preliminary assumptions for regional LMT scaling narratives and model runs.

As the preliminary results for the coupled models were not available, these could not be presented, and this limited somewhat the technical details that could be obtained in terms of baseline results vs. higher climate ambitions. Thus, we used the following basic principles for the consultation:

- The emphasis was on gaining a general understanding of stakeholder knowledge and priorities across different LMTs and the issues arising in deployment;
- Given the challenge to gather practitioners that are familiar with a range of LMTs, and yet specialised enough to provide new insights on specific LMTs, the first event was organized with the aim to engage a network of practitioners that could bring in some regional perspectives of relevance to LANDMARC.
- For practical reasons in relation to case study LMTs and for language reasons, the regions chosen were: Latin America, Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and North Europe + Canada.

Events were scheduled to last two hours, with the first thirty minutes having presentations on initial LANDMARC findings, especially national case studies and the results of the survey. Events were all planned to be held online, except for Latin America, where it was possible to hold a hybrid event, with enough participants based in Bogotá, Colombia. Break-out groups were divided along the following themes: Energy (BECCS and Biochar), Agriculture (organic farming, agroforestry) and Forestry. However, in Latin America, all LMTs were discussed simultaneously, with two groups online and one physically in the same location. Given the limited number of participants, there were no break-out groups for Africa. Discussions centred around the following key questions:

- What are the best practices in your region in terms of LMT adoption? What have you learned from it? Are these solutions transferrable to other countries?
- Which topics are the most important to promote and implement the LMT at a regional level?
- What are the limitations of your group's LMTs for its adoption in your region?
- What do you think regarding permanence of the CO₂ removal specific LMTs provide?
- What is the priority LMT for the first half of the century and for the second half? What learning curve/trend should we expect?

Table 1 presents the number of stakeholders that were invited to join and fill in the pre-consultation survey, the number of people who registered and the number of people who attended (excluding organisers). Email reminders were sent three times to invitees, for the event and the survey, some specific invitees were reminded personally over the phone. The events were recorded, and some details are given in Annex A4: Regional consultation presentation guide. The notes and guidance are found in Annex A5: Summary of regional consultation notes and Annex A6: Guidance questions for Consultations. An example of the facilitation guide for Asia is provided in: Annex A7: Facilitation Guide Asia example.

Table 1: Stakeholder response to survey and attendance to consultation

	Invited + Received Survey	Responded to survey	Registered to event	Date of event	External attendance
North Europe + Canada	57	11	20	01/09/22	9
Asia	125	7	50	20/09/22	22
Latin America*	86	14	41	05/10/22	29
Sub-Saharan Africa	68	10	15	27/10/22	7

*This event was hybrid (online and in-person while all others were fully online).

4.5 Summary/synthesis from Consultation results

This section highlights key points from the four regional stakeholder consultations that generally relate to LMT potential and implementation, and the relation to policies and carbon markets. Difficulties and limitations are discussed as well, with respect to the overall approach.

4.5.1 North Europe

- It is crucial to not only focus on carbon, not only get into fast-growing species, especially if implementing these will destroy soil and other ecosystem services.
- Carbon tax revenues could be allocated to land-owners taking action to raise the level of their carbon sink
- Consider the relationship between land-owners and land users.
- Financial opportunities: There are only a few finances/subsidy schemes/state aid with few strings attached. It is essential to focus on how to move something more nuanced without being too bureaucratic.
- Effective communication: there is a lot of technological expertise in the area of forest management, and we need to be able to share these solutions with a wider audience, especially with people that are not aware of a wide variety of options on what agroforestry looks like or what close to nature forestry looks like and be able to pilot and scale up those solutions;
- Climate models address tree planting or removals but cannot consider subtle changes resulting from shifts in forest management.
- More studies are needed to cover knowledge gaps, such as regarding permanence and stability. In this way, trust can be built for the quality of products (e.g. for biochar) in the market. Additionally, there is possibility that conflicts will arise between LMTs regarding which technology will secure first carbon storage. The permanence of BECCS should be supposedly good so permanence needs to be certified somehow.

4.5.2 Asia

- Biochar: The sale of carbon credits has become a game changer, there is a large demand for credits. There are no regional organizations supporting biochar that a company could affiliate themselves to. If there had been an institution at this level that would endorse and recognize a laboratory for testing, for example, or endorse policy frameworks, this would be beneficial.

- Carbon interests have been growing. For example, Singapore wants to be the carbon hub of the region. In the near future, we need a regional consultation to discuss what it means to have a voluntary carbon market in the region.
- The biggest limitation in the market-based carbon is that the rate of adoption is not optimal now. We still do not know which policy frameworks are in place and being accepted. Thus, there is a missing infrastructure on standards and liquidity issues.
- Afforestation and forest management are the priority for the first half, and then we can work on the second half of the century. Up to 2050, afforestation is important as a priority. BECCS will be more developed in the second half. We have limitations in land-based climate mitigation, and we cannot increase forest land and soil carbon. So, we need to think about when we reach the limitation.

4.5.3 Latin America

- BECCS has the capacity to develop in Latin America because many large companies have the installed capacity to co-produce energy; however, the biggest gap is in carbon capture and storage.
- Whatever the technology to be implemented, it is very important to know that for this technology to be accepted and incorporated, it must bring higher returns than the activities that producers are already engaged in. In other words, for a farmer to migrate from conventional agriculture to agriculture in an agrosilvopastoral system, the agrosilvopastoral system must provide higher returns than conventional agriculture. Otherwise, this new technology will not be attractive.
- For organic agriculture, large companies have had the need to seek alternatives to conventional agriculture, given that current market conditions, shortage of synthetic fertilizers have raised prices up to 5 times. Different from what has happened with coffee, where these increases, apparently, have not been so noticeable, or simply, they have stopped fertilizing.
- There are no methodologies to include carbon sequestration actions in projects.
- There is limited knowledge about reforestation technologies. Guidelines should be established about seeds, ecological restoration, nursery, etc.

4.5.4 Africa

- Government officials' position are mostly focused on adaptation and food security. There is potential for LMTs in Africa, but western countries may need to pay for it. There is a conflict between afforestation and land-use for crops in Burkina Faso and Kenya. Crop-based LMTs may help reduce this conflict.
- People using small farm areas use naturally more sustainable agriculture practices to reduce costs. With larger areas, it is too much work, and they prefer to use pesticides.
- Carbon can be kept locked in trees or biochar if there are incentives. It needs to make sense economically or socially to the partner involved in the process.
- In the African context storage in geological formations is limited, so it would be stored in soils. Perennial grasses sequester more carbon than aerial crops. Relying on afforestation and other measures dependent on above ground storage are risky because of fires and land-use change.

- Agroforestry is the best LMT; better to protect trees than to plant trees; difficult to project beyond 2050. Biochar need to invest more.

4.6 Some limitations and lessons learned

The target size for each regional workshop was around 15-20 persons, with the aim of allowing three breakout groups by LMT. Participation in two of the consultations (Latin America and Asia) surpassed the target while the other two did not reach the target range. Response to the survey in relation to participation (i.e., percentage) was highest in Latin America, and this higher participation was most likely because it was conducted in Spanish: the regional cohesion of a common language makes regional engagement somewhat easier in Latin America. The other reason that the Latin America event had highest attendance is because it was hybrid and in-person participants received lunch. The Asia event was able to achieve a high attendance because of the significant number of invitations sent out. However, the participation in the survey was quite low, considering that it was requested to complete the survey in order to participate in the event. More than half of those registered in Africa and North Europe + Canada did not show up. Low attendance for some regions was also related to time zones that were not very compatible (e.g. Europe and Canadian time zones).

Stakeholder engagement can be rather labour-intensive depending how it is accomplished, and the effort and methods need to be weighed against the value of the information obtained. The first round of consultations were aimed at obtaining some preliminary indications on LMT priorities across different world regions, and this could only be done in a general way since stakeholders could not be provided with specific national or regional LMT portfolios or scenarios, as neither the baseline model results (D7.1) nor the national LMT scaling scenarios (D2.6) were available.

There were several topic-related challenges. LMTs are not a widely known and used concept, which means that most stakeholders are not used to thinking in and across these categories. The subject of LMTs is complex due to the wide range of areas and implications that come with understanding and implementing them. Discussions on LMTs span across different scales (from local to global), across different timeframes (from years to decades), across different stages of deployment (from early scientific assessment to testing and implementation) and across different areas of society (science, environment, economics, policy). Consequently, a focus even just on one LMT allows for an interesting and lengthy discussion. The fact that the LANDMARC LMT portfolio includes many different LMTs adds a layer of complexity that influenced many of the methodology- and organization-related challenges. Eliciting coherent information from diverse stakeholders on multiple sectors within a complex set of topics was not always feasible due to diversity of knowledge and stakeholder interests. Therefore, a lot of effort went into selecting stakeholders and modes of engagement in a way that would maximize the likelihood of meaningful and fruitful discussions. Some methodological questions that arose after the consultations included how to weight information from stakeholders with varying degrees of expertise, whether stakeholders operating at a national level could make valuable contributions to a regional perspective, and whether LMTs should be discussed separately or combined.

5 Background and Conceptual Framework

The online consultations provided useful preparation for designing the regional workshops that were the main activity in Task 6.3. This section provides the conceptual framing for the approach to the workshops and the methods and means used in Task 6.3. An overall framing and motivation is first provided and then the details for the application to LANDMARC LMT studies and scenarios are presented.

The subjective nature of stakeholder engagement and the lack of any statistical significance needs to be acknowledged in the context of this exercise. The diversity of stakeholders involved in LMTs and the fact that their participation is unpaid and voluntary means that it is not feasible, when aiming to cover almost the entire world, to have a representative set of stakeholders. For this reason, the aforementioned notion of co-production becomes more nuanced and has particular meaning in a regional context. With these limitations in mind, an approach has been designed to co-create a narrative for each region around the basic notion of climate ambition that is used in the UNFCCC context when analysing mitigation options and applications. This approach aims to build on national LMT scaling but also recognising the long-term potential for *regional engagement* that might in principle go beyond what countries can do on their own.

One important consideration in this exercise is the long timeframe along which stakeholder information might be elicited, i.e., out to 2050 or 2100, to be consistent with the models. This long timeframe means that the exercise cannot be limited to options and institutions that are well known at the present time, and there must be some space for a rather imaginative exercise.

5.1 Conceptual framing for regional engagement

As the title of WP6 suggests, a key issue to be discussed with stakeholders is *regional engagement*. We employ a normative framework and argue that more regional cooperation on matters related to LMTs and/or climate change mitigation and adaptation would offer some tangible benefits, as discussed further in this section. In this context, regional cooperation is essentially a variable qualifier for *regional engagement* that differs according to different scenarios and/or storylines. It is by exploring this added value of regional cooperation that our regional scenarios and narratives add value as compared to the simple summation of national case study insights. Thus, for example in the case of BECCS, there might be greater effort at transnational capacity building and/or joint infrastructure vs. more general cooperation embodied in differentiated national plans. Thus, we can consider *improved regional engagement* as entailing greater regional cooperation that enhances implementation of NDCs beyond what would be expected from strictly nationally-focused approaches (see Section 9).

Moreover, we employ a *neo-functional* view to regional cooperation in the sense that countries might start cooperating on specific issues and spill-over effects would lead to cooperation in other areas and to the emergence of shared institutions that would generate trust, lower transaction costs and provide shared norms, rules and regulations (Haas, 1958; Pollack, 2010; Schmitter, 1969). However, we are also aware that in certain regions of the world, this neo-functional approach with its emphasis on (supranational) institutions might not adequately reflect policy making; in such cases, cooperation arrangements and frameworks such as intergovernmentalism (Moravcsik, 1993) or neo-

realism, which emphasises the role of power politics (Keohane, 1984)—might describe those countries’ and regions’ approach better. Nevertheless, as per our scenario building activities, we will indeed assume that there are tangible benefits to more economic and political integration on the regional level. Indeed, economic as well as political sciences literature does suggest several benefits of increased regional cooperation:

- Economic integration and trade: technologies, biomass, and other inputs can be traded across borders and - according to liberal economic theories – could offer benefits in harnessing competitive and comparative advantages. Moreover, scholars argue that regional integration fosters market building (Orcalli, 2017), noting that the EU and its fully integrated internal economic market offers the best example of how regional economic integration usually leads to increased economic wellbeing as compared to a non-integration scenario (de Bruijn et al., 2008; Mion & Ponattu, 2019; Moravcsik, 2005; Peterson & Shackelton, 2012).
- Besides a market-based approach, increased regional cooperation could also lead to more regulatory and environmental harmonisation. While this sort of harmonisation is sometimes criticised as race to the bottom (Konisky, 2007), harmonisation can also lead to tightening environmental regulation. The EU’s carbon border adjustment tax is one example, where a bloc decides to apply high environmental standards consistently across one region and the EU’s regulatory experience has generally shown a race to the top according to research (Holzinger & Sommerer, 2011). Moreover, there are other advantages to regional collaboration or engagement, including co-benefits for pollution, health, water resources and other situations where a regional approach adds value AND increases LMT ambitions. Overall, economic and environmental harmonisation need to be carefully balanced to address both social-economic and climate challenges.
- Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) and Loans: although land is not physically traded *per se*, there are an increasing number of foreign direct investments in the land sectors that affect the scale of effort or ambition for LMTs since the capital mobilised may be far greater than what is feasible with domestic capital.
- Article 6 of the Paris Agreement: international cooperation may aim to directly undertake climate mitigation actions across borders, again using comparative advantage and recognising the differences in costs and benefits for climate mitigation.
- Regional Learning and Knowledge Sharing: due to commonalities in agroecological zones, socio-economic conditions, or historical relations – there may be regional learning for certain LMTs, in terms of facilitating transnational replication of LMT best practices or possibly for combinations of LMTs (portfolios) that take advantage of synergies in land sectors. Advances in regional cooperation could also lead to positive spillover effects in learning through the share of knowledge on LMT implementation and challenges and best practice examples as well as with policy processes (Bößner, Suljada, et al., 2020).
- Technology Transfer and Capacity Building: as with Finance, these are part of the Means of Implementation for the Paris Agreement and as such can be expected to include transnational and/or regional approaches. Such efforts are already underway in the land sectors through

various convening mechanisms but at this early stage it is difficult to place them within a common framework, but more context specific info could be elicited from stakeholders.

In addition to the role of economic integration and regional cooperation in market building (Orcalli, 2017), it can also allow for the pooling of resources and efficient allocation and strengthen the exchange of knowledge (Bößner et al., 2020) and can be potentially beneficial for overall prosperity (de Bruijn et al., 2008; Mion & Ponattu, 2019; Moravcsik, 2005).

5.2 National/regional aggregation

LANDMARC research includes analysis at levels from local to national to regional to global. For Task 6.3, we are especially interested in the scaling up or replication of LMTs and/or LMT portfolios and in particular the relation between national and regional/continental and the relation between regional/continental and global. Since case studies include analysis on the national LMT portfolios and the creation of a national “narrative” this information can be used in constructing the regional narrative as well. Doing so offers a practical approach as there are few other mechanisms to gather information at the regional level. In some cases, case study countries may be quite relevant and strategic in the region, while in others they may be small and less representative. Nevertheless, the stakeholder feedback can provide some cross-section of voices and perspectives for the construction of regional narratives. The national-level case study results inform the regional scaling, as suggested in , which also gives an overview of the overall updated process under Task 6.3, using the example for Asia where there were three relevant case study countries. It should be noted that the information flow in Figure 3 is not deterministic or standardised due to the fact that LMT priorities and portfolios differ in each national case study and do not necessarily correspond to the LMTs in the coupled model; thus the use of results at regional level is somewhat heuristic, via presentation to the stakeholders, along with complementary analysis to fill in any gaps.

Figure 3: Task 6.3 process flow chart example

The approach outlined in again adopts a triangular method for evaluating evidence in the context of stakeholder co-production. Screening of policies and institutions accompanied by interviews with stakeholders and focus groups conducted at regional level form the three components of the methodology. The policy/legislation screening will focus mainly on issues related to selected countries' NDC ambitions and long-term strategies (LTS) in combination with regional level literature that places climate and development goals in a transnational or regional context.

Figure 4: Triangular method for stakeholder engagement and analysis

5.3 LMT Scenarios in the coupled model

As discussed further in D6.3, there were two alternative baselines in the coupled model (which links LandSHIFT-G and LPJ-GUESS models), as documented in D7.1, which relied on climate forcing results from previous runs of the EC-Earth3-CC modelling system. In addition to a standardised baseline, there is also an afforestation scenario in which afforestation or reforestation gets highest priority, resulting in net shifts from other land use types to forest in the coming decades. It is possible that this scenario may change somewhat due to stakeholder inputs; however, in this case the stakeholder inputs would be more associated with corrections related to regional conditions as opposed to policy priorities. Thus, this scenario is best viewed as an alternative baseline rather than being stakeholder-driven. These baseline results will undergo some final corrections that are generally not dependent on any stakeholder information or policy assumptions.

It will be feasible to run just two scenarios other than these baseline scenarios with the modelling framework due to the significant costs of running the full modelling ensemble (see LANDMARC D6.3). Different policy-and-stakeholder-driven processes can rely on various sources of information:

- (1) NDCs and any other policy targets or plans, such as Long-Term Strategies submitted to the UNFCCC, to the extent that they include LMTs or land sectors;
- (2) Stakeholder information and feedback at national level, including as expressed especially in the LMT scaling scenarios/portfolios (D2.6);
- (3) Stakeholder information and feedback with some regional character.

This third element is a key focus in Task 6.3 aims to add some value by considering any additional scaling, learning or replication effects in a regional context that might be considered. In addition to being policy-driven, the scenarios also incorporate stakeholder views as to what LMT portfolio(s) would be most likely to achieve climate mitigation goals and therefore the result is intended to provide some nominal level of stakeholder co-production. The view on climate mitigation can be seen as cross-sectoral and holistic to the extent that NDCs and stakeholder views are reasonably holistic, i.e., incorporating expectations and trends for mitigation actions in other sectors. The view on LMT potential is based on the notion of low vs. high LMT ambition in relation to regional engagement, as outlined in the next section.

5.4 Regional perspectives on LMTs and Scenarios

In the multilateral climate regime and in discussions on climate policy, reference to low or high “carbon dioxide removal (CDR) ambition” might normally be anchored with respect to the NDCs. We focus on CDRs to highlight the fact that the ambitions do not fully consider adaptation ambitions. However, in the analysis under LANDMARC, National Long-term Strategies (LTS) are also relevant as they provide some indication of the direction of national climate policy to 2050 and beyond. According to Article 4, paragraph 19, of the Paris Agreement, “all Parties should strive to formulate and communicate long-term low greenhouse gas emission development strategies, mindful of Article 2 taking into account their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, in the light of different national circumstances.” (UNFCCC, 2016). However, to date, about 40% of Parties (countries + the EU) have submitted an LTS. Where the LTS exists, it can be used as the primary guide in the stakeholder engagement for discussing and/or anchoring ambitions. The overall reference points in global terms for all GHG mitigation measures for low and high ambition can be associated with the 1.5 and 2 °C targets of the Paris Agreement, respectively.

Although most submissions to the UNFCCC provide some indication on goals or measures in the land use sectors (LULUCF), in general the ambitions expressed in NDCs and/or LTS are not necessarily specified in a way that easily translates into an evaluation on LMT priorities and portfolios as envisioned in LANDMARC. Therefore, we will need to first establish what is considered “low CDR ambition” and here we expect that low CDR ambition is current policies with limited support given to LMTs, considering also that relatively few NDCs provide rich detail on LMT portfolios, that LMTs are not as well developed as mitigation measures in other sectors, and that stakeholders often do not know the details across many LMTs (as determined from the capacity gap report, D6.4). More generally, the heterogeneity of LMTs means that a considerable amount of learning may be needed, and this learning could be slow, even where there is regional as well as national replication effort.

Based on these observations and theoretical underpinnings, we develop regional scenarios and storylines, including consultations with appropriate stakeholders, using a two-axis framework. Figure 5 provides a depiction of this framework, with low and high LMT ambition on one axis and the level of regional engagement (low/national-focus vs. high/intra-regional learning) on the other axis. Examples are given as to how distinctions might be described, such as the “All-of-Society” approach that aims to bring regional value-added AND high CDR ambition for LMTs. Ultimately such depictions need to come

from the bottom-up process of talking with stakeholders, so here we describe only the space for discussion in terms of the relation between CDR ambition and regional engagement.

Figure 5: CDR/LMT ambition vs. degree of regional engagement

One of the aims in LANDMARC is to be able to use regional narratives or storylines to inform land use modelling results and specifically for the coupled model refinements (LandSHIFT-G/EC-Earth3-CC). It should be noted that the regional engagement narratives in some cases may be harder to translate into modelling assumptions. Some aspects may translate more easily, for example applying or replicating best practices from one country to another. Others, such as regional learning, are more difficult to incorporate since learning curves in the land sectors, which include both technologies and practices, are quite different than learning curves modelled for renewable energy technologies, for example.

Translating the narratives or storylines that emerge from application of this framework into a useful discussion at the policy level will provide some contribution to the ongoing efforts to enhance the current national-based structure of the multilateral climate regime. The creation of events by the UNFCCC such as the regional climate weeks and the establishment of institutions that can mobilise cross-country linkages or learnings (e.g., the Green Climate Fund) are among efforts in the existing regime that have aimed to add value at regional and/or transnational level. Therefore, the results of this exercise will be of general interest at such regional events or activities, and to these institutions.

It should also be noted that low and high CDR ambition in this case applies to the land sectors and/or LMTs. In order to understand the dynamics of low and high ambition, we will ask stakeholders to envision what drivers, barriers and opportunities would need to be met and/or addressed in order to

move from the status quo to more ambitious plans. It may well be that some countries are not giving priority to land sectors and LMTs in their NDC and/or LTS, as they may be emphasising other sectors. Therefore, it will be valuable in the regional workshops and further consultation activities to ensure that stakeholders have some common understanding on the main drivers and barriers in a policy context for the region being discussed. Consequently, stakeholders will be provided with background reports for their respective regions.

6 Regional Profiles: inception/background reports

The information presented here encapsulates the key takeaways from the inception reports from the four regions of Europe, Africa, Asia and Latin America (see Annex C: Inception/Background Reports), which was shared with participants of the workshop upon their confirmation of attendance. Its purpose was to furnish participants with background knowledge about the region, preparing them adequately for the workshop, as well as providing a literature review that helps to complement the evidence base for evaluating LMTs. The African and Asian reports primarily delve into climate change, land-use-based mitigation measures, potential LMTs in the region, regional integration and cooperation, and stakeholder perspectives gathered from interviews. The European report presents the climate change targets and land use change targets rather than climate change and land-use-based mitigation measures. As the Latin American inception report was originally written in Spanish, only select content has been translated into English for reference.

6.1 Africa

6.1.1 Climate change and land use

Climate change and its impact on land use in Africa create a variety of pressing concerns that require urgent attention and action. The climatic changes are exacerbated by rapid economic growth in Africa, straining progress in developing clean energy sources, due to financial and technological limitations (IPCC, 2023). In East Africa, the warming trend and economic expansion have led to a significant rise in GHG emissions. Although African countries have different obligations compared to OECD countries, they have committed to mitigation actions to support low emissions development pathways. Countries in the region have pledged substantial emission reductions ranging from 20% to 65% by 2030 through their NDCs, demonstrating a collective effort to combat climate change (Kweyu et al., 2023).

Table 2: Land use changes* in the EAC and some member countries (as % change from 2000-2021)

Item	Area								Changes -37% 106%
	East African Community	Burundi	Congo	Kenya	Rwanda	South Sudan	Uganda	United Republic of Tanzania	
Cropland	35%	23%	26%	19%	24%		23%	55%	
Permanent meadows and pastures	0%	-12%	0%	0%	-26%		4%	0%	
Naturally regenerating forest	-12%	106%	-1%	-9%	-21%		-37%	-16%	
Planted Forest	18%	0%	0%	0%	19%		77%	0%	

*Note: the land use changes of the EAC have been corrected compared to the graph in the inception report.

A summary of land use dynamics in East Africa is given in Table 2, which outlines the land use changes over the past two decades in the EAC and six of the member countries. The data reveal notable trends, such as an increase in cropland and planted forests, while the area of permanent meadows has remained relatively stable. However, there has been a decline of 12% in naturally regenerating forests, highlighting the ongoing challenges in preserving natural ecosystems amidst climate change and changing land use patterns.

6.1.2 Land based mitigation potential

A study by Roe et al. (2021) shows that the highest cost-effective mitigation potential comes from reducing deforestation ($0.97 \pm 0.4 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$; 39%), then afforestation and reforestation ($0.25 \pm 0.2 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$; 10%), sequestering soil organic carbon in grasslands ($0.24 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$; 10%), shifting diets ($0.2 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$; 8%), and agroforestry ($0.19 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$; 8%). Across the countries, the DRC as the largest country, has the most cost-effective mitigation potential at $0.4 \pm 0.2 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{eq yr}^{-1}$, or about 16% of Africa’s potential. The DRC is followed by Tanzania where land-based emissions are largely driven by deforestation from shifting agriculture; “forest protection” measures present the highest cost-effective mitigation potential.

6.1.3 Role of LMTs in African context

Land-based emission mitigation technologies, including agroforestry, afforestation, biochar, and minimum tillage, hold considerable potential for Africa. In a region where climate change poses substantial challenges, these technologies offer a multifaceted solution (Roe et al. 2021). An approach that significantly expands reliance on LMTs can potentially not only mitigate greenhouse gas emissions but also enhance the resilience of African farming systems to a changing climate, bolstering food security and sustainable land management. The aim is to address climate, agriculture, and land degradation challenges simultaneously, making LMTs a potentially vital component of Africa’s sustainable development and climate adaptation strategies.

Table 3 Barriers, enablers, and opportunities for LMT development in Africa based on regional interviews

Regional perspectives from stakeholder interviews		
Barriers	Enablers	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness and understanding among smallholder farmers • Initial investment costs and limited access to credit and funding mechanisms • Limited infrastructure hindering technology distribution • Inconsistent policies and regulations • Climate change variability affecting technology success 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support from NGOs, international organizations, and governments • Ongoing research and innovation in technology development • Involving local communities in decision-making and implementation • Access to markets and consumer demand for sustainably produced products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple benefits offered by mitigation technologies • Global attention and climate finance availability • Collaborative efforts and regional cooperation • Alignment with Sustainable Development Goals

6.1.4 Regional integration and cooperation

Enhanced regional integration and cooperation create a supportive environment for scaling up land-based emission mitigation technologies in Africa. A synthesis of regional perspectives derived from interviews is given in Table 3. By sharing knowledge, harmonizing policies, and attracting investments collectively, African nations can more effectively combat climate change and build a sustainable and resilient future for the continent.

6.2 Asia

With some of the world’s largest archipelagic states, Southeast Asia has increasing risk of losing infrastructure and low-lying coastal settlements to sea-level rise. By 2050, 64% of Asia’s population will be urban; in coastal cities where high concentration of people and activities is found, an estimated 77% - are seen as ‘high-risk areas’ (IPCC, 2023). Alongside the adaptation needs arising from this exposure to climate change, rapid changes in land use illustrate the context for land-based mitigation, as discussed further below.

6.2.1 Climate change mitigation and Land use

Over the past two decades, Southeast Asia has undergone significant changes in land sectors over the past two decades; as shown in Table 4, there is a clear reduction in natural forest, and an increase in plantation forests and cropland.

Table 4: Land use changes in ASEAN and seven member countries, expressed as % change from 2000-2021

Item	Area								Changes
	Southeast Asia	Indonesia	Thailand	Malaysia	Vietnam	Philippines	Laos	Cambodia	
Cropland	29.8%	48.9%	7.6%	24.5%	44.0%	14.9%	35.3%	19.8%	
Naturally regenerating forest	-10.8%	-10.7%	-4.0%	-3.8%	4.5%	-2.1%	-6.8%	-31.7%	
Permanent meadows and pastures	2.6%	-1.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	-15.9%	61.3%	
Planted Forest	51.6%	16.4%	76.3%	3.8%	129.5%	19.6%	13.2%	516.5%	

Most countries in the region are heavily dependent on natural resources, land, and biodiversity (for agriculture, tourism, and production of goods and services), which are directly affected by climate impacts. In countries such as Myanmar, Cambodia, and Lao PDR, agriculture still represents a significant part of GDP (20% or more) (World Bank, 2022).

6.2.2 Potential of NbS and LMTs in Asia

The land sector offers an important opportunity to mitigate emissions through projected contribution of nature-based solutions (NbS) to reach net-zero by 2050 in the Asia-Pacific region (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Many of these measures can also address climate impacts and/or adaptation strategies. Over the last two decades, there has been an increased number and intensity of extreme climate events and disasters: floods, typhoons, droughts, and heat waves. During the last 20 years, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Thailand have been among the top 10 countries most affected by extreme climate hazards (Eckstein et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is a

densely populated region, now around 680 million inhabitants, approximately a third of whom are in

Indonesia (IMF, 2023).

Figure 6: Projected contribution of NbS to net-zero in Asia-Pacific. Source: UNESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022

As Asia-Pacific is the world’s largest region, so it is not surprising that it has high LMT potential. As with most regions, afforestation and reforestation are a significant share of the estimated potential. Taken together with forest management and agroforestry, these represent more than 70% of the estimated potential. However, there are many factors that must be considered alongside the estimated potential, for example the permanence of carbon removal is less assured with standing biomass in forests compared to sequestration of carbon in soils or in geological formations (Karki et al. 2023).

6.2.3 Regional perspective from stakeholder interviews

The ASEAN region has had a limited amount of regional cooperation on transboundary environmental issues, but many challenges are not yet taken up at regional level, as suggested by Table 5.

Table 5: Barriers, enablers, and opportunities for LMT development in SE-Asia based on regional interviews

Barriers	Enablers	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weak regional coordination and resource mobilization External factors driving land use, sometimes overriding internal considerations Initiatives at high levels may not align with local realities Focus on economic development can overshadow environmental concerns Misalignment between national and local governments Lack of funding and technical capacity for implementation Insufficient region-specific research and data on ecosystem services and land-use dynamics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harmonized regional policies and regulations for effective implementation Regional champions showcasing successful projects for adaptation Collaborative solutions to shared challenges like population growth and land tenure issues Enhanced communication, joint research, and networking opportunities at all levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ASEAN’s potential role in promoting cooperation on land management and land-use mitigation Importance of involving the private sector in land-use discussions and leveraging their influence on supply chains Diverse funding sources such as carbon markets, payments for ecosystem services, and market-based interventions driven by consumer demand and company standards

6.3 Europe

6.3.1 Climate mitigation targets

Within the European continent, the EU has taken the lead in championing ambitious emission reduction and climate action across its Member States. In its latest NDC update, the EU sets a goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, relative to 1990. In terms of land use, the region has undergone changes in the land sectors over the past two decades. In general, as shown in Table 6, there is a reduction in cropland, natural forest and meadows and pastures, while an increase in plantation forests.

Table 6: The land use change in the EU and seven case countries, expressed as % change from 2000-2021

Item	Area								Changes
	The EU (27)	Germany	Netherlands	Portugal	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Ukraine	
Cropland	-9%	-1%	-2%	-28%	-9%	-2%	-3%	1%	
Naturally regenerating forest	-1%	1%	-18%	4%	9%	-22%	10%	1%	
Permanent meadows and pastures	-14%	-6%	-15%	50%	-16%	25%	-5%	-5%	
Planted Forest	17%	1%	6%	-1%	8%	37%	-14%	3%	

6.3.2 Land-based mitigation targets

The EU has established detailed guidance on the land sectors, and there is also ongoing legislation. The carbon neutrality target in the NDC update (2020) includes for the first time the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector. The quantitative aim is to increase EU carbon sinks levels in LULUCF to above 310 Mt CO₂eq by 2030, while LULUCF emissions may not exceed removals (Rayner et al., 2023). Under the LULUCF regulation and effort sharing regulation and between 2021 to 2030, EU MS may use up to 280 Mt CO₂eq net removals from land use categories excluding forest management (Rayner et al., 2023). From 2026, removals within the LULUCF sector should exceed emissions. By 2030, each MS will have to deliver results on a natural amount of removals.

6.3.3 Potential of LMTs in Europe

The potential LMTs in the EU case study countries are summarized in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 7 LMTs in national case studies (* denotes an LMT included in Land-vegetation-carbon modelling)

	Germany	Netherlands	Portugal	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Ukraine
Afforestation*	X	X		X	X		
BECCS*		X			X		
Biochar*					X		
Agroforestry*		X	X			X	X
Reduced/no tillage*						X	X
Forest management	X		X	X	X		
Soil carbon	X						
Peatland rewetting		X					
Organic agriculture						X	X
Cropland management			X				

Grassland management	X	X
Agrosilvopastoral land		X
Bioenergy		X

On a global level, Europe holds significant potential to contribute to emission mitigation through the utilization of land-based technologies. An assessment of the mitigation potential of the most common global LMTs from the LANDMARC technology portfolio suggests that Europe could mitigate between 3,5 to 3,8 Gt CO_{2eq} per year (Karki et al. 2023). Europe has significant potential in afforestation and BECCS, with agroforestry, forest management, and biochar following closely behind. It is worth noting that in Europe, BECCS holds one of the most substantial potentials for emissions reduction when compared to other regions.

6.3.4 Regional perspectives from stakeholder interviews

The EU differs naturally from other regions in having the strongest zone of economic integration by far, but there are nevertheless a number of challenges due to issues such as limited availability of land and biomass, and the constraints on LMT implementation for farmers and landowners facing significant environmental regulations and administrative procedures, as suggested in Table 8.

Table 8 The barriers, enablers, and opportunities for LMTs development in Europe based on interview results

Barriers	Enablers	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex permission processes hinder new technology implementation Challenges in accessing finance and uncertain markets affect adoption Disparities in policies and competition within biomass utilization pose hurdles Limited availability of arable land and trade-offs in regenerative farming practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating local value chains and implementing carbon credits incentivize adoption Collaboration and knowledge transfer between regions and countries enhance adoption Eco-tourism and support from governmental measures promote sustainable practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encouraging dialogue and cooperation facilitates knowledge sharing and support Focusing on landscapes and infrastructure enhances dissemination of practices Collaboration with companies and standards/regulations create reliable markets Transferring decision-making power to younger generations and addressing knowledge gaps drive innovation

6.4 Latin America

6.4.1 Climate change emission and mitigation

Unlike other regions of the world, in LAC, AFOLU sectors represent more than 40% of the region’s total emissions (Bárcena Ibarra et al., 2020), which is double the world average. The main contributors are deforestation and land use change, which in addition to carbon dioxide (CO₂) generate emissions of nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄) (Cárdenas and Orozco, 2022). The Amazon Cooperation Treaty region has also undergone a significant decrease in natural forest over the past two decades, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 9 The land use changes* in the ACTO and the eight member countries, expressed as % change from 2000-2021

Item	The ACTO	Bolivia	Brazil	Colombia	Area Ecuador	Guyana	Peru	Suriname	Venezuela
Cropland	18%	55%	20%	-1%	-18%	3%	24%	-7%	-3%
Naturally regenerating forest	-10%	-8%	-12%	-6%	-10%	-1%	-5%	-1%	-7%
Permanent meadows and pastures	-1%	-2%	0%	-5%	-41%	0%	6%	-24%	0%
Planted Forest	172%	79%	217%	158%	54%		53%	0%	84%

*Note: the land use changes of the ACTO have been corrected compared to the graph presented in the inception report in Annex C4: Inception report (in Spanish) for Latin America

In total, the six main economies in LAC committed to reducing their emissions by 34.3% compared to the business-as-usual scenario between now and 2030. At the continental levels, the Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) countries concentrate 24% of the terrestrial ecosystems, 18% of the world’s marine ecosystems, and a third of the planet’s water resources (IADB & CEPAL, 2018; UNEP, 2022). The agricultural sector, which is of great economic importance in the region, is especially vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. It is estimated that agricultural productivity may fall between 12 and 24% because of climate change (Samaniego et al., 2022).

6.4.2 Potential of LMTs in Latin America

Most NDCs in the region prioritize adaptation sectors and actions. In the case of mitigation, the most important sectors, according to their potential to reduce GHG emissions, are energy, transportation, agriculture, forestry, and other land uses (AFOLU), and they focus on the deployment of renewable energies, sustainable management of biodiversity, climate-smart agriculture (CSA).

In LAC, the NDCs include a few measures or lines of action on the removal or negative emissions technologies and are not part of a priority plan to strengthen adaptive capacity or reduce emissions (Samaniego et al., 2022), as shown in Figure 7

Figure 7 Suggestion for phased large-scale deployment of CDR (DRC) options in Latin American countries

7 Workshop Design & Implementation

Whereas the online stakeholder consultations served as an exploration of the stakeholder network and an introduction of stakeholders to LANDMARC and its approach to LMTs, the next set of regional stakeholder events were designed more like focus groups aimed at having more in-depth discussions. Therefore, the discussion groups for participants were generally smaller. SEI in collaboration with its LANDMARC consortium partners, organized the regional stakeholder workshops during October and November 2023 in its four regional centres in Bogotá, Nairobi, Bangkok, and Stockholm. The overall design is explained in this section.

7.1 Objectives

The regional workshop on LMTs aimed to bring together a diverse group of stakeholders to review and evaluate land-based mitigation options in the region, focusing on three key dimensions or elements:

- I. Identifying and characterising a regional portfolio of LMTs;
- II. Evaluating how ambitions for LMTs can be raised in the region; and
- III. Offering recommendations on how regional cooperation can facilitate such higher ambitions.

7.2 Stakeholder Profiles

This section considers invited stakeholders in terms of countries and expertise in LMTs,.

7.2.1 Europe

The European workshop adopted a hybrid format and invited about 90 stakeholders, and it illustrates the approach taken for all the workshops, in terms of seeking diversity in the process of identifying stakeholders across the different LMTs (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Profile of invited stakeholders in European workshop

They showcased expertise across Europe in multiple LMTs: afforestation, agroforestry, BECCS, biochar, reduced tillage, rewetting, organic agriculture, and bioenergy. About 20 registered and 12 attended the workshop.

7.2.2 Africa

The African workshop on LMTs extended invitations to 67 experts from various fields such as water resources management, community organizations, climate change research, forestry and land use planning, agriculture, GIS and modelling, energy, private sector initiatives, and policy advocacy. The aim was to put the diverse group of participants together and bring a wealth of knowledge and experience, fostering rich discussions and collaborations aimed at advancing sustainable land use and climate mitigation strategies across Africa. Of these, 23 attended the in-person workshop, and were covering the key LMTs.

7.2.3 Asia

The Asian workshop identified a total of 31 stakeholders with a wealth of expertise from countries such as Cambodia, Thailand, Indonesia, Vietnam, and across Southeast Asia, reflecting a broader Asian perspective. These stakeholders represent a diverse range of backgrounds, encompassing international NGOs, local NGOs, research institutes, consultancy firms, the finance sector, and bilateral agencies. The participants have specialized knowledge in various fields, including agriculture, agroforestry, forestry, biochar, bioenergy, wetlands conservation, land-use modelling, land policy advocacy, NbS, BECCS, and carbon removal and carbon markets. The diverse mix of expertise were invited to ensure a comprehensive and holistic approach to addressing land-based mitigation technology challenges and opportunities across the Asian region. There were 17 attendees at the workshop, coming from 5 countries and representing different stakeholder groups.

7.2.4 Latin America

To the Latin American workshop, 13 stakeholders participated, each with different expertise and covering several countries, including Peru, Brazil, Ecuador, Costa Rica, and Colombia. The expertise spanned from biochar production to afforestation/reforestation, forest management, natural forest regeneration, and agroforestry practices.

7.3 Structure and Facilitation

The workshop was structured in five parts and the details can be found in Annex D1: Details of Regional Workshop Design. To summarise, Part I focused on an introduction to the workshop, including an overview of LANDMARC and LMTs, as well as discussions on the scenario framework based on “CDR Ambition” and the “Regional Engagement” framework. LANDMARC modelling results were presented, and participants invited to provide the feedback to the modelling assumption and results. Then it was followed by structured breakout group sessions (Parts II and III) for deeper discussions. Part II delved into Climate Ambition for LMTs, with an introduction to the session and subsequent breakout group discussions on the LMT portfolio. In Part III, the focus shifted to Regional Engagement for scaling up LMTs, with another session introduction and breakout group discussions on regional engagement strategies for LMT implementation. Part IV synthesized the insights gained, featuring reporting from breakout groups, discussions on Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement, and reflections on

regional narratives or storylines. The meeting concluded with Part V, including final remarks, a brief survey, and evaluation to gather feedback for future improvements.

To ensure consistency in methodology across the various groups in the four regions, matrices were designed for each of the two breakout sessions and agreed upon for use in all four regions. These matrices can be found in Annex D1: Details of Regional Workshop Design. A few brief points are noted below with respect to the two dimensions of CDR/climate ambition and regional engagement, which also corresponded to the two sets of breakout groups.

7.3.1 CDR/Climate Ambition

Participants were tasked with providing insights into afforestation (which was a key LMT for the modelling/simulation) and two additional LMTs. The second choice of LMT was to be among the other four included in the modelling/simulation (i.e. biochar, BECCS, agroforestry, or no/low tillage agriculture). The third choice was open in that they could choose LMTs that were not among those modelled. In some cases, the participants could choose to group similar LMTs together in their discussions, and where they had additional time, they could discuss additional LMTs beyond the three.

7.3.2 Regional engagement

This exercise asked participants to envision how stronger regional cooperation help the adoption of LMTs. From a methodological point of view, the organisation team had to strike a balance between not biasing the participants too much while at the same time providing enough guidance on what the research team meant by regional cooperation and which kind of qualifiers (or indicators) could be used to measure or assess regional cooperation. In the end, participants were provided with three broad categories of qualifiers, namely ‘economic integration and harmonisation’, ‘formal governance mechanisms’ and ‘research cooperation and technology transfer’, with each category containing several sub-qualifiers; however, the details were not revealed to the participants in order to let them come up with their own qualifiers. Analogous to the climate ambition session, a matrix with guiding questions across the three categories of qualifiers was used by facilitators, including inquiries about boosting LMT adoption, identifying beneficial LMTs, implementation strategies, key actors, barriers, and overcoming challenges.

8 Summary/synthesis for workshops

The key takeaways of feedback to modelling results and the results of two sets of group breakout discussions at the workshop are summarized and synthesised below. It should be noted that the breakout groups had an open approach that allowed participants to consider LMTs other than those that were covered under the modelling/simulation. The full package of workshop documentation, including all the info synthesised below and covering the four sets of regional workshop results, is found in the set of annexes: Annex D: Regional Workshops.

8.1 Feedback on modelling/simulation results

At each workshop, the LANDMARC modelling team presented the assumptions and the initial results from the land use simulations for that region, as shown in Annex D2: Land Use Modelling Assumptions and Results . Following the presentation of the initial modelling assumptions and results during the

workshop, participants were encouraged to share their feedback and comments. The insights gathered from the four regions provided reference points for refining assumptions and adopting a broader perspective when analysing land use change trends and presenting the results in different regions. Participants provided comments specific to their area of expertise and interest, as detailed below.

8.1.1 Africa

The key takeaways from the African workshop discussions and questions for the modellers included inquiries about the effectiveness of focusing solely on purpose-grown crops for biochar and whether incorporating both biological and pyrogenic loops could lead to better outcomes. Participants sought clarification on how the model quantifies soil moisture, whether it considers soil depth and different photosynthetic pathways (C3 and C4 plants), and if CO₂ feedback to climate can be initialized in the model. They also questioned how water cycling, forest fires, and regional carbon similarities are addressed in the model and how these factors might impact the results for East Africa. Additionally, concerns were raised about the technical complexity of communicating model results to policymakers and the practicality of scenarios for adoption by local communities, highlighting the importance of considering socio-economic changes and climate realities in the region.

8.1.2 Asia

The key takeaway from the Asian workshop feedback on modelling assumptions and results encompasses four crucial areas: strategies to curb expansion, synergizing land types, concerns about LMTs' carbon sequestration stability, and a novel business model for biochar development in Southeast Asia. Participants highlighted the importance of leveraging the narrowing yield gap as an opportunity to boost production while minimizing rapid expansion. They also stressed considering the dynamics of abandoned croplands due to urban migration and recommended exploring policies and sustainable agriculture methods to repurpose such lands. Regarding afforestation and deforestation trends, while acknowledging an increase in forest cover, concerns were raised about the quality of new forests in terms of carbon sequestration capacity compared to primary forests. The need for collaboration between agriculture and forestry sectors to optimize land use decisions, especially in mapping areas for emission reduction potential, was emphasized. Lastly, participants recognized the theoretical potential of biochar but noted a lack of proven business models, highlighting the need for an integrated approach and regional strategy for biochar production in Southeast Asia.

8.1.3 Europe

The key takeaway from the EU workshop feedback revolves around several critical points. Firstly, the assumption of a 40% increase in crop yields, while deliberately cautious, was challenged by participants who highlighted the need for dietary changes alongside such yield increases to achieve carbon emission reductions. Secondly, there was interest in understanding the inclusion of feedstocks and carbon pools in the models, especially regarding roots and their categorization. Temperature differences and their impact on soil carbon turnover were also discussed, with participants noting discrepancies in how forest management is handled, particularly the absence of woody biomass as a source of negative emissions. Suggestions were made to incorporate woody biomass and address double-counting issues, especially concerning biofuels and BECCS, while ensuring transparency in

reporting model assumptions and handling of removals and substitutions. Additionally, participants recommended including the potential use of woody biomass in combined heat and power plants and cautioned against assumptions about land allocation that might not align with reality, such as reducing agricultural land for afforestation in certain regions like Sweden. The overarching recommendations emphasized clear documentation and communication of model design, assumptions, and results to avoid misconceptions that could hinder the development of technologies and land-use management strategies for climate change mitigation.

8.1.4 Latin America

The key takeaway from the Latin American workshop feedback to the modellers includes the following points. Firstly, experts questioned assumptions about agricultural productivity, due to growing population and demand. They highlighted the assumptions made on higher total yield of agroforestry systems compared to monoculture systems, cautioning against assumptions that may not align with productivity realities. Secondly, participants stressed the critical role of maintaining the Amazon rainforest's storage capacity to prevent the release of stored carbon into the atmosphere, emphasizing the need for better forest management practices. They identified gaps in reflecting natural forest management in Latin America within the model, which then complicates analysis on deforestation, biodiversity conservation, and community livelihoods. Additionally, the discussion focused on technologies associated with biodiversity conservation, such as natural forest management and ecological restoration, rather than BECCS based on miscanthus as a feedstock, which were not deemed relevant for the region. The priority in the region, attendees noted, is multi-purpose technologies that promote nature-human relationships, sustainable forest management, and income generation for rural communities while addressing climate change adaptation and mitigation.

8.2 Climate Ambition

The key takeaways from the four workshops are provided in the following sub-sections.

8.2.1 Africa

The African workshop delved deep into discussions surrounding the LMTs' impact on climate/CDR ambitions. The covered LMTs include afforestation and forest management, agroforestry, and rangeland management (note that this last LMT is NOT covered in the modelling/simulation). The scaling-up options, risks, co-benefits and climate ambitions, as well as the key timing of development of each LMTs are discussed as summarized below:

Afforestation and forest management:

- Scaling-up options: Secure land tenure and ownership rights were identified as crucial for scaling up afforestation efforts, ensuring clear incentives and access to financing for sustainable practices. However, it was noted that fragmented land ownership, especially prevalent among smallholder farmers, poses challenges to large-scale afforestation projects.
- Risks: Insufficient understanding of local ecosystems, suitable tree species, and effective land management practices were noted as knowledge gaps hindering successful afforestation. Political influence and inconsistent policies were recognized as potential disruptors to long-term implementation.

- Co-benefits: participants stressed that afforestation offers multifaceted benefits, including carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and economic opportunities.
- Ambition: Strategic land use planning, effective governance, and supportive policies were considered necessary for the ambition to achieve sustainable afforestation goals by 2050 .
- The key timing of development: The urgency of addressing challenges and implementing scalable solutions to achieve sustainable afforestation goals by 2050 was emphasized.
- Other Info: Enabling factors such as traditional knowledge, supportive policies, and capacity building were identified as critical for successful afforestation initiatives.

Agroforestry:

- Scalability: Government support, economic incentives, and collaborative partnerships were highlighted as drivers for scaling up agroforestry. Participants also stated that market risks, limited awareness among farmers, and upfront investment costs pose barriers to replication.
- Risks: Price fluctuations, pest control challenges, and uncertainties in product availability due to climate changes were discussed as risks.
- Co-benefits: It was pointed out that agroforestry contributes significantly to adaptation, resilience, and diversified livelihoods.
- Ambition: The group concluded that high-ambition scenarios should focus on seed conservation, financial support for farmers, and education on sustainable practices.
- Timing: Challenges mentioned by stakeholder include market demand, reduced productivity, and lack of young labourers.
- Barriers: Enumerated strategies for overcoming barriers included ecological education, technical guidelines, and accessible financing.

Biochar:

- Scalability: Regional quality control mechanisms and collaboration with industries were suggested to drive scaling.
- Risks: Carbon footprint amplification, uncertainties in carbon sequestration benefits, and land tenure issues were identified as risks.
- Co-benefits: It was concluded that biochar can be used as fertilizer, reduces health risks from burning crop residues, and positively impacts biodiversity.
- Ambition: Investment in research, technology, and policies were considered imperative for upscaling biochar.
- Timing: Evidence of benefits on soil health and crop yields were requested for of long-term adoption.
- Challenges mentioned include high prices, slow impact on soil properties, and unintended impacts like deforestation.

Rangeland Management:

- Scalability: Proper management of rangelands prevents overgrazing, soil erosion, and degradation, ensuring continued availability of forage for livestock and supporting biodiversity. Collaborative efforts, traditional knowledge, and capacity building are essential for successful rangeland management
- Risks: Overgrazing, soil erosion, and degradation due to improper management pose risks to rangeland ecosystems.
- Co-benefits: Sustainable rangeland management supports healthy ecosystems, livestock forage availability, and biodiversity conservation.

- **Ambition:** Scaling up rangeland management requires effective policies, community involvement, and sustainable practices.
- **Timing:** Addressing challenges in rangeland management is crucial for long-term sustainability and resilience.

8.2.2 Asia

The Asia workshop convened LMTs encompassing a range of crucial topics such as afforestation and forest management, agroforestry, biochar, biofuels, climate-smart rice production, BECCS and sustainable agriculture. The discussions delved into scaling options, risks, co-benefits, ambitions, and proposed timelines for these LMTs to achieve sustainable and impactful outcomes in the region.

Afforestation and Forest Management:

- **Scalability:** Options includes governance improvements, stakeholder engagement, and market demand.
- **Risks:** Trade-offs with food security, economic losses, soil degradation, and wildfires.
- **Co-benefits:** Increased export opportunities, ecosystem services, and biodiversity enhancement.
- **Ambitions:** Zero deforestation by 2030 with a top-down approach.
- **Timing:** The focus is on achieving long-term benefits by 2050 and beyond.

Agroforestry:

- **Scalability:** Strategies include government commitments, international cooperation, and carbon market demand.
- **Risks:** High costs, farmer awareness, and reduced productivity of main crops.
- **Co-benefits:** Adaptation resilience and diversified livelihoods.
- **Ambitions:** The aims of sustainable practices and improved soil quality.
- **Timing:** Gradual progress with accessible guidelines is emphasized for the set timing.

Biochar:

- **Scalability:** Efforts include quality control mechanisms, digitalization, and collaboration with industries.
- **Risks:** High initial costs, uncertainties in production efficacy, and land tenure issues.
- **Co-benefits:** Soil health improvement, reduced burning, and biodiversity enhancement.
- **Ambitions:** The focus is on gradual adoption with technological advancements.
- **Timing:** Ongoing research and technology development is emphasised for the set timing.

Biofuels:

- **Scalability:** Strategies incorporate policy incentives, capacity building, and technology adoption.
- **Risks:** Trade-offs with food security, land competition, and reduced farmer engagement.
- **Co-benefits:** Biofuel production, carbon removal goals, and non-fossil fuel utilization.
- **Ambitions:** The aims are renewable energy integration and reduced emissions.

- Timing aligns with climate goals in transport and energy sectors

BECCS:

- Scalability: Efforts require research investment, policy standards, and partnerships.
- Risks: Technology failures, land use concerns, and carbon market uncertainties.
- Co-benefits: Carbon sequestration, emission reductions, and job creation.
- Ambitions: The aim includes sustainable bioenergy production and reduced environmental impact.
- Timing aligns with long-term sustainability goals by 2050 and beyond.

Climate-Smart Rice Production:

- Benefits: Reduced emissions, input costs, and water savings.
- Challenges: Soil degradation, climate risks, and unsustainable practices.
- Co-benefits: Enhanced sustainability, water conservation, and climate resilience.
- Ambitions: Focus on technological advancements and behaviour change.
- Timing emphasizes ongoing awareness campaigns and technology transfer.

Sustainable Agriculture:

- Challenges: Soil degradation, climate risks, unsustainable practices, and education gaps.
- Strategies: Technological integration, education, and agricultural diversification.
- Co-benefits: Reduced carbon footprints, self-sufficiency, and wildlife conservation.
- Ambitions: The aim includes sustainable food production, climate resilience, and ecosystem preservation.
- Timing focuses on ongoing education efforts and technological advancement

8.2.3 Europe

In the European workshops, focused discussions revolved around LMTs such as Afforestation and Forest Management, BECCS, Biochar, Agroforestry, and Cropland Management. These discussions underscored the complexity of scaling up LMTs in Europe, emphasizing the need for clear policies, collaborative efforts, and sustainable practices to overcome challenges and achieve meaningful impact in addressing environmental concerns.

Afforestation and Forest Management:

- Scalability: Challenges due to limited land availability and monoculture risks.
- Risks: Concerns about fire risks impacting carbon sequestration and long-term viability.
- Co-benefits: Biodiversity enhancement and water cycle improvements.
- Ambition: Uncertainty in defining ambition levels and EU-level policy challenges.
- Timing: Future considerations for harmonized carbon accounting guidance and operational scale-up.

BECCS and Biochar:

- Scalability: BECCS potential in key industries but challenges in CO₂ storage collaboration.
- Risks: Energy input challenges for biochar and sourcing sustainability risks.
- Co-benefits: Bioenergy production and negative emissions market creation.
- Ambition: Uncertain levels, emphasizing operational scale-up and sustainable sourcing.
- Timing: Timeline linked to storage challenges and sustainable biomass sourcing.

Agroforestry:

- Scalability: Considered scalable with positive impacts on farmers and farms.
- Risks: Adoption barriers include policy gaps, knowledge gaps, and short-term yield loss concerns.
- Co-benefits: Pest control, erosion prevention, and diversified income sources.
- Ambition: Uncertain levels requiring supportive policies and adoption incentives.
- Timing: Crucial for addressing barriers and promoting adoption for successful implementation.

Cropland Management:

- Scalability: Effective and scalable with sustainability practices.
- Risks: Uncertainties in definitions, energy choices, and systemic impacts.
- Co-benefits: Energy efficiency, waste utilization, and sustainable crop practices.
- Ambition: Policy-making crucial for defining rules and incentivizing practices.
- Timing: Need for addressing uncertainties and promoting sustainable practices for impactful implementation.

8.2.4 Latin America

In Latin America, the discussions centred around crucial Land Management Technologies (LMTs), including biochar implementation, afforestation, sustainable forest management, ecological restoration, and agroforestry. These technologies play pivotal roles in addressing environmental challenges, promoting sustainable land use, and fostering resilience in the face of climate change. The conversations delved into scaling up options, risks, co-benefits, barriers, ambitious goals, and timing considerations specific to these LMTs.

Afforestation, Sustainable Forest Management, Ecological Restoration, and Agroforestry:

- Scalability: Promote regional forest management policies to encourage afforestation and sustainable practices; explore payment mechanisms for environmental ecosystem services to incentivize landowners and communities; ensure the availability of native tree planting material to support afforestation efforts; and develop markets for sustainable forest products to create economic incentives for forest conservation and management.
- Risks: Illegal and unsustainable economic activities, such as deforestation for profit, pose significant threats to forest ecosystems; logistical challenges in sourcing native seedlings and providing rural extension services hinder afforestation and restoration efforts.
- Co-Benefits: Afforestation contributes to carbon sequestration and enhances biodiversity; sustainable forest management ensures ecological balance while providing economic benefits; ecological restoration activities help rehabilitate degraded ecosystems and conserve soil; and

agroforestry improves soil fertility, enhances climate resilience, and diversifies income sources for communities.

- **Barriers:** The absence of regulations aligned with conservation objectives leads to conflicting incentives and unsustainable practices; and perverse incentives favour deforestation over sustainable forest management practices, impacting long-term environmental goals.
- **Ambition:** Halt deforestation and improve sustainable forest use through innovative policies and practices; and promote alternative approaches like improved forest management to achieve long-term conservation and environmental sustainability.
- **Timing:** Immediate actions are needed to address illegal activities and logistical challenges hindering afforestation and sustainable forest management. Long-term strategies focus on achieving sustainable land use practices, conservation goals, and environmental resilience.

Biochar:

- **Scalability:** Facilitate biochar use and demand by implementing supportive regulations and incentives; and develop markets beyond fertilization, focusing on supply chains, demand generation, and pricing strategies.
- **Risks:** The lack of regulatory frameworks in Colombia and Latin America hinders the widespread adoption of biochar; and logistical challenges such as sourcing clean organic feedstocks pose barriers to large-scale biochar production.
- **Co-Benefits:** Biochar offers significant benefits like soil enrichment and long-lasting effects, as evidenced by successful cases such as biochar derived from Brazil nuts in Peru.
- **Barriers:** The absence of essential regulations and standards for biochar use and production; and governance challenges and perverse incentives that favour practices not aligned with sustainable land management.
- **Ambition:** Aim to develop a thriving biochar industry by integrating biochar into sustainable land management practices; and establish biochar as a mainstream solution for soil enrichment and climate resilience
- **Timing:** In the short term, the focus is on developing regulatory frameworks and supply chains. The long-term goal is to establish biochar as a sustainable practice contributing to environmental and agricultural sustainability.

8.3 Regional Engagement

After discussing the LMTs and the barriers and opportunities as well as the risk to their scaling, workshop participants were now invited to discuss how different manifestations of increased *regional engagement*, e.g. regional cooperation and coordination, could drive LMT scaling at the regional level.

Regional engagement discussions in Africa, Asia, Europe, and Latin America highlighted crucial qualifiers like economic integration, formal governance, research cooperation, and technology transfer. Participants stressed collaboration and standardized policies to promote sustainable land management practices and LMT adoption in their regions.

8.3.1 Africa

The African workshop delved into the nuanced aspects of regional engagement in adopting LMTs, focusing on three key qualifiers. Firstly, economic integration and harmonization were highlighted as crucial foundations for fostering collaboration and coherence among East African nations. The discussions underscored the importance of integrated economic strategies and policies to create an enabling environment for shared responsibility in sustainable land management practices. This included exploring mechanisms for fair distribution of costs and benefits, encouraging mutual support, and enhancing financial sustainability through regional funds. Secondly, formal governance mechanisms played a pivotal role in promoting structured collaboration and joint decision-making. Participants emphasized the significance of bilateral agreements, interregional working groups, coordination bodies, and agreements on land use and forest management. These mechanisms were seen as essential enablers for harmonizing policies, fostering information-sharing, and creating a standardized framework that reduces regulatory complexities and uncertainties. Lastly, research cooperation and technology transfer were identified as pivotal drivers for informed decision-making and skill empowerment. Collaborative efforts in research cooperation were deemed essential for building comprehensive understandings of local ecosystems, identifying suitable tree species, and developing effective land management practices. Similarly, technology transfer initiatives were emphasized for disseminating best practices, innovations, and skills across borders, empowering local communities, foresters, and policymakers with the necessary expertise for successful LMT adoption.

8.3.2 Asia

The Asian workshop showcased a diverse range of qualifiers for regional engagement, emphasizing economic integration and harmonization, formal governance mechanisms, and research cooperation and technology transfer. One key qualifier proposed was a carbon crediting mechanism under the Paris Agreement, focusing on bilateral carbon credit markets and cross-border agreements. Participants argued that this mechanism, led by government and private sector collaboration, could incentivize LMT adoption through positive compensation or tax discounts. It was emphasized that implementation requires strong government involvement to address regulatory gaps and national sovereignty concerns, with key actors being governments and private sectors in the region. Regarding regional governance mechanisms, participants discussed the importance of regional quality standards to reduce risks for the private sector in LMT development and enhance scalability. It was discussed that implementing these standards requires trust-based research, regular communication among involved actors, and insights gathering by governments and collaborating businesses. Key actors for this implementation mentioned included regional organizations like ASEAN, large companies, corporations involved in land-related activities, and financial institutes. For research cooperation & technology transfer, network building emerged as a crucial qualifier. It was discussed that transnational networks can advance LMTs by sharing best practices, fostering regional research cooperation, and promoting collaboration within the business sector. Technology transfer, particularly at the community level, was deemed essential for successful LMT adoption. Key actors for driving this cooperation mentioned included ministries, high-level university researchers, local communities, and private businesses, with

a focus on careful management of research networks to mitigate private sector reluctance and ensure knowledge-sharing effectiveness.

8.3.3 Europe

The European workshop discussions delved into three key qualifiers for regional engagement. For *Economic Integration and Harmonization*, the focus was on enhancing trading practices, particularly for BECCS and biochar, by establishing standardized carbon market standards and certifications. This would enable smoother adoption across the region and drive sustainable practices. In terms of *Formal Governance Mechanisms*, there were discussions about establishing integrated working groups throughout the supply chain, fostering public-private collaborations, and ensuring community participation. These mechanisms were considered crucial for successful technology implementation, investment strategies, and effective communication. The discussions on *Research Cooperation & Technology Transfer* highlighted the importance of science-based knowledge, research partnerships, and practical training. Participants noted that these elements play a vital role in informed decision-making, policy development, and addressing uncertainties related to LMTs. The workshop emphasized the need for robust research collaborations, training programs, and knowledge-sharing platforms to facilitate the adoption of sustainable land management practices across Europe.

8.3.4 Latin America

There was a discussion of participants on regional engagement in Latin America workshop with emphasis on green certifications and good practices, such as those seen in Brazil's Emissions Reduction Market (MBRE). Participants highlighted the benefits of stronger qualifiers like coordinated action through intergovernmental panels and specialised funds for technologies like afforestation, reforestation, and agroforestry. It was stated that implementing these qualifiers requires political commitment, clear regulations, knowledge transfer, and the involvement of key actors such as regional bodies, companies specialized in environmental investments, and multilateral institutions like the Inter-American Development Bank (IADB).

Challenges identified include bureaucratic hurdles, policy short-termism, and the need for stronger forestry services. To overcome these barriers, participants suggested facilitating market connections, promoting associativity, encouraging fair trade practices, enhancing market intelligence, and developing domestic markets. Formal governance mechanisms like working groups led by organizations such as FAO and regional agreements like the Leticia Pact and CAN regional strategy were seen as crucial for strengthening LMT adoption. Participants emphasised that overcoming leadership and monitoring challenges requires replicating successful mechanisms from other regional organizations and creating platforms for the exchange of genetic resources and biological material.

9 Regional Narratives

The level of CDR ambition (moderate vs. high) and the level of regional engagement (current, improved, and/or high) were used to structure different narratives that describe a set of future pathways that are representative of stakeholder deliberations. Up to four narratives were developed for each of the regions and are outlined below, in accordance with Table 10. Limiting the narratives to four was in part related to the emphasis on going beyond baseline CDR ambition and beyond current

levels of regional engagement (the shaded box in Table 10). However, neither the stakeholders nor the research team steered the results so as to place one narrative in a given box or aim to create a one-to-one relation; instead, the results were left more open to consider other environment, climate and development priorities, such as biodiversity or food security. It is also possible that ambition stagnates and does not go much beyond the baseline. With such considerations, it is possible for example to have two narratives that have the same level of CDR ambition, but through improved regional engagement, may achieve better in terms of food security, biodiversity or other sustainable development priorities. In this way, more freedom of expression is extended to workshop participants. For practical reasons, it is also useful to limit to four, considering the overall scope of the exercise.

Table 10: Alternative narratives or storylines according to CDR ambition and regional engagement

	CDR Ambition		
Regional Engagement	<i>Baseline or Low ambition</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>			
<i>Improved</i>	N/A		
<i>High</i>	N/A		

Stakeholders were informed on baseline and current conditions in the inception reports (Annex C: Inception/Background Reports) and presentations and then with the help of workshop facilitators, they developed detailed content taking inspiration from the four shaded boxes in Table 10. The research team developed the narratives¹ in each case based on an analysis of the stakeholder-provided content, in conjunction with the physical and socio-economic conditions outlined in the background report alongside the constraints on internal consistency imposed by the modelling results. There are some differences in the descriptive elements of the narratives across the regions and the eventual manifestation in the resulting scheme (i.e. placement of narratives within these dimensions) but the design structure (regional engagement vs. CDR ambition) is the same.

9.1 Africa

Based on the evidence and the workshops results, the East African context required consideration for all three levels of ambition: baseline or low, as well as moderate and high ambition. The placement of the narratives in the structure is shown in Table 11. For the implementation with respect to local, national and regional levels, there was a distinction between bottom-up and top-down approach, with the latter requiring improved regional engagement. There was also an emphasis on high regional engagement that aims for broader development goals, as opposed to one that maximises the opportunities for transition to high CDR regime. The fact that the high ambition column is empty for the East African case is logical from an ethical or historical responsibility perspective under the UNFCCC, i.e. that countries in this region should not have high responsibility for climate mitigation.

¹ We use only the term “narratives” henceforth in this section and not “storylines”, as they are developed *ex-post* with respect to the workshop and are different from the storylines that were presented *ex-ante* to workshop participants and that are discussed in LANDMARC D6.2 in relation to the framework for modeling/simulations.

Table 11: Alternative narratives for East Africa according to CDR ambition and regional engagement

Regional Engagement	CDR Ambition		
	<i>Baseline or Low ambition</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>	<i>Narrative C</i>	<i>Narrative A</i>	
<i>Improved</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative B</i>	
<i>High</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative D</i>	

9.1.1 Narrative A: Community led approach for scaling of agroforestry, afforestation, reforestation in East Africa

In this narrative, agroforestry, afforestation, and reforestation are key components of the grassroots initiatives championed by local communities in East Africa. Indigenous groups, smallholder farmers, and community-based organizations leverage traditional knowledge and sustainable land management practices to spearhead these efforts. Through community-led efforts, degraded forests are rehabilitated, and native tree species are reintroduced, enhancing habitat connectivity, protecting watersheds, and supporting wildlife populations. Governments and NGOs play a supportive role by providing capacity-building opportunities, facilitating land tenure reform to ensure community ownership and stewardship of natural resources, and offering financial incentives to incentivize participation in community-led conservation initiatives. This collaborative approach ensures a sense of ownership and empowerment among local communities, leading to a groundswell of bottom-up action aimed at restoring degraded ecosystems, conserving biodiversity, and mitigating climate change through the adoption of agroforestry, afforestation, reforestation and other land-based mitigation technologies such as biochar in the East Africa region. This shows the intrinsic link between social equity, cultural preservation, and the successful scaling of land-based mitigation technologies and practices in East Africa. Through their collective efforts, local communities become the driving force behind meaningful impact in LMT scaling, contributing to the sustainable management of land resources for generations to come.

9.1.2 Narrative B: Policy-led transition

The narrative centres on policy-led transition. In this storyline, ambitious policy interventions drive the scaling of LMT in East Africa, with governments taking a proactive role in setting targets, implementing regulations, and mobilizing resources. Comprehensive land-use planning, coupled with robust carbon pricing mechanisms and subsidy reforms, incentivize the adoption of agroforestry, sustainable rangeland management, afforestation, and reforestation across sectors. Regional cooperation frameworks facilitate knowledge exchange, harmonization of policies, and cross-border collaboration on shared environmental challenges. As a result, East Africa will achieve significant emissions reductions from land use activities, while simultaneously unlocking economic opportunities and promoting inclusive development. Hence, the importance of strong political will and effective governance structures in catalysing the transition towards sustainable land management practices that are implemented at scale.

9.1.3 Narrative C: Resource-constrained realities

The third narrative is characterised by a lack of resources and financial support for scaling LMTs. In this scenario, East Africa grapples with persistent challenges such as limited financial resources, formal institutional capacity constraints, and competing development priorities, hampering the scaling of LMTs. Governments face trade-offs between short-term economic imperatives and long-term environmental sustainability, leading to insufficient investment in LMT scaling efforts such as agroforestry. International support is sporadic and fragmented, failing to adequately address the complex socio-economic and environmental dynamics in the region. As a result, progress in scaling LMTs remain slow and uneven, exacerbating vulnerabilities to climate change and environmental degradation. There is an unfulfilled need for proper environment for targeted interventions to overcome systemic barriers and mobilize resources effectively, ensuring that the region can unlock the full potential of LMT in addressing climate change and sustainable development goals.

9.1.4 Narrative D: Strong regional engagement supports ambition

The fourth narrative from the workshop is on the need for strong regional engagement required for increasing CDR/climate ambition in East Africa. In this storyline, East African countries prioritize regional cooperation over ambitious climate targets. This emphasizes the need for government to recognize the interconnectedness of environmental challenges in the East Africa region and work together to implement shared strategies for land-based mitigation. Regional initiatives focus on ecosystem restoration, sustainable agriculture, and community-led conservation efforts. While climate ambition may not be as high in the region, the collective approach leads to significant progress in reducing emissions and enhancing resilience to climate change. International partners play a supportive role, providing technical expertise and financial resources to amplify regional efforts. This narrative underscores the importance of inclusive governance structures and participatory decision-making processes to ensure that land-based mitigation benefits all stakeholders in East Africa.

9.2 Southeast Asia

The cultural, physical and socio-economic diversity of Southeast Asia tends to add some complications to increased regional engagement and thus the “Current” level remains a feasible narrative, as suggested in Table 12. Improved regional engagement can enable alternative pathways for CDR that require cooperation on infrastructure investment, namely BECCS. More details are provided below.

Table 12: Alternative narratives for Southeast Asia according to CDR ambition and regional engagement

Regional Engagement	CDR Ambition		
	<i>Baseline or Low ambition</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>		<i>Narrative A</i>	
<i>Improved</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative B</i>	
<i>High</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative C</i>	<i>Narrative D</i>

9.2.1 Narrative/Storyline A: biochar and bioenergy production is connected well with agroforestry and forest waste utilisation.

The first narrative emerging from the workshop discussions emphasizes the symbiotic relationship between biochar and bioenergy production with the utilization of waste from agroforestry and afforestation. This narrative utilises a circular economy approach where waste materials from agroforestry and afforestation are not viewed as mere byproducts but as valuable resources for biochar and bioenergy production. The integration of these processes contributes to enhancing soil fertility through biochar, while simultaneously generating renewable energy, showcasing a model of sustainable land management that leverages synergies between different land based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs).

This model not only addresses the challenge of waste management in agricultural and forestry operations but also contributes to carbon sequestration and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through biochar soil amendments and the production of clean energy. The approach exemplifies how interconnected LMTs can create multiple environmental benefits, including improved land productivity, biodiversity conservation, and resilience to climate change.

Furthermore, the narrative highlights the potential for creating new economic opportunities and fostering rural development. By integrating biochar and bioenergy production with agroforestry and afforestation practices, communities benefit from diversified income streams, enhanced food security, and increased access to clean energy. This comprehensive approach to land management and waste utilization, although not necessarily requiring significant increase in regional engagement, does present a forward-looking model for sustainable development in Southeast Asia, balancing ecological integrity with economic viability and social well-being.

9.2.2 Narrative/Storyline B: Enabling environment for BECCS implementation is created in next 10 years by connecting with existing LMTs.

The second storyline from the workshop discussions centres on creating an enabling environment for BECCS implementation within the next decade, through regional cooperation that facilitates synergies with existing biochar, bioenergy, and waste utilization practices in the AFOLU sector. This approach emphasizes the strategic integration of BECCS into the current landscape of sustainable land management across the region, aiming to capitalize on the established infrastructure and knowledge base related to biochar production and bioenergy generation.

The narrative suggests that fostering a conducive environment for BECCS involves addressing technological, regulatory, and financial challenges, while simultaneously drawing on the strengths of biochar and bioenergy practices to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of carbon capture and storage technologies. This forward-looking perspective advocates for collaborative efforts among government, industry, and research institutions to develop policies, incentivize innovations, and mobilize investments that support the transition towards a low-carbon economy.

Furthermore, the storyline underscores the importance of holistic approaches that consider the lifecycle emissions, energy balances, and socio-economic impacts of integrating BECCS with biochar

and bioenergy production. By focusing on waste utilization from the AFOLU sector, this narrative not only aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions but also promotes sustainable land management practices that enhance soil health, biodiversity, and rural livelihoods, contributing to the broader goals of climate change mitigation and sustainable development in Southeast Asia.

9.2.3 Narrative/Storyline C: Biodiversity protection with high ambitions of afforestation and agroforestry by scaling out best practices

The third storyline developed during the workshop focuses on enhancing biodiversity protection through ambitious afforestation and agroforestry projects, emphasizing the scaling out, i.e. replication, of best practices. This narrative recognizes the critical role of biodiversity in ensuring ecosystem resilience and the provision of ecosystem services vital for human well-being and climate mitigation efforts. By adopting and expanding upon proven agroforestry and afforestation techniques, the strategy aims to create more diverse and sustainable landscapes that support a wide range of species, including those at risk of extinction.

Scaling out these best practices involves not only the replication of successful models across different regions but also the adaptation of these models to suit local ecological and socio-economic conditions. This approach ensures that afforestation and agroforestry projects contribute positively to local communities, offering economic benefits while preserving natural habitats. The emphasis on community involvement and Indigenous knowledge in the planning and implementation phases is crucial for the success and sustainability of these initiatives.

Moreover, this storyline highlights the importance of integrated land management policies that support biodiversity conservation alongside climate mitigation and adaptation objectives. By fostering synergies between afforestation, agroforestry, and biodiversity protection, Southeast Asia moves towards a more holistic approach to environmental stewardship, ensuring that efforts to combat climate change also contribute to the preservation and enhancement of the region's rich biological diversity.

9.2.4 Narrative/Storyline D: high climate ambitions with high regional engagement to improve implementation and knowledge transfer

The fourth storyline elaborates on the necessity for high climate ambition to be matched with high regional engagement, to boost implementation and facilitate knowledge transfer. This narrative underlines the importance of collaborative efforts across Southeast Asia, urging nations to not only set ambitious climate targets but also actively participate in regional initiatives that foster the sharing of insights, technologies, and best practices. Such engagement is crucial for overcoming the technical, financial, and policy barriers to effective climate action.

Emphasizing the role of knowledge transfer, the storyline advocates for the establishment of platforms and networks that enable the exchange of information and experiences related to land mitigation technologies and sustainable land management practices. This approach aims to accelerate the

adoption of innovative solutions across the region, enhancing the capacity of countries to meet their climate objectives.

Finally, the narrative calls for strengthening partnerships between governments, the private sector, civil society, and international organizations. These collaborations are essential for mobilizing resources, driving technological advancements, and implementing effective policies that support the region’s transition towards a more sustainable and climate-resilient future.

9.3 European Union

Unlike the other regions, the EU already has a high level of regional engagement due to the mature institutions for economic integration and regional cooperation. It is also assumed that moderate and high CDR ambition must be considered, to be consistent with EU emissions reduction targets and to acknowledge UNFCCC obligations. Along with the expectations for increasing ambition significantly, an even higher level of regional engagement could enhance CDR ambition by aiming to optimise LMT portfolios across the regional rather than emphasising national approaches. High reliance on BECCS is considered essential for achieving high ambition due in part to limited land area, population density, and high standards of living. The narratives thus cover the four cases as shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Alternative narratives for the EU according to CDR ambition and regional engagement

Regional Engagement	CDR Ambition		
	<i>Baseline or Low ambition</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>
<i>Improved</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative A</i>	<i>Narrative B</i>
<i>High</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative C</i>	<i>Narrative D</i>

9.3.1 Narrative/Storyline A: Forest protection and forestry residues for BECCS

EU regulation has enabled the preservation of forests across the region; however, increasing temperatures and limited forestry practices within the agricultural sector increases the difficulty in managing wildfires.

Under current levels of regional engagement, the use of residual woody biomass is deemed necessary for the implementation of BECCS across the European region. BECCS is considered as essential for achieving negative emissions in Europe. Residual woody biomass has the potential to produce bioenergy and the capture and sequestration of carbon dioxide emissions. The expected removal of emissions under a scenario with moderate ambition using BECCS would represent around 3 million tonnes CO₂-eq per year sequestered in Sweden by 2045, with additional commercial plants in other parts of Europe where discussions for the technology have been ongoing including Finland, Denmark and Germany. Energy utilities lead the use of BECCS across Europe and emission removals regulated in a negative emissions market, where countries and private actors are able to trade.

9.3.2 Narrative/Storyline B: Ambitious scaling-up of BECCS and embracing agroforestry

Woody biomass waste is integrated into the development of BECCS across Europe with a notable higher ambition in the Nordics. The increased ambition leads to scaling up BECCS in the energy sector removing more than 10 million tonnes of CO₂-eq per year. Sweden alone removes approximately 10 million CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Additional efforts by other European nations add up to this number and contribute to emission removal in the region. Reaching this level is possible due to parallel efforts including the introduction of enabling policies for the use of forest residues, de-risking of investments, ensuring agreements withing Europe for underground storage of emissions, and enabling a market for negative emissions. The energy utilities continue to be in the lead of emission removal using BECCS and the pulp and paper sector use their own residues to enter the negative emission market. Pilot plants in the pulp and paper sector across Europe start to operate.

There is an increasing trend on the use of agroforestry practice for southern European nations where woody biomass residues are less abundant and thus constrained to local availability BECCS is not attractive for that region. Benefits of integrating agroforestry in agriculture and food production are acknowledged and are more common.

9.3.3 Narrative/Storyline C: Improved forest management across Europe contributes to risk prevention and climate resilience

Forest management resumes a crucial role in emission reduction in Europe. Although European countries have explored the possibility of implementing afforestation across the continent, there is a consensus that the strategy does not fit all countries due to space constraints and forest type variability (i.e., forests differ between the Iberian Peninsula, Eastern Europe, and Nordic regions). The EU and its Member States have been prompted to implement alternative strategies for carbon storage. The region agrees to prioritise forest management over afforestation. Ensuring effective carbon storage in trees and mitigating risks like fires and droughts becomes a primary focus. European countries, as a result, actively promote forest management initiatives by creating training opportunities for farmers. This approach aims to bridge the knowledge gap between agriculture and forestry, fostering meaningful efforts across the continent. Industries reliant on forest resources express interest in participating in the negative emissions market. Notably, pulp and paper industries in the Nordics take a proactive step by deploying their own full scale BECCS facilities. This allows the pulp and paper industry to leverage residual woody biomass for both energy generation and carbon dioxide capture. The expanded use of BECCS in these industries increases the potential for technology transfer beyond the Nordic regions.

9.3.4 Narrative/Storyline D: high ambition, high engagement to enhance carbon removal in energy, forestry and agriculture sectors

Europe has a high level of ambition and a robust engagement between countries in the region. The practise of agroforestry is commonly used by farmers, bringing positive effects to fire risk minimisation. Likewise, forest management gained a critical role through the continent and is prioritized. Forest

products are used in a sustainable way meaning that woody biomass waste is also employed by different sectors for the production of energy and the removal of carbon dioxide emissions.

The recognition of agroforestry’s substantial potential for tree conservation and carbon dioxide capture underscores the necessity for expansive certification schemes. Targets to the short and long terms are stated in Europe’s regional roadmap for agroforestry implementation. Europe’s leadership on agroforestry is fortified by regulatory measures pertaining to crop management, which seek to standardize practices like organic agriculture, reduced tillage, and conservation agriculture. Certification schemes play a pivotal role by endorsing farms that comply with these standards, solidifying agriculture’s significant contribution with negative emissions to Europe’s carbon inventories.

Simultaneously, policymakers in Europe recognize the need of evaluating the forestry sector through a separate lens in the case of the Nordics, which have a high potential but also need to be preserved and used wisely. Legislative frameworks promoting the balanced use of wood resources and mandating the utilization of biomass residues are endorsed. These conditions allow BECCS to thrive both in the energy utility and in pulp and paper industries of the region.

9.4 Latin America

The placement of Narratives for Latin America is provided in Table 14.

Table 14: Alternative narratives for Latin America (ACTO) according to CDR ambition and regional engagement

	CDR Ambition		
Regional Engagement	<i>Baseline or Low ambition</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>
<i>Improved</i>	<i>Narrative A</i>	<i>Narrative B</i>	
<i>High</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Narrative C</i>	<i>Narrative D</i>

The Amazon region is a resource shared by the eight ACTO countries and its significance for climate and biodiversity means that regional engagement will have to be improved, even though this does not necessarily translate into increased CDR ambition. Consequently, the column for baseline or low ambition is maintained as feasible. Other options can raise ambition, as shown in Table 14.

9.4.1 Narrative/Storyline A: Strengthening governance and funding

With financing and effective governance mechanism led by ACTO and adhered to by the countries, exchange of information and knowledge, regulation, and facilitation of the implementation of CDR technologies is achieved. This effective exchange is based on technological integration between research institutes with rural extension and technical assistance tools as well as agencies promoting sustainable forest management. Markets that meet the needs of communities are expected to be accessed through organized value chains.

9.4.2 Narrative/Storyline B: Amazon deforestation is reduced

Commitment within countries to institutional presence in the region has improved. Command and control policies are more coordinated with social, environmental, and economic policies in the region

and the deforestation in the Amazon is reduced. Policies promote natural forest economies with financial and science, technology and innovation (STI) instruments that are available to small producers and local enterprises and associations. Economic alternatives based on sustainable forest management, including timber, non-timber forest products and nature tourism are strengthened. Barriers of land tenure, financing and standardized norms are overcome. Private, academic and governmental actors promote the adoption of LMTs and develop markets and value chains.

9.4.3 Narrative/Storyline C: Best practices and innovation

Standards and best practices for natural forest management, agroforestry systems, ecological restoration and forest and non-forest production are established. Technical assistance is targeted at small producers through specialised agencies. Integration and sustainability agreements across the value chain lead to generation of value-added products and expansion of high-value markets, and enhanced market intelligence for forest and non-forest products.

9.4.4 Narrative/Storyline D: Amazon bioeconomy

Deforestation has been controlled and minimised in this scenario. The bioeconomy is the predominant model in the Amazon, based on the sustainable use of the forest for value-added products and services for the food, cosmetics, pharmaceutical and nature tourism industries. LMT such as sustainable management of natural forests, ecological restoration, biochar and agroforestry systems predominates. The welfare of rural populations has increased. The conservation of biodiversity and its sustainable use is profitable for people and companies, in this way the forest remains standing generating material and non-material benefits. A mature, productive, and sustainable Amazon bioeconomy achieves high conservation as well as high CDR ambition.

10 Conclusions

Achieving the 1.5° or 2°C targets of the Paris Agreement is expected to require significant levels of CDR in the future, with land-based mitigation technologies and measures being the most significant, especially in the global South where land use change is a major source of emissions and sustainable land use management is critical for achieving multiple SDGs. Climate ambition for CDR through land-based mitigation could potentially be enhanced through regional engagement, as suggested by stakeholder engagement conducted at regional level for Africa, Asia, Europe and Latin America. The stakeholder workshops drew on modelling and analysis of various mechanisms and pathways for CDR/climate ambition. The widely applicable and/or nature-based LMTs were deemed particularly important due to biodiversity and rural development goals and can in some contexts be accomplished in a more decentralised fashion, while novel LMTs such as BECCS require more extensive regional engagement. The stakeholder narratives developed across the four regions provide a better understanding on the evolution of CDR/climate ambition and how regional engagement can facilitate such ambitions. Future research could seek to embed stakeholders at earlier stages in the process so as to consider more detailed pathways for regional engagement to enhance or increase CDR ambition.

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ANNEX A: CONSULTATIONS

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ANNEX A1: PRE-CONSULTATION SURVEY

LANDMARC - Survey for stakeholder consultations

This survey should only take 20 minutes of your time.

LANDMARC is an EU financed research project consisting of nineteen partners from all over the world. LANDMARC combines satellite data, soil measurements and climate and econometric model efforts with social sciences approaches to better understand the potential of land-based mitigation technologies and practices.

This survey combined with upcoming stakeholder consultations held in 5 platforms (Europe North, Europe South, Africa, Asia, Latin America) will enrich the models and inform decision-making at regional and global levels.

You have been invited to participate in one of the 5 continental platforms of LANDMARC. Platforms cover vast geographical areas. Please answer this survey for a region that covers best your area of knowledge and expertise. The results of this survey will be discussed during the first online consultation.

In this survey you will rate LMTs in your region according to six criteria:

1. CO2 removal potential
2. Climate risk exposure and permanence potential
3. Biodiversity and ecosystems impacts
4. Socio-economic impacts
5. Capacity for implementation and Administration: barriers and opportunities
6. Public acceptance and citizen participation: barriers and opportunities

The survey invites you to do this ranking twice: the first time thinking of the timeframe until 2050 and the second time for the timeframe from 2050 until 2100. Your answers will be used for long-term forecasting modelers.

We thank you for your time and input and look forward to discussing the results of this survey during our online consultation in one of our 5 platforms.

LANDMARC team

Disclaimer & Data protection:

In submitting this form, I agree that the information provided by me is being used for the purposes of contributing to an international research project. The information will only be accessed by necessary research staff. I understand my data will be held securely and will not be distributed to third parties. I have a right to change or access my information. I understand that when this information is no longer required for this purpose, official procedure will be followed to dispose of my data. My data will be used

anonymously, however, I am able to voluntarily provide researchers with my contact details.

Which part of the world are you answering for?

LANDMARC aims to gather a variety of viewpoints from different countries and regions. Please indicate the country/region you are most familiar with, not necessarily the country/region you are currently based

1. Which LANDMARC continental platform are you participating in? *

- Africa
- Asia
- Latin America
- Europe North
- Europe South

2. When answering this survey, which region are you answering for? *

- The whole of Africa
- EasternAfrica*
- NorthernAfrica*
- Western Africa
- Southern Africa
- The whole of Asia
- South Asia
- South East Asia
- East Asia
- Central Asia
- The whole of Latin America
- South America
- The Carribbean
- North America
- Northern Europe

3. Which country are you most knowledgeable about? *

Rating of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) until 2050

LANDMARC studies all LMTs worldwide. The project pays particular attention to afforestation, agroforestry, biochar, organic agriculture and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) for the models. This is why we are looking at these five LMTs in this survey.

This first series of questions looks into the timeframe from today until 2050.

4. Rate your knowledge of each LMT for your region

	None	Some	Moderate	High
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. Rate the following six criteria by importance for any LMT. What matters the most for LMTs to be successful in your opinion for your region?

	Doesn't matter	Matters a little	Matters moderately	Matters a lot	I don't know
CO2 Removal potential	<input type="radio"/>				
Climate risk exposure and permanence potential	<input type="radio"/>				
Biodiversity and ecosystem services impacts	<input type="radio"/>				
Socio-economic impacts	<input type="radio"/>				
Capacity for implementation and administration: barriers and opportunities	<input type="radio"/>				
Public acceptance and citizen participation: barriers and opportunities	<input type="radio"/>				

6. CO2 Removal potential: Does the LMT have potential to cost-effectively remove CO2 in your region (from today until 2050)?

	No removal potential	Less removal potential	Moderate removal potential	High removal potential	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Permanence and climate risk exposure: Does the LMT have potential to store CO2 permanently, taking into consideration climate risks for your region (from today until 2050)?

	No permanence potential	Less permanence potential	Moderate permanence potential	High permanence potential	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services: How will biodiversity and ecosystem services be impacted by this LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3).

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>						
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>						
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>						
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>						
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>						

9. Impacts on society and economy: How will society and the economy be impacted by this LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3).

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>						
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>						
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>						
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>						
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>						

10. Barriers and opportunities, capacity for implementation and administration: Is there human and institutional capacity in your region to deploy this LMT (from today until 2050)? is the administrative framework supporting the deployment?

	No capacity	Less capacity	Moderate capacity	High capacity	I don't know
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>				
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>				
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>				
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>				
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>				

11. Barriers and opportunities, public acceptance and citizen participation: Is the general public in favour of the deployment of the LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? are citizens willing to participate in the deployment of the LMT?

	No acceptance	Limited acceptance	Moderate acceptance	High acceptance	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>				
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>				
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>				
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>				
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>				

12. Would you like to add any qualifying comments with regards to your answers for the period up to 2050?

Rating of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) from 2050 until 2100

13. CO2 Removal potential: Does the LMT have potential to cost-effectively remove CO2 in your region (from 2050 and 2100)?

	No removal potential	Less removal potential	Moderate removal potential	High removal potential	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. Permanence and climate risk exposure: Does the LMT have potential to store CO2 permanently, taking into consideration climate risks for your region (from 2050 until 2100)?

	No permanenc e potential	Less permanenc e potential	Moderate permanenc e potential	High permanenc e potential	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services: How will biodiversity and ecosystem services be impacted by this LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3).

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>						
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>						
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>						
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>						
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>						

16. Impacts on society and economy: How will society and the economy be impacted by this LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3).

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>						
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>						
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>						
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>						
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>						

17. Barriers and opportunities, capacity for implementation and administration: Is there human and institutional capacity in your region to deploy this LMT (from 2050 until 2100)? is the administrative framework supporting the deployment?

	No capacity	Less capacity	Moderate capacity	High capacity	I don't know
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>				
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>				
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>				
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>				
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Barriers and opportunities, public acceptance and citizen participation: Is the general public in favour of the deployment of the LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? are citizens willing to participate in the deployment of the LMT?

	No acceptance	Limited acceptance	Moderate acceptance	High acceptance	I don't know
BECCS	<input type="radio"/>				
Afforestation/ Reforestation	<input type="radio"/>				
Agroforestry	<input type="radio"/>				
Biochar	<input type="radio"/>				
Organic Agriculture	<input type="radio"/>				

19. Would you like to add any qualifying comments with regards to your answers for the period from 2050 to 2100?

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

ANNEX A2: PRE-CONSULTATION SURVEY RESULTS

LANDMARC - Survey for stakeholder consultations

43
Responses

160:56
Average time to complete

Active
Status

1. Which LANDMARC continental platform are you participating in? (0 point)

● Africa	10
● Asia	7
● Latin America	14
● Europe North	11
● Europe South	1

2. When answering this survey, which region are you answering for? (0 point)

● The whole of Africa	1
● EasternAfrica	7
● NorthernAfrica	0
● Western Africa	1
● Southern Africa	0
● The whole of Asia	0
● South Asia	1
● South East Asia	7
● East Asia	0
● Central Asia	0
● The whole of Latin America	1
● South America	11
● The Carribbean	2
● North America	2
● Northern Europe	10

3. Which country are you most knowledgeable about? (0 point)

43
Responses

Latest Responses

- "Brazil"
- "Brazil"
- "Colombia"

10 respondents (23%) answered **Colombia** for this question.

4. Rate your knowledge of each LMT for your region (0 point)

None Some Moderate High

5. Rate the following six criteria by importance for any LMT. What matters the most for LMTs to be successful in your opinion for your region? (0 point)

Doesn't matter Matters a little Matters moderately Matters a lot I don't know

6. CO2 Removal potential: Does the LMT have potential to cost-effectively remove CO2 in your region (from today until 2050)? (0 point)

■ No removal potential
 ■ Less removal potential
 ■ Moderate removal potential
 ■ High removal potential
 ■ I don't know

7. Permanence and climate risk exposure: Does the LMT have potential to store CO2 permanently, taking into consideration climate risks for your region (from today until 2050)? (0 point)

■ No permanence potential
 ■ Less permanence potential
 ■ Moderate permanence potential
 ■ High permanence potential
 ■ I don't know

8. Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services: How will biodiversity and ecosystem services be impacted by this LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3). (0 point)

Legend: -3 (dark orange), -2 (orange), -1 (light orange), 0 (grey), 1 (light blue), 2 (medium blue), 3 (dark blue)

9. Impacts on society and economy: How will society and the economy be impacted by this LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3). (0 point)

Legend: -3 (dark orange), -2 (orange), -1 (light orange), 0 (grey), 1 (light blue), 2 (medium blue), 3 (dark blue)

10. Barriers and opportunities, capacity for implementation and administration: Is there human and institutional capacity in your region to deploy this LMT (from today until 2050)? is the administrative framework supporting the deployment? (0 point)

11. Barriers and opportunities, public acceptance and citizen participation: Is the general public in favour of the deployment of the LMT in your region (from today until 2050)? are citizens willing to participate in the deployment of the LMT? (0 point)

12. Would you like to add any qualifying comments with regards to your answers for the period up to 2050? (0 point)

17 Responses

Latest Responses

"Brazil is a country with different realities. It has a robust legal structu..."

Update

3 respondents (18%) answered **uncertainty** for this question.

13. CO2 Removal potential: Does the LMT have potential to cost-effectively remove CO2 in your region (from 2050 and 2100)? (0 point)

■ No removal potential
 ■ Less removal potential
 ■ Moderate removal potential
 ■ High removal potential
 ■ I don't know

14. Permanence and climate risk exposure: Does the LMT have potential to store CO2 permanently, taking into consideration climate risks for your region (from 2050 until 2100)? (0 point)

■ No permanence potential
 ■ Less permanence potential
 ■ Moderate permanence potential
■ High permanence potential
 ■ I don't know

15. Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services: How will biodiversity and ecosystem services be impacted by this LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3). (0 point)

■ -3
 ■ -2
 ■ -1
 ■ 0
 ■ 1
 ■ 2
 ■ 3

16. Impacts on society and economy: How will society and the economy be impacted by this LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? You may consider impacts to be highly negative (-3) up to highly positive (3). (0 point)

17. Barriers and opportunities, capacity for implementation and administration: Is there human and institutional capacity in your region to deploy this LMT (from 2050 until 2100)? is the administrative framework supporting the deployment? (0 point)

18. Barriers and opportunities, public acceptance and citizen participation: Is the general public in favour of the deployment of the LMT in your region (from 2050 until 2100)? are citizens willing to participate in the deployment of the LMT? (0 point)

19. Would you like to add any qualifying comments with regards to your answers for the period from 2050 to 2100? (0 point)

10 Responses

Latest Responses

[Update](#)

2 respondents (20%) answered **uncertainty** for this question.

uncertainty in these answers **socio-economic risk of bias priorities and lack**
Hard to foresee implementation of forestry agroforestry and afforestation **European count**
fort and wild benefit greatly **uncertainty** **forestry and agroforestry**
ecosystem restoration **scale of implementation** **implementation of agroforestry** **emission purpo**
uncertainty regarding scenarios **greatly improve** **degrees of uncertainty**
access to tec

ANNEX A3 - PRE-CONSULTATION SURVEY RESULTS DISCUSSION

This section highlights some of the initial findings and trends that could be identified through the survey results, based on the response of 43 individuals.

The element that was generally considered to be crucial when it comes to the success of LMTs in the different regions, is the socio-economic impact of the development of any given LMT. The other factors that were considered rather important by most respondents were biodiversity and ecosystem services impacts, as well as the capacity for implementation and administration. Respondents generally indicated that elements such as CO₂ removal potential, climate risk exposure and permanence potential, as well as public acceptance and citizen participation were also important, but the view that these are important to a lesser extent was slightly more common among respondents.

Afforestation/reforestation came out on top of the LMT list when respondents assessed cost-effective CO₂ removal. When it came to biochar, agroforestry, and organic agriculture, a larger share of respondents thought that potential to be lower. BECCS was deemed to have a good cost-effective CO₂ removal potential, but a larger share of respondents indicated not being knowledgeable about this technology.

Respondents' views on permanence of carbon capture reflected findings from literature, with afforestation/reforestation, and agroforestry offering the highest permanence potential, organic agriculture the lowest, and uncertainty with regard to the permanence potential of BECCS and biochar.

While all surveyed LMTs were generally considered to benefit the economy and society, BECCS and afforestation/reforestation were indicated to pose potential biodiversity and ecosystem services risks.

The relative technological character and infrastructural investment cost of technologies such as BECCS and biochar was reflected in respondents' answers about current capacity and institutional support, rating these technologies lower in terms of capacity for deployment.

BECCS was singled out when it comes to public acceptance, as the only LMT with significantly limited acceptance.

Finally, respondents highlighted the fact that there is a large element of uncertainty that comes with foreseeing scenarios about the development of LMTs on a timescale of multiple decennia into the future. This was particularly the case for questions aimed at the more distant period 2050-2100, but was also mentioned for the period present-2050. Evaluations of the importance or impact of different elements regarding the LMTs or their potential were similar for both periods of time.

ANNEX A4 - REGIONAL CONSULTATION PRESENTATION GUIDE

Annex A4: Regional consultation presentation guide

Slide 1

Welcome to the first regional consultation on land mitigation technologies for the LANDMARC project

Slide 2

LANDMARC is a European Commission financed research project with nineteen partners from all over the world. We combine satellite data, soil measurements and climate- and econometric model efforts with social-sciences approaches to better understand the potential of land-based mitigation technologies and practices.

Slide 3

Mention type of organisations and countries the partners come from

Slide 4

Go through agenda, ask if there are any questions

Slide 5

Launch poll from the teams app. Allow 2 minutes for answers to come in, briefly discuss them afterwards and say these helps with future events as well

Slide 6

- Challenges and opportunities when it comes to LMT adoption and scaling will be highly context specific —> **regional engagement needed**
- The regional stakeholder consultations aim to obtain qualitative characterisations (narratives) for each region but they also aim to extract some quantitative information from the participants based on their knowledge of different LMTs. This information should assist modelling efforts with respect to assumptions and parameters for scaling up LMTs in each region.

Slide 7

Now short about the tolls and methods we use in the project...

Slide 8

In-situ and remote sensing

Slide 9

Go through bullet list and then mention model areas of focus

Mention: "we will focus on the modelling results in the next consultation where some preliminary modelling results will be presented for you to give feedback and suggestions for adjustments for better regional focus"

Slide 10

Overview of map, start from the local CS and then discuss the platforms

Slide 11

We have reviewed the literature and interviewed stakeholders for selecting the most relevant LMTs for Northern Europe and Canada. And now Olle will help us take a close on these selected LMTs

Slide 12-18

Olle's slides

Check participants and prepare break-out rooms

Slide 19

And now that we have an overview of these LMTs, let's see how we work with them in the LANDMARC project as part of the national case study portfolios.

***share links to CS from Landmarc page*

Slide 20

We have 4 examples from Canada, Germany, The Netherlands and Sweden.

Slide 21-22-23

Call CS leads to shortly present their CS slide (1-2 minutes)

Slide 24

Present Sweden

Biochar and BECCS are most profitable under the most ambitious scenarios of implementation, meaning wide policy support and incentives for their implementation, as well as well-functioning carbon and heat sales in the market which would lead to positive NPVs. With the exception of the most ambitious scenario for BECCS implementation, heating sales are the main source of income for these systems.

Slide 25

So before we move on, I would like to show you the plan for the regional platform consultations..

**go through the 3 phases*

Slide 26

And now, let's see some of the results from the survey we asked you to fill before this session. We got 14 answers in total, feel free to comment or ask questions as I show some results.

Slide 27

Most of you have knowledge about afforestation and reforestations, followed by agroforestry and organic agriculture. Biochar seems to be the one we have less experts on here with us today, hope we have some good discussions.

Slide 28

Considering biodiversity impacts, CO2 removal potential and climate risk exposure and permanence are the factors most important for LMTs to be successful according to the responses here.

Slide 29-32

Rest of survey results

***any reflections/questions about the survey?*

Slide 33

Present the groups and ask if all has heard their names. If not assign to groups. Explain we will be doing a discussion with some guiding questions to consider and we will have rapporteurs to do the note taking. We will spend up to 15.30 discussing and then we will gather up and report insights from both groups.

Slide 35-39

Go through questions at the discussion

Slide 40

*Describe next steps, thank participants and mention we will share all material and the notes form the discussion for feedback.
Whoever has not done the survey, feel free to fill in.*

Thank you and see you at the next consultation!

ANNEX A5 - SUMMARY OF REGIONAL CONSULTATION NOTES

North Europe

Climate models focus largely on trees coming up and trees coming down, whereas more subtle changes result from shifts in forest management.

It is crucial to not only focus on carbon, not only get into fast-growing species, especially if implementing these will destroy soil and other ecosystem services

Carbon tax revenues could be allocated to land-owners that do things to raise the level of their carbon sink

Consider the relationship between landowners and land users.

Financial opportunities: There are only a few finances/subsidy schemes/state aid with few strings attached. It is essential to focus on how to move something more nuanced without being too bureaucratic.

Effective communication: there is a lot of technological expertise in the area of forest management, and we need to be able to share these solutions with a wider audience, especially with people that are not aware of a wide variety of options on what agroforestry looks like or what close to nature forestry look like and be able to pilot and scale up those solutions;

More studies are needed to cover knowledge gaps, such as regarding permanence and stability. In this way, trust can be built for the quality of products (e.g. for biochar) in the market. Additionally, there is possibility that conflicts will arise between LMTs regarding which technology will secure first carbon storage. The permanence of BECCS should be supposedly good so permanence needs to be certified somehow

Asia

Biochar: The sale of carbon credits has become a game changer, there is a large demand for credits. There are no regional organizations supporting biochar that a company could affiliate themselves to. If there had been an institution at this level that would endorse and recognize a laboratory for testing for example, or endorse policy frameworks, this would be beneficial

Carbon interests have been growing. For example, Singapore wants to be the carbon hub of the region. In the near future, we need a regional consultation to discuss what it means to have a voluntary carbon market in the region.

Biggest limitation in the market-based carbon is that rate of adoption is not optimal now. We still don't know which policy frameworks are in place and being accepted. Thus, there is a missing infrastructure on standards and liquidity issues.

Afforestation and forest management are the priority for the first half, and then we can work on the second half of the century. Up to 2050, afforestation is important as a priority. BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture Storage) will be more developed in the second half. We have limitations in land-based,

and we cannot increase forest land and soil carbon. So, we need to think about when we reach the limitation.

Latin America

BECCS has the capacity to develop in Latin America because many large companies have the installed capacity to co-produce energy; however, the biggest gap is in carbon capture and storage.

Whatever the technology to be implemented, it is very important to know that for this technology to be accepted and incorporated, it must bring higher returns than the activities that producers are already engaged in. In other words, for a farmer to migrate from conventional agriculture to agriculture in an agrosilvopastoral system, the agrosilvopastoral system must provide higher returns than conventional agriculture. Otherwise, this new technology will not be attractive.

For organic agriculture, large companies have had the need to seek alternatives to conventional agriculture, given that current market conditions, the shortage of synthetic fertilizers have raised prices up to 5 times. Different from what has happened with coffee, where these increases, apparently, have not been so noticeable, or simply, they have stopped fertilizing.

There are no methodologies to include carbon sequestration actions in projects.

There is limited knowledge about reforestation technologies. Guidelines should be established about seeds, ecological restoration, nursery...

Africa

Government officials' position are mostly focused on adaptation and food security. There is potential for LMTs in Africa, but western countries may need to pay for it. There is a conflict between afforestation and land-use for crops in Burkina Faso and Kenya. Crop-based LMTs may help reduce this conflict.

People using small farm areas use naturally more sustainable agriculture practices to reduce costs. With larger areas, it's too much work and they prefer to use pesticides.

Carbon can be kept locked in trees or biochar if there are incentives. It needs to make sense economically or socially to the partner involved in the process.

In the African context storage in geological formations is limited, so it would be stored in soils. Perennial grasses sequester more carbon than aerial crops. Relying on afforestation and other measures dependent on above ground storage are risky because of fires and land-use change.

Agroforestry is the best LMT; better to protect trees than to plant trees; difficult to project beyond 2050. Biochar need to invest more.

ANNEX A6 - GUIDANCE QUESTIONS FOR CONSULTATIONS

The use of Miro for the discussion is encouraged but not mandatory if the organizers consider that it will hinder the participation of stakeholders. If Miro is not used, the chatbox of Zoom or Teams could be used.

1. What do you think about the results of the survey? (10 minutes)
 - Why did you prioritise a specific LMT?
 - Why do you think the results changed without forestry?
2. What are the best practices in your region in terms of LMT adoption? (10 minutes)
 - What have you learned from it?
 - Are these solutions transferrable to another country?
3. Please discuss the limitations of your group's LMT for its adoption in your region:
 - Economic
 - Technological
 - Management
 - Environmental
 - Institutional (cultural, political and social)
4. Which issues are the most important to promote and implement the LMT at a regional level? (10 min)
 - Economic
 - Technological
 - Management
 - Environmental
 - Institutional (cultural, political and social)
5. What are the risks of non-permanence of CO₂ removal of the LMT? (not sure about this one, but just not to lose this point from David)
6. What's the priority LMT for the first half of the century and for the second half?
Learning curve?
7. Homework, 2nd survey: Think of land areas for wetlands, agroforestry?

ANNEX A7 - FACILITATION GUIDE ASIA EXAMPLE

Facilitation Guide

1st Asia Stakeholder Consultation

20th September 2022
2:00 to 4:00 Bangkok time

1. Background

The LANDMARC team, led by the SEI Asia centre [in close partnership with CIAT and su-re-co](#), is organizing a series of regional engagement actions, called platforms. The main objectives of these platforms are to discuss LMTs in their regional contexts (North Europe&Canada, Europe South, Africa, Asia, Latin America), link them to the global perspective, enrich the LANDMARC models and inform decision-making at regional and global levels.

Each platform will run a series of three online consultations, the first consultation of the series taking place on [1st of September for North Europe and Canada](#). It will be followed by the [consultation for Asia on the 20th of September](#). Every consultation will bring together a group of 20 to 30 experts and practitioners of land-based climate mitigation. Afforestation, agroforestry, biochar, organic agriculture and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) are the main LMTs that will be discussed across all platforms, but there may be regional variations. For example, Latin America will also focus on indigenous forest management and Asia will cover peatlands or dry-seeded rice.

The same stakeholders for each continental platform will meet again early 2023 to discuss results of the models run by LANDMARC, LandSHIFT, that focuses on land use changes and variations, and E3ME that helps to analyse economy-environment policy challenges.

2. Facilitation Framework

The participants of the consultation were carefully selected with the aim to invite the same group of stakeholders to the next two events in 2023. To the extent possible, the LANDMARC team contacted each stakeholder bilaterally to present briefly the project and the questions that LANDMARC and these stakeholder consultations aim to address.

The consultation stakeholders were invited to fill in a [survey](#). The survey was reviewed and amended by the group of modelers from the LANDMARC project. This quantitative data will complement the qualitative information obtained by the stakeholder consultations

3. Agenda

LANDMARC Stakeholder consultations - Asia 20 September 2022, 2:00 to 4:00 pm

Objective:

Discuss the potential, challenges and opportunities of the Land based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in the Asian context to enrich information and link them to the global perspective.

Time	Topics	Presenter
14:00 – 14:10	Welcome – Presentation of LANDMARC project and event (agenda)	Kuntum Melati Dr. Francis X. Johnson
14:10 – 14:20	Presentation of LMTs for Asia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BECCS • Afforestation / Reforestation / Forest management • Paludiculture and Peatlands • Irrigated Agriculture Presentation of survey results	Stefan Bößner
14:20 – 14:35	Presentation of case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vietnam • Indonesia • Nepal 	Stefan Bößner Thao Pham Siti Indriani Lokendra Karki
14:35 – 15:35	Break-out Groups; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 1 Energy (BECCS and Biochar): Moderated by Stefan Bößner, Note-taker: Elodie Maria-Sube • Group 2 Forestry (Afforestation, reforestation, Peat/Wetland management): Moderated by Kuntum Melati, Note-taker: Thao Pham • Group 3 Agriculture (Agroforestry and Agriculture): Moderated by Takeshi Takama, Note-taker: Siti Indriani 	
15:35 – 15:55	Discussion: Presentation of results by Group Discussion, moderated by Elodie Maria-Sube, note-taker: Stefan Bößner	
15:55 – 16:00	Closing remarks and next steps	Elodie Maria-Sube

4. Facilitation agenda

Time	Onscreen	Speaker	Offscreen
PLENARY			
14:00 – 14:05	Welcome and House-Keeping	Kuntum Melati	Elodie: Admit participants in room Elodie: send-out Attendance form in chat
14:05 - 14:10	Presentation of LANDMARC project and event (agenda)	Francis X. Johnson	
14:10 – 14:15	Presentation of LMTs for Asia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BECCS • Afforestation / Reforestation / Forest management • Paludiculture and Peatlands • Irrigated Agriculture 	Stefan Bößner	Elodie and Kuntum: Assign participants to break-out rooms according to registration info Takeshi and Francis: Answer to questions in chat
14:15 – 14:20	Presentation of survey results	Stefan Bößner	Elodie: Time-keeper
14:20 – 14:35	Presentation of case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vietnam • Indonesia • Nepal 	Stefan Thao Pham Siti Indriani Lokendra Karki	Stefan: Time-keeper and slides Takeshi and Francis: Answer to questions in chat
14:35- 14:40	Present break-out rooms	Stefan	Elodie: Open break-out rooms

BREAK-OUT GROUPS			
Time	Onscreen	Speaker	Offscreen
14:35 – 15:35	Group 1 Energy Group 2 Forestry Group 3 Agriculture	Group 1 : Moderated by Stefan Group 2: Moderated by Kuntum Group 3: Moderated by Takeshi	Group 1: Note-taker + start recording: Elodie Time keeper: Elodie Group2 Note-taker + start recording : Thao Time-keeper: Francis Starts recording: Thao Group 3 Note-taker + start recording: Indri Time-keeper: Lokendra
BREAK-OUT GROUPS STEP BY STEP			
Time	Onscreen	Speaker	Offscreen
14:40 – 14:45	Round of presentations	Led by moderator	
14:45 – 15:00	Discussion on best practices	Led by moderator	
15:00 – 15:10	Discussion on limitations	Led by moderator	
15:10 – 15:20	Discussion on scope for promotion	Led by moderator	
15:20 – 15:25	Discussion on permanence	Led by moderator	
15:25 – 15:30	Priority LMT	Led by moderator	
15:30 – 15:35	Invite participants to return to plenary	Led by moderator	Note-taker: send link to return to plenary
PLENARY			
Time	Onscreen	Speaker	Offscreen
15:35 – 15:55	Discussion: Presentation of results by Group Invite participants to answer to poll	Moderated by Elodie	Time-keeper: Indri Note-taker: Stefan Bößner Takeshi and Francis: Answer to questions in chat Kuntum: Put poll on screen

Time	Onscreen	Speaker	Offscreen
15:35- 15:45	Presentation group 1 Presentation group 2 Presentation group 3	Elodie Thao Indri	
15:45 – 15:55	Discuss results of poll	Elodie	Note-taker: Stefan
15:55 – 16:00	Closing remarks and next steps		

Guiding questions in [Teams](#)

Note-taking format in [Teams](#)

ANNEX B: REGIONAL INTERVIEWS

ANNEX B1: STAKEHOLDER LIST FOR REGIONAL INTERVIEWS

ANNEX B2: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

ANNEX B3: CONSENT FORM

ANNEX B4: MODEL-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

ANNEX B5: INTERVIEW GUIDE FLOWCHART

ANNEX B6: INTERVIEW GUIDE

ANNEX B7: REGIONAL INTERVIEW TRAINING

ANNEX B1- STAKEHOLDER LIST FOR REGIONAL INTERVIEWS

Stakeholder list for regional interviews

Please note that the stakeholder lists for Asia and Europe are provided below, while the lists for Africa and Latin America are available upon request from the author. In Asia, interviews were conducted at both regional and country levels, resulting in stakeholder lists for the Asia region, Indonesia, Vietnam, and Nepal. For Europe, interviews were conducted only at the regional level.

Asia

Asian region:

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
Male	India	South Asia	forestry (economics)	Expert & Consultancy
Female	Indonesia (currently in Canada for study)	Asia	Nature-based solutions	
Female	Cambodia	Asia	probably various (ex. biochar)	
Male	Regional-based in Bangkok	Asia	climate change and bioenergy	International Organisation
Male		Asia	Restoration/aforestation/wetland	Research/practitioner/advisor
Male		Asia	AFOLU	International Organisation
Male		Asia	Forestry, AFOLU	International Organisation
Female	Thailand	South-East Asia	Agriculture / Forestry (program development and finance)	International Organisation
Female	Thailand	Mekong	Wetlands	Research
Male	Indonesia	Asia	Forestry	International Organisation
Male	Nepal	Asia	Agriculture, land-use modeling	Research

Indonesia

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
Male	Indonesia, Thai, Vietnam, Nepal, Bhutan, Timor Leste, Lao PDR	Asia	Forestry (reforestation, afforestation, agroforestry)	International Organisation
Male	Indonesia, Timor Leste	Asia	Forestry (reforestation, afforestation, agroforestry), peatland	International Organisation
Male	Indonesia	Asia	Bioenergy, soil carbon enhancement, waste management	Expert & Consultancy
Male	Indonesia, Timor Leste, Vietnam, Myanmar and Papua New Guinea	Asia	Agroforestry, Agriculture (crop management, no tillage), soil carbon enhancement (biochar, biogas, compost)	International Organisation
Female	Indonesia, Malaysia, Timor Leste, Philippines	Asia	Agroforestry, Agriculture (crop management, no tillage), soil carbon enhancement (biochar, biogas, compost)	Expert & Consultancy
Male	Indonesia, Asian countries	Asia	Forestry (reforestation, afforestation, agroforestry), Agriculture (crop management, no tillage)	Business/Company
Male	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	Agriculture (crop management, no tillage), soil carbon enhancement (biochar, biogas, compost)	Research
Male	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	Peatland and Mangrove management	Policy Maker
Male	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	Agriculture (crop management, no tillage), soil carbon enhancement (biochar, biogas, compost)	Research
Female	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	Bioenergy, soil carbon enhancement, waste management	Expert & Consultancy
Male	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	AFOLU (reforestation, reforestation, peatland), agroforestry	Expert & Consultancy
Male	Indonesia, Southeast Asia countries	Asia	Bioenergy, soil carbon enhancement, waste management, BECCS	Business/Company

Vietnam

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry;	Research
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry	Research
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry	Research
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry;	NGO
Female	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry	Research
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry	Research
Male	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Low carbon rice; sustainable Ag.	NGO

Nepal

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
			Agroforestry	Under Secretary and Researcher
			Forestry	Professor
			Land policy advocacy	National Facilitator
			Land policy advocacy	Chairperson
			Rice	National Coordinator
			Rice, Soil management	Senior Scientist

EU

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
Female	Sweden	Nordics	Biochar	Academia
Male	Vietnam	Nordics	Biochar	Consultancy
Male	Sweden	EU	Generalist, CDR	Consultancy
Male	Sweden	Nordics	Afforestation	-
Female	Vietnam	South-east Asia	Agroforestry	-
Male	Finland	Nordics	Biochar	Researcher
Male	Norway	Nordics	Biochar	Research/consultancy
Female	-	EU	Land use, forestry and carbon removal	-
Female	-	EU	CDR	-

ANNEX B2 - INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

Interview Protocol

Introduction

The LANDMARC research program spans all scales from the local level to the global scale in analysing land-use based mitigation technologies (LMT). In this part of the project, we primarily assess the regional level and the issue of scaling up from the national level. A literature review provided basic information on the applicability, barriers, and potential of LMTs across different regions, and we have identified stakeholders who have knowledge at the regional, continental and/or transnational level. The engagement actions and workshops provide the platform for stakeholder co-production of scaling scenarios of LMT portfolios, including both a qualitative narrative for different regions and technical analysis using the modelling tools employed within LANDMARC.

Land-use modelling of the scenarios (LANDSHIFT-G) coupled to earth-system modelling (EC-Earth3-CC) and modelling of techno/social-economics (E3ME) provide the analytical basis for scaling up LMTs. Finally, the capacity gap analysis identified barriers and opportunities to refine the LMT outlook and calibrate achievable potentials. The final results from these analyses will aim to incorporate stakeholder co-production, which is organised and coordinated across the associated levels and includes both the techno-economic and the socio-economic context for different world regions.

We are synthesising and incorporating stakeholder perspectives, aiming to mediate between the LMT portfolio/scenario analysis developed in case studies at national/local level and the results of global models evaluating changes in land-use associated with LMTs and the implications for carbon sequestration and climate mitigation. Here, we aim to:

- (1) Investigate stakeholder perspectives on LMT portfolios in a regional, transnational and/or continental context, in order to develop a set of **regional/continental narratives** across different scenarios.
- (2) Elicit regional/continental stakeholder views on the priority and feasibility of different LMTs so as to **inform the configuration of alternative scenarios or pathways** in the coupled land-use modelling framework and fill gaps arising from the limited number and type of case studies employed.
- (3) **Engage stakeholders in discussions** at regional/continental level **for knowledge-sharing** on the deployment of LMT portfolios and the associated drivers and impacts.

Interview questions

Respondent background

1. What is your role?
2. How are you currently working with LMTs?
3. From the list provided which are the LMT(s) you are most familiar with? We will be focusing our discussion on those LMTs you are most familiar with, but trying also to link to trends in your country and region that might affect synergies with other LMTs.
4. Which countries or regions are you most familiar with when it comes to LMTs?

Scaling from National to Regional

5. How would you describe the current LMT status and trends in your country?
6. How could these LMT portfolios scale up from the national to the regional level?
7. In your experience, what are the main trends in scaling up LMTs from national to regional and are there any opportunities to impact those?
8. Could there be any opportunity in potential sources of revenue? How could this LMT be funded? e.g. carbon credits government or voluntary), sale of agricultural products, ecotourism, other government subsidy, etc.
9. What are the barriers to scaling up this LMT portfolio regionally? What is missing?
10. What would be the costs of running this LMT (e.g. capital investment, labour, material inputs, tax)? How expensive are these likely to be and could this be a barrier as well?
11. How might the regional LMT portfolio change over time and space? Are there any countries in the region focusing on specific LMTs? Do you think other countries do and should differ on which LMTs they prioritize?
12. Is there a knowledge/technology transfer opportunity regionally? Do you foresee regional cooperation on LMT development?

13. Are there likely to be any impacts on trade? Are products generated by this LMT likely to be exported? Could this LMT push out other land-using activities which are export-led?

14. Do you see any challenges or potential competition between LMTs when it comes to availability of land and biomass, production of food and energy, or other domains in future scenarios? Are some of these challenges already happening? What could be done to manage these tensions?

15. What trends should be considered when designing future regional LMT scenarios? Will or should some LMTs be more important than others in the future. Think specifically in “your” region, which would and should, according to you, be the changes and how would they happen?

General closing questions

16. Are there any additional insights you would like to share with us?

17. Do you have any tips for experts we could get in touch with and discuss?

18. Do you have any policies or datasets you see as particularly useful for us? For example, policies on financial, trade, or spatial regulation of LMTs, or datasets for spatial allocation of the LMTs?

ANNEX B3 - CONSENT FORM

LANDMARC: Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways WP6 regional scenarios

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Sponsor(s): European Union HORIZON 2020: The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation and xxx

Researcher: xxx

Researcher contact details: xxx

Interviewee name: xxx

Interviewee contact details: xxx

Date: xxx

1. Background purpose of the study:

Land-based negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that some residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at land-based negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, for example in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

2. What will I be asked to do?

We anticipate that the interview will last for approximately between 60-90 minutes. We will take written notes and may make a digital recording of the interview for transcription purposes. The interviewer may be accompanied by a research-assistant who will also takes notes to ensure the accuracy and completeness of the information we use.

You are under no pressure to participate in the interview. You are free to decline to answer questions on topics that you do not wish to discuss. You are free to break off the interview at any time or to withdraw from the interview altogether at any point of time. Any information collected to that point will be destroyed if you do not wish of us to use the information.

3. What type of information will be collected?

You will not be identified in the research findings either directly or indirectly unless we have your permission to do so. Even after receiving your permission, we will not identify or quote you in any publication (e.g. direct quote or paraphrase your comment) without allowing you to verify the accuracy of quotes that are being used. Information collected will be restricted to questions relevant to your official role (length of time in this position, responsibilities, prior relevant experience).

Please put a check mark on the line corresponding to your willingness to be identified:

You may quote me and use my name: Yes____ No____

4. Can we contact you for further research?

You may contact me in the future for further research related to the LANDMARC project:

Yes____ No____

5. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the interview will be used to help formulate assumptions and what-if conditions for the quantitative models to assess *the extent* of synergies, conflicts, and risks associated with different low-carbon technological pathways.

6. Who is organising and funding the research?

LANDMARC has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme through Grant Agreement No 869367.

The Stockholm Environment Institute is leading the study and working with LANDMARC consortium partners whose researchers will be assisting in carrying out the research.

7. Signatures (written consent):

Your signature on this form indicates that you:

- 1) Understand to your satisfaction the information provided to you about your participation in this research project,
- 2) Understand that your participation is voluntary, that you can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that you can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way
- 3) Consent to the processing of your personal information for the purposes of this research study. You understand that such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, the co-ordinating institutions' country requirements and the relevant ethics approval process.

Participant's Name: (please print)

Participant's Signature

Date:

Researcher's Name: (please print)

Researcher's Signature:

Date:

8. Contact for further information, questions, or concerns

If you have any further questions or want clarification regarding this research and/or your participation, please contact:

Stockholm Environment Institute, leading LANDMARC Work Package 6: Stakeholder Engagement.

- Mathieu Mal, SEI, Programme Coordinator, mathieu.mal@sei.org

ANNEX B4 - MODEL-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

Dear Stakeholder,

The following questions aim to gather technical information about the LMTs that will be included in the LANDMARC simulation models (Afforestation, No tillage, BECCS, Biochar, and Agroforestry).

Given that you have a background in at least one of these LMTs, we would like to request your help in providing us with some additional information by answering any question that is relevant to your knowledge and background.

After filling out your details below, please provide your views on the questions in section 1, then proceed to the section(s) (2-6) with questions about the LMT(s) you are familiar with.

How to answer the questions:

- Some of these questions are very specific and ultimately aim to obtain a certain **quantitative value** such as a volume or percentage. If you are able to provide such precise information, please do so. If not, please give an indication in **qualitative and relative terms** such as for example “the land allocated to this LMT will increase significantly”, “this LMT will be prioritized over this LMT”, etc.*
- Please always specify the specific **country or region** context in which you are answering the question.*
- Please always specify on which **type of information** you are basing your answer, whether it is your personal judgement based on your experience, a specific piece of research, a dataset, or other.*

Your name:

The LMT(s) you are most familiar with:

The country and region you are most familiar with regarding LMTs:

1) Questions on relative implementation of LMTs

- Could a fraction of cropland and pastureland be freed to convert the land to implement other LMTs? If so, how large could this fraction be according to you? (e.g. 5% of total cropland and 10% of total pastureland)
- If the freed-up space was to be divided among afforestation, BECCS, and biochar, what would that allocation of space realistically look like? (e.g. 33% afforestation, 33% BECCS, 33% biochar)
- How would this reduction of cropland and pasture be achieved? Would it be through less consumption (e.g. dietary changes), improvements in productivity, or both?

2) Expert in Afforestation

- What are the parameters that need to be met for land to be suitable for afforestation?
- Which fraction of the suitable available area could realistically be dedicated to afforestation?
- Is it (im)possible, (un)realistic, (un)likely, that areas afforested are converted into other land use at a later stage?
- What would be the impact of this LMT on productivity/yields? How would this affect costs?
- What impacts would the implementation of this LMT have on economic activity in other sectors? What other land-using economic activity is likely to be pushed out? e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban development, mining, etc
- Are there any specific policies that should be considered with regard to this LMT?

Example policy categories:

- Financial: taxes & subsidies, carbon pricing, price guarantees, public investment, etc
- Public management: public land management, restoration projects, skills/training programs, sustainability certifications, energy policy, etc
- Regulation: eco product standards, land-use zoning, emissions quotas, etc
- Trade: trade regulations, carbon border adjustments, etc

3) Expert in No tillage

- What are the parameters that need to be met for land to be suitable for no tillage?
- What fraction of cropland could realistically be dedicated to the no-tillage LMT?
- What would be the impact of this LMT on productivity/yields? How would this affect costs?
- What impacts would the implementation of this LMT have on economic activity in other sectors? What other land-using economic activity is likely to be pushed out? e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban development, mining, etc
- Are there any specific policies that should be considered with regard to this LMT?

Example policy categories:

- Financial: taxes & subsidies, carbon pricing, price guarantees, public investment, etc
- Public management: public land management, restoration projects, skills/training programs, sustainability certifications, energy policy, etc
- Regulation: eco product standards, land-use zoning, emissions quotas, etc
- Trade: trade regulations, carbon border adjustments, etc

4) Expert in Biochar

- Does biochar in your country/region currently come from waste streams such as crop residues or biomass crops cultivated for only this purpose?
- How do you see the potential for biochar from crops cultivated only for this purpose in your country/region?
- How do you see the potential for biochar from waste streams in your country/region?
- What are the parameters that need to be met for land to be suitable for biochar?
- Which fraction of the suitable available area could realistically be dedicated to biochar?
- In your country/region, are biofuel crops irrigated and/or rainfed?
- For which crop types would biochar be an option? (See Glossary at end of document for more information on these categories)
 - Annual C3 plants (e.g. wheat, rice)
 - Perennial C3 plants (e.g. oil palm)
 - C3 Nitrogen fixing plants (e.g. legumes like soybean, alfalfa, peanut)
 - Annual C4 plants (e.g. corn, sugarcane)
 - Perennial C4 plants (e.g. Miscanthus, switchgrass, Spartina, and Andropogon)
- Do you have any suggestions on how to represent the high costs of biochar compared to alternative LMTs?
- What are realistic values of the biofuel harvest (fraction of crops harvested that are used as biofuels)?
- What are realistic values of the carbon capture factors (fraction of harvested biomass than can be effectively stored)?
- To what extent can these assumptions for biofuel crop factors in your region be realized?
- What would be the impact of this LMT on productivity/yields? How would this affect costs?
- What impacts would the implementation of this LMT have on economic activity in other sectors? What other land-using economic activity is likely to be pushed out? e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban development, mining, etc

- Are there any specific policies that should be considered with regard to this LMT?

Example policy categories:

- Financial: taxes & subsidies, carbon pricing, price guarantees, public investment, etc
- Public management: public land management, restoration projects, skills/training programs, sustainability certifications, energy policy, etc
- Regulation: eco product standards, land-use zoning, emissions quotas, etc
- Trade: trade regulations, carbon border adjustments, etc

5) Expert in BECCS

- What are the parameters that need to be met for land to be suitable for BECCS?
- Which fraction of the suitable available area could realistically be dedicated to BECCS?
- In your country/region, are biofuel crops irrigated and/or rainfed?
- For which crop types would BECCS be an option? (See Glossary at end of document for more information on these categories)
 - Annual C3 plants (e.g. wheat, rice)
 - Perennial C3 plants (e.g. oil palm)
 - C3 Nitrogen fixing plants (e.g. legumes like soybean, alfalfa, peanut)
 - Annual C4 plants (e.g. corn, sugarcane)
 - Perennial C4 plants (e.g. Miscanthus, switchgrass, Spartina, and Andropogon)
- What are realistic values of the biofuel harvest (fraction of crops harvested that are used as biofuels)?
- What are realistic values of the carbon capture factors (fraction of harvested biomass than can be effectively stored)?
- To what extent can these assumptions for biofuel crop factors in your region be realized?
- What are the capacities for carbon capture storage in BECCS in your region?
- What would be the impact of this LMT on productivity/yields? How would this affect costs?
- What impacts would the implementation of this LMT have on economic activity in other sectors? What other land-using economic activity is likely to be pushed out? e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban development, mining, etc
- Are there any specific policies that should be considered with regard to this LMT?
Example policy categories:
 - Financial: taxes & subsidies, carbon pricing, price guarantees, public investment, etc
 - Public management: public land management, restoration projects, skills/training programs, sustainability certifications, energy policy, etc
 - Regulation: eco product standards, land-use zoning, emissions quotas, etc
 - Trade: trade regulations, carbon border adjustments, etc

6) Expert in Agroforestry

- What are the parameters that need to be met for land to be suitable for agroforestry?
 - Which fraction of the suitable available area could realistically be dedicated to agroforestry?
 - In regions where agroforestry is a solution to compensate for yield reduction due to climate change: can average long-term crop yields be increased by agroforestry practices? What is the potential magnitude of this increase (%)?
 - In other regions: what is the maximum tree cover on cropland or pasture land not compromising the productivity of the crop/pasture (e.g. due to competition for sunlight and moisture)?
 - For which crop types would agroforestry be an option? (See Glossary at end of document for more information on these categories)
 - Annual C3 plants (e.g. wheat, rice)
 - Perennial C3 plants (e.g. oil palm)
 - C3 Nitrogen fixing plants (e.g. legumes like soybean, alfalfa, peanut)
 - Annual C4 plants (e.g. corn, sugarcane)
 - Perennial C4 plants (e.g. Miscanthus, switchgrass, Spartina, and Andropogon)
 - What would be the impact of this LMT on productivity/yields? How would this affect costs?
 - What impacts would the implementation of this LMT have on economic activity in other sectors? What other land-using economic activity is likely to be pushed out? e.g. agriculture, forestry, urban development, mining, etc
 - Are there any specific policies that should be considered with regard to this LMT?
- Example policy categories:
- Financial: taxes & subsidies, carbon pricing, price guarantees, public investment, etc
 - Public management: public land management, restoration projects, skills/training programs, sustainability certifications, energy policy, etc
 - Regulation: eco product standards, land-use zoning, emissions quotas, etc
 - Trade: trade regulations, carbon border adjustments, etc

LANDMARC Glossary

➤ Crop Types:

Crops were defined based on their life history strategy (annual vs perennial), the metabolic pathway for carbon fixation in photosynthesis (C3 vs C4) and the association with nitrogen fixing bacteria.

- Annual crops complete their life cycle, from germination to the production of seeds, within one growing season.
- Perennial crops require several growing cycles before producing seeds. They do not need to be replanted each year and grow back from remaining vegetative organs after harvesting.
- Nitrogen-fixing crops associated with nitrogen fixing bacteria hosted in root nodules. Plants benefit from the ability of symbiont bacteria to fix nitrogen (an essential nutrient for plants) from the atmosphere. They include legume plants (family Fabaceae or Leguminosae).
- C4 crops optimize water use in hot and dry environments through compartmentalization of photosynthetic reactions. The most important C4 crops are maize, sorghum, and sugarcane.
- C3 crops thrive under moderate sunlight and mild temperatures where groundwater is abundant. Important C3 crops include rice, wheat, soybeans, and barley.
- First-generation biofuels are made from sugar-starch feedstocks (e.g., sugarcane and corn) and edible oil feedstocks (e.g., rapeseed and soybean oil).
- Second-generation biofuels, also known as advanced biofuels, are fuels that can be manufactured from various types of non-food plant biomass (e.g., leaves, stems).

➤ Land-Based Mitigation Technologies and practices (LMTs):

- Agriculture
 - Agroforestry: Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land
 - Dry seeded rice – no till: Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.
 - Reduced tillage: A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.
 - Integrated soil fertility management: Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.
 - Organic agriculture: An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.

- Biochar: Organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.
 - Forestry
 - Afforestation/reforestation: Afforestation: Establishing forest by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover. Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.
 - Forest management: Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.
 - Forest fire management: Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.
 - Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS): Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.
 - Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost): Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and bio-gas slurry as compost.
 - Peatland management: Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.
 - Pasture management: Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.
- Region: The regions considered in LANDMARC are: North America, South America, Africa, Northern Europe, Southern Europe, and South-east Asia + China & India.
- Scaling up: to bring a technology or practice from experimental or small-scale implementation at the local level to wide and large-scale deployment at national and regional level.

ANNEX B5: INTERVIEW GUIDE FLOWCHART

Before the interviews

- Stakeholder selection: regional perspective and diverse LMTs
- Prepare stakeholder list (A)
- Send interview invitation (B), include background doc. (C)
- If respondent accepts: send scheduling email (D), include interview protocol (E) and consent form (F)
- If respondent is unresponsive: follow up within a week
- Be familiar with the interview protocol
- Prepare “respondent background” before each interview

During the interviews

- Briefly introduce LANDMARC
- Validate respondent background information
- Follow interview protocol
 - Be mindful of time
 - Move on if respondent does not provide information
 - Take note of context of answer: geography, timeline
 - Allow time for comments that may lead to contacts or data
- Check suitability for modeling questions and introduce them

After every interview

- Send thank you email, include interview notes for validation, model-specific questions if suitable (G)

After all interviews

- Process the interview information into a 4–5-page narrative report
- Upload all the information to Bitrix:
 - Stakeholder list
 - All interview files with notes
 - Signed consent forms
 - Narrative report

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ANNEX B6- INTERVIEW GUIDE

LANDMARC Regional Stakeholder Engagement Interview Guide

Before the interview

1) Respondent selection

Each partner is requested to aim to conduct 10 interviews.

Together, the interviews should aim to cover the relevant LMTs in the region, therefore, respondents' backgrounds should be varied. Ideally, respondents would have a regional outlook (knowledge not limited to a single country).

Respondents can be a combination of people with a generalist perspective and people with specialist knowledge about a specific or multiple LMTs. Both perspectives are necessary to construct scenarios on the one hand and provide input for the models on the other hand.

Respondents can be selected from earlier participants in stakeholder engagement activities, or can be new to the project.

List the respondents in the provided Excel file (Annex A).

2) Interview preparation

1) Send out invitation for interview (Annex B), include:

- Background document (information on LANDMARC, the first regional stakeholder consultation, and the modelling simulation tool) (Annex C)

2) If the respondent accepts the invitation, send email to schedule interview time (Annex D), include:

- Interview questions (Annex E)
- Consent form (Annex F)

3) If the respondent has not reacted within a week, send a follow-up email or call over phone.

4) Be fluent in briefly introducing LANDMARC, and be familiar with the interview protocol.

5) To allow more time for data-gathering, interviewers are requested to complete interview section 2.1 "Respondent background" to the best of their ability before the interview. It is likely that there is already a certain level of knowledge about the respondent, if not, do some background research.

Interview Protocol

1) Introduction

Goal: Remind the respondent of, or familiarize them with LANDMARC.

Task: Explain LANDMARC to the respondent in your own words. The below text can be used as a guide, but level of detail and focus may vary based on extent of prior engagement.

Time: Max. 5 minutes

The LANDMARC research program spans all scales from the local level to the global scale in analysing land-use based mitigation technologies (LMT). In this part of the project, we primarily assess the regional level and the issue of scaling up from the national level. A literature review provided basic information on the applicability, barriers, and potential of LMTs across different regions, and we have identified stakeholders who have knowledge at the regional, continental and/or transnational level. The engagement actions and workshops provide the platform for stakeholder co-production of scaling scenarios of LMT portfolios, including both a qualitative narrative for different regions and technical analysis using the modelling tools employed within LANDMARC.

Land-use modelling of the scenarios (LANDSHIFT-G) coupled to earth-system modelling (EC-Earth3-CC) and modelling of techno/social-economics (E3ME) provide the analytical basis for scaling up LMTs. Finally, the capacity gap analysis identified barriers and opportunities to refine the LMT outlook and calibrate achievable potentials. The final results from these analyses will aim to incorporate stakeholder co-production, which is organised and coordinated across the associated levels and includes both the techno-economic and the socio-economic context for different world regions.

We are synthesising and incorporating stakeholder perspectives, aiming to mediate between the LMT portfolio/scenario analysis developed in case studies at national/local level and the results of global models evaluating changes in land-use associated with LMTs and the implications for carbon sequestration and climate mitigation. Here, we aim to:

- (1) Investigate stakeholder perspectives on LMT portfolios in a regional, transnational and/or continental context, in order to develop a set of **regional/continental narratives** across different scenarios.
- (2) Elicit regional/continental stakeholder views on the priority and feasibility of different LMTs so as to **inform the configuration of alternative scenarios or pathways** in the coupled land-use modelling framework and fill gaps arising from the limited number and type of case studies employed.
- (3) **Engage stakeholders in discussions** at regional/continental level **for knowledge-sharing** on the deployment of LMT portfolios and the associated drivers and impacts.

2) Interview questions

2.1 Respondent background

Goal: Ensure that we get a good understanding of the person's background and expertise, this will help inform which questions can be included, facilitate the analysis, and allow for better follow-up.

Task: Quickly summarize the information collected before the interview to verify its accuracy with the respondent, adapt and add if needed.

Time: Max. 5 minutes

1. What is your role?
2. How are you currently working with LMTs?
3. From the list provided which are the LMT(s) you are most familiar with? We will be focusing our discussion on those LMTs you are most familiar with, but trying also to link to trends in your country and region that might affect synergies with other LMTs.
4. Which countries or regions are you most familiar with when it comes to LMTs?

2.2 Scaling from National to Regional

Goal: Gather information that will provide input for the regional scenarios.

Task: Follow the questions, follow up in case something is unclear or more information seems available.

Time: Max. 45 minutes

5. How would you describe the current LMT status and trends in your country?
6. How could these LMT portfolios scale up from the national to the regional level?
7. In your experience, what are the main trends in scaling up LMTs from national to regional and are there any opportunities to impact those?
8. Could there be any opportunity in potential sources of revenue? How could this LMT be funded? e.g. carbon credits government or voluntary), sale of agricultural products, ecotourism, other government subsidy, etc.
9. What are the barriers to scaling up this LMT portfolio regionally? What is missing?
10. What would be the costs of running this LMT (e.g. capital investment, labour, material inputs, tax)? How expensive are these likely to be and could this be a barrier as well?

11. How might the regional LMT portfolio change over time and space? Are there any countries in the region focusing on specific LMTs? Do you think other countries do and should differ on which LMTs they prioritize?
12. Is there a knowledge/technology transfer opportunity regionally? Do you foresee regional cooperation on LMT development?
13. Are there likely to be any impacts on trade? Are products generated by this LMT likely to be exported? Could this LMT push out other land-using activities which are export-led?
14. Do you see any challenges or potential competition between LMTs when it comes to availability of land and biomass, production of food and energy, or other domains in future scenarios? Are some of these challenges already happening? What could be done to manage these tensions?
15. What trends should be considered when designing future regional LMT scenarios? Will or should some LMTs be more important than others in the future. Think specifically in “your” region, which would and should, according to you, be the changes and how would they happen?

2.3 General closing questions

Goal: Provide the opportunity for the respondent to share relevant information that was not directly elicited through the questions.

Task: Follow the questions, make sure to get clear details in case a contact or data source is given.

Time: Max. 10 minutes

16. Are there any additional insights you would like to share with us?
17. Do you have any tips for experts we could get in touch with and discuss?
18. Do you have any policies or datasets you see as particularly useful for us? For example, policies on financial, trade, or spatial regulation of LMTs, or datasets for spatial allocation of the LMTs?

3) Closing the interview

Time: Max. 5 minutes

If the respondent is a specialist in one of the 5 LMTs that are being modelled in the land-use model, inform them that we have some more technical questions regarding these LMTs and ask if they would be willing to share their knowledge on those in written form through a follow-up email.

If there are no further comments, close the interview, thank the interviewee, and inform them that their anonymous input will be used for constructing regional narratives and adjusted model scenario results, to be shared with all involved stakeholders at later stage.

Remind the respondent to sign and submit the consent form if not done already.

After the interview

Send email thanking the respondent for their participation, include:

- Notes taken during the interview for validation
- Model-specific questions: to be sent only to respondents who are specialists in one of the 5 LMTs that are being modelled (Annex G)

After completing all interviews

1) Process the information gathered in the interviews and write-up a 4-5 page, narrative style report compiling and analysing the information to get a full overview of trends and findings. Guiding questions will be provided to facilitate this report and ensure a similar focus between countries and regions.

2) Upload the stakeholder list, all interview files with notes, the signed consent forms, and the narrative report to Bitrix. A [dedicated folder](#) has been prepared.

LANDMARC Glossary

➤ Land-Based Mitigation Technologies and practices (LMTs):

- Agriculture
 - Agroforestry: Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land
 - Dry seeded rice – no till: Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.
 - Reduced tillage: A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.
 - Integrated soil fertility management: Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.
 - Organic agriculture: An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.
 - Organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.
- Forestry
 - Afforestation/reforestation: Afforestation: Establishing forest by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover. Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.
 - Forest management: Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.
 - Forest fire management: Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.
- Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS): Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.
- Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost): Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and bio-gas slurry as compost.
- Peatland management: Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.
- Pasture management: Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.

➤ Region: The regions considered in LANDMARC are: North America, South America, Africa, Northern Europe, Southern Europe, and South-east Asia + China & India.

➤ Scaling up: to bring a technology or practice from experimental or small-scale implementation at the local level to wide and large-scale deployment at national and regional level.

ANNEX B7: REGIONAL INTERVIEW TRAINING

LANDMARC

WP6: Regional scenarios interview training

May 15th, 2023

Mathieu Mal

Programme Coordinator

SEI Asia, Bangkok

LANDMARC | This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020
research and innovation program under grant agreement No 869367

Objectives

To collect information from the stakeholders to:

- construct the regional LMT scenarios and lay the basis for the regional workshops.
- provide input for the models (land-use and economy).

Process Steps

Before the interviews

- Stakeholder selection: regional perspective and diverse LMTs
- Prepare stakeholder list (A)
- Send interview invitation (B), include background doc. (C)
- If respondent accepts: send scheduling email (D), include interview protocol (E) and consent form (F)
- If respondent is unresponsive: follow up within a week
- Be familiar with the interview protocol
- Prepare “respondent background” before each interview

During the interviews

- Briefly introduce LANDMARC
- Validate respondent background information
- Follow interview protocol
 - Be mindful of time
 - Move on if respondent does not provide information
 - Take note of context of answer: geography, timeline
 - Allow time for comments that may lead to contacts or data
- Check suitability for modeling questions and introduce them

After every interview

- Send thank you email, include interview notes for validation, model-specific questions if suitable (G)

After all interviews

- Process the interview information into a 4–5-page narrative report
- Upload all the information to Bitrix:
 - Stakeholder list
 - All interview files with notes
 - Signed consent forms
 - Narrative report
 - Completed model-specific questions files

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More elaborate instructions and background for this process provided in the interview guide

Stakeholder Selection

- Aim to interview 10 stakeholders per case study country
- Formerly engaged or new stakeholders
- Coverage:
 - Stakeholders with regional outlook
 - Cover relevant LMTs
 - Balance generalist and specialist perspectives
- Add stakeholders' details to the provided stakeholder list

Interview protocol

- Introduction
- Validation of respondent background
- Scaling national to regional:
 - Trends, barriers, opportunities
 - Intra-regional synergies, differences
 - Implications for land-use allocation and economy
- Final questions: identify data and contacts
- Closing the interview
 - Introducing model-specific questions **if suitable**
(Afforestation, No tillage, BECCS, Biochar, Agroforestry)

Interview guidance

Before the interview:

- Make sure you are familiar with the interview protocol and understand it before starting the interview. More details in the interview guide.
- Prepare “respondent background” before each interview.

During the interview:

- If possible: one interviewer and one notetaker to ease the process.
- Take notes in empty interview protocol file.
- There are a lot of questions, keep an eye on time and don't dwell.

Outputs by end of June

- Stakeholder list
- All interview files with notes
- Signed consent forms
- Narrative report: 4-5 pages narrative
(template with guiding sections will be provided)
- Completed model-specific questions files

- All documents can be found [here](#)

Company drive > 6. WP6 Continent (regional) platforms > 6.3 Organisation continental engagement > Regional interview package

- Folders to store your documents can be found [here](#)

Company drive > 6. WP6 Continent (regional) platforms > 6.3 Organisation continental engagement > Regional interview results

- For questions: mathieu.mal@sei.org

Questions, comments, concerns?

ANNEX C: INCEPTION/BACKGROUND REPORTS

ANNEX C1: INCEPTION REPORT FOR AFRICA

ANNEX C2: INCEPTION REPORT FOR ASIA

ANNEX C3: INCEPTION REPORT FOR EUROPE

ANNEX C4: INCEPTION REPORT (IN SPANISH) FOR LATIN AMERICA

ANNEX C1- AFRICA LANDMARC REGIONAL WORKSHOP INCEPTION REPORT

Preface

LANDMARC

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date, most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking also at negative emission solutions. Among them, we find land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) such as afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, agriculture, biochar, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), grassland and wetland management. However, many LMTs, their impacts and their implementation needs, are still insufficiently understood.

The four-year LANDMARC project is filling this knowledge gap by employing a triangular research approach, encompassing both technical and social aspects: the use of satellite data and soil sampling is combined with climate, land-use, and economic scenario modelling, and stakeholder engagement. This global effort carried out by 19 partners and spread over 16 national case studies aims to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors.
- Assess the regional and global upscaling potential of negative emission solutions.
- Map potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs.

Regional Stakeholder Workshops

In the period October to November 2023, SEI will organize regional stakeholder workshops in its four regional centres in Bogotá, Nairobi, Bangkok, and Stockholm. The regional expertise and insights of the workshop participants will enrich our understanding of scaling LMTs by making scenario and modelling assumptions more realistic, and, consequently, it will also allow us to make better recommendations to policy- and decision makers.

The Stockholm Environment Institute

The Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) is an international non-profit research and policy organization that tackles environmental and development challenges. SEI's work spans climate, water, air, and land-use issues, governance, the economy, and gender. Stakeholder involvement is at the heart of our efforts to build capacity, strengthen institutions and equip partners for long-term change.

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1.0 Introduction and overview of workshop objectives

The regional workshop on land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) brings together a diverse group of stakeholders to review and evaluate land-based mitigation options in the region, focusing on three key dimensions or elements:

- i. Identifying and characterising a regional portfolio of land-based mitigation options.
- ii. Evaluating how ambitions for land-based mitigation can be raised in the region; and
- iii. Offering recommendations as to how regional engagement (as well as regional and transnational cooperation) can facilitate such higher ambitions.

The workshop takes input from various research results, syntheses and stakeholder engagements that have been carried out at local, national, or regional levels, and can be divided into three main types:

- 1) National case studies, in which detailed analyses and stakeholder consultations for different LMTs were carried out, resulting in an “LMT portfolio” and LMT scaling scenarios to characterising the most promising LMTs and their expected impacts and interactions, in terms of how they could be scaled up to achieve NDCs and/or other climate and development goals.
- 2) Regional outlooks, based on a review of key policies and mechanisms at regional level, along with regional perspectives obtained through stakeholder interviews and consultations; and
- 3) Land-vegetation-carbon modelling, carried out at national, regional and global levels, all based on Shared Socio-economic Pathway 2 (SSP2), which is the “middle of the road” pathway among the five SSPs used as reference points within the Integrated Assessment Modelling Community and as the basis for IPCC Assessments. Three scenarios are used to determine the implementation until the year 2100, using a particular set of LMTs, with each scenario related to the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCPs) adopted in IPCC Assessments, and corresponding to different greenhouse gas concentration in the year 2100:
 - i. Baseline: uses RCP of 4.5 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 3C.
 - ii. Moderate ambition: uses RCP of 2.6 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 2C.
 - iii. High ambition: uses RCP of 1.9 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 1.5C.

The models are limited in the number of LMTs that can be evaluated and thus five were chosen:

1. Afforestation (includes reforestation and forest management);
2. Agroforestry (trees planted within agricultural areas, with specific characteristics);
3. Biochar (sourced from land availability as calculated and used as a soil amendment);
4. Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)
5. No tillage (no or minimal tillage in agricultural areas)

There be limited discussion on LMTs not modelled as appropriate to their national or regional significance. After presentations on selected issues outlined above, workshop participants will be asked to debate and evaluate LMTs, levels of ambition, and regional engagement options, and will thereby contribute to a set of narratives to be developed later to capture these elements.

2.0 Overview on climate mitigation and land sectors

2.1 Climate change mitigation

Climate change represents a new threat and challenge to Africa because many households, social groups and regions have a limited capacity to adapt to climate variability and change (Baptista et al. 2022). Africa's vulnerability to climate change is shaped by the complex interaction of social, political, economic, cultural, and environmental factors, all of which are likely to be affected by the projected impacts of climate change ((Pueyo, 2018). In its most recent assessment, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reported that all of Africa is likely to warm during this century, with the drier subtropical regions warming more than the moist tropics. Annual rainfall is likely to decrease throughout most of the region, apart from eastern Africa, where annual rainfall is projected to increase (Palmer et al. 2023). Anthropogenic factors, led by greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, are the main cause of climate warming. The major source of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions is carbon dioxide emissions from fossil energy consumption, which is an indispensable part of economic development (Kibet, et al. 2022).

Generally, East Africa is at the initial stage of industrialization and urbanization where economic growth and emissions are highly coupled (Mburamatatare et al. 2022). And the existing development model and the high growth rate of the economy are likely to be sustainable in the future (UNECA, 2020). On the one hand, the pursuit of rapid economic growth, as well as rising standard of living, will bring a huge energy gap. On the other hand, these less developed countries are unable to quickly improve energy efficiency and develop clean energy sources (wind and

solar, etc.) in the short term, due to budget constraints and technological backwardness (Pueyo, 2018). Therefore, strong mitigation measures, international attention and support are necessary.

East African countries have already taken active steps to mitigate climate change. All countries in East Africa have committed to mitigate emissions through the submitted NDCs. Countries have committed to GHG emission reductions ranging from 20 to 65% by 2030 (compared to the BAU scenario) (Kweyu, et al. 2023). Almost all of them emphasise on improving energy efficiency and the share of electricity generated from renewable sources. East African countries mainly rely on their geographical endowments to develop hydro, geothermal, wind and biomass energy. In terms of total emissions and evolutionary trends for the region, emissions in East Africa have been rising at an average annual rate of 6.03%, nearly tripling from 17.6Mt in 2000 to 47.6Mt in 2017 and showing a two-stage exponential growth pattern with 2010 as the turning point (Sun et al. 2022). At the same time, the region's rapid economic growth, with an average annual GDP growth rate of 6.45%, is highly consistent with emissions in terms of trends, with economic growth linked to emissions. Since 2010, the rate of increase in emissions has accelerated and gradually exceeded the rate of GDP growth, implying that without aggressive action on energy mix and energy efficiency, future growth per unit of GDP in East African countries will come at the cost of higher emissions (Ntiamoah, et al. 2023).

In terms of emissions by country, Kenya emits the most, while Tanzania and Ethiopia have the fastest growth rates. Uganda's emissions are highly volatile, with a jump in emissions occurring between 2013 and 2015 due to large oil imports for the transport sector. The combined emissions of Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia and Uganda account for more than 80% of emissions in East Africa (Ayugi et al. 2022). The spatial distribution of emissions shows an agglomeration pattern. Kenya is the peak of emissions, while Ethiopia and Tanzania are the secondary peaks. From 2000 to 2017, the core drivers of CO₂ emissions growth are economic and population growth, resulting in 13Mt and 11Mt of emissions respectively, accounting for 27% and 23% of total emissions in 2017 (Sun et al. 2022). While the driving effects of economic structure, energy intensity and energy mix are regionally heterogeneous.

Source: (Sun et al. 2022).

Item	East African Community	DR Congo	Tanzania	Kenya	South Sudan	Uganda	Burundi	Rwanda
Cropland	0.594	0.256	0.552	0.193		0.230	0.227	0.239
Naturally regenerating forest	-0.106	-0.012	-0.158	-0.092		-0.371	1.058	-0.215
Permanent meadows and pastures	0.372	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.040	-0.117	-0.258
Planted Forest	0.331	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.770	0.000	0.194

Item	Area								Changes
	East African Community	DR Congo	Tanzania	Kenya	South Sudan	Uganda	Burundi	Rwanda	
Cropland	59.4%	25.6%	55.2%	19.3%		23.0%	22.7%	23.9%	
Naturally regenerating forest	-10.6%	-1.2%	-15.8%	-9.2%		-37.1%	105.8%	-21.5%	
Permanent meadows and pastures	37.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%		4.0%	-11.7%	-25.8%	
Planted Forest	33.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%		77.0%	0.0%	19.4%	

SOURCE: FAOSTAT 2023

2.2 Land based mitigation measures.

Land- based climate mitigation measures, also known as Agriculture, Forestry, and other Land Uses (AFOLU) mitigation or natural climate solutions have gained significant attention and importance in public and private sector climate strategies and policies (Fujimori, et al. 2022). Land based mitigation measures constitute nature- based solutions and if implemented, have significant benefits to human well- being and biodiversity (Seddon et al., 2020). Land- based measures reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and/or enhance carbon removals (Roe et al. 2021). They include supply- side interventions in forests and other ecosystems (to protect, manage, and restore), agriculture (to reduce emissions and enhance carbon sequestration), and bioenergy (to reduce fossil fuel emissions and sequester carbon), as well as demand- side interventions on food waste, diets, and resource use. Most countries have included AFOLU measures in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement, either by specifically listing actions or by including the land sector in their broader GHG reduction targets (Crumpler et al., 2019). Collectively, AFOLU- related NDC actions make up about 25% of planned GHG reductions in 2030 (Grassi et al., 2021), with most focus on reducing deforestation. Land- based mitigation measures are also embedded in other international agreements and initiatives, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN), Aichi Biodiversity Targets, the goals of the New York Declaration on Forests (NYDF), the

Bonn Challenge, and the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration. Recent studies estimate that land-based measures have the potential to mitigate approximately 10–15 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹ by 2050, corresponding to about 20%–30% of the mitigation needed to achieve the 1.5°C temperature target (Griscom et al., 2017).

Achieving climate targets and addressing other land-related challenges synergistically at national levels remains a large challenge and global progress is lacking. GHG emissions from AFOLU have been increasing since 2000 (Roe et al., 2021). The efficacy and extent of benefits or risks of land-based measures largely depend on the type of activity undertaken, deployment strategy (e.g., scale, method, complementarity with other measures and sectors), and geographic context (e.g., current biome dynamics, climate, food system, land ownership) (Smith et al., 2019). As such, successful and sustainable adoption and appropriate prioritization of land-based mitigation measures would benefit from more regional and country-level information on drivers of emissions, mitigation potentials, co-benefits, and risks (Crumpler et al., 2019). The success of different policies and implementation of land-based measures is dependent on enabling conditions and barriers that vary greatly by country. Available funding and economic incentives, governance and institutional capacity, technological capacity, geophysical capacity, socio-cultural context, and environmental-ecological conditions all make implementation more or less likely (de Coninck et al., 2018).

A study by Roe et al. (2021) shows that the highest cost-effective mitigation potential comes from reducing deforestation (0.97 ± 0.4 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹; 39%), then afforestation and reforestation (0.25 ± 0.2 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹; 10%), sequestering soil organic carbon in grasslands (0.24 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹; 10%), shifting diets (0.2 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹; 8%), and agroforestry (0.19 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹; 8%). Across the countries, the DRC has the most cost-effective mitigation potential at 0.4 ± 0.2 GtCO₂eq yr⁻¹, or about 16% of Africa's potential. The DRC is followed by Tanzania where land-based emissions are largely driven by deforestation from shifting agriculture, “forest protection” measures present the highest cost-effective mitigation potential.

In contrast, the Democratic Republic of Congo, a “Surplus potential, low feasibility country,” is characterized by relatively low fossil fuel emissions and high AFOLU emissions (Schwingshackl et al. 2022). DRC has the potential to generate surplus AFOLU mitigation, largely through the protection of forests and other ecosystems that can enable the country to achieve net negative emissions by mid-century (Ajonina et al. 2014). However, according to their NDC, the DRC faces a series of feasibility challenges that undermine the deployment and scaling up of mitigation action: limited national financial resources, external financial support, and technical,

jurisdictional, and institutional capacity; as well as the absence of policies and incentives that adequately addresses competing sectoral interests (mining, agriculture and forestry). Activating DRC's mitigation potential will require addressing drivers of deforestation such as commercial agriculture, subsistence farming, or wood fuel harvesting and development challenges at the nexus of food security, rural development, energy supply, and forest conservation (Shapiro et al. 2021; Namubamba et al. 2023). Various programs and initiatives to reduce deforestation in the DRC have been in place for a long time; however, funding has been slow to materialize, and feasibility constraints make it difficult for DRC to access result- based finance (Mosnier et al 2014). DRC is an example a country that would significantly benefit from deploying an integrated development strategy that leapfrogs carbon- intensive development in favour of clean and sustainable development choices, and from international partnership and assistance.

3.0 Overview on LANDMARC results

3.1 Potential of LMTs in Africa

Land-based emission mitigation technologies, including agroforestry, afforestation, biochar, organic farming, and minimum tillage, hold immense potential for Africa (Figure 1). In a region where climate change poses substantial challenges, these technologies offer a multifaceted solution (Roe et al. 2021). Agroforestry and afforestation not only sequester carbon but also promote biodiversity and provide sustainable sources of wood and non-timber forest products (Shapiro et al. 2021). Biochar, known as "black gold," acts as a carbon sink, enhancing soil fertility and crop yields (Sundberg et al. 2020). Organic farming and minimum tillage practices contribute to improved soil health, reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers and pesticides (Osewe et al. 2021). This approach not only mitigates greenhouse gas emissions but also enhances the resilience of African farming systems to a changing climate, bolstering food security and sustainable land management. It presents a unique opportunity to address climate, agriculture, and land degradation challenges simultaneously, making these technologies a vital component of Africa's sustainable development and climate adaptation strategies.

Figure 1 Mitigation Potential of LMTs in different regions, Gt CO₂ e/year. Source: Karki, L. et al., 2023.

3.2 Enhanced regional integration and cooperation.

Enhanced regional integration and cooperation play a pivotal role in scaling up land-based emission mitigation technologies in Africa, including agroforestry, afforestation, biochar, organic farming, minimum tillage, and peatland conservation (Shapiro et al. 2021; Sundberg et al. 2020). Firstly, by fostering regional collaboration, countries can pool their resources and knowledge, ensuring a more efficient and coordinated approach to addressing climate change. This approach allows for the sharing of best practices and experiences in implementing these technologies, creating a collective learning environment that accelerates their adoption (Gichuki et al. 2019). Moreover, regional cooperation promotes knowledge transfer, enabling countries with more experience in specific mitigation technologies to support their neighbours in adopting and adapting these practices. Regional integration provides a platform for harmonizing policies and standards related to land-based emission mitigation technologies. Consistency in regulations across neighbouring countries can remove barriers to the adoption of these practices, making it easier for farmers and landowners to implement them. It ensures that the benefits of these technologies are not constrained by conflicting regulations or standards when goods or services cross national borders, thereby facilitating trade in mitigation products. By working together, East African nations can develop comprehensive proposals for funding that address the unique challenges and opportunities within the region, which can be more attractive to investors and international partners (Lal, 2019).

Enhanced regional integration and cooperation create a supportive environment for scaling up land-based emission mitigation technologies in Africa. By sharing knowledge, harmonizing

policies, and attracting investments collectively, African nations can more effectively combat climate change and build a sustainable and resilient future for the continent.

3.3 Regional perspective from stakeholder interviews

A series of semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather individual stakeholders' perspectives on the role and potential of enhanced regional integration and cooperation for the scaling up of LMTs. Below are some highlights of insights shared by stakeholders.

Barriers:

- Many smallholder farmers and communities in Africa may lack awareness of these land-based emission mitigation technologies. They may not fully understand the potential benefits and how to implement them effectively.
- Implementing these technologies often requires an initial investment, which can be a significant barrier for resource-constrained farmers. Access to credit and funding mechanisms is limited.
- In some areas, limited access to infrastructure, such as roads and transportation, can hinder the distribution of technology-related inputs, making it difficult for farmers to adopt these practices.
- Inconsistent or inadequate policies and regulations related to land-based emission mitigation can hinder adoption. Farmers may face legal barriers or lack incentives for change.
- Climate change and variability can pose challenges, particularly in regions with unpredictable weather patterns. These variations may affect the success of mitigation technologies.

Enablers:

- Local and International Support from NGOs, international organizations, and governments including training, knowledge sharing, and financial resources to help farmers adopt these technologies.
- Ongoing research and innovation in land-based emission mitigation technologies can lead to the development of more affordable and accessible solutions that suit local conditions.
- Involving local communities and farmers in the decision-making process and implementation of these technologies can enhance their adoption. This approach can empower communities to take ownership of the solutions.

- Access to markets for sustainably produced products can provide an economic incentive for farmers to adopt these technologies. Certification schemes and consumer demand for eco-friendly products can drive adoption.

Opportunities

- Land-based emission mitigation technologies often offer **multiple benefits**, such as increased soil fertility, enhanced crop yields, and improved resilience to climate change. These co-benefits can make adoption more attractive.
- Increasing global attention on climate change mitigation opens doors for **climate finance**. African nations can tap into these funding sources to support the scaling up of these technologies.
- Collaborative efforts between nations promote the sharing of knowledge, experiences, and best practices in adopting these technologies. **Regional cooperation** can create economies of scale and reduce costs.
- These technologies align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly those related to zero hunger, clean water, and climate action. Leveraging this alignment can drive adoption.

While barriers to the scaling up of land-based emission mitigation technologies exist, enablers and opportunities can help overcome these challenges. Support from various stakeholders, research and innovation, community engagement, and market opportunities can drive adoption. The multiple benefits of these technologies, access to climate finance, and regional collaboration offer promising avenues for their expansion.

4.0 Brief National Profiles

Land-based mitigation technologies offer a multitude of co-benefits that extend well beyond their primary goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. These co-benefits encompass a wide range of social, economic, and environmental advantages. For instance, afforestation and reforestation efforts enhance biodiversity and provide habitat for various wildlife species, contributing to ecosystem health. Agroforestry and organic farming practices not only sequester carbon but also improve soil quality, leading to increased crop yields and sustainable land use. These approaches promote water conservation and water quality improvements, safeguarding valuable water resources. Moreover, land-based mitigation technologies often empower local communities by creating employment opportunities, enhancing food security, and bolstering resilience to climate change. They also contribute to cleaner air, improved air quality, and reduced soil erosion, furthering overall environmental sustainability. An assessment of key LMTs

was done in Kenya as well as DRC which is a significant country in East Africa regarding emission sequestration.

4.1 Kenya

Kenya's economy is largely dependent on rainfed agriculture, tourism and natural resources, sectors that are susceptible to climate variability and change and extreme weather events. Kenya's updated Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) that was submitted to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in December 2020 notes that successive climate change impacts result in socio-economic losses estimated at 3-4 percent of Gross Domestic Product annually and that they impede development efforts. Although Kenya contributes less than 0.1 percent of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions annually, the country has put measures in place to pursue a low carbon and resilient development pathway to help realize its Vision 2030: to transform Kenya into a newly industrializing, middle-income country. Furthermore, Kenya's Climate Change Act of 2016 and the National Climate Change Action Plan (NCCAP) 2023-2028 provide guidance for low carbon and climate resilient development. Kenya's priorities as articulated through these instruments include adaptation, afforestation and reforestation, landscape restoration, climate-smart agriculture, geothermal and clean energy development, energy efficiency, and drought and flood risk management.

The Climate action tracker (CAT) rates Kenya's climate targets and policies as overall "Almost sufficient". Kenya's policies and unconditional target meet its fair-share contribution to limiting warming to 1.5°C. However, Kenya's target with international support is currently only compatible with 4°C of warming or higher and should be strengthened. The strong difference in the two ratings reflects Kenya's situation as a country with strong development needs and a small historical responsibility, but with relevant mitigation potential in its own territory, which could be exploited to a large extent with international support.

Source: Climate Action tracker <https://climateactiontracker.org/countries/kenya/policies-action/>

Kenya’s emissions from Land-use, land-use change, and forestry have contributed to almost one third of the country’s total emissions over the last 20 years on average (USAID, 2022). The major reasons for deforestation are the conversion of forest land to agriculture, unsustainable utilisation of forest products (including charcoal), forest fires and shifting cultivation. In Kenya, land-based mitigation technologies play a critical role in addressing climate change, enhancing agricultural practices, and promoting sustainable land management. These technologies encompass various strategies that aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, enhance carbon sequestration, and improve the resilience of ecosystems. These key components include agroforestry, afforestation, biochar, organic farming, minimum tillage, and peatland conservation. Agroforestry practices involve integrating trees and shrubs with crops and livestock, contributing to carbon sequestration, soil fertility, and increased agricultural productivity. Afforestation and reforestation initiatives focus on planting trees on deforested or degraded land to sequester carbon, protect watersheds, and preserve biodiversity. Biochar, produced by heating organic material in a low-oxygen environment, is added to soil to enhance its structure, nutrient retention, and carbon sequestration capacity. Organic farming prioritizes soil health and biodiversity by avoiding synthetic inputs and promoting organic matter incorporation. Minimum tillage reduces soil disturbance during cultivation, improving carbon retention, water infiltration, and erosion control. Lastly, peatland conservation safeguards critical wetland ecosystems, preventing carbon emissions and supporting biodiversity. The government of Kenya, in collaboration with various stakeholders, actively promotes these

strategies to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, enhance agricultural resilience, and maintain sustainable land use practices in the context of climate change and food security.

The government of Kenya, in collaboration with international organizations and non-governmental bodies, has been actively promoting these land-based mitigation technologies. Kenya recognizes the importance of balancing environmental conservation with agricultural productivity to ensure food security and climate resilience. Kenya has also published sectoral plans for reaching emission reductions targets for the transport and agriculture sectors. The Transport Sector Climate Change Annual Report(s) and Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) Strategy focus on the implementation of the priority mitigation actions outlined in the NCCAP to ensure the sectors' emissions reduction efforts are in line with achieving the 2030 NDC target (Government of Kenya, 2020).

Kenya's political commitment to climate change mitigation issues is evident - the President and line ministries support climate mitigation action. However, leadership from the head of state and leading institutions could take a more proactive stance on scaling up climate action domestically and drive the transition to a zero emissions economy and society. Greater autonomy and power for the Climate Change Directorate would further advance the development and implementation of climate mitigation policies aimed at Kenya's zero emissions transition. The institutional framework of Kenya is clearly defined and enshrined in law, but the coordination between ministries, and between national and county levels is not yet effective. As a result, climate change and the fulfilment of national climate change mitigation targets are not consistently included in all sectoral plans. While the national climate change lead agency has qualified staff, its budget is insufficient to enable effective implementation of some statutory tasks, such as the analytical support to sector ministries, which could be improved.

Source: Climate Action tracker <https://climateactiontracker.org/countries/kenya/policies-action/>

Kenya does not yet have long-term emissions reduction strategies and targets. While the contours of a comprehensive transparency framework in line with the country's climate law are in place, these are not yet widely applied across sectors. It is therefore difficult to assess the effectiveness of policy measures being implemented and whether the sectors' contours are on track to meet their targets. Whether domestic climate action becomes progressively more ambitious will be seen once the country has published its revised NDC, which is currently under development.

A defined Paris-compatible decarbonisation pathway is an important component to aid short, medium and long-term planning for, and alignment with, the Paris Agreement's overall objectives. Kenya, however, has no publicly available long-term decarbonisation goal. The NCCAP and NDC set emissions reductions targets for 2022 and 2030 respectively, but do not cover later years. These targets are a reduction from a BAU scenario and allow for an increase in emissions compared to current emission levels. While the 2016 Climate Change Act provides for the institutional framework to address climate change and indicates that the National climate change council (NCCC) shall set the targets for the regulation of greenhouse gas emissions, it does not include a quantitative emissions reductions target (Republic of Kenya, 2016). Making provisions for empowering clauses for such targets would give line ministries a stronger incentive to set sector-specific emissions reductions targets. Currently, most line ministries do not align the existing national medium-term plans (e.g. NDC) with near-term policy development and implementation. There are, however, positive examples, such as the Transport Ministry, that considers NDC mitigation targets for short-term policy development, bases sectoral actions on the NCCAP and aims to reduce emissions compared to a BAU scenario (Government of Kenya, 2019). An enhanced transparency framework mechanism is necessary to track progress towards achieving emissions reduction targets in line with the Paris Agreement, as well as providing checks and balances for the government's climate commitments.

The Climate Change Act mandates climate change directorate (CCD) to establish and manage a national registry for appropriate mitigation actions by public and private entities and tasks government entities to report on sectoral greenhouse gas emissions for the national inventory (Republic of Kenya, 2016). The National Environmental Management Authority (NEMA) should, on behalf of the NCCC, regulate, enforce and monitor compliance on levels of greenhouse gas emissions (Republic of Kenya, 2016). Several sectors have published sectoral greenhouse gas inventories, such as the land sector, through the System for Land-based Emissions Estimations (SLEEK) or the agriculture sector in its inventory report of GHG emissions from dairy cattle (ECOS, 2017; Republic of Kenya, 2020).

4.2 Democratic republic of Congo

The ecosystem of the Democratic Republic of the Congo both absorbs and emits carbon dioxide (Ajonina et al. 2014). The gross carbon absorption from established forests surpasses the gross

emissions resulting from land-use change, as well as the combustion of fossil fuels and industrial operations (Tyukavina et al. 2013). The net forest carbon absorption in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is estimated to be roughly 0.4 Giga ton of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e) each year, establishing the DRC as the primary carbon absorber in Africa (Dargie et al. 2017). DRC alone can absorb up to two thirds of Africa's annual carbon emissions (IMF, 2022).

The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) harbors the second largest tropical peatland globally. Peatlands serve as a significant reservoir for long-term carbon sequestration, effectively removing carbon from the atmosphere (Sonwa et al. 2022). According to Dargie et al. (2017), the Congo Basin contains around 30 gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e) in its storage. The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) represents around 60 percent of the Congo basin, and within its borders lies a peat area spanning 90,800 square kilometers (Crezee et al. 2022). This peat area is estimated to have a significant carbon stock of approximately 19 gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e) (Dargie et al. 2017). The data presented indicates that the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) holds a significant position as the second most important country in the tropical region in terms of peat lands and peat carbon stocks, following Indonesia and Brazil (Ribeiro et al. 2021). The peatlands of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) remain mostly unaffected by human activities (Sonwa et al. 2022). However, these ecosystems face potential threats from alterations in land utilization and potential decreases in precipitation in the future (Senga et al. 2023).

The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) is also recognized as the home of the world's second biggest tropical forest (Namubamba et al. 2023). The forests of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) are believed to encompass an area over 100 million hectares, accounting for around 58 percent of the country's total land area (Morgan et al. 2023). This vast expanse constitutes approximately 10 percent of the global tropical forest coverage and approximately 60 percent of the Congo basin. In general, the forests of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) possess a collective carbon stock of 23.3 gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e), which is accumulated and stored above the ground. Although DRC's Forest plays a crucial role in absorbing carbon, there has been a notable rise in carbon emissions resulting from land-use change and forestry activities. In 2018, the activities of Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LUCF) was responsible for 91 percent of the total emissions. Agriculture accounted for 5 percent of total emissions, making it the second greatest contributor in the country.

According to the World Resources Institute (WRI, 2021), the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) had a very low deforestation rate until 2010, with an annual average of 0.2 percent for the period between 1990 and 2010. Although the DRC is considered to have a relatively low deforestation rate, the total area of deforestation is large in actual terms, losing 15.9 Mha of tree cover between 2001 and 2020; equivalent to an 8.0% decrease in tree cover since 2000, and 9.71 Gt of CO₂e emissions (Morgan et al. 2023) The phenomenon of tree cover loss has had a notable escalation, mostly propelled by agricultural activities, illegal artisanal logging, and the production of charcoal. It is worth noting that a significant proportion, around 70 percent, of this tree cover loss is concentrated in rural areas characterized by high levels of poverty. The Democratic Republic of

Congo's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are mostly driven by land-use change and forestry, accounting for 86 percent of the total emissions. Waste contributes 11 percent, while agriculture and energy provide 0.86 percent and 0.61 percent, respectively (USAID, 2022).

Source WRI 2021

Conclusion

The exploration of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa reveals a promising pathway towards sustainable development and climate resilience in the region. As Africa grapples with the dual challenges of mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to the impacts of climate change, leveraging the potential of land-based solutions emerges as a critical imperative. Through the adoption and implementation of practices such as agroforestry, soil carbon sequestration, sustainable land management, and afforestation/reforestation initiatives, East Africa nations can significantly contribute to global efforts to combat climate change while simultaneously enhancing food security, biodiversity conservation, and rural livelihoods.

However, realizing the full potential of land-based mitigation technologies requires concerted action and collaboration at multiple levels. Governments, policymakers, researchers, and civil society organizations must work together to create enabling policy frameworks, mobilize financial resources, and build institutional capacities to support the widespread adoption and scaling-up of these technologies. Furthermore, efforts to promote sustainable land management and restoration practices must be integrated into broader development strategies, ensuring alignment with national priorities and socioeconomic objectives.

For the long-term success of land-based mitigation efforts in East Africa, it is imperative to address the underlying drivers of deforestation, land degradation, and unsustainable land use practices is essential. This necessitates addressing issues such as land tenure insecurity, inadequate land governance systems, and unsustainable agricultural expansion, which often contribute to land degradation and deforestation. By adopting holistic and inclusive approaches that prioritize community engagement, indigenous knowledge systems, and gender-sensitive

interventions, East Africa can foster more resilient and equitable land-use systems that deliver multiple co-benefits for both people and the planet.

Considering the urgent need to accelerate climate action and achieve the objectives of the Paris Agreement, the role of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa cannot be overstated. As the region continues to urbanize, industrialize, and develop, it is imperative to prioritize sustainable land management practices that safeguard natural resources, enhance ecosystem resilience, and promote climate-smart agriculture. By harnessing the power of land-based mitigation technologies, East Africa can not only mitigate greenhouse gas emissions but also build a more sustainable, inclusive, and prosperous future for its people and the generations to come.

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Annex I: LANDMARC LMT Glossary

- Agriculture
 - Agroforestry: Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land
 - Dry seeded rice – no till: Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.
 - Reduced tillage: A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.
 - Integrated soil fertility management: Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.
 - Organic agriculture: An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.
- Forestry
 - Afforestation/reforestation: Afforestation: Establishing forest by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover. Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.
 - Forest management: Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.
 - Forest fire management: Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.
- Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS): Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.
- Biochar: organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.
- Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost): Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and bio-gas slurry as compost.
- Peatland management: Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.
- Pasture management: Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.

Annex II: List of Acronyms

ANNEX C2: INCEPTION REPORT FOR ASIA

Preface

LANDMARC

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date, most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking also at negative emission solutions. Among them, we find land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) such as afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, agriculture, biochar, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), grassland and wetland management. However, many LMTs, their impacts and their implementation needs, are still insufficiently understood.

The four-year LANDMARC project is filling this knowledge gap by employing a triangular research approach, encompassing both technical and social aspects: the use of satellite data and soil sampling is combined with climate, land-use, and economic scenario modelling, and stakeholder engagement. This global effort carried out by 19 partners and spread over 16 national case studies aims to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors;
- Assess the regional and global upscaling potential of negative emission solutions;
- Map potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs.

Regional Stakeholder Workshops

The regional implications of LMTs across different countries are of growing interest due to similar physical and socio-economic conditions across different world regions. Furthermore, economic integration, harmonisation, governance and research collaboration is growing within regions and offers a valuable means to enhance the Means of Implementation in the Paris Agreement, namely finance, technology transfer and capacity-building.

In the period October to November 2023, SEI in collaboration with its LANDMARC consortium partners, organizes regional stakeholder workshops in its four regional centres in Bogotá, Nairobi, Bangkok, and Stockholm. The regional expertise and insights of the workshop participants will enrich our understanding of scaling LMTs by making scenario and modelling assumptions more realistic, and, as a consequence, it will also allow us to make better recommendations to policy- and decision makers.

The Stockholm Environment Institute

The Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) leads the regional engagement Work Package of LANDMARC. The SEI is an international non-profit research and policy organization that tackles environment and development challenges. SEI's work spans climate, water, air, and land-use issues, governance, the economy, and gender/equity. Stakeholder involvement is at the heart of our efforts to build capacity, strengthen institutions and equip partners for long- term change.

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1. Introduction/overview of workshop objectives

The regional workshop on land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) brings together a diverse group of stakeholders to review and evaluate land-based mitigation options in the region, focusing on three key dimensions or elements:

- I. Identifying and characterising a regional portfolio of land-based mitigation options;
- II. Evaluating how ambitions for land-based mitigation can be raised in the region; and
- III. Offering recommendations as to how regional engagement (as well as regional and transnational cooperation) can facilitate such higher ambitions.

The workshop takes as input various research results, syntheses and stakeholder engagements that have been carried out at local, national or regional levels, and can be divided into three main types:

- 1) **National case studies**, in which detailed analyses and stakeholder consultations for different LMTs were carried out, resulting in an “LMT portfolio” and LMT scaling scenarios to characterising the most promising LMTs and their expected impacts and interactions, in terms of how they could be scaled up to achieve NDCs and/or other climate and development goals;
- 2) **Regional outlooks**, based on a review of key policies and mechanisms at regional level, along with regional perspectives obtained through stakeholder interviews and consultations; and
- 3) **Land-vegetation-carbon modelling**, carried out at national, regional and global levels, all based on Shared Socio-economic Pathway 2 (SSP2), which is the “middle of the road” pathway among the five SSPs used as reference points within the Integrated Assessment Modelling Community and as the basis for IPCC Assessments. Three scenarios are used to determine the implementation until the year 2100, using a particular set of LMTs, with each scenario related to the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCPs) adopted in IPCC Assessments, and corresponding to different greenhouse gas concentration in the year 2100:
 - i. Baseline: uses RCP of 4.5 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 3C.
 - ii. Moderate ambition: uses RCP of 2.6 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 2C.
 - iii. High ambition: uses RCP of 1.9 W/m², which is expected under most scenarios to be associated with average temperature increases close to 1.5C.

The models are limited in the number of LMTs that can be evaluated and thus five were chosen:

1. Afforestation (includes reforestation and forest management);
2. Agroforestry (trees planted within agricultural areas, with specific characteristics);
3. Biochar (sourced from land availability as calculated and used as a soil amendment);
4. Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)
5. No tillage (no or minimal tillage | agricultural areas)

There be limited discussion on LMTs not modelled, as appropriate to their national or regional significance. After presentations on selected issues outlined above, workshop participants will be asked to debate and evaluate LMTs, levels of ambition, and regional engagement options, and will thereby contribute to a set of narratives to be developed later to capture these elements.

2. Overview on climate mitigation and land sectors

2.1 Asia-Pacific

The latest IPCC reports warn that there is essentially a decade left to reverse a climate catastrophe. Nonetheless, the enhancement of climate pledges and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) has been limited in recent years (UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022; Meinshausen et al., 2022). If all targets from the current 2030 NDCs and Long-term strategies (LTS) are met, the best-estimate of warming will be around 1.9°C, just below 2°C (ibid.).

In the Asia-Pacific region, the energy transition is a crucial component of climate change mitigation strategies. The latest Statistical Review of World Energy shows that the Asia Pacific region continues to increase its share of total global emissions (now around 46%) due to its growing energy consumption and reliance on coal, the most carbon-intensive fossil fuel (The Energy Institute, 2023; IEA, 2022). As a result, the focus of the region’s mitigation related targets is on removing the barriers to decarbonization of key and carbon-intensive sectors through phasing down and phasing out coal, reducing dependence on other fossil fuels, scaling up penetration of renewable energy resources and e-mobility, and enhancing energy efficiency (UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022).

Table 1 2019 GHG emissions of the three Landmarc case studies (Indonesia, Vietnam and Nepal), plus China.

Source: Climate Watch. Note: In Vietnam and China, LUCF are a carbon sink.

	Indonesia	Vietnam	Nepal	China
Land use change and forestry (LUCF)	47%	-3% (-12.93 mtco2e)	8%	-5% (-647.2 mtco2e)
Agriculture	8%	15%	53%	5%
Energy	36%	68%	28%	88%
Transport	8%	10%	10%	8%
Total including LUCF	1913.58 mtco2e	441.96 mtco2e	48.4 mtco2e	12085.05 mtco2e
Share of global GHG	3.94%	0.88%	0.10%	27%

In parallel to the energy sector, the land sector offers an important opportunity to mitigate emissions as shown in Table 1. Although already acknowledged in NDCs for adaptation benefits, and mitigation benefits to a much lesser extent, nature-based solutions, including land-based mitigation measures, should become more of a focus area with specific commitments and implementation plans for enhanced mitigation targets in the next revisions of the NDCs. Particular attention should be paid to the questions of financing and social safeguards regarding inclusion and livelihoods regarding land-based mitigation measures. Investments in nature-based solutions have been estimated to be cost-effective and offer high mitigation benefits with multiple environmental, social, and economic co-benefits (UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022). Figure 1 shows the projected contribution of nature-based solutions to reach net-zero by 2050 in the Asia-Pacific region.

Figure 1 Projected contribution of NbS to net-zero in the Asia-Pacific. Source: UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022

Across Asia and the Pacific, examples of successful collaboration exist, but to meet the challenge of climate change mitigation as well as building resilience, regional cooperation should be strengthened, ambitions should be raised, and climate action should include improved sustainable land management and nature-based solutions (UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022; UN ESCAP, 2022). To enhance regional cooperation for environment and development, there should be a focus on solidarity, data-sharing, transparency, increased accountability, coordinated and participatory action, and a transformation of economic and financial systems (UN ESCAP, 2022). To raise NDC targets with nature-based solutions, UN ESCAP proposes the following concrete measures (UN ESCAP, UNEP & UNICEF, 2022):

- Build a regional platform to facilitate the exchange of best practices and lessons learned from policies and projects supporting NDC implementation, and increase technical cooperation for developing, deploying and replicating decarbonization technologies;
- Engage stakeholders and increasing public awareness to support NDC updates and implementation;
- Build a regional programme to unlock the energy and knowledge to drive climate action;
- Build regional dialogues around new technologies, including those on carbon dioxide removal to determine effectiveness, scientific soundness, and deployment of such technologies;
- Increase transboundary ecosystem adaptations and finding NbS for building the region's resilience, move towards net-CO₂-zero and achieving climate resilient development for all.

2.2 Southeast Asia

All ASEAN Member States (AMS) have signed the Paris Agreement and formulated their NDCs, which they submitted or updated between 2020 and 2022. However, the NDCs have been considered lacking ambition (Overland et al., 2021). NDC commitments and mitigation targets need to be strengthened to meet the reduction of GHGs aligned with the 1.5°C goal. The tables in Annex I provide an overview of climate commitments, including targets related to land-based mitigation for a selection of countries.

Southeast Asia's GHG emissions are increasing in parallel to its economic development, and it is therefore key to enhance the efforts to mitigate climate change. At the same time, the region is one of the most vulnerable areas worldwide to the climate crisis's adverse consequences. Over the last two decades, there has been an increased number and intensity of extreme climate events and disasters: floods, typhoons, droughts, and heat waves. During the last 20 years, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Thailand have been among the top 10 countries most affected by extreme climate hazards (Eckstein et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is a densely populated region: its population has consistently risen over the last decades, reaching now around 680 million inhabitants, a third of whom living in Indonesia (IMF, 2023). According to the IPCC, the greatest effects of sea level rise will be felt the most in South and Southeast Asia, with some of the world's largest archipelagic states, and with increasing risk of losing infrastructure and low-lying coastal settlements to sea-level rise (IPCC, Chapter 10, 2022). By 2050, 64% of Asia's population will be urban, and coastal cities - where a high concentration of people and activities is found, an estimated 77% - are seen as 'high-risk areas' (ibid.).

Most countries in the region are heavily dependent on natural resources, land, and biodiversity (for agriculture, tourism, and production of goods and services), which are directly affected by climate impacts. In countries such as Myanmar, Cambodia, Lao PDR agriculture still represents a significant part of GDP (around 20%) (World Bank, 2022). The region has undergone significant changes in the

land sectors over the past two decades, as shown in Figure 2 and Table 2. In general, there is a clear reduction in natural forest, and an increase in plantation forests and cropland.

Figure 2 Absolute land use change (2000-2021) in selected ASEAN countries.

Source: FAOSTAT, 2023. Note: Indonesia and Southeast Asia TOTAL are on a separate scale.

Table 2 Percentage land use change (2000-2021) in selected ASEAN countries. Source: FAOSTAT, 2023.

**Note: Area increases in land use type displayed in blue, decreases in orange. Darker shadings represent larger changes.

Climate change is expected to have a widespread impact on various land systems and to alter the application and effectiveness of land-based mitigation measures (LMTs) that aim to reduce emissions from the land sectors. Disturbances in temperatures and rain patterns could heavily affect afforestation efforts, especially in the early phases, growth patterns of grasses and legumes, or yields of more sensitive crops such as coffee. This could compromise carbon stocks provided by these systems, as well as their general productivity (LANDMARC, 2023).

3. Overview on potentials and policies

Due to the vast land area along with the physical and socio-economic diversity of the Asia-Pacific Region, it is difficult to conduct a complete regional study, nor are workshop participants expected to consider all individual countries. However, the case study in Nepal provided some insights on South Asia, and we also conducted an analysis on China because of its outsized importance in the region in economic and technical terms as well as its considerable land area and population.

3.1 Potential of LMTs in Asia-Pacific

As Asia-Pacific is the world's largest region, it is not surprising that it has been estimated as having the highest LMT potential as shown in Figure 3. As with most regions, afforestation and reforestation are a significant share of the estimated potential. Taken together with forest management and agroforestry, these represent more than 70% of the estimated potential. However, there are many factors that have to be considered alongside the estimated potential, for example the permanence of carbon removal is less assured with standing biomass in forests compared to sequestration of carbon in soils or in geological formations (Karki et al., 2023). Furthermore, in some cases potentials are estimated with respect to existing productivities and uses of land and biomass, which is relatively low in Africa for example, and potentials might be enhanced by improved productivity and use (van de Ven et al., 2019). Therefore, the technical or economic potential needs to be viewed as one of several indicators of actual or realisable potential.

Figure 3 Mitigation Potential of LMTs in different regions, Gt CO₂ e/year. Source: Karki, L. et al., 2023.

3.2 Asia-Pacific regional perspective from stakeholder interviews

A series of semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather individual stakeholders' perspectives on the role and potential of enhanced regional integration and cooperation for the scaling up of LMTs. Below are some highlights of insights shared by stakeholders.

Barriers:

- Weak regional coordination and resource mobilization: different policy priorities, landscapes, and realities, inconsistent or conflicting policies, regulations, and institutional frameworks.
- External factors such as the economy are the main reason for a certain land use type (sometimes more than internal factors like who holds the land, what they want to grow etc.).
- Initiatives at too high and general levels risk not being “in touch” with the reality on the ground, and not resulting in applicable measures in the local context.
- Focus on economic development.
- Misalignment between governments at national and local levels.
- Governments, practitioners, networks, and other stakeholders are often faced with lack of funding or technical capacity needed for implementation.
- Lack of region-specific research, data, and information on ecosystem services, carbon stocks, and land-use dynamics.

Enablers:

- Harmonized policies and regulations at the regional level and aligning sectoral policies to mainstream LMT strategies into broader land-use planning is crucial for implementation.
- Champions in the region that can showcase successful national projects and programs that can be adapted and adopted regionally.
- Shared solutions for shared problems such as the challenges of increasing pressure on land due to population growth and expanding economic activity, smallholders' livelihoods and land tenure issues, and transboundary issues (e.g., illegal timber trade, forest/peatland fires).
- Enhanced communication processes, joint research by regional organizations, joint actions between the corresponding national ministries, networking opportunities and awareness at all levels and sectors (and not only in education/among universities), international agreements, and careful consideration of the political realities in the region.

Opportunities:

- ASEAN might be the key organization that could play an important role in the region to foster cooperation on LMT development through influencing decision making and policy development.
- The private sector is often overlooked in discussions around land-use but plays a major role in driving land-use system changes. Major commodities in global supply chains dictate land-use through demand, leading to large amounts of land dedicated to high-intensity and high-input production of rubber, palm oil, cassava, etc. Large companies' supply chains can run through many countries and can therefore have far-reaching effects when they implement changes.
- Public budgets for LMTs are often limited, other sources of funding such as carbon markets, certification, payments for ecosystem services, ecotourism, and blended finance, or market-based interventions based on company standards and consumer demand can drive the development of LMTs.

3.3 Brief National Profiles

3.3.1 Indonesia

Forests cover 65% of Indonesia's area and the forest sector is the main contributor to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Indonesia lost 26.8 million ha of tree cover from 2002 to 2019, contributing to 10.9 Gt of CO₂ emissions. Therefore, afforestation and agroforestry, together with activities that reduce deforestation are crucial in Indonesia. Peatland covers 20.6 million ha or 10.8% of the total land area in Indonesia. Emissions peaked in 2015 due to extreme warming effects attributed to El Niño. Peatland management in the form of Rewetting, Revegetation, and Revitalization, therefore, plays a key role in preserving and enhancing the country's carbon stock. Agriculture accounts for 13% of Indonesia's total greenhouse gas emissions. Agricultural activities are extremely vulnerable to climate change impacts on soil health and water availability. Therefore, solutions that offer mitigation and adaptation benefits in agriculture are of high importance. BECCS and biochar, although potentially relevant in the Indonesian context, were not included in case study discussions due to their current limited scale, high implementation cost, low technological readiness, and low prioritization.

Afforestation / forest management	Agroforestry	Peatland management	Cropland management	Soil carbon enhancement
Policy context				
Rehabilitating 11.55 million ha of degraded forest and land by 2030	Agroforestry to rehabilitate degraded land	Restoring 3.35 million ha of degraded peatland by 2024	Focus on productivity, adaptation, and food security, no system for mitigation which is seen as co-benefit	Reducing waste emissions by 94% from 2024 to 2030, generating 5.5 GW of electricity from biogas by 2025
Land use competition				
Expansion of plantations, agricultural, residential, and industrial land	Expansion of agricultural, residential, and industrial land	Expansion of agricultural, residential, and industrial land	Rice fields conversion to other land use such as settlements and industry	Rice fields conversion to other land use: settlements and industry
Climate risks & sensitivities				
Fires, floods, biodiversity loss, desertification, drought	Drought, floods	Drought, extreme weather and heat, salinity from sea level rise, erosion, biodiversity loss	Soil health, water availability, erratic weather and temperature, erosion, salinity	Soil health, water availability, erratic weather and temperature, erosion, salinity
Economic implications				
Need for financial incentives for forest conservation and rehabilitation	Income increase and diversification, reduced costs of labour, inputs	Income from paludiculture, carbon farming	Need for financial incentives and subsidies, potential premium price	Income increase and reduced purchase of inputs, need for capital investment
Co-benefits and synergies				
Water and nutrient cycling, biodiversity, ecosystem services, resilience	Increased biodiversity, resilience, soil health, food security	Diversified agricultural production, nitrogen fixing, water quality		Production of bioenergy reducing fossil fuels, increased soil health and yields, water quality
Trade-offs				
Inflexible, long-term lock in of land	Potential yield decrease	Reduce water accessibility to locals during dry season	Potential yield decrease and labour increase	Labor increase, weed and pest management
Risks associated with scaling up				
Projects often fail at large scale, need tailor-made approach depending on unique localities	Need tailor-made approach depending on unique localities, need market	Projects often fail at large scale, need tailor-made approach depending on unique localities	Focus on productivity or income, otherwise will not be adopted by farmers, limited reproducibility	Resistance to change at farmer level

Knowledge gaps				
Research on species, climate impacts, technology, MRV		Remote sensing and satellite imagery	Transition cost, local suitability, socio-econ implications	Limited data on SOC

3.3.2 Nepal

The forestry sector plays an important role in Nepal's economy, with forest covering 40.36% of Nepal's the total area. The majority of forests in Nepal are community forests and serve as a source of fuelwood, timber, and fodder for forest dependent households. Afforestation and forest management together have significant carbon sequestration potential of 25.67 4 Mt CO₂e/y. Nepal is among the first countries globally to adopt a national agroforestry policy for increasing the productivity of agriculture, forestry, and livestock sectors. Organic agriculture in Nepal is well embedded into national agricultural policies and its potential in the overall development of the agricultural sector is acknowledged. At the same time, the pace of increase in organic production will be low, as current policies still favor conventional agriculture by providing subsidies and grants for inputs, including chemical fertilizers. Although Nepal has a very small share of global rice production and trade, it plays a significant role in food security and the economy of the country, contributing about one fifth of agricultural GDP. Rice is not only a primary source of employment and income but also provides food and nutrition security for the majority of smallholder farmers.

Afforestation / forest management	Agroforestry	Organic farming	Rice management: dry-seeded rice
Policy context			
NDC: from 40 to 45% forest cover by 2030, community forests, REDD+	Promotion of agroforestry in private, public, and uncultivated farmlands, National Agroforestry Policy 2019	NDC: 2% to 3.95 % SOC by 2030, aim to reduce agriculture emissions, increase carbon sequestration, growing interest and policy support for organic agriculture	NDC: 2% to 3.95 % SOC by 2030, aim to reduce agriculture emissions, increase carbon sequestration
Land Use competition			
Expansion of agriculture and infrastructure	No significant competition since agroforestry is being applied on abandoned plots	Projected to expand as international demand increases	Higher return activities like commercial vegetable production and housing development increasingly displace rice cultivation
Climate risks & sensitivities			
Fires, floods, landslides	Drought, floods, hailstone	Drought, floods, hailstone	Impacts on soils and water retention, shifting monsoon season with heavier rains and stronger wind
Economic implications			
Commodities such as timber and non-timber products	Diversification of commodities, increased revenue	Premium prices (+20%), but struggle with certification	Higher return, reduced labour and costs, lack of financial and tech support
Co-benefits and synergies			
Biodiversity, water quality	Combat soil erosion, improve water quality, biodiversity, food security, resilience	Increased resilience, SOC, biodiversity, lower energy consumption	Improve SOC and soil health, increase yields, reduce water consumption
Trade-offs			
Risk of water depletion, negative impact on communities, risk of biodiversity loss with monocultures of fast-growing, high-value trees	Labor intensive, requires technical expertise, risk of water depletion and negative impact on communities	Yield loss risk	Increased weeds and pests, yield can vary, loss of seeds to birds, N ₂ O increase if high use of N-fertilizer

Risks associated with scaling-up			
Tensions between localized and centralized forest management	Lack of alignment between subnational and national policies, lack of market	Policies incentivize conventional agriculture, yield loss risk, lack of market	Cannot be applied in Nepal's Lowlands as the soils do not drain
Knowledge Gaps			
Species suitability, load bearing capacity of land, carbon storage capacity, value chains	Lack of technical capacity, suitability analysis	Lack of knowledge in soil nutrient management, lack of economic analysis	Lack of data, knowledge on soil types, suitable varieties, management methods

3.3.3 Vietnam

Agroforestry, a traditional agricultural practice in Vietnam, has the highest potential of all of Vietnam's LMTs. Expanding the practice of agroforestry in Vietnam has a sequestration potential of 2.3–44 MtCO₂e. Vietnam is a country with a very intensive agriculture system that produces a lot of agricultural residues. Using residues from rice, maize, and coffee husks to produce biochar is a traditional technique that improves soil quality. However, it must be considered that this is only possible when the competition for biomass is low, such as in Vietnam, but this could change if BECCS is implemented at a larger (regional or global) scale. Vietnam is one of very few tropical countries where forest areas have increased in the last 30 years. This is due to efforts made by Vietnam's government in the late 1980s to combat deforestation. These efforts lead to an increase in total forest cover to 14.4 million ha, covering 42 percent of the country. However, Vietnam's natural forests are in poor or regenerating condition, with rich and closed-canopy forests constituting only 5 percent.

Agroforestry	Biochar	Afforestation / reforestation
Policy context		
High potential for expansion, included in NDC but lacking technical guidelines and support	Discussion around including biochar in policy given focus on food security with carbon sequestration solutions	National forestry development strategy: 42% current forest cover increasing, but quality deteriorating
Land Use competition		
Large international commodity-driven agriculture displacing other types	Currently no competition over biomass, high availability from waste	Large international commodity-driven agriculture driving forest loss
Climate risks & sensitivities		
Less of suitable areas due to temperature change, drought, water availability	Temperature change, drought, water availability impact vegetation growth as well as suitability for agriculture	Temperature change, extreme weather, salinity
Economic implications		
High transition cost, long-term investment, increased and diversified income, potential carbon credits financing but not in current schemes	High investment cost, at current prices and benefits mostly commercially viable for large farms	Economic growth, job creation, and poverty alleviation
Co-benefits and synergies		
Resilience, food security, biodiversity, water quality, microclimate regulation, soil conservation	Improved soil quality and biodiversity, erosion control, reduced fertilizer needs and nitrate leaching, heat	Watershed and coastal protection
Trade-offs		
Potential yield loss requiring expansion	Potential nutrient deficiency	Ethnic minorities are often excluded and negatively impacted
Risks associated with scaling-up		
Different species and systems depending on focus: economic, carbon, environmental	Volume needed to improve soil, varying quality depending on source material and process, no market	Insufficient capacity for forest governance and management, Different species and systems depending on focus: economic, carbon, environmental
Knowledge Gaps		
Agronomy and economy of systems, characterization of different systems and their attributes	Limited information on SOC, biochar effect on soil quality, productivity, and carbon sequestration	Societal impacts (ethnic minorities)

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Annex I: Selected ASEAN countries' climate policies

Indonesia

NDC Targets
Unconditional: 31.89% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 (Enhanced NDC, 2022)
Conditional: 43.2% compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 - including emissions from LULUCF (Enhanced NDC, 2022)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Peak national GHG emissions at 1,244 million tonnes of CO ₂ e by 2030; Net-zero before 2060 (LTS 2021, NDC, 2022)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
Targets: emissions reduction of 140 Mt CO ₂ by 2030, and 304 Mt CO ₂ by 2050 (Enhanced NDC, 2022); Peatlands: targets under the low-carbon scenario - peatland improvement and water management of 0.95 Mha by 2030 and 1.04 Mha by 2050; Peatland restoration: 2.7 Mha by 2030 and 4.2 Mha by 2050 (LTS, 2021); Policies: FOLU Net Sink 2030 Policy → it constitutes 60% of emissions reduction targets; National Forestry Plan (RKTN); The LTS (2021) mentions integrated farming/complex agroforestry, forest restoration, peatland restoration, water-saving paddy cultivation system, utilization of livestock waste for biogas
Energy decarbonization
Target: 23% of renewables by 2025 (ASEAN Plan of Action on Energy Cooperation 2016-2025; RUPTL 2021-2030); Policies: Low-Carbon Development (LCD) policy (initiated); Global Coal to Clean Power Transition Statement (COP26); the new Electricity Business Plan (RUPTL) 2021-2030, New and Renewable Energy Bill (expected in 2023); Presidential regulation 112 (2022) sets a 2050 phase out date for unabated coal-fired power generation; The LTS (2021) mentions carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS)

Vietnam

NDC Targets
Unconditional: 15.8% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 (NDC, 2022)
Conditional: 43.5% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 (NDC, 2022)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Aim peaking GHG emissions by 2030 (latest 2035); Net-zero by 2050 (National Climate Change Strategy, 2022)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emission reduction from LULUCF sector by 90% in 2050 relative to the BAU; • Increase the forest cover to 42% by 2030 and maintaining a stable level to 2050; • Increase carbon sequestration by 30% relative to the BAU level. <p>In total, expectation of a 185 MtCO₂e sink (NDC, 2022; National Climate Change Strategy, 2022) The NDC (2022) mentions various land management practices, including the scaleup of agroforestry models to improve carbon stocks and conserve soil, alternating wet and dry irrigation and SRI, organic agriculture</p>
Energy decarbonization
Reduction of methane emissions by 30% from 2020 levels by 2030 – among others, through the development of biogas and use of agriculture by-products (NDC, 2022); Decarbonization: by 2050 all coal plants must be converted or cease operation Policies: Global Coal to Clean Power Transition Statement (COP26); the Just Energy Transition Partnership (joined 2022)

Thailand

NDC Targets
Unconditional: 30% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 (NDC, 2022)
Conditional: 40% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU scenarios by 2030 – excluding LULUCF (NDC, 2022)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Peak national GHG emissions in 2030 (at approximately 370 MtCO ₂ eq) (revised LTS, 2022); Carbon neutrality by 2050 (NDC 2022; revised LTS 2022); Net zero by 2065 (NDC 2022; revised LTS 2022)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
No separate target for LULUCF in the NDC (Note: LULUCF in Thailand is historically a carbon sink since 2000 (CAT, 2022); Targets from national policies: increase forest cover to achieve 55% of the total country area by 2037/reaching a level of LULUCF removals of 120 MtCO ₂ e from 2037 (The National Strategy, 2017-2036; revised LTS 2022); Relevant policies: the National Forest Policy; The National Strategy, 2017-2036; the Community Forest Act B.E. 2562 (2019); Climate Change Act and National Energy Plan (expected in 2023) NDC mentions enhancement of forest carbon stocks; revised LTS afforestation and reforestation, direct dry seeded rice
Energy decarbonization
Target: at least a 50% share of RE from new power plants by 2050 (revised LTS, 2022) Note: detailed decarbonization targets expected in the National Energy Plan (2023) (revised LTS, 2022); Other policies: The Climate Change Master Plan (2015-2050); The NDC and LTS mention the research development and deployment of advanced technologies such as carbon capture and storage (CCS), carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS), Bioenergy with CCS

Lao PDR

NDC Targets
Unconditional: 60% GHG emissions reduction compared to BAU by 2030, ca. 62,000 ktCO ₂ e (revised NDC, 2021) Conditional sectoral targets (revised NDC, 2021)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Net zero by 2050 (revised NDC, 2021)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forestry, unconditional: reduce LUCF emissions 1,100ktCO₂e/year between 2020-2030 (revised NDC, 2021) • Conditional: Increase of forest cover to 70% of land area (16.58 million hectares) (revised NDC, 2021) Agriculture: development of 50,000 hectares adjusted water management practices in lowland rice cultivation; Policies: National Forestry Strategy; World Bank and Green Climate Fund's projects (revised NDC, 2021)
Energy decarbonization
Mainly three sub-sectors: hydropower, energy efficiency and transport. The most relevant (unconditional) target is about hydropower: 13GW total hydropower capacity (domestic and export use) in the country (revised NDC, 2021).

The Philippines

NDC Targets
Mostly conditional: 75% GHG emissions reduction below a cumulative 2020-2030 BAU scenarios by 2030 – (NDC, 2021) Unconditional share: 2.71% of 75% (NDC, 2021)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Aspirational target to peak emissions by 2030 (NDC 2021); The country does not have a net zero target
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
High uncertainty on the actual national GHG emissions from LULUCF sector, now a 'shrinking net sink' (CAT, 2023); No separate target for LULUCF, and in general lack of key information in the NDC and its update
Energy decarbonization
Target: 35% renewable energy share in power generation by 2030, and 50% by 2040 (NREP, 2021) Energy sector plan to 2050 is being revised (2023); First country in SEA region to set a moratorium on new coal (2020) Relevant policies: The National Renewable Energy Program (NREP) 2020-2040

Cambodia

NDC Targets
Almost all conditional: -41.7% GHG by 2030 compared to BAU scenarios /64.6 million tCO ₂ e/year, incl. FOLU (NDC 2020)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Peak national GHG emissions projected in the early 2030s (LTS, 2021); Carbon neutrality by 2050 (with the FOLU sector providing a total carbon sink of 50 MtCO ₂ e (LTS, 2021)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
Target: 50% deforestation rate by 2030 (59.1% GHG reduction of the 41.7% conditional target FOLU sector (NDC, 2020); Note: the FOLU sector is expected to be carbon neutral from 2031 (LTS, 2021). Relevant policies: the National Strategic Development Plan (NSDP); the Cambodia Climate Change Strategic Plan 2014 – 2023; the National Environment Strategy and Action Plan 2016–2023 (NESAP); National REDD+ Strategy 2017-2026; Mention of direct seeding practices among key actions for agriculture in the LTS (2021)
Energy decarbonization
Targets: overall 40% GHG emissions reduction from energy by 2030 (NDC, 2020); The NDC mentions the improving sustainability of charcoal production through enforcement of regulations (2020) Policy: The Cambodia Basic Energy Plan (2019)

Malaysia

NDC Targets
Unconditional: 45% GHG emissions reduction compared to 2005 levels by 2030 – including LULUCF (NDC, 2021)
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
Net zero by 2050 (NDC, 2021)
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
Targets: to increase national protected area to at least 20% by 2025; to maintain at least 50% of the national land area as forest and tree cover; to stop all forest conversion for palm oil (3rd biennial update report to the UNFCCC, 2020); Policies: 12th Plan 2021-2025, Malaysia Forestry Policy (DPSM 2020); The Social Forestry Strategic Plan 2021-2025
Energy decarbonization
Target: RE of 31% and 40% by 2025 and 2035 in installed capacity (The Malaysia Renewable Energy Roadmap - MyRER) Policies: Peninsular Malaysia Generation Development Plan 2020 (2021-2039)

Annex II: LANDMARC LMT Glossary

- Agriculture
 - **Agroforestry:** Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land, in order to obtain ecological co-benefits and synergies
 - **Dry seeded rice – no till:** Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.
 - **Reduced tillage:** A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.
 - **Integrated soil fertility management:** Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.
 - **Organic agriculture:** An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.
- Forestry
 - **Afforestation/reforestation:** Afforestation: Establishing forest by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover. Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.
 - **Forest management:** Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.
 - **Forest fire management:** Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.
- **Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS):** Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.
- **Biochar:** organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.
- **Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost):** Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and bio-gas slurry as compost.
- **Peatland management:** Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.
- **Pasture management:** Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.

Annex III: List of Acronyms

AFOLU: Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use

AMS: ASEAN Member States

AP: Asia-Pacific

BAU: Business as usual

BECCS: Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage

CO₂e: CO₂ equivalent

GDP: Gross domestic product

GHG: Greenhouse gas

Gt: Gigatonnes

IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

LANDMARC: Land Use Based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

LMTs: Land-based Mitigation Technologies and practices

LTS: Long-Term Strategy

LUCF: Land Use Change and Forestry

LULUCF: Land Use, Land Use Change ,and Forestry

Mt: Megatonnes

NbS: Nature-based Solutions

NDCs: Nationally Determined Contributions

RCP: Representative Concentration Pathway

SSP: Shared Socio-economic Pathway

ANNEX C3: INCEPTION REPORT FOR EUROPE

Preface

LANDMARC

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date, most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking also at negative emission solutions. Among them, we find **Land-based Mitigation Technologies** and practices (referred in this project as LMTs) such as: afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, agriculture, biochar, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), grassland and wetland management. However, many LMTs, their impacts and their implementation needs, are still insufficiently understood.

The four-year LANDMARC project is filling this knowledge gap by employing a triangular research approach, encompassing both technical and social aspects: the use of satellite data and soil sampling is combined with climate, land-use, and economic scenario modelling, and stakeholder engagement. This global effort carried out by 19 partners and spread over 16 national case studies aims to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors.
- Assess the regional and global upscaling potential of negative emission solutions.
- Map potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs.

Regional Stakeholder Workshops

Between October and November 2023, SEI will host regional stakeholder workshops in its four regional centres: Bogotá, Nairobi, Bangkok, and Stockholm. The participation of regional expertise in these workshops will enhance our comprehension of scaling Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) by making scenario and modelling assumptions more realistic, resulting in improved recommendations for policymakers and decision makers.

The Stockholm Environment Institute

The Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) is an international non-profit research and policy organization dedicated to addressing environmental and development challenges. SEI's work spans climate, water, air, land-use issues, governance, economy, and gender. Central to our mission is active stakeholder engagement, which lies at the core of our efforts to build capacity, strengthen institutions and empower partners for long-term change.

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1. Introduction and overview of workshop objectives

In this document we present a description of the status of land-based mitigation technologies in the EU region¹ and an overview of the project results for the European national case studies. The project national case studies in Europe include Germany, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland. Ukraine² is also considered in the workshop. Across this workshop, focus will be directed to the European region.

This regional workshop on land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) brings together a diverse group of stakeholders with varying backgrounds and areas of expertise. Its primary focus is to review and assess land-based mitigation options within the region¹, emphasizing three key dimensions:

- I. Identifying and characterising a regional portfolio of land-based mitigation options.
- II. Evaluating how the ambition level for land-based mitigation can be raised in the region.
- III. Providing recommendations for enhancing regional engagement (as well as fostering regional and transnational cooperation) to support these heightened ambitions.

The workshop incorporates a range of inputs, including various research results, syntheses and stakeholder engagements that have been carried out at local, national or regional levels. These inputs can be divided into three main types:

- 1) **National case studies:** in these studies, detailed analyses and stakeholder consultations were conducted for different LMTs. The outcomes include an “LMT portfolio” and LMT scaling scenarios that characterise the most promising LMTs. These outcomes also evaluate their expected impacts and interactions, particularly in terms of *how* they could be scaled up to achieve NDCs and/or other climate and development goals.
- 2) **Regional outlooks:** these are based on reviews of key policies and mechanisms at the regional level, along with regional perspectives gathered through stakeholder interviews and consultations.

¹ In the context of LANDMARC, we define a ‘region’ as a collection of countries within a specific geographical area of interest. For instance, the ‘European region’ comprises countries located in Europe. Within the European region, we further identify two distinct sub-regions: ‘North Europe’ and ‘South Europe’.

² Outside the scope of the LANDMARC project, a small research project has been set up between Ukrainian (Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research, and Adverio Engineering UA) and Dutch (JIN Climate & Sustainability and Adverio Engineering NL) partners to assess different development scenarios for biogas development and deployment in Ukraine, post-war. The small project, titled: “*Post-war recovery and energy independence strategy through biogas deployment in Ukrainian agriculture*” is funded via a small grant from the TPM (Technology, Policy, and Management) faculty, Energy Transitions Lab from TU Delft.

- 3) **Land-vegetation-carbon modelling:** this modelling is conducted at national, regional and global levels, all based on ‘Shared Socio-economic Pathway 2’ (SSP2)³. SSP2 is considered the “middle-of-the-road” pathway among the five SSPs used as reference points within the Integrated Assessment Modelling Community and as the basis for IPCC Assessments. Three scenarios are utilised to project the implementation until the year 2100, each based on a particular set of LMTs. Each scenario is related to the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) adopted in IPCC assessments and correspond to different greenhouse gas concentration in the year 2100. The scenarios are as follows:
- i. Baseline: utilises an RCP of 4.5 W/m², which is expected, under most scenarios, to be associated with average temperature increases of approximately 3 °C.
 - ii. Moderate ambition: utilises an RCP of 2.6 W/m², which is expected, under most scenarios, to be associated with average temperature increases of approximately 2 °C.
 - iii. High ambition: utilises an RCP of 1.9 W/m², which is expected, under most scenarios, to be associated with average temperature increases of approximately 1.5 °C.

The **Land-vegetation-carbon modelling** previously described is constrained to the number of LMTs that can be evaluated, thus five specific ones have been chosen:

1. **Afforestation and forest management** (which includes reforestation and forest management)
2. **Agroforestry** (involving the planting of trees within agricultural areas, with specific characteristics)
3. **Biochar** (sourced from land availability as calculated and used as a soil amendment)
4. **Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)**
5. **No tillage** (involving little or no tillage in agricultural areas)

While these five LMTs are subject to modelling, it is important to note that other LMTs of national or regional significance will also be discussed during the workshop, even though they may not have undergone modelling.

In the workshop, there will be introductory presentations to the three types of input described above. Following these presentations, workshop participants will engage in discussion, evaluations, and prioritisation of LMTs, ambition levels, and regional engagement options.

The expected outcome of the workshop collaborative efforts is a series of narratives that capture the key elements of LMT prioritisation, ambition and regional engagement.

³ For more details about the Shared Socio Economic Pathway and SSP2 please refer to (O’Neill *et al.*, 2017) [[link](#)]

1.1 Project Terminology

This section provides a summary of the frequently used acronyms and units in this background document and during the workshop. Additionally, we have included a quick-reference glossary to the Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) mentioned in this document as a complementary resource, which can be found in Annex I.

Acronyms

BECCS	Bio-energy carbon capture and storage
GHG	Greenhouse gases
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LMT	Land-based mitigation technology
LST	Long-term strategies
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SSP2	Shared Socio-economic Pathway 2

Units

°C	Degrees centigrade
W	Watts

2. Climate mitigation goals and policies

2.1 EU

The latest IPCC reports warn that there is essentially a decade left to reverse a climate catastrophe. Nonetheless, the enhancement of climate pledges and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) has been limited in recent years (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2022; UNDP, 2022). If all targets from the current 2030 NDCs and Long-term strategies (LTS) are met, the best-estimate of warming will be around 1.9 °C, just below 2 °C (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2022).

Within the European continent, the European Union (EU) has taken the lead in championing ambitious emission reduction and climate action across its Member States. In its latest NDC update, the EU sets a goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, relative to 1990. Furthermore, the EU has advocates in international negotiations for the limitation of global average temperature increase to 2°C above pre-industrial levels, with the aim of halving global GHG emissions from 1990 levels by 2050 (Rayner *et al.*, 2023).

The European Union stands apart from other regions studied in the LANDMARC project due to its unique position as a union of nations operating under a common institutional framework. This positions the EU as a global example and pace-setter in climate action. Functioning as a ‘policy laboratory’, the EU has proposed innovative policies and institutional innovations across various sectors, including climate change mitigation. Effort sharing policies, allowing Member States to distribute emissions reduction targets across different economic sectors are a hallmark of this approach (Rayner *et al.*, 2023).

While EU climate policy advocates coordinated actions to combat climate change, challenges may arise during the adaptation of Union policy into Member State actions, potentially leading to implementation gaps and unmet targets. Therefore, effective coordination is crucial. Regulations have been proposed to ensure the attainment of climate goals, such as the European Climate Law, legally binds the EU to achieve net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 and a 55% net reduction by 2030. Complementary to this, the concept of effort sharing, and flexible mechanisms aim to enhance cost-efficiency, solidarity among Member States, and overall flexibility (Rayner *et al.*, 2023). The Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) plays a key role in balancing emissions across sectors, including the Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) sector, by measuring both CO₂ removals and emissions.

In addition to regulations, the EU utilizes the Emission Trading System (ETS) to enabling the conditions for a carbon emissions market, empowering Member States to establish the necessary regulatory frameworks for its operation. Likewise, there has been on going discussions on the proposal for a regulation on carbon removal certification framework (CRCF), including definition setting for permanent storage, carbon farming and carbon storage in products (European Commission, 2022; European Parliament, 2023).

This multifaceted approach demonstrates the EU's commitment to tackling climate change, as summarized in Table 1 , which provides an overview of the primary policies and targets within the EU.

Table 1. Summary of main climate targets and policies in the EU

NDC Targets
<p>Unconditional: At least 55% domestic reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 1990 (European Union, 2020). <u>Geographical scope:</u> EU and its Member States (Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Estonia, Ireland, Greece, Spain, France, Croatia, Italy, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Hungary, Malta, Netherlands, Austria, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Finland, Sweden) (European Union, 2020).</p> <p>Conditional: Not applicable for developed economies such as the EU (WWF, 2021)</p>
Carbon neutrality and net-zero
<p>Objective of achieving a climate neutral EU by 2050 (European Union, 2020).</p>
Land-based mitigation targets and policies
<p>Targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The carbon neutrality target included in most recent NDC update (2020) includes for the first time the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector. • Increase EU carbon sinks levels in LULUCF to above 310 Mt CO_{2eq} by 2030 • No debit rule: LULUCF emissions may not exceed removals (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023). • Under the LULUCF regulation and Effort sharing regulation and between 2021 to 2030, EU MS may use up to 280 Mt CO_{2eq} net removals from land use categories excluding forest management (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023). • From 2026 removals within the LULUCF sector should exceed emissions. By 2030, each MS will have to deliver results on a natural amount of removals. <p>Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fit-for-55 • EU climate policy framework for 2030 (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023) • Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023) • EU common agricultural policy (CAP) • Land use, land use change and forestry Regulation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Includes binding commitment for each Member State to ensure land use accounted emissions are at minimum compensated by an equivalent removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023). ○ MS access to the up to 280 Mt CO_{2eq} net removals requires previously meeting emissions reduction goals in the LULUCF sector. ○ LULUCF must be compliant with net removals results (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023)
Energy decarbonization
<p>Target:</p> <p>To 2030: At least 32% share for renewable energy, at least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency and for the energy sector at least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels) (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023)</p> <p>Policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2030 climate and energy framework • Renewable Energy Directive (RED) • Energy efficiency Directive (EED) • Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) (Rayner <i>et al.</i>, 2023)

2.1.1 Case study countries

The objective of this section is to give a brief overview of the different European case study countries considered LANDMARC. For this purpose, figures of emissions per country and land use are introduced,

The European focus of the LANDMARC project has been developed for specific case studies. The project national case studies in Europe include Germany, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland. A more recent addition to the project was the case study of Ukraine.

Greenhouse gas emissions for the case study countries are presented in Figure 1, categorized by sectors. On a European Union scale, energy-related emissions dominate, constituting the largest portion. Agricultural emissions also contribute significantly to the overall emissions landscape, while industrial and waste-related emissions remain comparatively smaller.

Notably, for the LANDMARC project's objectives concerning land use and emissions reduction, the EU takes into account emissions reductions achieved through Land Use Change and Forestry (LUCF). The assessment at the EU level reveals the presence of negative emissions, underscoring the net removal of greenhouse gases. This trend is also observed within specific case study countries such as Germany, Spain, and Sweden, where they report negative emissions originating from the LUCF sector. Emissions GHG emission removal from the LUCF sector in Sweden shows a removal comparable to the sum of emissions coming from industrial processes, agriculture and waste. Detailed figures depicting the emission distribution are presented in Table 3.

Figure 1. Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) per sector as of 2019 of the EU (left) and European LANDMARC studies (right) (EU countries: Germany, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden; Non-EU: Switzerland and Ukraine). Source: (Climate Watch, 2023)

Table 2. Percentage share of GHG emissions per sector of the EU and the European LANDMARC case studies. Source: (Climate Watch, 2023) – Note: Negative emissions are represented with a minus sign.

	EU	Germany	Netherlands	Portugal	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Ukraine
Energy	85%	89%	83%	70%	80%	100%	82%	77%
Industrial Processes	5%	3%	2%	8%	6%	6%	8%	4%
Agriculture	12%	8%	10%	12%	14%	22%	12%	14%
Waste	3%	1%	2%	10%	4%	3%	2%	6%
Land-Use Change and Forestry	-5%	-2%	4%	0%	-5%	-32%	-4%	-1%
Total including LUCF	3236.19	740.09	178.86	61.83	295.48	35.44	44.75	233.09
(Mt CO_{2eq})								
Share of global GHG emissions	6.5%	1.5%	0.4%	0.1%	0.6%	0.1%	0.1%	0.5%

With the purpose of establishing a common ground for the changes in the land sectors in the European Union and the LANDMARC case studies presented in this report, a comparative summary of the land use in 20 years is presented in Figure 2. Further comparison in the changes in land use is introduced in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Comparative of land use for forestry and agriculture in a 20 year period (2000 and 2021) – Units: thousand hectares (1000 ha) Source: (FAOSTAT, 2023)

Figure 3. Percentage change of land use between the years 2000 and 2021, per change type. (Note: Area increases in land use type displayed in blue, decreases in orange. Darker shadings represent larger changes)**

Climate change is expected to have a widespread impact on various land systems and to alter the application and effectiveness of land-based mitigation measures (LMTs) that aim to reduce emissions from the land sectors. Disturbances in temperatures and rain patterns could heavily affect afforestation efforts, especially in the early phases, growth patterns of grasses and legumes, or yields of more sensitive crops such as coffee. This could compromise carbon stocks provided by these systems, as well as their general productivity (LANDMARC, 2023).

3. LANDMARC Overview of potentials

Due to the vast land area along with the physical and socio-economic diversity of the Asia-Pacific Region, it was not feasible to conduct a complete regional study, nor are workshop participants expected to consider all of these countries. However, the case study in Nepal provided some insights on South Asia, as well as capturing the nature of countries with both mountainous areas and key agricultural crops. We also conducted an analysis on China because of its outsized importance in the region in economic and technical terms as well as its considerable land area and population. A brief summary is provided below of the overall regional context, the insights gained from regional interview, and the key information obtained in our national case studies as well as our analysis on LMT-related policies in China.

3.1 Potential of LMTs in Europe

On a global level, Europe holds significant potential to contribute to emission mitigation through the utilization of land-based technologies. An assessment of the mitigation potential of the most common global LMTs from the LANDMARC technology portfolio suggests that Europe could mitigate between 3,5 to 3,8 Gt CO_{2eq} per year (Karki *et al.*, 2023). Figure 4 illustrates a comparison of the LMT mitigation potentials across continents, mapped as a preliminary result of the LANDMARC project.

Figure 4. Mitigation potential of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) in different regions. Source: (Karki *et al.*, 2023).

In the context of climate change mitigation, Europe stands out with significant potential in afforestation and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), with agroforestry, forest management, and biochar following closely behind. It's worth noting that in Europe, BECCS holds one of the most substantial potentials for emissions reduction when compared to other regions. However, it's essential to acknowledge that various factors come into play beyond potential estimates. For

instance, the long-term permanence of carbon removal differs between standing biomass in forests, carbon sequestration in soils, and geological storage (Karki *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, these preliminary estimates are subject to a broader analysis of the potential under the political, technical and economic context of the respective countries of implementation.

3.2 Regional perspective from stakeholder interviews

A series of semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather individual stakeholders' perspectives on the role and potential of enhanced regional integration and cooperation for the scaling up of LMTs. Below are some highlights of insights shared by stakeholders.

In the European context, LMTs of preference can be subject to variability according to the geographical location. LMTs used in the North of Europe might differ from those used in the South of Europe. However, there is recognition of the technologies across the Europe. The LMT (Land-based Mitigation Technologies) portfolio in the European region is diverse and dynamic, with various countries pursuing specific strategies tailored to their resources and priorities.

Barriers:

- Complex and time-consuming permission processes for projects for new technology implementation hinder progress.
- Access to finance for sustainable practices can be challenging due to the scale requirements and technical specifications for funding eligibility. Changes in production systems can necessitate the development of supportive value chains, posing challenges for farmers. Long-term investments may not yield immediate revenue, and there's a potential for increased labour-intensity. Inadequate financial incentives discourage landowners from adopting new land management practices.
- Unsettled markets for products derived from LMTs create uncertainty, making it difficult to establish reliable income streams. This was the case for products from rewetted soils and biochar.
- Disparities exist between European and national policies, affecting the adoption of practices such as agroforestry. While European policies favour agroforestry, member states enact regulations to varying extents, with some choosing not to embrace such measures. Translating research into policy can be complex,
- Government support is crucial, particularly regarding carbon credit purchasing and regulations for voluntary carbon markets.
- Competition within biomass utilization as well as land limitations.
- It was frequently mentioned that scaling up of LMTs is restricted high operational costs, and limited availability of agricultural arable land in certain regions.
- Reduced crop yield was frequently mentioned as a trade-offs of regenerative farming practices. In addition, concerns have been raised about the use of herbicide use in reduced tillage practices.

Enablers:

- Creating local value chains is crucial for promoting sustainable products and supporting local economies, both for small scale and large-scale implementation of LMTs.
- Carbon credits were mentioned as an alternative to offer financial support for rewetting projects, encouraging climate protection. Developing a certification system that rewards activities rather than carbon storage was presented as an alternative to enhance carbon credit trading.
- Governments and regulatory bodies can play a crucial role by providing advice, incentives, and regulations that promote the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies. Support through governmental measures, such as agri-environmental and climate measures, could provide funding to make LMTs implementation widespread.
- Collaboration between regions and countries in Europe can facilitate knowledge sharing, research, and the exchange of best practices, promoting the adoption of sustainable land management techniques.
- Peer-to-peer learning, educational programs, and partnerships with farmers can enhance the dissemination of knowledge and best practices in the agricultural sector.
- Implementing eco-tourism can generate income and raise awareness about ecosystems including wetlands, forests and Dehesas.

Opportunities:

- Encouraging dialogue and cooperation at various levels can facilitate knowledge sharing and support for LMTs.
- The spread of sustainable practices relies on pioneers and knowledge transfer between farmers. Farmers can adopt practices that suit their region, serving as success stories for others. Collaborative efforts involving farmers, policymakers, and farm advisors can bridge the gap between policy and practice.
- Focusing on landscapes and infrastructure rather than individual countries can enhance the dissemination of practices across borders, especially when regions share common characteristics.
- Support from governmental measures at various levels can help finance land conversion and LMT projects.
- Collaborating with companies with global reach can encourage the adoption of sustainable practices. These companies can create labels for regenerative agriculture, incentivizing farmers to adopt these practices.
- Trustworthy carbon credit markets can be created with the integration of IT systems for tracking carbon removals can enhance trading.
- Standardization and regulation are necessary to create reliable markets and control green claims. The inclusion of sustainability requirements in trade agreements ensures a level playing field and promotes the use of land-based mitigation technologies.
- In many farming environments, older generations, who tend to be more conservative, make decisions while younger generations work the land. Transferring decision-making power to younger generations could enhance the adoption of innovative techniques.

- Northern Europe lacks the widespread knowledge and practice of agroforestry compared to regions like southern Europe, where it is more common and widely adopted.

3.3 Brief national profiles - National Case Studies

Together with stakeholders, LANDMARC case study partners determined relevant land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) for each case study country and collected information to assess their realistic scaling potential at the national level. An initial scoping of key LMTs resulted in a comprehensive list of different LMTs that could be viable within the various case study countries. Then, case study partners proposed a shortlist for each country, and validated their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews, surveys, meetings, workshops, and discussions. Finally, they developed national scaling narratives for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessment focuses on climate risks, vulnerabilities, socio-economic co-benefits, and trade-offs associated with scaling up LMTs to the national level in the case study countries. Table 3 presents a summary of the LMTs included in the national cases studies overseen by the project partners.

Table 3. LMTs corresponding to each national case study. (* denotes a LMT included in Land-vegetation-carbon modelling) – Adapted from (LANDMARC, 2023)

	Germany	Netherlands	Portugal	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Ukraine
Afforestation*	X	X		X	X		
BECCS*		X			X		
Biochar*					X		
Agroforestry*		X	X			X	X
Reduced/no tillage*						X	X
Forest management	X		X	X	X		
Soil carbon	X						
Peatland rewetting		X					
Organic agriculture						X	X
Cropland management			X				
Grassland management			X	X			
Agrosilvopastoral land				X			
Bioenergy							X

In the following sections, summaries of the status of the LMTs per case study country is presented. The information presented is collected from the previous analysis and stakeholder engagements, led by the LANDMARC project partners. In this sense, this information sums up research and analysis reported by the consortium partners (LANDMARC, 2023).

3.3.1 Germany

The German LMT portfolio includes i) forest management, ii) afforestation, iii) soil carbon enhancement. In densely populated Germany, land scarcity presents a significant challenge, particularly for agricultural land, which spans 19.7 million hectares. The pressure to convert or manage these lands differently is compounded by the importance of cattle farming and the production of meat and dairy products in sustaining the national agricultural sector.

In 2018, Germany's land use sector acted as a net carbon sink, absorbing approximately -30 million metric tons (Mt) of CO_{2eq}. Forests played a crucial role in capturing substantial amounts of CO₂ (-67 Mt CO_{2eq}) from the atmosphere and storing carbon in wood products (-3 Mt CO_{2eq}). The forest ecosystem, including above- and below-ground biomass, was responsible for significant CO₂ sequestration (-50 Mt CO_{2eq}), while carbon was also sequestered in the mineral forest soil (-16 Mt CO_{2eq}). In contrast, emissions were reported from arable land (16 Mt CO_{2eq}), grassland (15 Mt CO_{2eq}), settlements (6 Mt CO_{2eq}) and wetlands (4 Mt CO_{2eq}) (UBA, 2020).

Forestry takes precedence as a key LMT in Germany. Forest management plays a pivotal role in CO₂ uptake by trees and enhances carbon stocks in living and decaying biomass and the soil. Forest land management practices vary significantly across ownership classes, with approximately 50 % of forests being privately owned, often with smaller areas (less than 20 hectares). State ownership accounts for 29%, the Federal government 4%, and communities 19% of the forested lands (BMEL, 2016).

Assessing the potential for afforestation potentials is notably challenging in a densely populated country like Germany with intense land use competition. Expanding forests holds promise for CO₂ sequestration and long-term storage, but it raises potential conflicts with nature conservation interests concerning diverse grasslands and sparsely vegetated heathlands. In 2018, approximately 17,000 hectares of new forest area were added, primarily through the conversion of grassland (UBA, 2020). However, during the same year 6,890 hectares of forest land in Germany were transformed into settlement areas, resulting in emissions of approximately 1.7 Mt CO_{2eq} (UBA, 2020).

Furthermore, organic carbon (Corg) is stored in soils in the form of dead soil organic matter (humus), such as plant residues, animal excreta and their microbially transformed components. The protection of organic soils can prevent emissions from land use while providing ecosystemic benefits.

Recent developments, such as the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine, have affected Germany's energy supply, leading to an increased demand for alternative energy sources including wood. This underscores the evolving nature of Germany's strategies for climate change mitigation.

Forest management	Afforestation	Soil carbon enhancement
Policy context		
Subject to Renewable energy directive. Debate on renewable status of primary wood biomass consumption	Currently not high on political agenda due to anticipated agricultural land demand	According to the BBodSchG (Law for protection against harmful soil changes and for the remediation of contaminated sites) it is part of good professional practice to ensure the

Forest management	Afforestation	Soil carbon enhancement
		long-term preservation of the site-typical humus content
Land use competition		
The measures to promote carbon sinks in the forest can be implemented on the existing forest area.	Afforestation potentials is very difficult to assess in a densely populated country like Germany with high land use competition. Expansion of agricultural land.	Competition for arable land, especially for animal feed, field crops and intensive pasture
Climate risks & sensitivities		
Heat waves, droughts, fires, strong winds and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.	Heat waves, droughts, fires, strong winds and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.	Droughts, fires, heat, cold waves, frosts, mild winters and landslides
Economic implications		
Intensity of forest management is determined by the economic interest of the forest owner and the market demands. Increase in demand for work products beyond the domestic forest might decrease the forest sink capacity.	Needs for financial investment. Negative relocation processes may occur abroad if some agricultural goods, such as meat and dairy products, can no longer be produced in Germany	
Co-benefits and synergies		
Wood products can contribute to reduce emissions in other sectors by substituting products with a worse climate balance	Afforestation areas can also make a positive contribution to the protection of biodiversity due to their succession stages to forest stand.	Influences humus content through factors such as tillage, crop rotation, and fertilization. Contribute to the resilience of arable soils to the impacts of climate change
Trade-offs		
Reduction of timber harvest to increase CO ₂ fixation.	Conflicts for species protection arise where species-rich grassland is converted into forest	Excess of organic fertiliser, as this can upset the nutrient balance of the soil and lead to N ₂ O emissions
Risks associated with scaling up		
Tree species selection and forest resilience are directly related to the success of the climate change mitigation measure of building carbon stocks in forests	Use of industrialized means might harm soil and nutrients; risks associated to the hydrologic balance according to tree species needs	Nitrogen, heavy metals, hormones and microplastics can enter the groundwater if compost or biogas waste is used for fertilisation in addition to manure.
Knowledge gaps		
The effects on the sink capacity of the forest have not yet been estimated.	Estimates on the loss of the carbon sink in the forest	Suitable pollutant-free initial substrate, profitability, and overall ecological assessment.

3.3.2 Netherlands

The Dutch LMT portfolio includes i) afforestation, ii) agroforestry, iii) peatland rewetting, and iv) CO₂ capture applied to biogas production facilities based on anaerobic digestion of liquid animal manure.

The Netherlands possesses a total forest cover of about 10% of its surface area, approximately 340,000 hectares, with over 55% of these forests (larger than 5 hectares) being owned by public organizations. Forests serve as a vital carbon sink for the country. However, deforestation has occurred due to restoration initiatives converting forested areas into more open nature landscapes. To increase the forest cover, the Netherlands must focus on afforestation and agroforestry practices, including silvopastoral system, silvoarable systems, windbreaks and food forests.

Within the Netherlands, approximately 274,000 hectares of organic soils are peat(y) soils, with about 207,000 hectares used for agriculture. The drainage of peat(y) soils contributes to 3- 4% of the national GHG emissions as the peat dries out and oxidizes, causing subsidence. Rewetting these peat(y) soils can help limit subsidence and retain soil carbon, although it comes with challenges related to water availability and business models. Several pilot projects are currently testing this solution.

The Netherlands is rich in domestically produced animal manure, with 5-10% of the annual total treated. The biogas produced from this manure can serve as a bioenergy source. This case study in the Netherlands focuses on BECCS wherein bioenergy is produced from biogas and the resulting gases are captured and stored or utilized. This approach offers advantages in reducing fossil fuel consumption and emissions removal, potentially contributing to the country's climate change mitigation efforts.

Agroforestry	Afforestation	Peatland rewetting	BECCS (manure AD-based CCS)
Policy context			
Not yet included in national policy. Its inclusion could be a potential transition to a more circular and nature-inclusive agriculture	National Forest Strategy with emphasis on the sequestration of CO ₂ , revitalization of forests and reinforcing biodiversity.	Included in the political agenda. In the Climate Agreement it is anticipated that measures for managing peat meadow areas will deliver 1 Mt CO _{2eq.} of emission reductions by 2030	CCS separated from Bioenergy in national law. Both are included. This application (AD) needs livestock sector policy context
Land use competition			
Requiring agricultural lands to partly integrate tree structures and/or by the land-use change to grasslands.	Pressure on land for new houses and transport infrastructure is high.	In the case of the peat meadow areas, however, current agricultural land use is competed by societal demands for increasing the groundwater level to reduce soil subsidence	Significant land-use change is not expected as in this case study the energy comes from existing animal manure
Climate risks & sensitivities			
Rising sea levels, subsidence, droughts, precipitation and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.	Drought, storm damage, extreme temperatures and intense rainfall and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.	Increasing levels of annual rainfall and prolonged periods of (extreme) drought	Biomass supply variability due to: Extreme temperatures, radiation, droughts, livestock diseases.
Economic implications			
Public funding available. Not economically viable based on regular income. Need of subsidies for farmers implementing it. Support of tax schemes. Monetization of ecosystem services.	Economic benefits of forest per ha land are relatively low compared with benefits from other land uses. Public budget available for increase in trees. Yet insecure if these funds will be sufficient.	A business model derived from ecosystem services could be promising if the long term and sufficient payments for these services could be guaranteed	Business model needed for anaerobic digestion, digestate and CCS
Co-benefits and synergies			
Support farmers to lower risk of total income loss in case of natural disturbances to agriculture. Ecosystem services Social benefits	Carbon sequestration, offer room for biodiversity, produce wood, and provide recreation opportunities	If increased groundwater levels in the peat meadow areas, farmers have broadly three options: to adapt their management practices, to stop their farming activities, to move their business to	Address problem of manure surplus. Mineral fertiliser substitution

Agroforestry	Afforestation	Peatland rewetting	BECCS (manure AD-based CCS)
		another area. It turns into a mix of wet grasslands and areas with wet cultivation, nature and water	
Trade-offs			
Lower harvesting efficiency; incompatibility of trees with agricultural practices. Reduction of area for crops.	Land used for forestry excludes its use for other functions (e.g., food production)	If continuing soil subsidence, farmers benefit and society suffers. When groundwater levels are increased to stop soil subsidence, the opposite applies: farmers suffer and society benefits.	Surplus of manure and cost of manure digestion. Needs to be executed in large scale. Nitrogen leaching
Risks associated with scaling up			
Not included in policy yet. Uncertain scalability without financial support for carbon sequestration and ecosystem services.	Increase in forests, decrease in agricultural production due to less agricultural land: negative consequences for the global food supply	Implementation of viable business models; soil area limitations; limited financial support; drop in agricultural production and abandonment of land	Supply of large-scale sustainable biomass Scale down of fattening farms impacts manure supply
Knowledge gaps			
Pathways for incentivizing the of agroforestry (in an EU level)	Doubts can be raised on the business model of agroforestry. The National Forest Strategy put in the years up to 2025 efforts in knowledge development, design of financial and fiscal instruments and support for pilot projects and agroforestry initiatives		Farmers' lack of knowledge about manure anaerobic digestion, costs and carbon capture.

3.3.3 Portugal

The Portuguese LMT portfolio includes i) forest management, ii) agroforestry (Montados), iii) pastures (Montados) and iv) cropland management.

Portugal aims to reduce emissions by -45% to -55% by 2030, -55% to -65% by 2040, and a substantial -85% to -90% by 2050, in comparison to the 2005 levels. To reach these goals, all sectors must contribute by either decreasing emissions or enhancing their carbon sink capacity.

Forests cover about 35% of Portugal's area and consist of four main types: planted forests for wood production, agroforestry Montados (featuring cork oak, holm oak and stone pine), forests of natural regeneration, and intensive forestry areas. These forests serve commercial purposes, such as pulp, timber and fruit extraction. Since 1990, Portuguese forests have maintained a consistent carbon sink, with annual values ranging from -6.1 Mt CO_{2eq} to -15.4 Mt CO_{2eq}. Changes in land use within these forests stem from conversions between forest types and shifts in dominant species in mixed forests. Effective fire management can further enhance sequestration levels.

Portugal's agroforestry system, also known as a '*Montado*', is characterised by complex interactions between climate, soil, pasture, trees and animals. This practise exemplifies the integration of traditional land-use methods and biodiversity conservation. Incorporating pastures within Montados aims at bolster soil organic matter. Challenges to forests include seasonal fires. However, the persistent threat of seasonal fires remains a challenge for the sustainability of these ecosystems.

Forest management and other land uses	Pastures - Grassland management	Cropland management
Policy context		
Existing policy: Forest Policy Act and National Forest Strategy	No specific mention in political agenda. Acknowledged potential on grasslands for supporting the carbon neutrality goals of the country.	Part of the political agenda of agricultural practices, environmental production, climate change mitigation and desertification decrease.
Land use competition		
Agriculture. Land is threatened by fires.	Competition between cropland and permanent grasslands. Grassland growth has made use of former croplands.	Duality between cropland and land for rising livestock
Climate risks & sensitivities		
Extreme temperatures, fires, droughts, pests, weeds.	Climatic conditions affect grassland productivity. Extreme weather events heat waves, hailstorms or dry spells can compromise the production	Rise in sea level, extreme weather conditions, droughts that impede crop irrigation
Economic implications		
Challenges on forest ownership structure.	Can reduce costs if used in mixed soils. Expected to reduce use of fertilizers and reduce production costs of concentrated feed. Economic aids are not sufficient to promote grasslands	Currently there is income support to producers subject to agricultural practices choice. Government support needed to ensure environmental, climate and management commitments. Potential increase in agricultural production thanks to precision agriculture can lead to increase in trade.
Co-benefits and synergies		
Increase in active afforestation, promotion of more efficient forestry and risk management practices. Productivity gains may arise from better forest management practices and less fire losses.	Cheap and good quality feed for ruminants. Cost decrease in animal feeding. Increased livestock health	Irrigated systems can benefit from precision agriculture practices. Provide ecosystem benefits: lower agricultural pollution and reduce water consumption.
Trade-offs		
Forest expansion may be limited	Lack of definition of national strategies to encourage the use of more productive, more resilient and persistent species and mixtures	Warming reduces crop cycle times and productivity while increasing CO ₂ increases photosynthesis rate.
Risks associated with scaling up		
Rural depopulation	Selection of grass, decrease in arable crop areas, increase of livestock in grasslands	Access to water is a constraint. Use of precision agriculture may be limited to areas where it is possible to use remote sensing tools.
Knowledge gaps		
	Studies on benefits of meadows and forage production as a guarantee of	

Forest management and other land uses	Pastures - Grassland management	Cropland management
	cheaper, higher quality and more sustainable animal productions. Experimentation needed to determine suitable varieties and mixtures	

3.3.4 Spain

The Spanish LMT portfolio includes i) forest management, ii) afforestation / reforestation of degraded agricultural areas, iii) grassland management, iv) agrosilvopastoral land management (Dehesas).

Agriculture, livestock, fishing, and aquaculture play pivotal roles in Spain's economy holding significant social, territorial, and environmental importance. The food sector stands as one of the country's leading industry. Spain's agricultural and livestock activities occupy around 25 million hectares, which represent half of the nation's total land area.

Forests serve as Spain's primary and stable carbon sink, concurrently preserving biodiversity on the Iberian Peninsula. Given the diverse forest landscapes and heightened vulnerability to climate change-induced risks, including extreme weather events, drought, desertification and wildfires, forest management has a critical role. Spain has initiated efforts to convert unproductive and degraded agricultural lands into grasslands or forests, promoting sustainable land use practices.

A unique feature in Spain is the Dehesas (similar to the portuguese montado), covering about 57% of the agricultural area (about 1.4 million hectares). This agroforestry approach, rooted in ancient traditions, fosters coexistence of grass, trees and often shrubs. The Dehesas feature a complex interplay of climate, soil, pasture, trees, and livestock, offering adaptable and resourceful landscapes. Grassland management is closely connected to Dehesas, as these grasslands flourish beneath the tree canopy, serving as feeding grounds for livestock.

Forest management	Afforestation	Grassland management	Agroforestry (Dehesas)
Policy context			
Considered in planning instruments such as Spanish Forest Strategy, the Spanish Forest Plan, the Forest Resources Management Plans, or the Spanish Strategy for the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Forest Resources	Policy actions in the Spanish Agricultural Lands Afforestation program, system for payments to maintaining plantation of trees.	Lack of political support although Increase of carbon content in soil is identified as one line of work in the Spanish Long Term Decarbonization Strategy 2050.	Disconnection policy-farmlands. Policies geared towards ecological conservation, not incentivising the use of traditional practices in the farmland.
Land use competition			
Forest regeneration in abandoned agricultural and farming lands. Productive and	Unlikely to have competition. Abandoned agricultural lands have potential to be reforested.	Migration to urban centres lead to abandonment of agricultural territories has a negative effect in the maintenance of grasslands.	Migration to urban centres lead to abandonment of agricultural territories, directing to uncontrolled extension of forest with

Forest management	Afforestation	Grassland management	Agroforestry (Dehesas)
unproductive forestry has increased.	One competition could be with area for renewable energy projects (photovoltaic for example)	Using grasslands and pastures for carbon sequestration would not encounter any conflict with other land uses, especially in isolated areas of the country	concentration of fire hazards. Expansion of dehesa management as a LMT would not necessarily mean the geographical expansion of dehesa system themselves but will need to be controlled.
Climate risks & sensitivities			
Shifting temperatures and rainfall patterns increase mortality of tree species. Forest fires are the main cause of forest loss in the Mediterranean. Erosion is also a climate risk.	Drought, heat waves, fires.	Extreme temperatures, extended drought periods and cold waves.	Drought, extreme temperatures, biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.
Economic implications			
Rentability is hard to assess due to long timescales of forests growth. An alternative to quantify could be carbon capture monetization.	Most reforestation has been executed thanks to subsidies from government/regional administration.	High capital costs to establish one hectare of grassland and long payback periods. Aids are not sufficient to promote production and forage of grass crops	Costly materials and technologies, unfavourable for carrying out improvement. High cost of land and long payback periods. Inadequacy of EU-level aid to match the concept of Dehesa.
Co-benefits and synergies			
Forests contribute to air quality, nutrient retention capacity and water balance. Well managed forests could reduce the risk of forest fires. Indirect benefits to biodiversity, erosion control and water cycle.	Implementation of reforestations on unproductive agricultural land represents a job opportunity. Thriving forestry firms due to demand for afforestation. Increase in biodiversity.	Contribute to water balance due to retention capacity. This leads to better soil quality and less erosion. Grasses adapt better to forest fires (grow quicker after fire). Social opportunities including livestock farming and employment, fixing population in rural areas	As a co-benefit dehesas provide high quality foodstuffs (e.g., Iberian pork products). Also provide benefits to soil, plants, and animals.
Trade-offs			
Devaluation of forests due to migration from rural areas (abandonment). Forests should not be understood separately from the society that could maintain them.	Carbon capture would need to be compatibilized with controlling the accumulation of fuels, to prevent large forest fires	Continuous grazing encourages the emergence of less productive species and biomass. This can negatively affect its consumption by livestock	Lack of workers aware of traditional agricultural practices due to urbanization and migration to urban centres. Lack of generational replacement working in agroforestry system is a barrier for implementation of new technologies.
Risks associated with scaling up			
Long rotation periods of forests can increase risk of fires due to accumulation of fuel	If widely applied, should be accompanied by fire prevention and extinction plan.	Grasslands and livestock raising are connected. Livestock farms could be highly polluting if unsustainably managed.	Related to climate change: dehesa ecosystems could be altered by shifts in temperature and rain patterns.

Forest management	Afforestation	Grassland management	Agroforestry (Dehesas)
(biomass storing carbon).		Not enough workers in the countryside.	
Knowledge gaps			
Not enough awareness from society or policy makers of the benefits of forestry and forest management.	Quantification of the carbon sequestered by a growing forest. Accurate growth and yield models adapted for carbon capture silvicultural management are required	Accurate monitoring and measuring methods for carbon uptake by grassland species are required. Lifecycle assessments to calculate the carbon effectively removed from the atmosphere by grassland systems.	More information on the carbon sequestration potential of dehesas and life cycle assessment of interactions between dehesas and livestock.

3.3.5 Sweden

The Swedish LMT portfolio includes i) Afforestation and forest management, ii) BECCS, and iii) biochar.

Sweden's ambitious long-term strategy aims for net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2045, with subsequent negative emissions. BECCS is expected to remove 1.8 million tonnes CO_{2eq} annually by 2030 and between 3 to 10 million tonnes CO_{2eq} per year by 2045. Biochar contributes to the increased carbon sink in forests and land, expected to remove 1.2 million tonnes CO_{2eq} annually by 2030 and a minimum of 2.7 million tonnes CO_{2eq} per year by 2045. Consequently, carbon removals ranging between 9.4 and 16.4 are a reasonable projection for 2045.

BECCS plays a vital role in Sweden's journey towards zero and negative emissions. However, the land-use aspect is less relevant due to Sweden's efficient biomass management. Two main BECCS routes are discussed: one involving liquid biofuel production (biodiesel or ethanol) and the other through biomass conversion to heat and power, typically employing direct pulverized combustion of biomass.

Biochar is currently produced on small scale in Sweden, primarily from residual biomass from forestry and gardening, and is used as a soil amendment in parks and tree plantations. It represents a land-based measure with potential for national, regional, and global upscaling, including replication across various locations and scales.

Sweden possesses the largest forested area in the EU, with Sweden around 70% of the country's land covered by forests, amounting to 28 million hectares. Approximately 22 million hectares are productive or available for extraction/ production. While around two million hectares are under protection for ecological and socio-cultural purposes, not driven by economic value. Given Sweden's mature and well-established forest resource management, afforestation and reforestation may not be in focus. Reforestation efforts began in the 19th century, followed by intensive management styles, ensuring high productivity for both biomass and wood product extraction (including bioenergy). Forest management and afforestation are considered in the case study as strategies that interact with biochar and BECCS in various ways. Forests play a pivotal role in the integration of these technologies two LMTs.

BECCS	Biochar	Forest management and afforestation
Policy context		
Key in national policy for reaching net zero emissions by 2045. Enables negative emissions. Considered in “Industriklivet” – Industrial Leap policy instrument	Complementary measure for emission reduction. Potential not integrated in policy as explicitly as BECCS, and rather added to accounting of carbon sink in forests and land	Considered in national plan for reaching net zero by 2045, in increased carbon sinks in forests and land. Swedish Forestry Act, National Forest Programme, Swedish Environmental
Land use competition		
Competition with area for food production	Could have competition for food production areas. If residual biomass is used the competition is minimized	Not expected
Climate risks & sensitivities		
Disturbances from a changing climate, e.g. from pests (spruce bark beetle), storms, wildfires, drought	Sensitivities in water retention, life under earth, nitrogen in soil	Subject to disturbances like fires if management is not proper
Economic implications		
High capital costs. Require public support for affording investment costs for pilots. Total costs of production and storage around about 65 to 110 €/ton CO ₂	Affordable if compared to other options. Costs varies according to technification. Biochar selling cost is tied to eventual revenues from carbon credits. There are no economic incentives for biochar production.	Costs need to be analysed under a holistic lens considering society and locations
Co-benefits and synergies		
Permanent ground storage is less sensitive to climate risks. Energy production: electricity and heating.	Energy production: heating. Permanent ground storage is less sensitive to climate risks. Carbon permanence in biochar. Used in soil biochar improve unhealthy soil and improve yields.	Linkages and synergies with BECCS and biochar.
Trade-offs		
Storage of CO ₂ emissions will most likely require transportation by vessels to Norway. This could negatively impact the life cycle emissions.	Pyrolysis could lead to pollution if not managed correctly.	Due to changing climate, carbon storage in forests is a strategy associated with risk. Concerns of the cultural and biodiversity impacts of intensive forest management.
Risks associated with scaling up		
Monocultures to increase biomass yield can lead to resource depletion, soil health, and biodiversity impacts. Industry’s potential scale-up. Reliance of significant quantities of biomass. Delays in mitigation action.	Competition with cropland if biomass is grown for the purpose of conversion to energy and biochar. More demand than supply.	Monocultures limiting tree species growth. Reduction in grazing land and feed for grazing animals, impact on food production. Loss of cultural heritage sites
Knowledge gaps		
Emission accounting protocols for enabling trade. Policy gap for large-scale implementation and storage of BECCS	More studies needed to assess effect of biochar on agriculture, environment and carbon sequestration.	

3.3.6 Switzerland

The Swiss LMT portfolio includes i) organic agriculture (soil carbon) & reduced / no tillage, and ii) agroforestry.

In pursuit of its goal to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050, Switzerland acknowledges the necessity of offsetting emissions that are challenging to eliminate, estimated at around 10 million tonnes of CO₂ per year. The country's limited arable land means that substantial changes in land use are impractical. Therefore, the emphasis lies on enhancing management practices to sequester carbon, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and maintain existing land use patterns.

One approach involves altering agricultural practices, with reduced tillage emerging as a potential means to boost soil organic carbon stocks. In addition to the potential for increased carbon storage, reduced tillage systems could reduce the mechanical energy required, further contributing to lower overall greenhouse gas emissions. Switzerland is also exploring other management options, including improved crop rotations, greater use of cover crops, and leaving residues on fields. Expanding the area under organic farming is another promising avenue to bolster soil organic carbon stocks.

As for increasing tree coverage and wood biomass in Switzerland, afforestation faces significant challenges due to land constraints and already substantial carbon stocks in forests. However, agroforestry offers an attractive alternative, enabling the expansion of tree biomass without encroaching on agricultural land. Currently, 16% of Swiss farmers are already engaged in organic farming, and this number continues to grow, reflecting a positive trend towards sustainable agricultural practices in the country.

Organic agriculture and reduced tillage	Agroforestry
Policy context	
Practices included in the Swiss agricultural policy	No direct policy supporting the LMT
Land use competition	
Organic agriculture practices compete with more productive conventional agriculture	Does not directly compete with other LMTs for land in Switzerland. May provide lower food yield.
Climate risks & sensitivities	
Extreme weather, droughts. Soil organic carbon turnover increase with temperature.	Can reduce effect of heavy rainfall by providing a canopy to protect soils from erosion.
Economic implications	
Existing subsidies for organic agriculture and reduced tillage practices. Expected to be a more affordable technology if compared to others (BECCS or biochar)	Eligible to agricultural subsidies but not includes timber agroforestry. Also, good economic feasibility.
Co-benefits and synergies	
Organic fields are more resilient to droughts. Reduced till can mitigate erosion. Higher soil fertility.	Would lead to more diverse landscape providing erosion control, increased biodiversity, habitat and food for pollinators and birds, increased soil fertility.
Trade-offs	
Reduced tillage can lead to increased pest pressure (weeds, fungal growth), requiring the need of pesticides. Practice of organic agriculture can reduce the yields.	Could decrease cereal yields, depending on agroforestry configuration. Trade-offs might be economical.
Risks associated with scaling up	
Organic agriculture: Lowering yields Reduced tillage: increased need to apply herbicides	Lack of systematic assessments of agroforestry systems. Fast scaling-up without enough regional knowledge may lead to establishment of unsuitable trees or systems.

Organic agriculture and reduced tillage	Agroforestry
Knowledge gaps	
Soil organic carbon (SOC) turnover increase with temperature and a changing climate. Effect of subsidies for maximizing carbon sequestration	Application of modern alleycropping agroforestry systems. Another gap is the effect of changing climate to modern and traditional Swiss agroforestry systems.

3.3.7 Ukraine

The Ukrainian LMT portfolio includes i) organic farming, ii) reduced / no tillage, and iii) agroforestry. In addition, one engineered LMT, bioenergy (biogas from agricultural feedstocks) is considered.

More detailed qualitative storylines/narratives for Ukraine are not available as Ukraine was added as a country case study at a later stage during the LANDMARC research process.

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3.4 Modelling/Scenario results for LMTs

Results from modelling will be introduced in the workshop. These models present the obtained result of interaction of land-vegetation-carbon across time, in the *European region* as a whole.

As presented in the introductory section, the models only include five comprehensive categories of LMTs:

1. Afforestation and forest management
2. Agroforestry
3. Biochar
4. Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)
5. No tillage

The modelling scenarios employed are:

1. Baseline – Average global temperature increase of approximately 3 °C.
2. Moderate ambition – Average global temperature increase of approximately 2 °C.
3. High ambition – Average global temperature increase of approximately 1.5°C.

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Annex I: LANDMARC Glossary

Agriculture

Agroforestry: Trees are deliberately combined with crops and/or animals on the same unit of land.

Dry seeded rice – no till: Rice seeds are sown directly in the fields, by directly drilling the soil, instead of transplanting of seedlings.

Reduced tillage: A decrease in disturbance to soil during crop cultivation, by reducing inversion tillage.

Integrated soil fertility management: Farming method that maximizes the agronomic efficiency of nutrients by using combination of chemical fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm.

Organic agriculture: An agricultural practice in which organic materials such as animal manures, compost, leguminous plants are applied and avoiding mineral fertilizer application.

Peatland management: Protection, partial or full restoring (returning degrading peatland areas back to its original state) of peatlands.

Pasture management: Management of pasture for greater availability of grazing pastures for animals, maintaining the soil quality and conserving biodiversity.

Forestry

Afforestation: Establishing forests by planting new trees where there was previously no tree cover.

Reforestation: Replanting trees in an area where there was previously forest.

Forest management: Process of planning and implementing practices for the use of forests to meet specific environmental, economic, social, and cultural objectives.

Forest fire management: Mixture of indigenous fire management and prescribed burning method to suppress and prevent large and uncontrollable forest fires.

Energy

Anaerobic fermentation of manures (biogas/compost): Process of using animal manure, and agricultural or food waste to produce methane as an energy source, and bio-gas slurry as compost.

Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS): Energy is generated from biomass and the emitted carbon dioxide is subsequently captured and stored in geological formations.

Biochar: organic material made by burning biomass in a pyrolysis process, a high temperature (above 300 °C) and without oxygen, which can be used to improve soil functions and to reduce GHG emission reduction.

ANNEX C4: INCEPTION REPORT (IN SPANISH) FOR LATIN AMERICA

PRELIMINAR - NO COMPARTIR

1. Introducción

Combatir el cambio climático no será posible solo reduciendo las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero (GEI), también son necesarias las tecnologías de emisiones negativas o tecnologías que capturan y retienen CO₂. Dentro de estas se encuentran las tecnologías y prácticas de mitigación basadas en el uso de la tierra (*Land based Mitigation Technologies*, LMT) que hacen parte de las Soluciones basadas en la Naturaleza (SbN), y son acciones que reducen y/o eliminan las emisiones de gases efecto invernadero GEI y mejoran la capacidad de la tierra como sumidero de estos, al tiempo que tienen en cuenta beneficios más amplios de sostenibilidad socioeconómica y medioambiental (Bölsner et al., 2023). El uso del suelo con actividades como la agricultura, ganadería y la transformación de ecosistemas naturales es una importante fuente de emisiones de carbono. De igual forma, el suelo tiene una gran capacidad de absorber carbono y almacenarlo. De esta manera, la capacidad de emitir o absorber carbono depende del manejo que se le dé.

El proyecto LANDMARC aborda la necesidad de encontrar soluciones de captura o remoción de CO₂ para lograr los objetivos climáticos mundiales y las metas del Acuerdo de París a partir de las LMT. El proyecto ha analizado 13 [tecnologías](#) relacionadas con el manejo de bosques, plantaciones y ecosistemas, sistemas agropecuarios, manejo de biomasa y bioenergía en 16 [estudios de caso](#) ubicados en 5 continentes. Ha empleado un enfoque de investigación triangular, que abarca aspectos técnicos y sociales: el uso de datos satelitales y muestreos de suelo se combinan con modelos climáticos, de uso de la tierra y de escenarios económicos, incluyendo la participación y análisis de los actores clave.

El Instituto de Ambiente de Estocolmo (SEI, por sus siglas en inglés) es una organización internacional de investigación y políticas sin fines de lucro que aborda los desafíos ambientales y de desarrollo sostenible. El trabajo de SEI abarca cuestiones climáticas, hídricas, uso de la tierra, gobernanza, economía y género. La participación de los actores clave está en el centro de nuestros esfuerzos por crear capacidades, fortalecer las instituciones y equipar a los socios para el cambio a largo plazo.

Durante octubre y noviembre de 2023, SEI realizará talleres regionales con actores clave en sus cuatro centros regionales: Bogotá, Nairobi, Bangkok y Estocolmo. La experiencia regional y los conocimientos de los participantes del taller enriquecerán la comprensión sobre el escalamiento de las LMT, facilitando mayor precisión a los supuestos de los modelos y mejorar las recomendaciones a los responsables de políticas y decisiones.

2. Objetivos del taller

El taller regional tiene por objetivo revisar y evaluar algunas tecnologías de mitigación basadas en el uso de la tierra (LMT) con un grupo de actores clave de Latinoamérica, enfocándose en tres objetivos específicos:

- I. Caracterizar un portafolio de LMT a nivel regional.
- II. Evaluar cómo se pueden aumentar las ambiciones de mitigación basada en el uso del suelo en la región a partir del compromiso y la cooperación regional.
- III. Desarrollar narrativas que definan un portafolio regional de LMT para varios niveles de ambición climática y varios niveles de compromiso regional.

El taller toma como insumo diversos resultados de investigación, síntesis y perspectivas de los actores clave que se han llevado a cabo a nivel local, nacional o regional, y se puede dividir en tres tipos principales:

- 1) **Estudios de casos nacionales:** A partir de revisión bibliográfica y consultas en campo, en Latinoamérica se analizó el manejo integrado del fuego a partir de prácticas indígenas en Venezuela y se analizó la producción de biochar a partir de residuos de palma de aceite en Colombia.
- 2) **Perspectivas regionales:** Basadas en una revisión de políticas y mecanismos de mitigación del cambio climático generados a nivel regional, junto con entrevistas y consultas con los actores clave.
- 3) **Modelamiento tierra-vegetación-carbono,** llevado a cabo a nivel nacional, regional y global, todo basado en las Trayectorias Socioeconómicas Compartidas 2 (SSP2, por sus siglas en inglés), que es la ruta "intermedia" entre los cinco SSP utilizados como puntos de referencia dentro de la Comunidad de Modelado de Evaluación Integrada y como la base para las evaluaciones del IPCC.

Se utilizan tres escenarios para determinar la implementación hasta el año 2100, utilizando un conjunto particular de LMT, cada escenario relacionado con las Trayectorias de Concentración Representativa (RCP) adoptada en las Evaluaciones del IPCC, y correspondiente a diferentes concentraciones de GEI en el año 2100:

- i. Línea de base: utiliza RCP de 4,5 W/m², que se espera que en la mayoría de los escenarios esté asociado con aumentos de temperatura promedio cercanos a 2.4 °C.
- ii. Ambición moderada: utiliza RCP de 2,6 W/m², que se espera que en la mayoría de los escenarios esté asociado con aumentos de temperatura promedio cercanos a 2.0 °C.
- iii. Alta ambición: utiliza RCP de 1,9 W/m², que se espera que en la mayoría de los escenarios esté asociado con aumentos de temperatura promedio cercanos a 1,5 °C.

Los modelos están limitados en el número de LMT que pueden evaluarse y por ello se eligieron cinco:

- Forestación (incluye reforestación y manejo forestal);
- Agroforestería (árboles plantados dentro de áreas agrícolas, con características específicas);
- Biocarbón (procedente de la disponibilidad de tierra calculada y utilizada como enmienda del suelo);

- Bioenergía con Captura y Almacenamiento de Carbono (BECCS)
- Labranza mínima (labranza cero en áreas agrícolas)

Otros LMT se discutirán en el taller debido a su importancia nacional o regional, aunque no hayan sido modelados.

3. Panorama de mitigación en América Latina y el Caribe (ALC)

3.1 Uso de la tierra y emisiones

América Latina y el Caribe (ALC) es una región caracterizada por su gran riqueza en biodiversidad, ecosistemas terrestres y marítimos incluyendo el mayor número de países megadiversos al interior de la región. A nivel mundial, ALC concentra el 24% de las ecorregiones terrestres, el 18% de las ecorregiones marinas del mundo y un tercio de los recursos hídricos del planeta (IADB & CEPAL, 2018; UNEP, 2022). Contradictoriamente, a su vez, esta riqueza la convierte en una región muy vulnerable al cambio climático. Es evidente que esta riqueza ha venido disminuyendo (ver Figura 1), los cambios en el uso de la tierra y la deforestación son la mayor amenaza para la región. Y aunque ALC aporta una mínima fracción a los GEI a nivel mundial, sufre de manera desproporcionada los efectos del cambio climático (Bárcena Ibarra et al., 2020) debido a la alta vulnerabilidad por pérdida en su biodiversidad y ecosistemas y su dependencia en el sector agropecuario.

El sector agropecuario, que es de gran importancia económica en la región, es especialmente vulnerable a los impactos del cambio climático. De hecho, se estima que la productividad de la agricultura puede caer entre el 12 y 24% como resultado del cambio en el clima (Samaniego y otros, 2022). Es importante notar que el número de fenómenos meteorológicos extremos se ha duplicado durante las últimas dos décadas (Cárdenas & Orozco, 2022).

Figura 1. Cambios en la cobertura boscosa de América Latina y el Caribe (ALC).

Nota. Fuente (CEPAL, 2021).

La pérdida de bosques en la región desde 1990 a 2020 se estima en 138 millones de hectáreas lo que equivale a un poco más de la superficie de Perú (CEPAL, 2021). En este contexto, conservar y fortalecer la biodiversidad y los ecosistemas existentes en la región es indispensable.

Las emisiones netas per cápita de los países de ALC se ubicaban en 5,98 toneladas métricas de dióxido de carbono equivalente (CO₂-eq) en 2020, del total de emisiones, los principales emisores de la región son Brasil, México, Argentina y Colombia, que representan un 70% del total de emisiones de la región (Climate Watch, 2022). A diferencia de otras regiones del mundo, en ALC el Sector de la Agricultura, la Silvicultura y Otros Usos de la Tierra (AFOLU, por sus siglas en inglés) representa más del 40% del total de emisiones de la región (Bárcena Ibarra et al., 2020) esto es el doble del promedio mundial. Los principales contribuyentes son la deforestación y el cambio de uso de la tierra que además de dióxido de carbono (CO₂) generan emisiones de óxido nitroso (N₂O) y metano (CH₄) (Cárdenas y Orozco, 2022). De 2001 hasta 2018 hubo un total de 361 millones de hectáreas perdidas de cobertura forestal, equivalente a un descenso de 9% en la cobertura desde el año 2000 y a 98,7 Gt de CO₂ emitidos (World Resources Institute, s. f.). Tradicionalmente en los bosques tropicales suramericanos, la degradación por extracción de madera es el proceso inicial de cambio de uso de suelo, seguido por el uso pecuario y posteriormente la agricultura comercial (Fearnside, 2006).

No obstante, aún es posible implementar soluciones para contener estos impactos. ALC tiene un gran potencial para absorber el CO₂ naturalmente a través de sumideros de carbono existentes, como humedales, bosques, océanos, manglares y páramos. Además, se resalta que las soluciones basadas en la naturaleza (SbN) representan una gran oportunidad de mitigación y adaptación para la región por los impactos actuales derivados de las emisiones de la agricultura y ganadería, el cambio de uso del suelo y la deforestación en la región, y teniendo en cuenta la riqueza en ecosistemas y biodiversidad (Samaniego et al., 2022).

3.2 Contribuciones Determinadas a nivel Nacional (NDC)

Las partes en el Acuerdo de París deben presentar sus NDC (por sus siglas en inglés) cada cinco años, y deben incluir medidas climáticas más ambiciosas que en la edición previa. En general, las NDC de la región de América Latina y el Caribe están por encima de la media mundial en lo referido a su calidad, lo que refleja el sólido compromiso de las partes interesadas, los mecanismos de transparencia y el interés de la región en los mercados mundiales de carbono (Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo, 2022). Entre 2020 y 2022, 20 de los 33 países de América Latina y el Caribe actualizaron sus NDC o presentaron otras nuevas, y nueve aumentaron su nivel de ambición (por ejemplo, al disminuir el límite máximo de emisiones para 2030). Esto incluye a las seis economías más importantes de la región: Argentina, Brasil, Chile, Colombia, México y Perú.

En total, las seis principales economías de América Latina y el Caribe se comprometieron a reducir sus emisiones en un 34,3% con respecto al escenario en que todo sigue igual de aquí a 2030. Sin embargo, existen diferencias notables en los niveles de ambición climática entre los distintos países. Colombia se ha comprometido a reducir sus emisiones un 51% con respecto a la hipótesis en que todo sigue igual, en tanto que el compromiso de reducción de Argentina es de apenas un 8%, y la reducción anunciada por México es insignificante (Cárdenas & Orozco, 2022).

Este panorama impone presiones adicionales para mejorar la capacidad adaptativa y recurrir a medidas de remoción de dióxido de carbono (RDC) o emisiones negativas, más relacionadas y/o

basadas en la naturaleza (Samaniego et al., 2021). En el sector AFOLU, varios países se han comprometido a impulsar iniciativas de reforestación, restaurando y gestionando de una mejor manera los bosques autóctonos, y a poner en marcha programas de conformidad con el marco REDD+. Otras iniciativas incluyen la adopción de medidas para promover la agricultura y la ganadería sostenibles, el pago de los servicios ambientales y la gestión de las zonas protegidas (Cárdenas & Orozco, 2022).

La mayoría de las NDC de la región priorizan los sectores y las acciones de adaptación. Para el caso de la mitigación, los sectores más importantes, según su potencial para reducir las emisiones de GEI, son energía, transporte, y la agricultura, la silvicultura y otros usos de la tierra (AFOLU), y se enfocan en el despliegue de energías renovables, la gestión sostenible de la biodiversidad, la agricultura climáticamente inteligente (CSA, por sus siglas en inglés). La actualización de las NDC permitió incluir otros sectores, como la gestión de residuos, la biodiversidad y el sector vivienda, e introducir un enfoque multisectorial incluyendo las soluciones basadas en la naturaleza. En este sentido, sobresalen medidas relacionadas con la conservación de los bosques y la reforestación, las cuales favorecen el secuestro de carbono, reducen la vulnerabilidad ante fenómenos extremos y protegen el medio ambiente. Por ejemplo, se destacan países como Costa Rica, Colombia, Chile, México y Panamá, que incluyen acciones para conservar los bosques y reforestar el territorio (Samaniego et al., 2022).

En ALC, las NDC incluyen pocas medidas o líneas de acción sobre tecnologías de remoción o de emisiones negativas y no forman parte de un plan prioritario para fortalecer la capacidad adaptativa o reducir las emisiones (Samaniego et al., 2022). Se identifican únicamente acciones aisladas, como el uso de nuevas tecnologías de generación, almacenamiento, transmisión y distribución de energía, pero no se profundiza con políticas concretas para impulsar la adopción de las medidas y tecnologías de remoción (Samaniego et al., 2022). Sin embargo, un punto de partida para el despliegue de las RDC en ALC puede ser el sugerido por (Samaniego et al., 2021) (ver Figura 2), este puede ayudar a los tomadores de decisiones, investigadores y financiadores a tener esfuerzos direccionados conjuntamente para la región.

Figura 2. Sugerencia de despliegue a gran escala de opciones de RDC por fases en países de América Latina y el Caribe.

Nota. Fuente (Samaniego et al., 2021).

3.3 Características de algunos países de la cuenca Amazónica (Colombia, Ecuador, Perú y Brasil)

La cuenca del Amazonas es una de las regiones del mundo más importantes para combatir el cambio climático por ser la selva tropical más grande del mundo con 6 millones de kilómetros cuadrados. Este bioma absorbe grandes cantidades de dióxido de carbono de la atmósfera lo que es fundamental para la mitigación. Se estima que el Amazonas absorbe entre el 10 y 15% de las emisiones anuales de GEI (Moreno Rincón, 2023). Sin embargo, en los últimos años esta capacidad de mitigar el cambio climático por ser sumidero de carbono se ha revertido debido al nivel de transformación del ecosistema principalmente por deforestación e incendios forestales (Castilhos, 2021). Con el propósito de focalizar el análisis en ALC, incluyendo países de un bioma común, se seleccionaron cuatro de los ocho países de la cuenca amazónica: Brasil, Colombia, Ecuador y Perú.

El cambio del uso del suelo en los países que conforman la Organización del Tratado de Cooperación Amazónica (OTCA o ACTO, por sus siglas en inglés) se puede apreciar en la Figura 3. En general, las áreas de cultivo se incrementaron, el área de bosque que se regenera naturalmente disminuyó, las pasturas prácticamente se mantuvieron y los bosques plantados se incrementaron.

PRELIMINAR - NO COMPARTE

Figura 3. Cambio en el uso del suelo para países de la cuenca amazónica.

Nota: Fuente (FAOSTAT, 2023) *Miles de hectáreas

La pérdida de los bosques tropicales y subtropicales pueden tener una importancia desproporcionada (FAO, 2018), pues desempeñan un papel fundamental en diversos procesos ecológicos. Por ejemplo, en el transporte de la humedad atmosférica, la cobertura nubosa y las precipitaciones a escala regional (Ellison et al., 2017). En la cuenca amazónica este efecto se conoce como “ríos voladores”, perder los

“ríos voladores” disminuiría las precipitaciones regionales (Ellison et al., 2017; Nobre, 2015) y tendría un efecto devastador en la economía suramericana.

En la siguiente Tabla se puede apreciar el nivel de emisiones GEI de los países seleccionados para el análisis.

Tabla 1. Emisiones de GEI en 2020 de los países de estudio de la cuenca amazónica.

	Colombia (2020) MtCO ₂ e	Colombia (2020) %	Perú (2020) MtCO ₂ e	Perú (2020) %	Ecuador (2020) MtCO ₂ e	Ecuador (2020) %	Brasil (2020) MtCO ₂ e	Brasil (2020) %
Cambio de uso de la tierra y silvicultura (CUTS)	83,31	30,82	89,92	50,02	26,14	27,75	404,94	27,55
Agricultura	68,33	25,28	26,51	14,75	13	13,80	518,86	35,30
Energía	88,18	32,62	46,27	25,74	39,7	42,15	440,02	29,94
Procesos industriales	12,77	4,72	5,35	2,98	2,94	3,12	34,28	2,33
Residuos	17,72	6,56	11,73	6,52	12,41	13,18	71,56	4,87
Total incluido CUTS	270,31	-	179,78	-	94,19	-	1469,66	
Proporción de GEI a nivel mundial	-	0,54	-	0,38	-	0,2	-	2,92

Nota. Datos extraídos de Climate Watch.

Todos los países que conforman la cuenca amazónica firmaron el Acuerdo de París y formularon sus NDC, sin embargo, del grupo de países analizados, Colombia es el único que ha actualizado sus compromisos y ha mejorado sus ambiciones frente a la primer NDC presentada (ver Tabla 2).

Tabla 2. Compromisos climáticos de los países seleccionados de la cuenca amazónica.

Compromisos climáticos	Colombia	Ecuador	Perú	Brasil
Primera NDC	✓	✓	✓	✓
NDC nueva o actualizada	✓	✗	✓	✓
Estrategia de largo plazo	✓	✗	✗	✗
Compromiso de cero emisiones netas	✓	✗	✓	✓
¿Ha mejorado su NDC con respecto a la anterior?				
Revisado a partir de la entrega anterior	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mitigación mejorada (reducción de las emisiones totales de GEI en 2030)	✓	✗	✓	✗
Objetivo de GEI mejorado o añadido	✓	✓	✓	✗
Objetivo sectorial mejorado o añadido	✓	✗	✗	✗
Políticas o acciones mejoradas o añadidas	✓	✓	✗	✗

Adaptación mejorada	✓	✓	✓	✓
Aportó información adicional para mayor claridad, transparencia y comprensión	✓	✓	✗	✓

Nota. Datos extraídos de Climate Watch.

3.3.1 Colombia:

En 2020, Colombia emitió 270.31MtCO₂eq lo que representa 0.57% de las emisiones globales (Climate Watch, 2022). Colombia presentó originalmente sus NDC en 2018 y en 2020 las actualizó. La meta de emisión de GEI para 2030 es como máximo 169.44 MtCO₂eq (equivalente a una reducción del 51% de las emisiones respecto a la proyección de emisiones en 2030 en el escenario de referencia), iniciando un decrecimiento en las emisiones entre 2027 y 2030 tendiente hacia la carbono-neutralidad a mediados de siglo. También se comprometió a establecer presupuestos de carbono para el periodo 2020-2030 a más tardar en 2023 y reducir las emisiones de carbono negro del 40% respecto al nivel de 2014. Estas metas fueron refrendadas en la Ley de Acción Climática (Ley 2169 de 2021, 2021) que fue sancionada en 2021 y se adicionó la meta de lograr deforestación neta cero a 2030 a través de medidas de mercado, políticas y cooperativas. Algunas acciones que contempla la Ley incluyen:

- Lograr la restauración ecológica de al menos 1 millón de hectáreas al 2030.
- Manejo sostenible de 2,5 millones de hectáreas mediante contratos de conservación para estabilizar la Frontera Agropecuaria. Esta estrategia comprende el otorgamiento del derecho al uso de la tierra y la celebración de acuerdos de conservación con familias rurales que habitan baldíos no adjudicables, tales como las Zonas de Reserva Forestal de Ley 2a de 1959.
- Calcular el potencial de reducción de GEI de los ecosistemas de alta montaña; manglares y pastos marinos; humedales y arbolado urbano para las ciudades de más de 100.000 habitantes.
- Sustitución de fogones tradicionales por la instalación de un millón de estufas eficientes de cocción por leña para el periodo 2021-2030.
- Acciones tendientes al desarrollo de sistemas de monitoreo y detección temprana de incendios forestales mediante el uso de tecnologías avanzadas y/o sistemas comunitarios para el suministro de información que permita la toma eficaz, eficiente y oportuna de decisiones en torno a la gestión de incendios forestales.

Colombia también cuenta con la estrategia a largo plazo para adaptarse al cambio climático y ser carbono neutral al 2050.

3.3.2 Ecuador:

Ecuador es un país relativamente pequeño, asimismo, su participación a las emisiones globales es baja, ocupa el número 60 de mayores emisores en el mundo, con una contribución de 0,2%. No obstante, es un país altamente vulnerable al cambio climático y aunque cuenta con instrumentos legales nacionales para planificar la reducción de GEI como la Estrategia Nacional de Cambio Climático 2012-2025, el Plan Nacional de Cambio Climático 2015-2018 y el marco legal nacional para

la protección de áreas silvestres, solo ha presentado su primer NDC y en ella no se especifica ninguna meta para la reducción de emisiones de GWI (Climate Watch, 2022).

3.3.3 Perú:

Perú tiene una participación del 0,38% en las emisiones globales y se ubica en el número 44 de mayores emisores en el mundo. Presentó su primera NDC en 2015 pero en esta no especificó la meta máxima de emisiones. En 2020, presentó su NDC actualizada y mejorada con respecto a su primera presentación, en esta se compromete a no exceder sus emisiones netas de GEI a 208,8MtCO₂eq para 2030 y limitarlas aproximadamente a 179 MtCO₂eq, esto se traduce a un aumento en su objetivo de mitigación del 30% al 40% y el establecimiento de una meta límite. También aumentó la ambición en adaptación incorporando el turismo y el transporte como nuevas áreas prioritarias (UNDP, 2022).

Así como Colombia, Perú plantea tener estrategia a largo plazo, actualizando la Estrategia Nacional de Cambio Climático al año 2050 (ENCC 2050), donde le apuntan a la adaptación al cambio climático y la carbono neutralidad por medio de toma de decisiones informadas, la reducción de emisiones de GEI mediante acciones enfocadas en el manejo de los bosques, la reducción de la deforestación, el mayor uso de energías renovables y la economía circular, entre otros (MINAM, 2022).

3.3.4 Brasil

Brasil es el mayor emisor de GEI en ALC y es el séptimo mayor emisor en el mundo, con una participación total de 3,09%. Sin embargo, sus emisiones han estado disminuyendo—en el 2010 generó 2,12 GtCO₂ eq y en 2020 se redujo a 1,47 GtCO₂ eq. Entre 2005 y 2010, una fuerte reducción de las tasas de deforestación condujo a una reducción general de las emisiones nacionales de GEI en un 41% (De Azevedo & Angelo, 2018), especialmente gracias a la aplicación de moratorias para evitar el uso de tierras deforestadas para la producción de soja y ganado. La actualización para 2023 de la Contribución Nacionalmente Determinada (NDC) de Brasil al Acuerdo de París, aprobada por el Comité Interministerial sobre el Cambio Climático (CIM) y anunciada en la Cumbre sobre la Ambición Climática en septiembre de 2023, devuelve la ambición climática del país al nivel de la Primera NDC de 2015: niveles de emisión de 1,32 GtCO₂e (reducción del 48%) en emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero (GEI) para 2025; niveles de emisión de 1,20 GtCO₂e (reducción del 53%) en GEI para 2030 (Política por Inteiro & Instituto Talanoa, 2023).

La primera versión de la NDC de Brasil al Acuerdo de París tenía como objetivo restaurar y reforestar 12 millones de hectáreas de bosques para 2030 (República Federativa do Brasil, 2020). La Ley de Pago por Servicios Medioambientales (PSA) (Ley n. 14.119, de 13 de enero de 2021) (República Federativa do Brasil, 2021) ha sido un avance clave en esta dirección, definiendo posibles fuentes y rutas de financiación para viabilizar proyectos de mitigación al cambio climático, especialmente con el enfoque de conservación de bosques alineada a buenas prácticas agrícolas. El 4 de octubre de 2023, la Comisión de Medio Ambiente del Senado aprobó en última instancia un Proyecto de Ley (PL n. 412/2022) (Senado Federal, 2022) que regula el Mercado Brasileño de Reducción de Emisiones (MBRE), determinado por la Política Nacional de Cambio Climático (Ley n. 12.187, de 29 de diciembre de 2009) (República Federativa do Brasil, 2009). El Proyecto de Ley propone la creación del Sistema Brasileño de Comercio de Emisiones de Gases de Efecto Invernadero (SBCE), un ambiente regulado

sujeto al régimen de limitación de emisiones de GEI y de comercio de activos representativos de emisiones, reducciones o remociones de GEI. Si aprobado también en el Congreso brasileño, este potencial dispositivo legislativo podrá tener implicaciones sustanciales tanto dentro del país como en la región amazónica.

4. Resultados LANDMARC en Latinoamérica

ALC es una región muy grande y comprende muchos biomas y diferencias entre sí, por lo cual, realizar un estudio para toda la región es complejo. Sin embargo, hemos realizado algunas aproximaciones, que incluyen un estudio en Venezuela sobre el manejo del fuego a partir de prácticas indígenas, una experiencia de acercamiento a la producción de biochar a partir de residuos agroindustriales en Colombia y un taller regional sobre el potencial y las barreras de las LMT con presencia de actores de Colombia, Brasil, Ecuador y Cuba. A continuación, se proporciona un resumen del contexto regional a partir de los estudios realizados por LANDMARC para ALC.

4.1 Potencial de las LMT en diferentes regiones

Suramérica es la segunda región en el mundo con mayor potencial de uso de tecnologías de mitigación basadas en el uso de la tierra (LMT) después de Asia. Su mayor potencial es la forestación y la reforestación, seguido se destacan la agroforestería, el biochar y BECCS.

Figura 4. Potencial de mitigación de los LMT en diferentes regiones, Gt CO₂ e/año.

Nota. Fuente: (Karki et al., 2023).

Este análisis coincide con los análisis de la CEPAL reseñados anteriormente donde se resalta que las soluciones basadas en la naturaleza son fundamentales en la región.

4.2 Estudio de caso – Venezuela

El estudio de caso que adelantó LANDMARC en Venezuela se centró en la gestión integrada de fuego (GIF) basada en las prácticas indígenas en el Parque Nacional Canaima (Bilbao y otros, 2022). El fuego tiene un papel vital en la preparación del suelo antes de la plantación de cultivos en las prácticas de agricultura itinerante en pequeñas parcelas dentro de los bosques. La quema de material vegetal es necesaria para liberar los nutrientes contenidos en la biomasa. Aumenta la fertilidad d

el suelo, reduciendo su acidez (pH) y la toxicidad del aluminio de los característicos suelos tropicales antiguos y empobrecidos y lavados. Los indígenas realizan quemas controladas contra el viento (contrafuegos) en las primeras horas de la mañana, evitando que el fuego se propague. Muy diferente de los incontrolados y dañinos incendios forestales que se propagan sin control.

Esta tecnología tiene el potencial de reducir las emisiones globales de los incendios forestales masivos. Esto debido a que las quemas controladas utilizadas por los pueblos indígenas en sus territorios son de baja intensidad y extensión limitada, y tienen en cuenta las condiciones ecológicas locales evitando que se produzcan grandes incendios forestales. Al igual que las quemas indígenas, las quemas prescritas son también tratamientos controlados aplicados por los bomberos, para la reducción del material combustible con el fin de prevenir la aparición y reducir la gravedad y extensión de los incendios forestales.

En general se resaltan los siguientes riesgos. Esta tecnología es sensible al cambio climático en especial al aumento de la severidad de las condiciones para incendios, olas de calor, temporadas secas prolongadas, entre otros. Esto afecta la producción de biomasa y puede facilitar la propagación de incendios más severos. La pérdida de biodiversidad es uno de los riesgos más altos de esta tecnología lo que afectaría servicios ecosistémicos críticos para la regulación del clima. Los incendios forestales reducen los sumideros de carbono y afectan la capacidad de captura de CO₂ de la vegetación.

El estudio resalta también algunos beneficios económicos por la introducción del nuevo paradigma de la Gestión Integrada del Fuego en lugar de políticas de exclusión de incendios y se basa en el análisis de programas de manejo del fuego de Brasil y de Australia. La prohibición de incendios y las actividades de extinción demanda recursos humanos, técnicos y financieros crecientes lo que puede superar las capacidades locales y nacionales. En Brasil, el Programa de Brigadas Federales es un ejemplo exitoso de la implementación de GIF con la participación de comunidades indígenas como una manera eficiente de reducir incendios forestales y emisiones de GEI a bajo costo. Con este programa se redujo la ocurrencia de incendios forestales contratando a personas locales e indígenas para este manejo.

Algunas brechas en investigación muestran que no existe suficiente información ni investigación científica para comprender adecuadamente los regímenes de incendios específicos y la ecología del fuego de los diferentes tipos de vegetación con el fin de diseñar programas de gestión del fuego adecuados y sostenibles (Bilbao et al., 2020). Además, en la actualidad en Venezuela, no existe legislación sobre la Gestión Integrada del Fuego.

La modelización de simulación se realizará con DayCent y la modelización con ALCES. Los modelos de simulación con ALCES pueden revelar diferencias en los impactos sobre los paisajes y la eficacia de la gestión de los incendios forestales con prácticas autóctonas (actualmente prohibidas) frente a la gestión de incendios forestales convencional o regulada.

Con este estudio se pretende demostrar que la restitución de las prácticas indígenas de gestión de incendios podría reducir los incendios forestales y la deforestación (emisiones indirectas de GEI). Asimismo, estas prácticas podrían servir de base a las políticas de conservación de los parques nacionales, al tiempo que favorecerían el bienestar socioeconómico y cultural de los pueblos indígenas.

4.3 Biochar

Durante la ejecución del proyecto LANDMARC, Torres Morales (2022) realizó una investigación en torno al biochar cuyo objetivo principal fue evaluar los parámetros técnico-económicos y los aspectos de despliegue del biocarbón como tecnología de mitigación basada en el uso de la tierra en Colombia. Mediante el uso de análisis Político, Económico, Social, Tecnológico, Ambiental y Legal (PESTEL), cuantificación de biomasa residual viable y cuantificación de emisiones secuestradas. El estudio se centró en los residuos de la industria de palma de aceite, en especial, la fibra y el cuesco de las cuales no se aprovechan el 20% y el 33%, respectivamente, y el uso actual se limita a combustible para calderas. Se encontró que en Colombia el desarrollo del biochar es muy incipiente aún, ya que se encuentra principalmente en estudio y pruebas piloto en universidades y en centros de investigación.

En particular, se encontró alto interés y estudios desde el sector palmero con experimentos e investigación desde Cenipalma, el centro de investigación del gremio, además, se encontró a una empresa del sector, llamada Sirius que actualmente produce biochar a partir del cuesco y la fibra de la palma de aceite en Casanare, Colombia. Los resultados mostraron que no existe mercado para comercio con biocarbón en Colombia, las inversiones en transporte y tecnología avanzada, además de los impuestos asociados a los ingresos del comercio del biocarbón puede afectar negativamente la viabilidad de un proyecto de biocarbón. Finalmente, se estimó que el precio del biocarbón en Colombia puede variar entre 2.00 USD y 1.000 USD, esta variabilidad depende de las tecnologías usadas, la disponibilidad de biomasa y los ingresos variables de la venta del biocarbón (Torres Morales, 2022).

4.4 Taller LANDMARC 2022 y resultados de entrevistas 2023

En 2022 se realizó el primer taller LANDMARC en Latinoamérica, con actores clave entorno a las LMT. Este taller fue realizado el 05 de octubre de 2022 de forma híbrida, en el que participaron expertos de Colombia, Brasil, Cuba y Ecuador. En el taller se analizaron las barreras y las necesidades para implementar 6 tecnologías en Latinoamérica: Manejo del bosque, reforestación, agroforestería, agricultura orgánica, manejo del fuego y biocarbón. A continuación, las principales observaciones por tecnología.

4.4.1 Agroforestería

Barreras

Aunque existe conocimiento y experiencia en la implementación de sistemas agroforestales en Latinoamérica todavía falta transferir esta tecnología a los productores de forma efectiva y a mayor escala. Se resaltan vacíos en sistematización, disponibilidad y distribución de la información para que pueda llegar a los productores. Los productores perciben los árboles como obstáculo para la maquinaria. Existe un enfoque orientado a la productividad y hay resistencia a diversificar los agroecosistemas.

Esta baja transferencia y acceso a la tecnología es resultado de la insuficiente asistencia técnica al productor para fomentar los sistemas agroforestales. La colaboración entre centros de investigación,

universidades y sectores industriales es muy baja, esto limita la escalabilidad de las soluciones tecnológicas.

Falta investigación sobre el potencial de captura de sistemas agroforestales validados por país y región. Sin embargo, algunos expertos consideran que no hay manera de estandarizar los sistemas agroforestales, pues tienen una amplitud de prácticas, técnicas, manejos de tiempo y espacios que lo hacen muy difíciles de homogenizar, además en el trópico existen diferentes pisos térmicos y condiciones biogeográficas muy variadas. Esto también dificulta establecer estándares sobre los potenciales de captura y almacenamiento de carbono. En todo caso, evaluar la huella de carbono del sistema productivo agroforestal es un requisito para entrar al mercado internacional.

En Colombia y otros países de la región, son escasas las políticas públicas que brinde instrumentos económicos para la transformación de sistemas productivos convencionales hacia sistemas agroforestales o agrosilvopastoriles. Sin embargo, se resalta el caso peruano con las Cesiones en Uso para Sistemas Agroforestales (CUSAF) que son un tipo de contrato reconocido en la Ley Forestal y de Fauna Silvestre del Perú (Ley Nro. 29763), que formaliza las prácticas productivas forestales y agroforestales de los agricultores familiares que se encuentran en tierras forestales y bajo protección. Los contratos tienen una duración de 40 años y contemplan derechos, acceso a beneficios y obligaciones como la de conservar los bosques mediante el manejo sostenible (ICRAF, 2021).

Los expertos en el taller de 2022 señalaron que el mercado de carbono tiene limitantes pues valora más los árboles que a otro tipo de plantas como los cultivos, desconociendo que ambos organismos son fotosintéticos y tienen potencial de captura de carbono. Además, se resalta que con los sistemas agroforestales hay dificultad en convertir los productos en ingresos, ya que los mercados son lejanos o escasos y falta acceso a cadenas de valor. Es una actividad de bajo volumen porque la productividad no se compara con la de monocultivos.

Bajo involucramiento y vinculación de actores privados en estas estrategias. Dificultad en acceso a créditos por falta de legalización de títulos.

Requerimientos para su implementación

Se requiere incentivos económicos y políticas de largo plazo para fomentar las inversiones en estos sistemas. Facilitar el acceso a crédito y la mayor participación de actores privados, asociaciones, cooperativas y empresas.

Es necesario concentrar el área de la implementación de los sistemas agroforestales, evitando la dispersión. Incentivar modelos asociativos/cooperativos que promuevan la rentabilidad en co-beneficios para venta y compra de carbono para cumplir con requisitos del mercado.

Los sistemas agroforestales en la cuenca amazónica han sido de subsistencia para comunidades locales y pueblos indígenas. Generalmente se evidencia la incorporación de estos sistemas en cultivos de cacao y café, pero no en otros cultivos extensivos. Un sistema ideal sería uno que incorpora al suelo materia orgánica, con mayor biomasa y captación de carbono.

4.4.2 Forestación y reforestación

Dentro de esta tecnología se incluyó la restauración ecológica que es el proceso que busca recuperar las condiciones de estructura y función ecológica original de un ecosistema que fue degradado por actividades humanas.

Barreras

En general, en Latinoamérica se recomienda reforestar con especies nativas, evitando los monocultivos. Sin embargo, el material vegetal y/o semilla nativa es de difícil acceso. Es necesario aumentar la investigación en especies nativas, con el fin de mejorarlas y equilibrar la productividad y competitividad frente a las comerciales, pues existe el riesgo de usar una misma especie en el ecosistema y promover los monocultivos. Las especies comerciales tienen un crecimiento más rápido frente a las especies nativas; de modo que, los retornos económicos en las especies comerciales son a un menor plazo, esta condición hace más atractiva la reforestación con especies comerciales, exóticas a la región.

Cada uno de los eslabones de la cadena productiva (recolección de semillas, plantación, viverismo) requieren tecnificación; sin embargo, existen barreras en cada uno de estos eslabones.

El área de forestación actual está muy dispersa, no se han podido aglutinar a varios predios para generar impactos a escala de paisaje. Los pagos por servicios ambientales (PSA), asociados a la restauración ecológica, deben fortalecerse para no estar fragmentados y lograr un mayor impacto.

Debe existir un plan de mantenimiento posterior a la reforestación para asegurar el éxito en el tiempo, porque luego de 30 o 40 años las retribuciones económicas se acaban.

El mercado de la reforestación carece de un enfoque diferencial; por ejemplo, debería valorar las diferencias que existen en reforestar con un bosque de eucalipto y restaurar ecosistemas estratégicos como la selva amazónica, el impacto ambiental es diferente.

Las entidades gubernamentales del nivel subnacional deben fortalecer sus capacidades y conocimientos en estos temas. Por ejemplo, se requiere más información sobre las dinámicas económicas de la restauración, y mayor entendimiento de la restauración y su importancia.

Se requiere una política de bonos de carbono y mecanismos legales para hacer seguimiento y contraloría a estos bonos. Colombia cuenta con la plataforma de Registro Nacional de Reducción de Emisiones de Gases Efecto Invernadero "RENARE"; sin embargo, presenta varias fallas, el registro es voluntario, no hay control en el registro y se pueden presentar casos de doble contabilidad.

Requerimientos para su implementación

En Brasil se ha implementado un mecanismo para "conversión de multas". Los infractores ambientales, como empresas grandes que deben multas al Estado pueden tener descuentos por implementar proyectos de restauración o recuperación ambiental. Este mecanismo ha sido exitoso y continúa en aumento.

Mejorar la información y capacidades en torno a la reforestación y restauración de las entidades de gobierno como del sector privado. Incrementar la investigación para superar vacíos tecnológicos como el potencial de captura de especies nativas de la biodiversidad de países Latinoamericanos a partir de la restauración ecológica.

4.4.3 Biocarbón

Al ser una tecnología nueva para Latinoamérica, existen muchas barreras y vacíos en conocimiento.

Barreras

La tecnología para la producción de biocarbón necesita regulación para su implementación. En diferentes países se ha promovido la producción de biocarbón con tecnologías artesanales que no tienen control de las emisiones para su producción. En Colombia, aunque no se han promovido estas tecnologías, la Unidad de Planeación Minero-Energética (UPME) promueve la venta y combustión de biomásas, reconociendo que esta combustión genera Gases de Efecto Invernadero (GEI). No obstante, se debe reconocer que la tecnología óptima para la producción de biocarbón a través de pirólisis en un sistema cerrado (sin emisiones a la atmósfera) es de difícil acceso por ser costosa.

Actualmente no hay normativa que designe al biocarbón como “enmienda de suelo” y técnicamente, por ser una transformación termoquímica se puede designar como químico; por lo cual, se debería compostar para poder designarlo como orgánico.

En Colombia y en general en los países de Latinoamérica no se encontró la existencia de un mercado de biocarbón formal.

No todas las biomásas sirven para la producción de biocarbón, las ideales deben tener bajo contenido de humedad y alto contenido en lignina; si se parte de una biomasa húmeda el gasto energético en la transformación incrementa y el potencial de captura de carbono disminuye.

Hasta el momento, la producción de biocarbón sólo es productiva si se cuenta con grandes cantidades de biomásas óptimas concentradas en un mismo lugar; por lo cual, la producción de biocarbón está limitada a grandes industrias.

Requerimientos para su implementación

Se deben generar estándares sobre la dosificación de biocarbón, teniendo en cuenta los tipos de suelo, los tipos de cultivos y sus requerimientos. En Colombia, la empresa Sirius S.A. adelanta ensayos para definirlo en el cultivo de palma de aceite.

Existe una gran oportunidad para la puesta en marcha de esta tecnología incluyendo el proceso de pirólisis de biomasa residual de la agricultura y plantaciones forestales para reincorporarla al suelo y devolverla a su ciclo. Además, existen empresas que dentro de su modelo de negocio contemplan el mercado de carbono, esto les genera ingresos adicionales, además promueve la rentabilidad en co-beneficios; por ejemplo, en la compra y venta de carbono.

4.4.4 Agricultura orgánica

Barreras

El mercado para la agricultura orgánica es muy pequeño en ciertos países como Colombia y la mayoría está destinado a exportación.

Para los productores, pasar de un sistema de producción convencional a uno orgánico representa un alto riesgo en la productividad y mayores costos asociados principalmente a la fertilización; por ejemplo, reemplazar la fertilización de síntesis por una fertilización orgánica se traduce en una relación 1:15; es decir, un sistema orgánico requiere 15 veces más fuentes de nutrientes que el convencional.

Existen barreras burocráticas que no han permitido el despliegue de la cadena de los bioinsumos en Colombia.

Falta asistencia técnica y extensión rural para acompañar a los productores a incorporar esta tecnología en sus predios.

Requerimientos para su implementación

El cambio de tecnología de la agricultura convencional a agricultura orgánica requiere mayor educación e información con los productores, ya que implica pasar de un manejo curativo a un manejo preventivo. La capa orgánica de los cultivos con fertilización de síntesis tiende a disminuir; razón por la cual se resalta la necesidad de mejorar las condiciones de la agricultura orgánica, tanto en la fertilización como en el control de plagas; por ejemplo, es necesario reconocer los requisitos de manejo de plagas por medio de manejo preventivo.

Se propone promover sistemas agroforestales ligados con agricultura orgánica para potenciar los beneficios económicos y no económicos. Esta tecnología puede tener múltiples co-beneficios ligados a la biodiversidad y servicios ecosistémicos. Se deben fortalecer políticas públicas que promuevan sistemas productivos más sostenibles evitando los monocultivos y facilitando asistencia técnica a los pequeños productores.

4.4.5 Manejo del fuego / Control de incendios

Barreras

Existe desconocimiento entorno a la tecnología de manejo integrado del fuego, se considera que puede ser conflictivo y en contra de las tendencias globales. De igual forma, se reconocen pocas capacidades y equipamiento para enfrentar y controlar incendios forestales. Existen limitaciones en el uso tradicional como practica para renovación de praderas.

Requerimientos para su implementación

Se debe trabajar en redes hidráulicas para manejar incendios en Colombia y en censado remoto para identificación temprana del fuego. Aunque es una tecnología de bajo costo y técnicamente puede ser efectiva, se deben superar algunas limitaciones como:

Superar la barrera mediática.

Mejorar la transferencia tecnológica.

Fortalecer la financiación y las capacidades.

Incluir metas NDC a largo plazo para garantizar iniciativas a largo plazo.

4.4.6 Manejo del bosque

Barreras

Altos niveles de deforestación en Colombia y Brasil y en general en LAC.

Se debe desestimular las infracciones ambientales y esto podría lograrse por medio de multas, sanciones y otros instrumentos de control económico que permitan ir de una justicia punitiva hacia una justicia reparativa o restaurativa.

En Brasil se resalta alta burocracia para la concesión de manejo del bosque, lo que desestimula su aprovechamiento.

Requerimientos para su implementación

Las instituciones gubernamentales y órganos ambientales deben capacitarse y empoderarse para comprender al máximo el potencial de esta tecnología.

Es necesario avanzar en instrumentos de manejo y restauración forestal, así como mejorar los aspectos legislativos para acelerar la aprobación de los proyectos y en consecuencia, se requiere de inversión pública que vincule a la sociedad civil.

En Brasil existe una estrategia denominada Manejo Forestal Sostenible (MFS) que es considerada una de las principales alternativas para la conservación de la selva amazónica. El MFS presenta algunas barreras como la alta burocracia que incrementa los tiempos de concesión forestal y limita su implementación.

4.4.7 Otras tecnologías para tener en cuenta

- Gestión de humedales
- Agricultura regenerativa, Agricultura urbana
- Tecnologías para el uso eficiente del agua
- Conservación de suelos
- Prevención de incendios forestales
- Sistemas de manejo de pasturas
- Tecnologías de reducción de la desertificación
- Sistemas agrícolas bajos en carbono

4.4.8 Tecnologías que pueden actuar en conjunto

- Agricultura orgánica/regenerativa y biocarbón
- Agricultura orgánica y agricultura regenerativa
- Forestería y restauración ecológica
- Co-procesamiento, BECCS y Biocarbón
- Conservación del suelo y agroforestería
- Reforestación, restauración ecológica y sistemas silvopastoriles / agroforestales
- Reducción de la desertificación y agricultura baja en carbono
- Agroforestería y agricultura orgánica

4.4.9 Consideraciones finales sobre las LMT en el contexto de la cuenca amazónica

Los expertos coinciden en que el sector AFOLU es el de mayor oportunidad para la cuenca amazónica, pues al aplicar las tecnologías se le hace frente a la deforestación, además, se plantea la integración del sector AFOLU y el sector energético para generar impactos en los dos ámbitos. No obstante, es necesario promover la adopción de estas LMT a nivel territorial, pues la reforestación en la Amazonía no se está adoptando con tanta ambición como se quisiera. Uno de los ejemplos que se presentan como oportunidad para la promoción de sistemas regenerativos y bajos en emisiones para el sector agropecuario son las presiones en el mercado de la Unión Europea (UE) hacia la Amazonía brasilera, pues las compras de la UE incentivan a mejorar las prácticas en el uso del suelo.

La mirada hacia el 'escalamiento' de las LMT en los países amazónicos pasa por muchos retos contextuales, que requieren más un abordaje de lo nacional a lo subnacional (*top-down*), que de lo nacional a lo regional (*bottom up*). La realidad socioeconómica en la zona amazónica de los países es, muchas veces, más desafiante que en otras zonas más económicamente desarrolladas, pues a nivel subnacional es donde se presentan los mayores cuellos de botella que impiden el flujo de información y el desarrollo de las acciones; se destacan problemas de gobernanza, falta de coordinación interinstitucional y falta de extensionismo. Así que los retos, además de la implementación exitosa de las LMT, son garantizar una fuente de renta sostenible para las comunidades y población local amazónica, incluyendo, por ejemplo, mayor asistencia técnica, oferta de alternativas económicas a la deforestación, monitoreo y seguimiento a nivel local con relación a las LMT, infraestructura adecuada y fortalecimiento de capacidades locales. El escalamiento regional de las LMT vendría en consecuencia del mayor intercambio de experiencias locales y escuelas de campo, siempre que éstas también estén bien integradas a sus respectivos contextos nacionales. No obstante, algunos expertos consideran que el escalamiento regional en ALC es difícil, pues la Organización del Tratado de Cooperación Amazónica (OTCA) existe desde 1995 y lastimosamente no se han visto estrategias funcionales a nivel regional, su implementación la consideran baja y no está claro cómo se implementan los acuerdos, p.ej. los establecidos en la Cumbre Amazónica 2023.

4.5 Insumos para la interpretación de los modelos/escenarios climáticos para las LMT analizadas

El proyecto LANDMARC ha desarrollado modelos globales con base en escenarios climáticos, modelando las siguientes LMT: forestación /reforestación; agroforestería; mínima labranza; biochar/biocarbón; bioenergía con captura y almacenamiento de carbono (BECCS). Los resultados que serán presentados en el Taller se enfocan en la región de los países-miembros de la OTCA (Organización del Tratado de Cooperación Amazónica), posibilitando una discusión informada sobre el desempeño de cada LMT a corto, mediano y largo plazo, así como la definición de la ambición climática bajo cada escenario.

El sistema de los modelos globales de LANDMARC está diseñado para modelar los bucles de retroalimentación entre el uso de la tierra y el clima, evaluando los efectos de las LMT en las variables climáticas de una forma simplificada que también evita tiempo y costos asociados a la ejecución de los modelos de carbono completos. Para facilitar el entendimiento de los modelos que serán presentados en el Taller, discutiremos aquí dos conceptos-clave para los escenarios globales con base en los informes del IPCC (Panel Intergubernamental sobre el Cambio Climático).

4.5.1 Concepto-clave 1: Trayectorias Representativas de Concentración (Representative Concentration Pathways, RCP por sus siglas en inglés)

Las **Trayectorias Representativas de Concentración**¹ (**Representative Concentration Pathways, RCP** por sus siglas en inglés) se refieren a los escenarios que incluyen series temporales de emisiones y concentraciones de todo el conjunto de gases de efecto invernadero (GEI) y aerosoles y gases químicamente activos, así como uso del suelo/cobertura terrestre. La palabra “representativo” significa que cada RCP proporciona sólo uno de los muchos escenarios posibles que conducirían a las características específicas del *forzamiento radiativo*. Según Castillo et al. (2017), “un forzamiento radiativo es una medida de la influencia que un factor, en este caso las emisiones, tiene para alterar el equilibrio de la energía entrante y saliente en el sistema tierra-atmósfera, medida en vatios por metro cuadrado (W/m^2)”.

El término “trayectoria” subraya el hecho de que no sólo interesan los niveles de concentración a largo plazo, sino también la trayectoria seguida a lo largo del tiempo para llegar a ese resultado. Los RCP se utilizaron para desarrollar proyecciones climáticas al Quinto Informe del Proyecto de Intercomparación de Modelos Acoplados (*Fifth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, CMIP5* por sus siglas en inglés) del IPCC.

Originalmente, los RCP comprendían cuatro proyecciones, que iban de la **RCP 2.6 a la RCP 8.5**, y tras la adopción del Acuerdo de París se les añadió la **RCP 1.9** para representar trayectorias de mitigación compatibles con el límite de calentamiento de $1,5^{\circ}C$ (**Tabla 3**). Los valores se refieren al forzamiento radiativo en vatios/ m^2 a finales de siglo en comparación con la época preindustrial, por ejemplo, $2,6 W/m^2$ en el caso del RCP 2.6. A título comparativo, una duplicación de la concentración atmosférica de CO_2 con respecto a la época preindustrial, es decir, de unas 280 partes por millón (ppm) de moléculas de aire a 560 ppm, equivaldría a un forzamiento radiativo de $3,7 W/m^2$. En 2016, las concentraciones de CO_2 alcanzaron las 400 ppm, y el forzamiento radiativo de todas las influencias antropogénicas sobre el sistema climático se estimó en unos $2,3 \pm 1 w/m^2$ en 2011.

Tabla 3. Relación entre las Trayectorias Representativas de Concentración (RCP) y la temperatura ($^{\circ}C$).

RCP	Forzamiento	Temperatura	Tendencia de Emisiones
1.9	1.9 W/m^2	$\sim 1.5^{\circ}C$	Emisiones Muy Fuertemente Declinantes
2.6	2.6 W/m^2	$\sim 2.0^{\circ}C$	Emisiones Fuertemente Declinantes

¹ Fuentes consultadas: Glosario del IPCC, disponible en el siguiente enlace: <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/chapter/glossary/>; Climate Data, disponible en el siguiente enlace: <https://climatedata.ca/resource/understanding-shared-socio-economic-pathways-ssps/>

RCP	Forzamiento	Temperatura	Tendencia de Emisiones
4.5	4.5 W/m ²	~2.4 °C	Emisiones Lentamente Declinantes
6.0	6.0 W/m ²	~2.8 °C	Emisiones Estabilizadas
8.5	8.5 W/m ²	~4.3 °C	Emisiones en Aumento

Nota. Fuente: adaptado de [ClimateScenarios \(s.f.\)](#)

Los niveles de forzamiento radiativo pertinentes para el Acuerdo de París son 2,6 W/m², que conducen a un calentamiento muy inferior a 2°C, y 1,9 W/m², que limita el calentamiento a 1,5°C o menos. Esto se recoge en los escenarios RCP 2,6 y RCP 1,9.

4.5.2 Concepto-clave 2: Trayectorias Socioeconómicas Compartidas (*Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, SSP por sus siglas en inglés*)

Las **Trayectorias Socioeconómicas Compartidas² (*Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, SSP* por sus siglas en inglés)** se desarrollaron para complementar las Trayectorias Representativas de Concentración (RCP por sus siglas en inglés) con distintos retos socioeconómicos para la adaptación y la mitigación. Los escenarios basados en el SSP se utilizaron en la serie más reciente de experimentos con modelos climáticos, conocida como Sexta Fase del Proyecto de Intercomparación de Modelos Acoplados (*Sixth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, CMIP6* por sus siglas en inglés). Los resultados de estos experimentos con modelos climáticos sirvieron de base para la evaluación del cambio climático pasado y futuro en el Sexto Informe de Evaluación (*Assessment Report, AR6*, por sus siglas en inglés) del IPCC. Basadas en cinco narrativas, las SSP describen futuros socioeconómicos alternativos en ausencia de intervención de la política climática, que comprenden la sustentabilidad (SSP1), la fragmentación (SSP3), la desigualdad (SSP4), el desarrollo basado en combustibles fósiles (SSP5) y el nivel intermedio de desafíos (SSP2) (**Figura 4**). Las cinco narrativas de escenarios basados en el SSP utilizados en el CMIP6 pueden clasificarse en dos grandes ejes: retos para la mitigación y retos para la adaptación. La combinación de escenarios socioeconómicos basados en el SSP y las proyecciones climáticas basadas en las RCP proporciona un marco integrador para el análisis del impacto climático y las políticas.

² Fuentes consultadas: Glosario del IPCC, disponible en el siguiente enlace: <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/chapter/glossary/>; Climate Data, disponible en el siguiente enlace: <https://climatedata.ca/resource/understanding-shared-socio-economic-pathways-ssps/>

Figura 4. Panorama de las SSP: espacio de desafíos que identifica cinco tipos de escenarios con diferentes retos socioeconómicos de mitigación y adaptación

Nota. Fuente: retirado de (Escoto Castillo et al., 2017)

Escoto Castillo (2017, p. 676) destacan las siguientes consideraciones con relación a la **Figura 4**: “Los escenarios que combinan niveles bajos de desafíos de mitigación y adaptación son los de la Trayectoria Socioeconómica Compartida 1 (**SSP1**), con la narrativa de ‘sustentabilidad’ ya que asumen: bajo crecimiento de la población, alto crecimiento económico, altos niveles de educación, gobernabilidad, una sociedad globalizada, cooperación internacional, desarrollo tecnológico y conciencia ambiental. Contrario a la SSP1, los escenarios de la **SSP3** se describen como de ‘fragmentación’. Éstos asumen crecimiento poblacional alto y desarrollo económico bajo, niveles de educación inferiores, y una sociedad regionalizada y con poca conciencia ambiental, por lo que representan un nivel alto de desafíos para la adaptación y la mitigación.

En la narrativa de ‘desigualdad’ de la **SSP4**, la tecnología avanza en los países desarrollados, pero no toda la población logra beneficiarse de ello, lo cual representa un nivel alto para la adaptación. En contrapartida, los escenarios de la **SSP5** asumen un bajo crecimiento en la población, un elevado crecimiento económico y un alto desarrollo humano; sin embargo, la conciencia ambiental y la dependencia de los combustibles fósiles es todavía muy alta, por lo que representa un elevado nivel de desafío para la mitigación. Es decir, *las trayectorias que son relativamente más optimistas son la SSP1 y la SSP5, y las relativamente más pesimistas son la SSP3 y la SSP4*. Finalmente, los escenarios de la **SSP2** se establecen *de manera intermedia* entre los que corresponden a la SSP1 y la SSP3”.

En conclusión, los SSP son fundamentales para la adaptación al clima y el diseño de políticas por dos razones principales. En primer lugar, estas trayectorias describen las posibles condiciones

socioeconómicas, los cambios en el uso del suelo y otros factores climáticos de origen humano que influyen en las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero, afectando así al *forzamiento radiativo*. El forzamiento radiativo describe la cantidad de exceso de energía atrapada en el sistema climático de la Tierra debido a la variación de un factor de cambio climático, como las concentraciones de GEI.

En segundo lugar, los SSP describen las características socioeconómicas que influyen en las emisiones de GEI (y, por consiguiente, en el forzamiento radiativo) de una manera normalizada, dando una indicación de las vías sociales asociadas a diferentes niveles de calentamiento. Además, las posibles medidas de mitigación pueden "aplicarse" dentro de estos escenarios socioeconómicos de referencia para evaluar su eficacia en la consecución de diversos objetivos, como tener una "buena oportunidad" de cumplir los compromisos del Acuerdo de París limitando el aumento de la temperatura global muy por debajo de 2°C con respecto a los niveles preindustriales (escenario SSP1-1.9).

4.5.3 ¿Cómo se diferencian y se complementan los escenarios de SSP y RCP?

Cuando se combinan los escenarios de RCP con los de SSP, se genera un marco sólido para explorar el espacio de las futuras trayectorias de mitigación en términos de diferentes niveles de rigor y diferentes supuestos-clave sobre el desarrollo socioeconómico. La **Figura 5** ilustra este marco sólido derivado de la combinación de los escenarios de RCP con los de SSP para la generación y comunicación de las proyecciones climáticas globales.

Figura 5. La secuencia de información utilizada para proyectar los niveles futuros de cambio climático, combinando los escenarios de SSP y RCP.

Nota. Fuente: adaptado de [Climate Data \(s.f.\)](#).

Los escenarios basados en los SSP refinan aún más los anteriores escenarios de concentración de gases de efecto invernadero conocidos como RCP. Los RCP se diseñaron explícitamente para que la comunidad de modeladores climáticos pudiera explorar los efectos de diferentes trayectorias de emisiones o concentraciones de emisiones (que dan lugar a diversos valores de Forzamiento Radiativo). Las características socioeconómicas utilizadas para definir los RCP no están estandarizadas, lo que dificulta la asignación de cambios sociales como la población, la educación y las políticas

gubernamentales a objetivos climáticos, como mantener el calentamiento global muy por debajo de los 2°C. Los SSP abordan esta cuestión definiendo cómo las opciones sociales pueden conducir a cambios en el Forzamiento Radiativo a finales de siglo. Como tales, los SSP amplían los RCP para permitir una comparación estandarizada de las opciones de la sociedad y sus niveles resultantes de cambio climático.

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ANNEX D: REGIONAL WORKSHOPS

ANNEX D1: DETAILS OF REGIONAL WORKSHOP DESIGN

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ANNEX D1 - DETAILS OF REGIONAL WORKSHOP DESIGN

Overall design concept, format, and timing for Landmarc workshops

There are four parts, each with some framing presentations and background information, followed by a hands-on segment where participants co-produce the regional level results. With breaks, it can thus be accomplished in two separate half days (more suitable for online or hybrid workshop) or can be done in one full day (more suitable for a full day in-person workshop). If less than full day is allotted, then the times below would need to be adjusted.

Part I: Introduction to the workshop: policies, scaling up/ambition, regional engagement

The first goal of this session is to choose an appropriate LMT portfolio for scaling up. A portfolio in this context is a simple algorithm that proceeds on the basis of implementing 3 LMTs based on the highest overall perceived benefits for the region. Baseline modelling results are provided at the start of the session.

**Check with participants if OK to record (registration).

- (1) 5 min: introduction of participants
- (2) 10 min: overview of LMTs and regional/policy context
- (3) 10 min: overview of Climate ambition exercise
- (4) 10 min: overview of Regional Engagement exercise
- (5) 10 min: Questions/discussion
- (6) 45 min: modelling results and discussion including baseline results (which includes no LMTs other than those historically included) and two scenarios (moderate and high ambition)

Information in the background/inception document will generally not be discussed or presented.

Part II: Climate Ambition for LMTs

Participants will characterise the LMT portfolio that has the most benefits, using the technical potentials estimated by the models, considering various non-technical factors, and recognising that the higher ambition scenarios will normally include applications and/or LMTs that are more costly and more difficult.

Break-out groups: three break-out groups is optimal, but avoid splitting by LMT, choose a group that is diverse with respect to LMT knowledge and interest. This division also allows to have the same structure in a more logical way for the ambition segment AND the regional engagement segment, considering that the latter needs mechanisms that work for multiple LMTs and their interactions. Furthermore, it allows consistency across regions since the choice of LMTs will be different for each region. It will be ideal to have 5-6 persons in a group, so all participants can talk and discuss.

<p>Key questions:</p> <p>LMTs</p>	Scaling options (how to upscale – barriers and enablers)	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards (note differences across LMTs – how to address them?)	Co-benefits (especially adaptation, biodiversity/ecosystems, livelihoods)	Ambition (baseline, moderate, high) The selected LMTs, one by one, will be discussed considering the various levels of ambition as per the model (baseline, moderate (RCP2.6), and high (RCP 1.9). What does the LMT implementation look like at various levels of ambition? Is LMT implementation possible at all levels of ambition?	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100 How might the expected scale, risks, and co-benefits change between the two different time periods?
Afforestation and forest management (Fixed by SEI)					
One LMT from the other 4 being modelled (Fixed by SEI, for each region)					
LMT chosen by participants, as seen relevant to the region (Selected by participants in each breakout group)					
Missing LMTs (for further research) (Selected by participants)					
Interactions across these LMTs (linkages, synergies, conflicts)—e.g., competition for land, water, biomass, or inputs	Is the scale changed due to interactions?	Is the scale changed due to interactions?	Are co-benefits changed due to interactions?		

Part III: Regional Engagement for scaling up LMTs

This session will emphasise how regional engagement and cooperation can facilitate higher ambition for LMTs through the means of implementation (technology transfer, capacity building, finance) as well as regional integration and cooperation more broadly (lowering barriers to trade, harmonised regulations, integrated carbon markets, etc.). The concept of regional engagement in this context must also acknowledge cooperation across regions, due to the global nature of mitigation and the Paris Agreement. Participants will develop qualifiers or characteristics for low, moderate, and high regional engagement contexts. Where existing regional engagement is significant, such as in the EU, the first row (low regional engagement) is not considered relevant, as in the example table below.

Independent of whether participants are invited to developed qualifiers completely independent from the consortium or the facilitators, it might be useful to think through some qualifiers beforehand, to provide session facilitators with some potential indicators/qualifiers to guide the conversation. The following table includes some qualifiers/indicators, largely borrowed from the most integrated space of independent countries, the EU.

Break-out groups: same as in session 2.

This table will be used to guide the discussions. Each of the qualifiers mentioned in table 1 can be discussed here, but we suggest giving the participants the liberty of discussing other indicators as they see fit. The facilitator should mention just the three broad categories first. If the discussion does not get into gear and/or if participants misunderstand which qualifiers they are supposed to talk to, the facilitator could give some examples from table 1 (or use the qualifiers in the parentheses in the categories column below). Ideally, each category should be discussed but you can let the participants discuss the qualifiers that they feel is most relevant.

Table 2 – Elicitation table

Categories	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question
	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation (includes trade, tariffs, standards/certification, carbon markets)						
Formal governance mechanisms (bilateral & interregional working groups/coordination bodies, agreements on land, forests etc., pooling of resources [regional funds])						
Research cooperation & technology transfer (research partnerships, capacity building, networks etc.)						

Table 1 - potential qualifiers and indicators

These indicators might help facilitators to stimulate discussions when participants are reluctant. However, as first prompt, giving only those in table 2 (the elicitation table, see below) is sufficient.

Qualifier/Indicator	Description	Source
Trade across borders	Economic integration is usually measured by this indicator; could be used specifically for biomass and other LMT relevant products	(Capannelli 2009)
FDI	Idem, used to measure economic integration, could be used to see, how much Thailand invests in Cambodia and vice versa; an argument could then be made that more FDI, especially from richer (China, Thailand) to poorer countries might strengthen LMT uptake	(Capannelli 2009)
Trade Agreements	Idem, often used; maybe specific trade agreements for biomass or LMT products could be devised although this seems highly unlikely	(Capannelli 2009)
Lower tariffs	ASEAN countries could decide to lower trade barriers and tariffs for certain LMT based products	
Agreements specific to LMTs and/or technology transfer	This might be relevant for costly or infrastructure heavy LMTs such as BECCS, but maybe bilateral or multi-lateral (ASEAN) cooperation agreements could facilitate the scaling of this and other technologies	
Regional Learning Networks	Are often thought of important to spur innovation and for the exchange of best practices and lessons learnt; on the European level, and from a public policy perspective, those learning networks include the KICs; from a SME perspective, the European Enterprise Network might be a replicable example especially when it comes to aggregate marketable products from LMT value chains	(Fumasoli and Rossi 2021)
Regional Research Cooperations	Are often thought of important to spur innovation and for the exchange of best practices and lessons learnt; examples from Europe include CERN, EMBL etc.	
Political bilateral or multilateral working groups	Some EU countries have ministerial working groups which sit together and exchange on issues and try to find bilateral solutions such as for climate change issues (there also was/is Franco-German inter-ministerial working group dedicated to energy). Similar working groups could be established in ASEAN countries on LMT issues or mitigation issues in general.	(CEW 2018)
Coordination bodies and networks on technical issues	In the EU, several bodies exist that coordinate a more harmonised and European response to more technical issues such as electricity grid management (ENTSO-E) or the maintenance of gas flows (ENTSO-G); another is the EUMETNET, which is a network body of EU met offices. Similar mechanisms could be established in ASEAN, especially on energy which might impact LMT development (especially for BECCS). Having better weather forecasts might also positively impact LMTs and therefore, more cooperation between met offices might be good.	
Pooling of resources	In the EU, several initiatives exist to co-finance so called projects of common interest (PCI) for instance to increase energy security. These projects are finance by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF); similar facilities and projects could be established in ASEAN countries, for instance for carbon capture and storage or for pilot projects to showcase LMTs such as functioning agroforestry systems etc.	
Carbon Markets	Either ETS or carbon offset markets	

Part IV: Synthesis for construction of Regional Narratives

In this plenary session, participants will synthesise the results from the previous 3 sessions to develop the basic concepts or inputs for a set of narratives that define a regional LMT portfolio for various levels of climate ambition (as per the model results) and various levels of regional engagement (as per the previous session). This is expected to consist of four narratives altogether, with two in each of the columns for moderate and high ambition, as suggested in the matrix below. This is the final result of the workshop.

Regional Engagement	Baseline	Moderate ambition	High ambition
Current	N/A (taken as input)	Narrative 1	Narrative 2
Improved	N/A (taken as input)	Narrative 3	Narrative 4
High	N/A	Narrative 5	Narrative 6

ANNEX D2 - LAND USE MODELLING ASSUMPTIONS AND RESULTS

Annex D2: Modelling Assumptions and Results by region for the Coupled Model (LandSHIFT-G and LPJ-Guess)

The preliminary modelling assumption used for the various LMTs in the scenarios “Reference”, “Moderate Ambition”, and “High Ambition” area summarized in Table A 1. All model inputs were specified as time series on country level. Time series were generated in 5-year time steps from 2015 to 2100. Input time series, which were not calculated from time-varying results of the Integrated Assessment Model MESSAGE-GLOBIOM or other datasets (see Deliverable D6.3), were generated by linear interpolation of values specified for key time steps (eg 2015, 2050, 2100). Assumptions either were made globally or were the results of calculation described in Deliverable D6.3 on the country level. For brevity, such country-specific values are not given in tables but regional aggregates are shown in Figures ????.

For each focus region of the workshops, an overview of the preliminary model inputs derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM is given (Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16). Preliminary results of the corresponding simulation runs with the coupled model system are shown as time series of land use change (Figures A 2, A 7, A 12, and A 17) and its implications for carbon pools and fluxes (Figures A 3, A 8, A 13, and A 18). See Table A 2 for a description of the output variables shown. Maps showing the spatial variability of differences in land use and carbon pools between the LMT scaling scenario and the Reference in 2095 are shown for Moderate Ambition (Figures A 4, A 9, A 14, and A 19) and High Ambition (Figures A 5, A 10, A 15, and A 20).

Table A 1 Overview of preliminary modelling assumptions

LMT	Model input	Year(s)	Reference	Moderate Ambition	High Ambition
Afforestation	Area afforested by country	all	for regional aggregates see “Afforestation area” in Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16		
No-till	Share in cropland of annual crops	2015	0	country spec. initial values (D6.3)	
		2050	0		2/3
		2100	0	2/3	2/3
Agroforestry	Average yield improvements for cash crops ¹	2015	0%	0%	0%
		2100	0%	25%	25%
BECCS	Fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for CCS AND biochar	all	for regional aggregates see “Fraction of CCS/biochar” in Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16		

¹ Effective country average of relative yield improvements achieved by, e.g., less heat stress for crops due to shadings trees resulting from the partial production of a crop in agroforestry systems

	Sub-fraction of above for CCS only	all	100%	50%	50%
	Area 2 nd generation bioenergy crops	all	for regional aggregates see “Cropland area” (dotted=bioenergy) in Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16		
Biochar	Fraction of bioenergy feedstock used for CCS AND biochar	all	for regional aggregates see “Fraction of CCS/biochar” in Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16		
	Sub-fraction of above for CCS only	all	100%	50%	50%
	Area 2 nd generation bioenergy crops	all	for regional aggregates see “Cropland area” (dotted=bioenergy) in Figures A 1, A 6, A 11, and A 16		

Table A 2 Description of important LPJ-GUESS output variables

Variable	Description
cVeg	Carbon mass in vegetation
cSoil	Carbon mass in model soil pool
cLitter	Carbon mass in litter pool
cLand	Total carbon in all terrestrial carbon pools
cBECCS	Total carbon accumulated from BECCS
cBiochar	Total carbon stored in Biochar
cLandAll	Total carbon on land including BECCS/Biochar
fBiofuel	Production of biofuels, replacing fossil fuels
nbp	Carbon mass flux out of atmosphere due to net biospheric production on land

North Europe

Figure A 1 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM. Values aggregated for EU-27 countries.

Figure A 2 EU 27 results: Land use for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region.

Figure A 3 EU 27 results: Carbon pools and fluxes for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region. Note: cLandAll = cVeg + cSoil + cBECCS + cBiochar (+ cLitter)

Figure A 4 EU-27 results: Differences between the Reference and Moderate Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Figure A 5 EU-27 results: Differences between the Reference and High Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Asia

Figure A 6 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM. Values aggregated for ASEAN countries.

Figure A 7 ASEAN regional results: Land use for Reference , Moderate Ambtion, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region.

Figure A 8 ASEAN regional results: Carbon pools and fluxes for Reference , Moderate Ambtion, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region. Note: cLandAll = cVeg + cSoil + cBECCS + cBiochar (+ cLitter)

Figure A 9 ASEAN regional results: Differences between the Reference and Moderate Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Figure A 10 ASEAN regional results: Differences between the Reference and High Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Latin America

Figure A 11 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM. Values aggregated for ACTO countries.

Figure A 12 ACTO regional results: Land use for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region.

Figure A 13 ACTO regional results: Carbon pools and fluxes for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region. Note: cLandAll = cVeg + cSoil + cBECCS + cBiochar (+ cLitter)

Figure A 14 ACTO regional results: Differences between the Reference and Moderate Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Figure A 15 ACTO regional results: Differences between the Reference and High Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Africa

Figure A 16 Summary of the input data on the development of the agricultural sector used as context for LMT deployment derived from MESSAGE-GLOBIOM. Values aggregated for EAC countries.

Figure A 17 EAC regional results: Land use for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region.

Figure A 18 EAC regional results: Carbon pools and fluxes for Reference , Moderate Ambition, and High Ambition scenarios given as percentage of the total land area in the region. Note: $cLandAll = cVeg + cSoil + cBECCS + cBiochar (+ cLitter)$

Figure A 19 EAC regional results: Differences between the Reference and Moderate Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

Figure A 20 EAC regional results: Differences between the Reference and High Ambition scenario in 2095 of (top) land use fraction and (bottom) different carbon pools

ANNEX D3 - WORKSHOP REPORT FOR AFRICA

1 Introduction and Overview

1.1 Setting and participant profile

The East Africa Landmarc workshop was held on 21st November 2023 at the International Centre for Research in Agroforestry, Nairobi Campus. The workshop brought together a diverse group of stakeholders across the region to review and evaluate land-based mitigation options in East Africa, focusing on three elements:

- Identifying and characterizing a regional portfolio of land-based mitigation options.
- Evaluating how ambitions for land-based mitigation can be raised in the region; and
- Offering recommendations as to how regional engagement (as well as regional and transnational cooperation) can facilitate such higher ambitions.

The workshop was a hybrid with some participants joining online. This also included the modelling experts who joined the workshop virtually. Table 1 shows the profile of the participants.

Table 1: Regional Stakeholders for EA workshop

	Sector	Gender	Mode of participation	LMT	Country of expertise
1.	Research	Male	Physical	AFOLU	Regional
2.	Research	Male	Physical	AFOLU	Regional
3.	Academia	Female	Online	Biochar	Kenya
4.	Research	Female	Physical	Soil carbon sequestration	DRC
5.	NGO	Male	Physical	Soil carbon sequestration	Kenya
6.	NGO	Male	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Uganda
7.	NGO	Male	Physical	Biochar	Kenya
8.	Research	Female	Physical	Agroforestry	Kenya
9.	Research	Female	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Regional
10.	Research	Male	Physical	Conservation Agriculture	Kenya
11.	NGO	Male	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Regional
12.	Private	Male	Physical	Agroforestry	Kenya
13.	Government	Male	Physical	Land use governance and policy	Kenya
14.	NGO	Male	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Regional
15.	NGO	Male	Physical	Biochar	Regional
16.	Research	Male	Physical	Agroforestry	Kenya

17.	Research	Male	Physical	Biochar	Kenya
18.	Research	Male	Physical	Afforestation	Kenya
19.	Research	Male	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Kenya
20.	Research	Female	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Kenya
21.	NGO	Male	Physical	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Regional
22.	Government	Male	Online	Afforestation and Agroforestry	Tanzania

1.2 Regional focus

The region's rapid economic growth, with an average annual GDP growth rate of 6.45%, is highly consistent with emissions in terms of trends, with economic growth linked to emissions. Since 2010, the rate of increase in emissions has accelerated and gradually exceeded the rate of GDP growth, without aggressive action, future growth per unit of GDP in East African countries will come at the cost of higher emissions (Ntiamoah, et al. 2023). Core drivers of CO2 emissions growth are economic and population growth, resulting in 13Mt and 11Mt of emissions respectively, accounting for 27% and 23% of total emissions (Sun et al. 2022). In terms of total emissions and evolutionary trends for the region, emissions in East Africa have been rising at an average annual rate of 6.03%, nearly tripling from 17.6Mt in 2000 to 47.6Mt in 2017 and showing a two-stage exponential growth pattern with 2010 as the turning point (Sun et al. 2022).

Land- based climate mitigation measures, also known as Agriculture, Forestry, and other Land Uses (AFOLU) mitigation or natural climate solutions have gained significant attention and importance in public and private sector climate strategies and policies in East Africa. Most countries in the region have included AFOLU measures in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement, by specifically listing actions or by including the land sector in their broader GHG reduction targets (Crumpler et al., 2019).

Collectively, AFOLU- related NDC actions make up about 25% of planned GHG reductions in 2030 (Grassi et al., 2021), with most focus on reducing deforestation. Achieving climate targets and addressing other land- related challenges synergistically at national levels remains a challenge in the region. The success of different policies and implementation of land- based measures is dependent on enabling conditions and barriers that vary greatly by country. Available funding and economic incentives, governance and institutional capacity, technological capacity, geophysical capacity, socio- cultural context, and environmental- ecological conditions all make implementation more or less likely (de Coninck et al., 2018).

A study by Roe et al. (2021) shows that the highest cost- effective mitigation potential in East Africa comes from reducing deforestation, then afforestation and reforestation, sequestering soil organic carbon in grasslands, shifting diets, and agroforestry. Across the countries, the DRC has the most cost- effective mitigation potential at about 16% of Africa's potential. The DRC is followed by Tanzania where land- based emissions are largely driven by deforestation from shifting agriculture, "forest protection" measures present the highest cost- effective mitigation potential.

The Democratic Republic of Congo is characterized by relatively low fossil fuel emissions and high AFOLU emissions (Schwingshackl et al. 2022). DRC has the potential to generate surplus AFOLU mitigation, largely

through the protection of forests and other ecosystems that can enable the country to achieve net negative emissions by mid- century (Ajonina et al. 2014).

East Africa region faces a series of feasibility challenges that undermine the deployment and scaling up of mitigation action: limited national financial resources, external financial support, and technical, jurisdictional, and institutional capacity; as well as the absence of policies and incentives that adequately addresses competing sectoral interests (mining, agriculture, and forestry). Activating the region's mitigation potential will require ad

Addressing drivers of deforestation such as commercial agriculture, subsistence farming, or wood fuel harvesting, relates closely to challenges at the nexus of food security, rural development, energy supply, and forest conservation (Shapiro et al. 2021; Namubamba et al. 2023).

2 Regional Modeling Results

2.1 Assumptions for models

Afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, no-tillage, biochar were the LMTs modelled for the East Africa region. Refer to the assumptions and model parameters given in deliverable 6.3.

2.2 Overview on modeling results

The modeling approach involved a simplified setup, specifically coupling the land shift model to the dynamic vegetation model instead of a complete climate model. In these simulations, the vegetation model responded to atmospheric climate data derived from a prior coupled run with climate forcers, aligning with the trajectory of the moderate ambition case. The dynamic vegetation model simulated various ecological processes, such as primary production, plant growth, soil biochemistry, and disturbances like fire and land use changes, considering inputs like climate, land use changes, management practices, background atmosphere, and nitrogen deposition. Sub grid variability was accounted for through patches representing cropland, pasture, and natural vegetation, addressing variations in biomass and disturbances.

Key LPJ-GUESS output variables included carbon mass in vegetation (cVeg), carbon in soil (cSoil), carbon in the litter pool (cLitter), and total carbon in terrestrial pools (cLand). New variables for Land Management Technologies (LMTs), such as BECCs and Biochar, were introduced. Biofuels, represented by the Biofuel variable, aimed to replace fossil fuels and contributed to a net negative carbon sink. Net Biome Production (NBP) reflected the integrated carbon mass flux from the atmosphere due to different land processes.

Figure 1: Land use for Reference Case + 2 Scenarios for East Africa

Figure 2: Carbon in Land/Biomass for Reference Case + 2 Scenarios for East Africa

At the regional level, changes in land use and carbon stocks were explored, particularly in Eastern Africa. Contrasts between the moderate ambition and reference scenarios at the end of the century highlighted significant decreases in cropland, notably in Tanzania, Kenya, and South Sudan, while natural vegetation experienced changes indicative of afforestation or avoided deforestation. The high ambition scenario demonstrated spatial patterns like the moderate ambition case but with a stronger increase in natural vegetation in specific regions. Regional averages for the East African Community area revealed subtle shifts in land cover and significant decreases in pasture, particularly in LMT scenarios. Carbon dynamics exhibited moderate growth in the reference scenario, with LMT scenarios showing higher carbon increases, emphasizing the contributions of vegetation carbon changes, biofuels, biochar, and BEX to global carbon sequestration.

On a global scale, LMT scenarios illustrated net afforestation, reduced cropland and pasture, and notable carbon sequestration in regions such as South America, India, and Southeast Asia, emphasizing the global significance of BEX and biofuels in carbon mitigation. In summary, the LMT scenarios showcased potential for increased carbon sequestration, with avoided deforestation, afforestation, biofuels, biochar, and BEX playing crucial roles globally. Further analysis will delve into specific dynamics and regional variations.

The scenarios used also assume that food demand is consistently met, with no shortage. To achieve predefined emissions, integrated assessment models consider various factors, including climate policies and assumptions like global dietary shifts away from heavy meat consumption. This shift frees up cropland, especially as global trade plays a role in food consumption. The output from prominent integrated assessment models indicates a significant decrease in the area needed for food production, alongside a substantial increase in cropping system productivity, ensuring no unmet demand for food.

Figure 3: Carbon difference for 2 Scenarios compared to Reference case for East Africa

2.3 Context for discussion and use of modeling results

The following issues in the table below were raised by the participants regarding the modelling results:

Issues raised	Responses from the modelers
<p>The participant wanted to know whether the decision to exclusively focus on purpose-grown crops for biochar was driven by the intention to maximize carbon buildup in agricultural soil, considering that the current approach may yield minimal results. With reference to a recently published paper highlighting the underestimated potential for biochar sequestration from crop residues in tropical Africa, the participant wanted to know if there was a consideration for a more integrated approach that incorporates both biological and pyrogenic loops. According to the participant, the research underscored the potential advantages of redirecting carbon residues through the biological loop, contributing to enhanced soil fertility and a land-neutral carbon removal strategy. In the broader context, the participant asked how such strategies align with the overarching goal of achieving a 150% yield increase to conserve land for forests.</p>	<p>The model is nearly completed, but there are aspects that haven't been addressed. The decision to primarily focus on crop residues was influenced by the perception that it might offer a small contribution compared to purposely grown crops. However, considering recent feedback, there is a growing conviction that incorporating purposely grown crops into the analysis, as suggested, may be valuable. The challenge lies in determining the proportion of crop residues to convert to biochar and whether this should be a widespread practice or site-specific. Additionally, reliable estimates for the conversion of crop residues to biochar are needed, and further feedback on these considerations would be highly appreciated. The challenge is in simulating how biochar improves soil fertility because of the tremendous work involved. Global vegetation models have not been used for this.</p>
<p>The participant wanted to know how soil moisture was quantified in the model, whether it was a constant number or zero. If soil moisture was quantified, did the model consider soil depth; and on the crop photosynthetic pathways, whether the two captured the C3 and C4 plants. The participant noted that data can be obtained and hence the need to quantify soil moisture in the model.</p>	<p>The soil moisture remained as it is because there are not many data sets on soil.</p>
<p>According to the model, there was no CO₂ feedback to climate, the participant wanted to know if it were possible to initialize the process of the feedback, and if so, if there would be big variation when one switches on the feedback process</p>	<p>It was explained that due to restrained resources, simplified models that do not give feedback from CO₂ were used. It was noted that the model diagnosed the CO₂ sequestration potential but needed a fully coupled run.</p>
<p>The participants wanted to know how water cycling as well as forest fires were captured in the model and if this can be captured in the model going forward.</p>	<p>It was noted that water cycle and forest fires were addressed by the global climate model. However, lateral transport of water through rivers was not simulated; instead, water moves from land to the ocean and into the atmosphere. Forest fires are represented simplified, with higher drought conditions correlating with increased occurrences. The project also investigates heightened drought risks in LMT areas, particularly in Eastern Kenya.</p>
<p>The participant questioned why the model results showed carbon for Congo shared similarities with the East African Community (EAC) as a whole despite having a substantial forest cover.</p>	<p>It was explained that Congo, characterized by its moist tropical forest, exhibits significantly higher carbon content compared to the rest of East Africa. Nevertheless, due to extensive land use changes in the reference scenario, much of the East African community experiences carbon loss, and the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies contributes to carbon gains, fostering a more sustainable future.</p>

<p>One participant noted that a similar study was undertaken in Kenya with the objective of conveying the results to policymakers. However, there was concern about the technical complexity of the content. Therefore, a web interface was developed to simplify the information for policymakers. The participant wanted to know how the results of the model would be simplified for use by decision makers in East Africa and how the communication products of the modelling results will be accessed by all stakeholders and the decision makers</p>	<p>It was explained that there was a prototype for an interface in the early stages of the project, which was later abandoned for internal development work. However, in other project components, there will be a climate atlas designed to showcase significant results, highlighting climate risks and sequestration potential specifically tailored for policymakers. The project acknowledges its expertise in climate and land use modeling. Other team members will transform the information into more understandable formats for different audiences.</p>
<p>The practicality of the model results was questioned especially with the reality of the East African region. The participant wanted to know if the assumptions used were informed by any background research in East Africa and if the experts assessed the practicality of the scenarios for adoption by policymakers and local communities, given the significant decline in crop land area indicated in the model.</p> <p>According to the participant, the model results have implications for crop production and food availability making the scenarios not realistic in terms of adoption. It was noted that the assumptions such as change of diet and reducing cropland to give way to the forests may be unrealistic in the context of East Africa. Advising reduction of crop land for afforestation may not easily work. Various levels of uncertainties need to be addressed to convince policy makers to act.</p>	<p>The experts explained that the scenarios assume that food demand is consistently met, with no shortage. To achieve predefined emissions, integrated assessment models consider various factors, including climate policies and assumptions like global dietary shifts away from heavy meat consumption. This shift frees up cropland, especially as global trade plays a role in food consumption. The output from prominent integrated assessment models indicates a significant decrease in the area needed for food production, alongside a substantial increase in cropping system productivity, ensuring no unmet demand for food.</p>
<p>The participants wanted to know if the assumptions made regarding changes in agricultural areas were feasible and if that remains abstract.</p>	<p>For afforestation – Following the results from the integrated assessment model, changes in agricultural areas, including cropland and pastureland, are observed. Comparing these changes to the reference scenario allows for the identification of areas potentially suitable for afforestation, contingent on a genuine increase in forest cover. Confidence in these calculations is tied to the realism of changes in the agricultural sector. The rest of the changes, compared to the reference scenario, essentially involve avoided deforestation rather than afforestation, presenting a different scenario from the current situation. The main challenge lies in accurately assessing the realism of these agricultural changes.</p>
<p>The participants noted that the model did not factor in the socio-economic changes in East Africa as well as Climate change realities which may affect the acceptability of the modelled scenarios by the policy and decision makers. Using a decade long data may not project the current reality of East Africa and this means the model may be overtaken by events.</p>	<p>It was explained that all the assumptions of the integrated assessment model are projections designed almost 10 years ago. The current realities are not covered in the models.</p>

3 Summary of Breakout Group Discussions

3.1 Climate Ambition

3.1.1 Breakout Group 1

The group underscored the importance of land tenure in influencing the scalability of afforestation and forest management initiatives in East Africa. The secure nature of land tenure emerged as a critical factor shaping the incentives and behaviors of landowners and communities in the region. Ownership rights not only provide a clear stake in the land's future but also facilitate access to financing, enabling necessary investments in sustainable practices. Conversely, insecure land tenure was identified as a barrier, potentially leading to short-term exploitation of forests, hindering community participation, and creating obstacles for policy implementation and effective land use planning. This was especially in the arid and semi-arid areas where land is communally owned particularly in the northern Kenya and the Karamoja cluster in the horn of Africa (Uganda, South Sudan, Ethiopia and Kenya). Therefore, addressing land tenure issues was highlighted as crucial for promoting large-scale afforestation efforts and ensuring the success of sustainable forest management initiatives. The size of land holdings was identified as another critical factor influencing the scalability of LMTs. Larger land holdings were seen to provide economies of scale, facilitating more efficient planning, implementation, and management. However, the prevalent pattern of smallholder farmers with limited land holdings in East Africa posed a significant challenge. The fragmented nature of land ownership made large-scale afforestation and agroforestry projects complex, with coordination across numerous small plots proving challenging. Additionally, smallholder farmers in the region often rely on their land for immediate subsistence, making it difficult to dedicate substantial portions to long-term afforestation efforts. The discussion emphasized the need for innovative approaches, such as community-based afforestation models, to address this barrier and promote sustainable forest management practices at a broader scale.

Insufficient understanding of local ecosystems, suitable tree species, and effective land management practices was identified as a knowledge gap hindering the development and implementation of successful LMTs. Limited awareness about the socio-economic dynamics of communities in East Africa was noted as a potential pitfall, leading to poorly designed initiatives that do not align with local needs. The absence of comprehensive knowledge-sharing mechanisms, extension services, and awareness campaigns was highlighted as a challenge, hindering the ability to tailor interventions to the diverse ecological and social contexts of the region.

Political influence was recognized as a potential disruptor to the implementation of long-term LMTs, with shifting priorities and inconsistent policies undermining sustained efforts. The lack of well-defined land use plans was identified as another challenge, making it difficult to allocate suitable areas for afforestation and coordinate efforts across regions. Effective scaling up was deemed contingent on stable, supportive policies and a strategic approach to land use planning that considers environmental conservation, community needs, and sustainable development goals. The group concluded that addressing these factors collectively is essential for successfully scaling up and ensuring the long-term success of afforestation and forest management initiatives in East Africa.

Key questions: LMTs	Scaling options (how to upscale – barriers and enablers)	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards (note differences across LMTs – how to address them?)	Co-benefits (especially adaptation, biodiversity/ecosystems, livelihoods)	Ambition (baseline, moderate, high) What does the LMT implementation look like at various levels of ambition? Is LMT implementation possible at all levels of ambition?	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management	<p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community involvement and ownership Effective governance and policies Collaborative partnership Technological innovation Capacity building and training Financial incentives <p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insecure Land Tenure Small land size Limited knowledge Economy of scale/poverty – Longer period to get return on investment. Water scarcity to maintain the trees due to prolonged droughts in some areas. 	<p>Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change Land tenure/land use changes Human activities and population pressure Invasive species and pests Limited financial resources Lack of technical capacity Market dynamics-demand for forest products 	<p>Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medicinal value of trees Mental health and the aesthetic value Increase farm productivity through biogeochemical cycles ie, Nitrogen fixation. Increase bee forage for pollination. 	<p>Implementation at all levels possible with the following in place:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory and policy frameworks Capacity building Clear guidelines on urban expansion Embracing sustainable policies on tree harvesting Realistic government policies to govern and maintain present forests. Restoration of degraded forests and hilltops Roll out extension services. Incentive policies - Payment for ecosystem services Sustainable value chains Carbon credits. Strengthening indigenous systems on trees Promotion of trees with high economic value. Climate finance Strengthen partnerships with stakeholders. Alternative livelihoods promotion 	By 2050
Agroforestry	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited awareness and knowledge of species combination Access to quality planting materials Short term economic pressures- farmers face immediate economic 	<p>Risks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unpredictable weather patterns and climate variability Pests and diseases Social and cultural factors, such as 	<p>Benefits</p> <p>Biodiversity conservation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil erosion prevention Low-cost solution and easily adaptable Wind breakers Multiple products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning national agricultural and environmental policies to integrate and incentivize agroforestry adoption. Training programs for farmers, extension workers, policymakers, and researchers on agroforestry principles, practices, and benefits 	By 2050

	<p>challenges and prioritize short term gains over long term benefits.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weak policy frameworks and inadequate institutional support Limited market access and poorly developed value chains for agroforestry products <p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supportive policies that recognize and promote agroforestry as a viable land-use option. Training programs for farmers, extension workers, and policymakers on agroforestry techniques, management, and benefits Access to quality tree seeds and seedlings Good market linkages for agroforestry products, such as timber, fruits, nuts, and non-timber forest products. 	<p>traditional land-use practices and beliefs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inadequate infrastructure, including roads and storage facilities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased crop yields and diversity-shade, Nitrogen fixation Improved soil health -soil structure, nutrient cycling, and microbial activity Filter and purify water by reducing runoff and preventing the transport of sediments and pollutants into water bodies. Diversification of income sources create employment opportunities, supporting small-scale enterprises, and providing sustainable livelihoods for local communities. Carbon sequestration and greenhouse gas reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involving local communities in the planning, decision-making, and implementation of agroforestry projects. Addressing land tenure issues and clarifying property rights to encourage long-term investments in agroforestry. Policy advocacy to create an enabling environment for agroforestry adoption. 	
<p>LMT chosen by participants, as seen relevant to the region. (Selected by participants in each breakout group)</p> <p>(NO TILLAGE)</p>	<p>Barrier</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of awareness and understanding of the benefits of no-tillage practices, including improved soil health, water conservation, and reduced erosion. Lack of appropriate equipment availability and affordability-seed drills and planters Weed management challenges. <p>Enabler</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge transfer – Capacity building Extension services to facilitate the dissemination of information and support for no-tillage practices. Research for adapting no-tillage techniques to local agroecological conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pest and disease dynamics The transition from conventional tillage to no-tillage can pose challenges, as farmers may experience adjustments in crop management and productivity during the initial year. Irregular rainfall patterns and extreme weather events, impacting crop performance 	<p>Benefit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil and water conservation Reduced fertilizer input Cost saving-Time and labor efficiency Biodiversity conservation Energy saving-less fuel consumption Carbon retention and sequestration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity building Increased research and funding 	2050

3.1.2 Breakout Group 2

The group explored various key factors that contribute to the success and sustainability of afforestation and forest management initiatives. Community involvement and ownership emerged as a crucial aspect, emphasizing that engaging local communities in decision-making processes fosters a sense of responsibility and promotes responsible resource use. Additionally, effective governance and policies play a pivotal role, creating an environment conducive to responsible forest management through clear regulations and transparent decision-making processes.

Collaborative partnerships were highlighted as essential for comprehensive and scaling up of LMTs. The group emphasized the importance of shared responsibilities among governments, NGOs, local communities, and the private sector. Investment in research and education was deemed vital to provide the necessary knowledge and skills for sustainable forest management, agroforestry, and afforestation with training programs benefiting local communities, foresters, and policymakers. Integrated land use planning was underscored as necessary for addressing conflicts between human needs and ecological considerations more so in pastoral communities. The incorporation of technological innovations, such as satellite monitoring and GIS, enhances forest monitoring capabilities, enabling real-time tracking and data-driven decision-making. Capacity building and training were recognized as critical components to empower local institutions and individuals involved in forest management.

Financial incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services and carbon offset projects, were discussed as motivators for communities and landowners to engage in LMTs. The group acknowledged the role of LMTs in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts, emphasizing the need to link conservation initiatives to global environmental goals. Cross-border cooperation was highlighted as crucial, given that ecosystems often transcend national borders. Collaborative efforts between neighboring countries in East Africa were seen as essential to address regional challenges like illegal logging and habitat fragmentation.

Transitioning to the risks and uncertainties faced by LMTs in East Africa, the discussion outlined various challenges. Climate change emerged as a significant risk, with unpredictable weather patterns impacting the success of afforestation initiatives. Droughts and floods have become more common than before in East Africa with droughts occurring after every two to three years compared to few years ago when droughts would occur after a decade. Land tenure issues were identified as a potential threat, leading to disputes over land that can result in deforestation and illegal logging.

Political instability and changes in governance were acknowledged as risks that could affect the implementation of LMTs such as forest management plans, potentially leading to corruption and illegal activities. The group highlighted the pressure exerted by rapid population growth on forests for resources, agriculture, and settlement, emphasizing the need for sustainable practices to mitigate these impacts. Invasive species and pests were recognized as potential threats, disrupting the natural balance of forest ecosystems. Limited financial resources, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of technical capacity were identified as challenges that could impede LMTs. Market dynamics and global economic factors, such as changes in market conditions and trade policies, were also acknowledged as external factors impacting the economic viability of LMTs such as forestry activities in East Africa.

In response to these risks and uncertainties, the group emphasized the importance of adaptive approaches. Strategies should focus on building resilience, enhancing adaptive capacity, and promoting

sustainable practices that consider both ecological and socio-economic factors. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to ensure long-term success and sustainability of LMTs in East Africa.

Key questions: LMTs	Scaling options (how to upscale – barriers and enablers)	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards (note differences across LMTs – how to address them?)	Co-benefits (especially adaptation, biodiversity/ecosystems, livelihoods)	Ambition (baseline, moderate, high) The selected LMTs, one by one, will be discussed considering the various levels of ambition as per the model (baseline, moderate (RCP2.6), and high (RCP 1.9). What does the LMT implementation look like at various levels of ambition? Is LMT implementation possible at all levels of ambition?	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management	<p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supportive government policy Availability of land Availability of tree seedlings Match the species of trees with the location. Mass awareness Partnership with community forest associations Community involvement <p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of monitoring of the growth of the trees to maturity Lack of land use plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate impacts Flooding, drought Pests and diseases Change of ecosystem dynamics Illegal cutting of trees Unfavorable government policies Competition with food crops Invasive species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land conservation Source of Income Carbon sink Improved biodiversity Water conservation 	<p>Medium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compensation scheme Government investment in the production of indigenous seedlings through the Shamba system Encourage valuable trees for communities. <p>High</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory programs for national targets Government to implement targets. Synergies between counties and communities in tree growing 	<p>Increased drought Communities attitude towards the resources Forest fires Increased competition Changed human behavior. Increased or decreased conflict</p>
Agroforestry	<p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness of the benefits Availability of local tree species for integration with the crops Improved food system <p>Barrier</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased pests Land tenure changes Increased urbanization Population increases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food security Income diversification Increased livestock and crops yield 	<p>Medium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> More public awareness Implementable government policies, and sustainable and realistic national targets Capacity-building <p>High</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentives for the communities to embrace Agroforestry. 	<p>Increased population Increased urbanization</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge on the right species • Long payback periods of investments 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased awareness and knowledge 	
BECCS was chosen – Biogas value chain, touches all sectors	<p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can scale-up to human waste. • Availability of bio-resources <p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition for alternative uses • Limited awareness • Low Market linkages • Poor Infrastructure • Technological challenges • Cultural beliefs 	Increased emissions if handled improperly.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can improve emissions and increase them depending on the management. • High value Bi-products • Green energy • Reducing pressure on natural forest 	<p>Medium</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness • Increased Research • Green energy adoption 	<p>High demand for clean and green energy</p> <p>Change of attitude</p> <p>Change of views</p> <p>Improved waste management</p> <p>Carbon trade</p>

3.1.3 Breakout Group 3

The group's efforts to understand the importance of agroforestry, rangeland management, and afforestation in East Africa, several key points emerged that underscored the significance of these practices in the region. One primary aspect discussed was the crucial role these land-based mitigation technologies play in promoting environmental sustainability. Agroforestry, characterized by the integration of trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes, helps diversify crops, enhance soil fertility, and mitigate the impacts of climate change. This practice was observed to have contributed to increased resilience of farming systems, especially in the face of unpredictable weather patterns and shifting climate conditions that East Africa often experiences. Rangeland management, identified as a key missing LMT in East Africa which involves sustainable practices in open land for grazing, emerged as a critical element for maintaining healthy ecosystems. With most of the land mass in East Africa considered as rangeland (80% of Kenya's land mass for example), proper management of rangelands helps prevent overgrazing, soil erosion, and degradation, ensuring the continued availability of forage for livestock and supporting biodiversity. This is particularly significant in East Africa, where a substantial portion of the population relies on livestock for their livelihoods. Afforestation was emphasized for its multifaceted benefits in the region. The importance of afforestation extends beyond carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation. The newly planted forests can contribute to the conservation of biodiversity, restoration of degraded landscapes, and the provision of ecosystem services such as water regulation and soil protection. Afforestation also plays a role in enhancing local livelihoods by creating opportunities for sustainable timber and non-timber forest product harvesting.

The discussions also highlighted the economic advantages associated with these land-based mitigation technologies. Agroforestry practices, for instance, were seen as an avenue for diversifying income sources for farmers, as trees provide additional products such as fruits, nuts, and timber. Rangeland management, when done sustainably, ensures the availability of fodder for livestock, contributing to the well-being of pastoralist communities. Afforestation projects, beyond their environmental benefits, were reported to create employment opportunities in forestry-related activities, fostering economic growth and poverty alleviation. Importantly, the group recognized the interconnectedness of these land-based practices with broader sustainable development goals. Agroforestry, rangeland management, and afforestation contribute not only to environmental conservation but also address issues related to food security, water management, and rural livelihoods. The integration of these practices into regional policies and development agendas was emphasized as a holistic approach to fostering resilience, combating climate change, and promoting sustainable land use in East Africa.

The group identified several enablers that contributed to the successful implementation of agroforestry, rangeland management, and afforestation initiatives. One prominent enabler is the rich tradition and knowledge of local communities in sustainable land management practices. Leveraging indigenous wisdom and involving communities in decision-making processes empowers them to actively participate in these initiatives, fostering a sense of ownership and long-term commitment. Additionally, supportive policies and effective governance play a crucial role in enabling land-based mitigation technologies. Clear regulations and transparent decision-making processes create an environment conducive to responsible practices, ensuring that initiatives align with broader conservation goals.

However, discussions also highlighted significant barriers that pose challenges to the successful adoption and scaling up of these land-based mitigation technologies. Land tenure issues emerged as a major barrier, with unclear property rights and ownership disputes hindering long-term investments in agroforestry,

rangeland management, and afforestation. Political instability and governance changes were identified as potential barriers, affecting the consistency of policies, and undermining the implementation of mitigation plans. Limited financial resources emerged as another significant challenge, hindering the necessary investments in tree planting, monitoring, enforcement, and community engagement. Insufficient infrastructure, such as roads and transportation networks, posed barriers to effective forest management and impeded the monitoring and enforcement of regulations.

Despite these challenges, the group discussed strategies for scaling up land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa. A key aspect is the importance of community engagement and capacity building. Empowering local communities with the knowledge and skills needed for sustainable land management practices creates a foundation for successful initiatives. Collaborative partnerships between governments, non-governmental organizations, local communities, and the private sector were identified as essential for scaling up efforts. The group emphasized the need for financial incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services or carbon offset projects, to motivate communities and landowners to engage in sustainable practices. Furthermore, integrating these land-based mitigation technologies into broader development agendas, such as poverty alleviation and food security, can enhance their acceptance and impact. While acknowledging the challenges posed by land tenure issues, political instability, and limited financial resources, the group emphasized the importance of community involvement, supportive policies, and collaborative partnerships in achieving successful outcomes.

<p>Afforestation and forest management</p>	<p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon financing programs which have fueled tree growing. • Government commitments- The president's 15billion tree planting challenge. • Investment in research and education • Integrated land use planning <p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial constraints (From seedlings to planting) • The minimum viable scale for getting carbon-Lead times for carbon payout is 3-5 years. • Limited alternative sources of energy/ livelihood. • Lack of clear policies & practices. 	<p>Risk</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Growing unfavorable non-native tree species. 2. Forest Fires 3. Competing land uses. 4. Cross boundary policy harmonization. 	<p>Co benefits</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prevent soil erosion. 2. Provide fuel and fruit. 3. Wildlife habitat/Ecotourism 4. Carbon sequestration 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compensation rates will be increased. 2. Less dependence on forest products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There will be greater access to renewable energy and reduce reliance on forest. • More jobs for young people in the areas.
<p>Agroforestry</p>	<p>Barriers</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inadequate policy guidelines 2. Limited awareness and knowledge of species combination 3. Lack of alternative sources of livelihood and energy sources. 4. Mismanagement of carbon finances for the communities. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invasive species and pests 2. Limited financial resources 3. Lack of technical capacity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Food security 2. Forest conversation 3. Soil erosion control 4. Conservation of habitats 5. Reduced use of fertilizers-nitrogen fixation 6. Carbon sequestration 	<p>Financing their alternate sources of livelihoods</p>	

<p>Rangeland management (Missing LMT)</p>	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncontrolled livestock grazing • Reduced pastureland. • Climate variability and change • Unsustainable land use practices, such as deforestation, improper irrigation, and inappropriate cultivation methods • Insecure Land Tenure • Inadequate infrastructure, such as water sources, roads, and veterinary services • Insufficient knowledge and skills among pastoralists and resource managers • Lack of awareness of rangeland management practices <p>Enablers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Involvement and Participation • Adoption of climate-resilient practices, such as rotational grazing, drought-resistant forage crops, and water conservation measures • Market linkages for rangeland products • Integrated livestock production • Partnerships and Collaboration • Using ICT tools for monitoring, early warning systems, and dissemination of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty in Weather Patterns • Lack of clear land tenure and property rights • Increased Demand for Resources resulting from population growth. • Conflict with Wildlife • Shifting societal values and preferences regarding land use and livelihood choices • Changes in market demand and prices for livestock products • Invasive species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biodiversity Conservation ● Healthy rangelands act as carbon sinks. ● Contribute to soil health by preventing erosion, improving water retention, and promoting nutrient cycling. ● Enhanced livestock productivity ● Economic diversification- ecotourism, non-timber forest products; Payment Ecosystem services 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide markets for rangeland products 2. Secure land tenure to pastoral communities ensures stability and reduces conflicts over land use 3. Supporting research on rangeland ecology, soil health, and climate patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More stringent carbon taxes ● Enclosed stock keeping ● Improved manure management. ●
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3.2 Regional Engagement (max 6 pages)

3.2.1 Breakout Group 1

The group's discussions have shed light on several key aspects surrounding the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa, with a focus on economic integration and harmonization, carbon markets, formal governance mechanisms, and research cooperation and technology transfer. The multifaceted nature of these discussions underscores the complexity of fostering sustainable land management practices in the region. The consensus within the group highlighted the pivotal role of economic integration in fostering collaboration and coordination among East African nations. Integrated economic strategies and policies were identified as crucial enablers, providing a conducive environment for the adoption of sustainable practices. Harmonization of policies emerged as equally essential, creating a standardized framework that reduces regulatory complexities and uncertainties. A coordinated policy environment was emphasized for its role in providing stability for long-term investments in sustainable land management practices. The instrumental role of carbon markets in incentivizing the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies, particularly agroforestry and afforestation, was a key point of discussion. The integration of carbon markets into the economic landscape offers East African countries a means to monetize environmental benefits and attract investments. However, the lack of clear carbon trading guidelines poses a challenge. The group acknowledged the need for streamlined guidelines to fully leverage the potential of carbon markets in supporting sustainable land management practices.

The group emphasized the significance of formal governance mechanisms, such as bilateral and interregional working groups, coordination bodies, and agreements on land and forests. These mechanisms were identified as essential enablers for fostering coordinated efforts and cooperation among East African nations. Coordination bodies were recognized for their role in harmonizing policies and strategies, creating a standardized framework, and facilitating information-sharing. Agreements on land use and forest management were seen as critical components contributing to consistency and cooperation.

Regional funds were acknowledged as powerful mechanisms for overcoming financial barriers associated with large-scale adoption of land-based mitigation technologies. These funds facilitate the collective mobilization of financial resources from multiple countries, encouraging a fair distribution of costs and benefits. The pooling of resources through regional funds not only enhances financial sustainability but also allows for the implementation of projects beyond the capacity of individual nations, fostering a spirit of mutual support and shared commitment.

The group explored the significance of research cooperation and technology transfer in promoting the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies. Research cooperation was identified as a key enabler, fostering partnerships among East African nations and research institutions. Technology transfer, involving the exchange of knowledge and skills, emerged as crucial for empowering local communities, foresters, and policymakers. Collaborative efforts in technology transfer contribute to building the necessary skills and expertise for the successful adoption of land-based mitigation technologies.

Categories	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question
	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonization (includes trade, tariffs, standards/certification, carbon markets)	Carbon markets adaptation – Intensified and replicated in all regions. Funds for carbon inventory Certification - functional systems) - forests	Afforestation reforestation - Carbon market – Preliminary work needs to be done. Intensify competition for funds.	Assessment of fields Robust prioritization of frameworks Repository hub – assist in mapping and monitoring.	Institutions County Governments CFAs KFS KEFRI KEFIS NGOs Donors	Opaque pricing for carbon markets Where is the money from carbon markets coming from or going to. Who determines quantities for funds and criteria. Existing enabling policies and guidelines are missing. Politics Weak community forest associations.	Transparency and Capacity building Re - constituting CoFAs Stakeholder workshops and barazas to deliberate on policies. What is needed? Institutional reforms that involve indigenous communities
Formal governance mechanisms (bilateral & interregional working groups/coordination bodies, agreements on land, forests etc.,	Proper coordination Establishing formal governance structures allows for organized	Agroforestry Coordinated efforts ensure that agroforestry initiatives align with broader land-use plans and	Through research and technical assistance by developing site-specific agroforestry models, taking	CFAs NGOs Donors Private sector Government agencies such as	Ambiguous or inconsistent policies Ineffective communication and information-sharing mechanisms	Coordination for policy influence Community engagement and empowerment

pooling of resources [regional funds])	knowledge-sharing platforms	development goals	into account local ecological conditions and the needs of farmers	KFS, KEFRI and KEFIS	Existing power dynamics and social inequity within communities	
Research cooperation & technology transfer (research partnerships, capacity building, networks etc.)	Research partnerships Collaborations	Afforestation	Partnership Collaboration	Collaborating Institutions (University, Research Institutes, Local communities)	Mistrust Poor match of expertise – Funding models – Unequal/unconsolidated – All parties should be included when formulating models for equality. Mismatch of expertise Top-down research.	Win-win collaborative agreements (MOUs) Get the appropriate expertise. Transparency and accountability Inculcate co development and co innovation processes of research and development

3.2.2 Breakout Group 2

The outputs of the discussions highlighted the holistic approach required to address the complex challenges associated with land-based mitigation technologies. Economic integration and harmonization were recognized as foundational elements that provide a conducive environment for the adoption of mitigation technologies in East Africa. Integrated economic strategies and policies was reported to create a collaborative framework for East African nations, fostering coherence and alignment in their efforts towards sustainable land management. Research cooperation and technology transfer were identified as key drivers for informed decision-making and effective implementation of mitigation strategies. Through joint efforts, East African countries can build a comprehensive understanding of local ecosystems, identify suitable tree species, and develop effective land management practices. Concurrently, technology transfer initiatives ensure that best practices and innovations in sustainable land management are disseminated across borders, empowering local communities and stakeholders with the skills and knowledge required for successful adoption. The role of formal governance mechanisms, including bilateral and interregional working groups, coordination bodies, and agreements, was underscored in our group discussion. These mechanisms provide a structured framework for collaboration and coordination, fostering a sense of shared responsibility among East African nations. The holistic approach involves creating an enabling economic environment, leveraging research and technology for informed decision-making, and establishing formal governance structures that encourage collaboration and coordination. The integration of these elements contributes to a comprehensive and sustainable strategy for the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa.

Categories	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question
	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonization (includes trade, tariffs, standards/certification, carbon markets)	Carbon Markets	Afforestation- Because of the carbon markets that can be traded in different markets.	High Engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Policies for carbon trading. ● Involvement of the right stakeholders ● Suitability analysis 	VERA-Carbon Markets Carbon futures Plant vivo Greening financing institutions NEMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Political interference ● Lack of standard policies in markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Chain of custody and audit ● Engagement of Civil society groups
Formal governance mechanisms (bilateral & interregional working groups/coordination bodies, agreements on land, forests etc., pooling of resources [regional funds])	Agreements on land, policies, grass root engagement,	Agroforestry (Because of the heavy dependence of the areas owned by the communities and collective management)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High engagement ● Stakeholder engagement ● Property rights ● Collective mechanism 	UNEP AATF SEI KEPHIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Political interference ● Zero prioritization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementation of environmental guidelines ● Prioritization of projects ● Allocation of enough funds.
Research cooperation & technology transfer (research partnerships, capacity building)	Research partnerships and capacity building	All LMTs	Medium <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technology access and transfer 	CGIAR Universities KALRO KFS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inadequate Financing ● Top-down approaches to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capacity building ● Participatory approach

building, networks etc.)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participatory approaches in research and development (Co design, cocreation) 	CABI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● research and development ● Poor information dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partnership for development ● Provide publications to the public ● Youth led extensions
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3.3 Discussion on interactions and interlinkages

The group discussions underscored the interconnected nature of these factors, emphasizing the need for a holistic and collaborative approach to foster the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa. The integration of economic, governance, financial, and research-related mechanisms is essential to address the challenges and leverage opportunities for sustainable land management practices in the region. The group discussed the role of economic integration and harmonization, including the utilization of carbon markets, in facilitating the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies like agroforestry, afforestation, forest management, biochar and BECCS in East Africa. Economic integration emerged as a crucial enabler, fostering collaboration and coordination among countries in the region. Integrated economic strategies and policies contribute to a conducive environment for the adoption of sustainable practices, promoting cross-border initiatives for agroforestry and afforestation. The sharing of resources, expertise, and technologies becomes more streamlined through economic integration, enabling a more efficient and effective implementation of land-based mitigation technologies.

Harmonization of policies was identified as essential for creating a standardized framework that encourages the widespread adoption of these technologies. A harmonized approach ensures consistency across borders, reducing regulatory complexities and uncertainties that may hinder the scaling up of agroforestry and afforestation initiatives. A coordinated policy environment fosters a sense of predictability, providing the necessary stability for long-term investments in sustainable land management practices. The discussion also highlighted the instrumental role of carbon markets in incentivizing the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies particularly agroforestry and afforestation. By incorporating carbon markets into the economic landscape, East African countries can monetize the environmental benefits derived from practices like agroforestry and afforestation. Carbon trading mechanisms provide financial incentives for sustainable land management, creating revenue streams for farmers and landowners who engage in these practices. The prospect of earning carbon credits through the sequestration of carbon dioxide in trees can attract investments and encourage the adoption of agroforestry and afforestation on a larger scale.

The group emphasized that economic integration and participation in carbon markets enable East African nations to leverage international funding and support. By aligning their land-based mitigation strategies with global climate goals, countries in East Africa can attract international investments and assistance. This financial support can be channeled towards capacity-building, technology transfer, and the implementation of large-scale agroforestry and afforestation projects. Additionally, participation in carbon markets enhances the visibility and marketability of sustainably managed lands, creating opportunities for East African countries to showcase their commitment to environmental conservation. The challenge, however, is the lack of carbon trading guidelines aimed at streamlining the carbon markets.

The group also examined the significance of formal governance mechanisms, including bilateral and interregional working groups, coordination bodies, and agreements on land and forests, as well as the pooling of resources through regional funds, in fostering the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies such as agroforestry and afforestation in East Africa. The group identified formal governance mechanisms as essential enablers that facilitate coordinated efforts and cooperation among East African nations. Bilateral and interregional working groups provide platforms for dialogue, collaboration, and the exchange of knowledge and best practices. These mechanisms foster a sense of shared responsibility, enabling countries to collectively address challenges related to land-based mitigation technologies.

Coordination bodies were recognized as instrumental in harmonizing policies and strategies across borders. According to the group, agreements on land use and forest management, when established through formal governance mechanisms, create a standardized framework that promotes consistency and cooperation. This consistency is crucial for the successful implementation and scaling up of land-based mitigation technologies, as it reduces regulatory complexities and provides a common understanding among participating nations. The coordination bodies also contribute to information-sharing, ensuring that countries in the region stay informed about advancements, challenges, and successful strategies in the adoption of agroforestry and afforestation.

Pooling of resources through regional funds emerged as a powerful mechanism for overcoming financial barriers associated with large-scale adoption of land-based mitigation technologies especially with cross border resources. Regional funds facilitate the mobilization of financial resources from multiple countries, providing a collective pool of funds that can be directed towards supporting initiatives related to agroforestry and afforestation. This approach enhances financial sustainability and allows for the implementation of projects that may be beyond the capacity of individual nations. It also encourages a fair distribution of costs and benefits among participating countries, fostering a spirit of mutual support and shared commitment to sustainable land management. The discussion emphasized that formal governance mechanisms play a critical role in addressing cross-border challenges and fostering a holistic approach to land-based mitigation. The coordination facilitated by these mechanisms ensures that countries align their efforts, share responsibilities, and collectively work towards common goals. This collaborative approach not only enhances the effectiveness of land-based mitigation technologies but also promotes regional stability and sustainable development.

The group also explored the significance of research cooperation and technology transfer in promoting the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies, specifically agroforestry and afforestation, in East Africa. The outputs of our discussions underscored the pivotal role of these collaborative efforts in enhancing knowledge, building capacity, and establishing networks for sustainable land management practices. Research cooperation emerged as a key enabler, fostering partnerships among East African nations and research institutions. Collaborative research initiatives provide a platform for sharing expertise, data, and innovative approaches to agroforestry and afforestation. By pooling resources and engaging in joint studies, countries in the region can benefit from a collective knowledge base, gaining insights into the most effective and context-specific strategies for sustainable land management. Research partnerships also facilitate a deeper understanding of local ecosystems, suitable tree species, and effective land management practices, addressing critical gaps in knowledge that may hinder the successful adoption of mitigation technologies. Technology transfer was identified as another crucial aspect of advancing land-based mitigation technologies. Capacity building, through the transfer of knowledge and skills, is essential for empowering local communities, foresters, and policymakers to effectively implement agroforestry and afforestation practices. Collaborative efforts in technology transfer involve the exchange of best practices, training programs, and the dissemination of information on sustainable logging, reforestation techniques, and conservation strategies. This, in turn, contributes to building the necessary skills and expertise for the successful adoption of land-based mitigation technologies.

4 Comparison and synthesis

This section provides a comprehensive analysis of the results obtained from various groups, focusing on synthesizing diverse perspectives into coherent storylines or narratives that show the potential

trajectories of Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMT) scaling in the East African region. The aim of the storyline is to construct nuanced narratives that capture the complex interplay of factors shaping the future development of LMT scaling in East Africa by comparing results across different groups and synthesizing them. These narratives shed light on how different scenarios, characterized by varying levels of community engagement, policy frameworks, and resource mobilization, could influence the adoption and effectiveness of key LMTs such as agroforestry, afforestation, and reforestation.

Narrative A: Scaling of agroforestry, afforestation, reforestation in East Africa, requires a community led approach.

In this storyline, agroforestry, afforestation, and reforestation are key components of the grassroots initiatives championed by local communities in East Africa. Indigenous groups, smallholder farmers, and community-based organizations leverage traditional knowledge and sustainable land management practices to spearhead these efforts. Through community-led efforts, degraded forests are rehabilitated, and native tree species are reintroduced, enhancing habitat connectivity, protecting watersheds, and supporting wildlife populations. Governments and NGOs play a supportive role by providing capacity-building opportunities, facilitating land tenure reform to ensure community ownership and stewardship of natural resources, and offering financial incentives to incentivize participation in community-led conservation initiatives. This collaborative approach ensures a sense of ownership and empowerment among local communities, leading to a groundswell of bottom-up action aimed at restoring degraded ecosystems, conserving biodiversity, and mitigating climate change through the adoption of agroforestry, afforestation, reforestation and other land-based mitigation technologies such as biochar in the East Africa region. This shows the intrinsic link between social equity, cultural preservation, and the successful scaling of Land-based Mitigation Technologies in East Africa. Through their collective efforts, local communities become the driving force behind meaningful impact in LMT scaling, contributing to the sustainable management of land resources for generations to come.

Narrative B: Policy-led transition

The second narrative centers on policy led transition. In this storyline, ambitious policy interventions drive the scaling of LMT in East Africa, with governments taking a proactive role in setting targets, implementing regulations, and mobilizing resources. Comprehensive land-use planning, coupled with robust carbon pricing mechanisms and subsidy reforms, incentivize the adoption of agroforestry, sustainable rangeland management, afforestation, and reforestation across sectors. Regional cooperation frameworks facilitate knowledge exchange, harmonization of policies, and cross-border collaboration on shared environmental challenges. As a result, East Africa will achieve significant emissions reductions from land use activities, while simultaneously unlocking economic opportunities and promoting inclusive development. Hence the importance of strong political will and effective governance structures in catalyzing the transition towards sustainable land management practices at scale.

Narrative C: Resource-constrained realities

The third narrative is on the need for resources and financial support for scaling LMTs. In this scenario, East Africa grapples with persistent challenges such as limited financial resources, institutional capacity constraints, and competing development priorities, hampering the scaling of LMT. Governments face trade-offs between short-term economic imperatives and long-term environmental sustainability, leading to insufficient investment in LMT scaling efforts such as agroforestry. International support is sporadic and

fragmented, failing to adequately address the complex socio-economic and environmental dynamics in the region. As a result, progress in scaling LMT remains slow and uneven, exacerbating vulnerabilities to climate change and environmental degradation. There is need for proper environment for targeted interventions to overcome systemic barriers and mobilize resources effectively, ensuring that the region can unlock the full potential of LMT in addressing climate change and sustainable development goals.

Narrative D: Need for strong regional engagement.

The fourth narrative from the workshop is on the need for strong regional engagement required for achieving high climate ambition in East Africa. In this storyline, East African countries should prioritize regional cooperation over ambitious climate targets. This emphasizes the need for government to recognize the interconnectedness of environmental challenges in the East Africa region and work together to implement shared strategies for land-based mitigation. Regional initiatives focus on ecosystem restoration, sustainable agriculture, and community-led conservation efforts. While climate ambition may not be as high in the region, the collective approach leads to significant progress in reducing emissions and enhancing resilience to climate change. International partners play a supportive role, providing technical expertise and financial resources to amplify regional efforts. This narrative underscores the importance of inclusive governance structures and participatory decision-making processes to ensure that land-based mitigation benefits all stakeholders in East Africa.

5 Limitations, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Limitations of the storyline and simulation approach

Decadal data used in the simulation models was observed not to accurately reflect current conditions, especially in East Africa experiencing rapid changes due to factors like population growth, urbanization, land use changes, and climate variability. Using this data can lead to inaccurate projections with analysis that makes it difficult to implement and convince the policy makers to act upon. Climate patterns may have shifted over the past decade, affecting factors such as precipitation, temperature, and soil moisture, which are crucial for simulating land-based mitigation strategies. Outdated climate data can lead to unreliable projections of the impacts of mitigation technologies.

Failure to account for changes in policies, regulations, and governance structures significantly influences the feasibility, implementation, and effectiveness of land-based mitigation technologies in modelling can affect the implementation of the simulation outcomes. The simulation approach also relied on simplified assumptions about complex socio-economic and environmental dynamics. These assumptions (refer to section 2.2) did not fully capture the diverse range of factors that influence land-based mitigation technologies, such as land tenure systems, governance structures, and cultural practices in East Africa. The approach may have overlooked the local context and failed to account for the unique socio-cultural, economic, and environmental conditions of specific regions within East Africa. This lack of contextualization could result in recommendations that are not well-suited to local needs and priorities, reducing their effectiveness and relevance. This can however be solved through co-creation of assumptions and incorporation of the socioeconomic and cultural indicators tailored to local needs and priorities.

5.2 Conclusions and Recommendations

In conclusion, the group discussions highlighted the pivotal role of LMTs in promoting environmental sustainability, economic development, and resilience in East Africa. These land-based mitigation technologies were recognized as crucial elements in addressing climate change, conserving biodiversity, and contributing to broader sustainable development goals. The group identified several challenges, including land tenure issues, political instability, limited financial resources, and inadequate infrastructure. Despite these challenges, the discussions emphasized the opportunities and strategies for scaling up these technologies. Community engagement, capacity building, collaborative partnerships, and financial incentives were identified as key components in overcoming barriers and promoting sustainable land management practices. Economic integration and participation in carbon markets were recognized as crucial enablers, providing avenues for international funding, creating economic incentives for sustainable practices, and enhancing the visibility of East African countries committed to environmental conservation. Harmonization of policies and the establishment of formal governance mechanisms, such as working groups and regional funds, were deemed essential for fostering cooperation, consistency, and coordination across borders. The importance of research cooperation and technology transfer was underscored as critical for building knowledge, capacity, and networks to support the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies. Collaborative research initiatives and the exchange of best practices contribute to informed decision-making, while technology transfer empowers local communities and stakeholders with the skills needed for effective implementation. The successful adoption and scaling up of land-based mitigation technologies in East Africa require a comprehensive and collaborative approach that addresses challenges, leverages opportunities, and integrates economic, governance, financial, and research-related mechanisms. By embracing sustainable land management practices and fostering international cooperation, East Africa can contribute significantly to global climate goals while promoting regional stability and development.

Based on the extensive discussions and insights gathered, the following key recommendations are proposed for upscaling land-based mitigation technologies and achieving high ambition targets in East Africa:

There is the need to:

- Prioritize community engagement and capacity building initiatives to empower local communities with the knowledge and skills required for the adoption of LMTs.
- Foster collaborative partnerships between governments, non-governmental organizations, local communities, and the private sector to leverage resources, expertise, and technology for the effective implementation of land-based mitigation technologies.
- Introduce financial incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services or carbon offset projects, to motivate communities and landowners to engage in sustainable practices.
- Explore innovative financing mechanisms, including public-private partnerships, to secure the necessary investments for large-scale adoption of land-based mitigation technologies.
- Integrate land-based mitigation technologies into broader development agendas, emphasizing their contribution to poverty alleviation, food security, and economic growth.
- Tackle land tenure issues by implementing clear property rights and ownership frameworks to encourage long-term investments in agroforestry, rangeland management, and afforestation.

- Embrace the utilization of carbon markets to incentivize the adoption of land-based mitigation technologies, particularly agroforestry and afforestation.
- Advocate for the development of clear and streamlined carbon trading guidelines to enhance the attractiveness of carbon markets.
- Promote economic integration and harmonization among East African countries to streamline resource sharing, expertise, and technologies, enhancing the efficiency of land-based mitigation technology implementation.
- Establish and strengthen formal governance mechanisms, such as bilateral and interregional working groups, coordination bodies, and agreements on land and forests, to facilitate coordinated efforts and cooperation among East African nations.
- Encourage the establishment and utilization of regional funds to pool financial resources from multiple countries, fostering collaboration and supporting large-scale initiatives related to agroforestry and afforestation.
- Promote research cooperation among East African nations and research institutions to build a collective knowledge base, address knowledge gaps, and identify context-specific strategies for sustainable land management.
- Facilitate technology transfer through collaborative efforts, sharing best practices, training programs, and information on sustainable logging, reforestation techniques, and conservation strategies.

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7 Additional Info: Agenda

Raising Climate Ambition for Land-Based Mitigation:

Regional Engagement for Global Impact in Africa

LAND-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate pathways (LANDMARC)

Regional Stakeholder Workshop, November 21st, 2023

ICRAF, Nairobi

08.30-09.00: Arrival, coffee, introductions

09.00-9.10: Welcoming remarks Dr. Philip Osano

09.10-10.30 Part I: Introduction to the workshop

- Introduction to LANDMARC and LMTs
- Introduction to Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement framework
- LANDMARC modelling results and discussion
- Breakout group structure

10.30-10.45 Coffee break

10.45-12.30 Part II: Climate Ambition for LMTs

- Introduction to session
- Breakout group discussion on LMT portfolio

12.30-13.30 Lunch

13.30-15.15 Part III: Regional Engagement for scaling up LMTs.

- Introduction to session
- Breakout group discussion on regional engagement for LMT implementation

15.15-15.30 Coffee break

15.30-17.00 Part IV: Synthesis

- Reporting from Breakout Groups
- Discussion on Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement
- Discussion on Regional Narratives

17.00-17.30 Final remarks

ANNEX D4 - WORKSHOP REPORT FOR ASIA

DRAFT - DO NOT SHARE

Annex D4: Workshop report for Asia

EU-LANDMARC FINAL Regional Workshop Report for ASIA

(from the workshop held on 19 Oct 2023, Bangkok, Thailand)

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1 Introduction and Overview

1.1 Setting and participant profile

The Asia workshop was organized on 19 October 2023 in-person in Bangkok, Thailand. The one full day workshop included the participant profiles as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Asia regional workshop participant profiles

Gender	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	LMT(s) of expertise	Sector
Female	Cambodia	Asia	Biochar	Private
Female	Thailand	Mekong	Wetlands	Research
Male	Indonesia	Southeast Asia	AFOLU (reforestation, reforestation, peatland), agroforestry	Consultancy
Male	Indonesia	Southeast Asia	Agriculture, soil carbon enhancement	Research
Female	Vietnam	Southeast Asia	Agroforestry	Research
Male	Cambodia		Agroecology	NGO
Female	Philippines		Climate resilience of rice-based systems and communities	Research
Female	Thailand		Agriculture, Land Use Planning and Policy	Public
Female		Asia-Pacific	General climate/environment	UN-agency
Female			NbS and land carbon sequestration	Consultancy
Female		Southeast Asia	Financing for agriculture and land systems	Private
Male	Lao	Mekong	Small-scale agricultural systems	Public
Female	Indonesia		Bioenergy/agro-forestry/governance	Research
Male		Global	Carbon removal/market	Private
Female		Asia-Pacific	General climate/environment	UN-agency
Male		Global	General climate/environment	NGO

1.2 Regional focus

The regional context of Southeast Asia in the land mitigation sector highlights the critical role of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) in addressing climate change. Southeast Asia, characterized by its diverse ecosystems and rapid economic development, faces increasing greenhouse gas emissions and vulnerability to climate impacts. The region's commitment to the Paris Agreement and formulation of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) reflects an acknowledgment of the need for enhanced mitigation efforts, including a stronger focus on land-based solutions such as afforestation, reforestation, agroforestry, and sustainable agriculture practices.

Despite the potential of LMTs to contribute significantly to emission reductions and adaptation strategies, challenges remain in terms of implementation, financing, and integration into national policies. The variability in socio-economic conditions, land use changes, and environmental degradation further complicates the scaling and effectiveness of these technologies. Regional cooperation and capacity building are essential for sharing knowledge, best practices, and technological advancements to overcome these barriers.

Investment in nature-based solutions and the development of robust policy frameworks can enable Southeast Asia to leverage its land sector for climate mitigation and adaptation. Enhancing the ambition of NDCs to include specific land-based mitigation targets and policies will be crucial for aligning regional efforts with the 1.5°C goal. The involvement of various stakeholders, including governments, private

sector, and local communities, in a participatory and inclusive approach will be key to the successful implementation of LMTs in Southeast Asia.

Furthermore, addressing knowledge gaps, promoting research and development, and ensuring the sustainability of land-based interventions are vital for maximizing their climate, environmental, and socio-economic benefits. As Southeast Asia moves towards a more sustainable and resilient future, land-based mitigation will play a pivotal role in its climate strategy, offering a pathway to not only reduce emissions but also enhance ecosystem services, biodiversity, and livelihoods.

One of the LANDMARC case studies is the Indonesia case study. In Indonesia, the Updated NDC submitted in 2021 reflects the progression beyond the existing NDC as well as new elements, including (1) enhanced ambition on adaptation as depicted in Annex 2, (2) enhanced clarity on mitigation by adopting the Paris Agreement Rules Book (Katowice Package), (3) national context that relates the existing condition, milestones, along with national development, from 2020 to 2024, and indicative pathways towards a long-term vision, (4) translating the existing NDC into the language of the Paris Agreement, and (5) translating Indonesia's updated NDC also seeks international cooperation options to help the attainment of the conditional target of up to 41% compared to the business as usual scenario.

Indonesia presents the Long-term plan for Low carbon and Climate Resilience in 2050 following the mandates of Article 4, Paragraph 19 of the Paris Agreement, and Paragraph 35 of the Dec. 1/CP.21 (LTS-LCCR 2050). Considering economic growth, climate resiliency, and impartiality, Indonesia is laying the groundwork for reaching a peak emission level by 2030, with forestry and other land uses as the leading sector and net-sink towards net-zero emission. The LTS-LCCR 2050 paper represents Indonesia's higher 2030 NDC ambitions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry 2021).

Furthermore, based on Operational Plan Indonesia's FOLU Net Sink 2030 published by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry in 2022, in the long-term strategy, the emission level in the LCCP scenario is significantly lower than in the present policy scenario (CPOS), which is an extension of the NDC scenario without conditions. By 2030, the forestry and other land use sector (FOLU), which was previously a net emitter, will become a net sink according to the LCCP (Low Carbon Compatible with Paris Agreement aim). The FOLU sector's net sinks are anticipated to increase until 2050. This sector plays a significant role in achieving the national NZE target, particularly in offsetting emissions from difficult-to-reduce sectors such as the energy sector.

The synergetic interaction across policies — FOLU Net Sink 2030, Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 98 of 2021, Decree of MOEF (Ministry of Environment and Forestry) No: 168/Menlhk/PKTL/PLA.1/2/2022, and Decree of MOEF (Ministry of Environment and Forestry) Number 21 Year 2022—creates a dynamic landscape with varying impacts on the system scope, particularly in relation to scaling up desired activities. FOLU Net Sink 2030, with its focus on achieving a greenhouse gas emission level of -140 million tons CO₂e by 2030 through mitigation actions in the forestry and land sector, is pivotal in shaping the overall effectiveness of the system. Its objectives align with the broader national strategies outlined in the Presidential Regulation and the Decrees of MOEF. In short, while the policies exhibit strong synergy, careful consideration of potential conflicts and effective coordination will be vital to harness the full potential of these instruments. Through continuous refinement and stakeholder engagement, the policies can work harmoniously towards achieving Indonesia's ambitious climate and environmental goals. The net-effect of the interaction is largely positive, as these policies collectively contribute to the

establishment of a structured and comprehensive approach toward sustainable forest management, carbon reserve enhancement, and conservation. The Presidential Regulation, complementing FOLU Net Sink 2030, emphasizes achieving National Determined Contribution (NDC) targets and introducing carbon economic value. This alignment enhances the effectiveness of both policies, fostering a synergistic relationship. However, a potential challenge arises with the interaction of Decree of MOEF No: 168/2022 and Decree of MOEF No. 21/2022. While both policies aim to implement FOLU Net Sink 2030, there might be a risk of overlapping or competing incentives. Clarity in delineating specific roles and activities within these policies is crucial to avoid redundancy and ensure streamlined implementation.

Moreover, significant efforts to cut FOLU sector emissions and convert them to net sinks by 2030 (under the LCCP scenario) will depend significantly on the success of the following actions:

- a) reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation by expanding protected natural forests, increasing community participation, and strengthening community partnership in forest management;
- b) increasing the carbon sequestration capacity of natural forests by reducing forest degradation and increasing its regeneration through the enrichment or implementation of a sustainable forest management system;
- c) increasing the carbon sequestration of land systems by maximising the use of inefficient or low-carbon land use for the development of forest plantations and other perennials (industrial crops);
- d) reducing emissions from fires and peat decomposition by enhancing peatland management systems;
- e) enforcing the law.

Since forests cover 65% of Indonesia's total area, forestry and land use are the main contributors to Indonesia's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry 2016). Peatland Restoration Agency was established in 2016 and engaged all stakeholders and actors (private, local governments, students, and communities) in a national program to control climate change in forests and peatlands. The main contributor to emission reduction in 2019 was the forestry and peatland sector. More than 80% of emission reductions are achieved through afforestation, forestation, and restoration of forest and peatland. For other LMTs, BECCS is still not implemented in Indonesia. The mainstream first pathway to implement BECCS technologies in Indonesia is through biomass, biogas, biofuel, thermal biomethane and co-firing for coal power plants (DEN 2019).

On the other hand, biochar is implemented in many locations in Indonesia. Some pilot cases are existing. Biochar is a potential alternative to improve soil quality and restore degraded land. Other advantages include a slower decomposition process and resistance to microorganisms. In agriculture, biochar has functions to reduce soil acidity, increase nutrient availability, and bind nutrients. For example, biochar can be applied on land with high acidity (around 3-5) to increase the pH. Also, biochar can be used for the areas with less water to bind this little water. The Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan), MoA, introduced the manufacture and application of biochar through technical guidance in several locations. The Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) suggested giving biochar gradually every season by utilising agricultural waste as the raw materials in the field (Bardono 2018). Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) has classified BIOCHAR SP 50, a simple technology from agricultural waste, as an agricultural product (Balitbangtan 2019). However, this

potential LMT is not included yet in the government priority. Hence, biochar implementation in Indonesia is still in the pilot stage.

In the agriculture management, organic fertiliser and biopesticides through fertilisers, organic subsidised and procurement of Organic Fertiliser Processing Unit (UPPO) are utilised. The utilisation of livestock and agricultural waste is conducted. Additional activities are the improvement of animal feed supplements by using reforestation. In 2019, the most significant emission reduction in agricultural cultivation technology activities was achieved. MoA recorded 114.74 million tonnes of CO₂ reduction from 2010-2019 (BAPPENAS 2020). For afforestation and reforestation in Indonesia, the government of Indonesia relies on reforestation and afforestation to counterbalance deforestation rates, along with other measures such as fire prevention and the halting of new permit issuance. During one year in both 2017-2018 and 2018-2019, 53.9 thousand ha and 31 thousand ha of forest were recovered due to these reforestation efforts (BAPPENAS 2020). These efforts successfully reduced net deforestation (gross deforestation – reforestation) in the last few years (KLHK 2020).

While in the peatland sector, aside from natural phenomena such as El Niño that frequently trigger fires and decomposition, human activities such as peatland clearings and conversion contribute to peatland's increased vulnerability. Those activities make forests and peatlands more prone to fires and decomposition. In the last decades, 6 out of 14.4 million ha of peatland has been converted from natural peat forests into agricultural land and industrial plantation (Masripatin et al. 2017). To address this problem, KLHK established the Peatland Restoration Agency (Badan Restorasi Gambut/BRG) in 2016 to manage and facilitate peatland restoration in seven priority provinces which still need more efforts to reduce emissions in the peatland sector. According to the Strategic Plan of BRG 2016-2020 (**BRG 2016**), BRG mainly relies on three strategic action plans to restore Indonesian peatland: i) rewetting, ii) revegetation, and ii) peatland-based socioeconomic revitalisation for the locals.

2.5 million ha of peatland will be subjected to rewetting by 2020 to restore its hydrologic characteristics by maintaining peatland surface water level and groundwater table, especially during drought. Also, rewetting could minimise the risk of peat fires and restore peatland to its original condition. While rewetting is designed to restore drained peatland, revegetation is designed for degraded peatland (peatland that has lost its full or partial vegetation). The purpose of revegetation is to restore the peatland ecosystem and improve land coverage by planting trees that are endemic to the land. The target of revegetation by 2020 covers 670,000 ha of peatland. The last focused restoration program is a peatland-based socioeconomic revitalisation that aims at encouraging people living in the proximity of the peatland area to participate in taking care of the degraded peatland. The very idea of this strategy is to assist the locals in improving their economy via peatland-based economic activities. By 2020, 185,000 ha of peatland is targeted to be restored for economic purposes. However, due to the limitation of the modelling tool, the peatland is not covered in the stakeholders engagement activities.

2 Regional Modelling Results

2.1 Assumptions for models

Afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, no-tillage, biochar, and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) were the LMTs modelled for ASEAN countries. Figure 1 presents an overview of

assumptions for the entire ASEAN region used in the LandSHIFT model, showing the absolute spatial allocation of selected LMTs.

Figure 1: LandSHIFT results for ASEAN - spatial allocation of land over time

In terms of **cropland dynamics**, the reference scenario (blue line) sees a consistent increase throughout the century, while the moderate ambition scenario (yellow line) exhibits lower cropland, plateauing around 2060, and the high ambition scenario (green line) maintains total cropland close to 2050 levels. Breaking down cropland into bioenergy (dotted line) and food production (dashed line), the reference scenario shows no additional **bioenergy production**, whereas both moderate and high scenarios experience an uptake with minimal differences between them. The extent of agricultural cropland managed without **no-tillage** is depicted, with reduced area in high scenario due to the assumed increased crop yield. The last plot illustrates the **fraction of bioenergy feedstocks** directed to Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) or biochar, both moderate and high ambitious scenarios peak around 2060 earlier than the reference scenario. Given **pasture area** is limited in the region, its area has negligible changes over time. The stable or slightly increasing cropland, combined with unchanged pasture area, negates actual **afforestation**, yet the reduction in cropland compared to the reference scenario results in avoided **deforestation**. The Assumptions are described in greater detail in Landmarc Deliverable 6.3.

2.2 Overview on modelling results

Figures provide a comprehensive overview of the results from the coupled model simulation, showing land use fraction and carbon differences on land between the Reference, Moderate, and High ambition scenarios. Notably, the distinctions are more pronounced in the comparison between the High ambition and Reference scenarios. The two graphs reveal a **significant reduction in cropland and a corresponding increase in natural cover** across most areas compared to the reference case. Interestingly, pasture areas remain relatively stable, except for the noted decrease in southeast China, which contrasts with the

Southeast Asian, while the alterations in carbon sequestered by vegetation predominantly occur in regions where there has been a rise in natural cover, underscoring the impact of avoided deforestation. In areas like Western Indonesia, carbon storage occurs through bioenergy-driven carbon capture, where minimal changes in cropland or natural cover are observed, which results from the conversion of cropland into carbon capture storage for bioenergy generation.

Figure 2: Land use fraction (top) and carbon on land (bottom) differences between Reference and Moderate Ambition Case in 2095

Figure 3: Land use fraction (top) and carbon on land (bottom) differences between Reference and High Ambition Case in 2095.

2.3 Context for discussion and use of modelling results

Participants provided feedback after the modelling results, highlighting four key areas, strategies to avoid expansion, the necessity of synergizing various land types and uses, concerns about the unstable carbon sequestration ability of LMTs, and a newly identified business model to enhance biochar development in Southeast Asia.

Regarding expansion, participants emphasized the significance of the narrowing yield gap, or the gap between yield and production area, as revealed in the modelling results. They viewed it as an opportunity to increase production while potentially reducing the need for rapid and extensive expansion. They also recognized the connection between the yield gap and afforestation, providing opportunities for reforestation efforts. Another aspect of expansion discussed was the trend of abandoned cropland linked to urban migration, as seen in Nepal, where cropland and pasture were left unused. Participants stressed the importance of considering this dynamic in modelling and proposed exploring solutions to reduce cropland expansion related to abandonment. They recommended investigating policies, natural tools, and organic agriculture methods to repurpose abandoned land.

Additionally, participants addressed the trend in deforestation and afforestation, acknowledging an increase in forest land cover but expressing concerns about the quality of those new forests compared to indigenous ones with regards to carbon sequestration capacity.

Another key point raised by participants focused on synergizing efforts, particularly advocating for collaboration between the agriculture sector and forestry to address the land use competition. They proposed a joint effort to map areas with high potential for greenhouse gas emission reduction in order to make the most effective land use decision, emphasizing the need for strategic decisions to maximize impact within resource constraints.

Participants also acknowledged a valuable academic opportunity for biochar but identified a practical gap on the ground with few proven business models. However, a successful model in Cambodia provided promise for scaling up. The participants suggested a holistic, integrated approach for biochar development, emphasizing the need to identify centralized locations with large biomass sources to reduce logistics costs and make biochar production more affordable. They called for a strategic Southeast Asia strategy on biochar production.

3 Summary of Breakout Group Discussions

3.1 Climate Ambition

3.1.1 Breakout Group 1

The group first chose to discuss the LMT afforestation. To bring this LMT to scale, Group 1 proposed the following measures that could boost LMT uptake: better governance and regulations, a better political commitment to LMT uptake, more stakeholder engagement and well-defined targets.

The trade-offs the group identified to scaling up involve food security and economic loss if land use change leads to decreased agricultural production. Participants also discussed solutions to mitigate these trade-offs, benefiting afforestation scaling up, for example, the adoption of genetic technology for enhanced agricultural productivity, the implementation of carbon credits to make afforestation more profitable (and therefore make up for economic losses when agricultural land is not used but afforested) and obtaining certifications for products like coffee and oil palm, proving no association with deforestation, boost international exportability. Certification and increased exportability were seen as particularly relevant to the EU market by participants, given its status as a large importer of agricultural products to ASEAN and the recent introduction of the EU deforestation regulation regulating products linked to deforestation

As far as the co-benefits of afforestation as a LMT was concerned, participants mentioned increased export opportunities for agricultural commodities but hazards, such as wildfires, were identified as potential barriers to scaling of afforestation. Therefore, planning afforestation activities carefully (including taking into consideration those and other hazards) would be good to drive scaling. As a way of anchoring the group discussions, group 1 decided to discuss how to achieve zero deforestation by 2030 with a 3.2 GT carbon removal goal, as outlined in the inception report. Interestingly, participants unanimously agreed on the necessity of a top-down approach to reach these goals which is somewhat contradictory to what some researchers often recommend (bottom-up approaches) Indeed, an interesting consideration is the trade-off between ambitious goals delivered from the top down, and local engagement from the bottom up. This raises questions about the priority of a top-down approach involving large companies and government decisions versus a bottom-up approach with active involvement from the local community and how to strike the right balance.

For the scaling of agroforestry, group 1 advocated government support in the forms of economic incentives and subsidies as options to facilitate scaling. Participants mentioned collaboration with scientists and the use of MRV (measurement, reporting and verification) digital tools of to make carbon sequestration more effective. Generally, participants argued that providing available financial resources was crucial for agroforestry to scale. Suggestions to facilitate that scaling were the use of carbon credits, to make agroforestry systems economically more attractive. Participants also discussed the difficulties of attracting private sector finance to agroforestry systems while at the same time acknowledging the long-term benefits. To address this difficulty of getting the private sector involved, participants proposed the development of a business model with phased revenue generation and clear, and encouraged the stakeholders drives innovation for financial models like blended finance. Risks discussed by the participants included price fluctuations of produce and biomass impacting farmers, pest control challenges, and uncertainties in product availability due to climate changes. For instance, a participant argued that some agricultural innovations and solutions, also in agroforestry systems might not be available in a 2C world compared to a 1.5C world. As far as the co-benefits of agroforestry were discussed, participants mentioned its significant contribution to adaptation and resilience.

Another LMT discussed by group 1 was biochar . Measures that would drive scaling included the setup of regional quality control mechanisms or facilitating the collaboration with industries for residue collection. Moreover, participants argued that introducing digitalization for MRV to reduce costs could enable smaller farmers to access carbon credits which would make biochar more profitable. Also, more research with a quantitative estimate of potentials and impacts was suggested as a science based c guide to facilitate private-sector investment. Operating at an industrial scale poses the risk of amplifying the carbon footprint during waste collection from diverse farmlands. Conversely, in smaller units, uncertainties revolve around the efficacy of biochar production and its carbon sequestration benefits. This underscores the critical importance of robust measurement, reporting, and verification mechanisms, particularly in small-scale operations. The land tenure and quality and availability of feedstock are also considered risks in biochar scaling up. The Co-benefits of promoting biochar as discussed by the participants were its use as fertilizer, an increased health benefit from avoiding the burning of crop residues in the field, and the positive impact biochar has on biodiversity, arguments usually also found in the literature.

In addition to aforementioned LMTs, group 1 also briefly discussed Biofuels. Biofuels stand a better chance of securing significant funding in the ASEAN context, given its association with renewable energy, which makes scaling up much easier, and due to climate goals in both transport and energy sectors. When it comes to biofuels, participants argued that current policies and blending mandates would encourage the production of biofuels in Southeast Asia. Also, capacity building like the training of farmers was deemed critical for technology adoption when scaling up. However, group 1 noted concerns about trade-offs with food security and ecosystem preservation (and land competition) when discussing biofuel promotion and potential diversion of land use, human resources from other LMTs due to the biofuel subsidies are noted. Another risk such as reduced farmer engagement would arise if large corporations come to dominate biofuel trading. Co-benefits include biofuel contributing to electricity and biochar production using non-fossil fuel, reinforcing their strategic carbon removal goal.

	Scaling options	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards	Co-benefits	Ambition	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation & forest management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good regulation and active political will (apply to all LMTs) • Active stakeholder engagement (apply to all LMTs) • Participatory knowledge creation (apply to all LMTs) • Clear presentation of quantitative targets to indicate the scale of actions (apply to all LMTs) • Implementation of carbon credits for carbon products • Certification of products (come out of LMTs) to increase exportability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease in agricultural land and products production leading to the trade-off food security (solution: utilize effective technology to enhance agricultural productivity) • Economic loss of private sector (solution: certification of products and carbon credit) • Fire disaster when scale up without plan • Land ownership is important in scaling up: community-based vs company owned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher exportability (if certificated): Increased access to European markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zero deforestation in 2030 • Quantitative target: 3.2 GT carbon removal in Asia 	—
Agroforestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic incentives and subsidies to local communities to promote agroforestry expansion • Deep engagement with scientists • Digitalization for monitoring to track outcomes and mitigate risks, for example, good spatial planning tools to measure carbon sequestered are needed, • Carbon credit mechanism to increase profitability, such as CDM • A less risky business model: a model with generating revenue at each phase throughout life cycle of agroforestry can make benefits more visible and attract investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price fluctuation of agriculture products • Insects infestation which requires pest control • Unavailability of certain products/solution with a 2-degree temperature increase by 2050 and/or 2100 (compared to 1.5C) • The complexity of agroforestry leads to uncertain business models: Challenging to invest due to its long-term and systemic benefits. (Suggestions: include generating revenue per phase for investment; stakeholder innovation to facilitate financial investment) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation and resilience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative target: 2GT carbon removal in Asia 	Difficult to image what is happening in 2050 and 2100 due to the uncertainty of changed climate
Biochar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality control to standardize various biochar quality with different residue types • Collaboration with industrial sectors for residue collection and reuse • Adoption of new digitalization methods for MRV to reduce costs and enable smaller farmers to access carbon credits • Research with quantitative estimate and good methodology can guide private sector on investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk in Industrial sale operation: Assess carbon footprint of waste collection for minimal volumes • Risk in smaller unit challenges: Increased risks associated with operating the unit; monitoring becomes crucial • unclear tenure and land rights in the region. • Different quality of waste as feedstock 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used as fertilizer and benefit to the land • Health benefits from banning the residue • Enhance Biodiversity through the invasive plant species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative target: 1 GT carbon removal potential in Asia 	—

BECCS/biofuel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrinsic alignment with renewable energy allows its larger funding availability • The blending mandate serves as a scaling option for biofuel • Implementation of training and education for farmers to adopt new technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biofuel incentives may take attention away from the other LMTs (suggestions: adopt systematic approach) • Food security and ecosystem trade-off: promoting biofuel balances challenges with food security and ecosystem preservation • Large corporations dominate biofuel trading, risking local farmer engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biofuel benefits electricity and biochar production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative target: 0.6 GT carbon removal in Asia 	—
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Table 2: Summary of Climate Ambition evaluation by **Stakeholder Group 1** for the chosen LMTs according to the key issues, enablers and/or barriers

3.1.2 Breakout Group 2

In terms of **afforestation and forest management**, the participants pointed out a range of opportunities for scaling this LMT. These include PES mechanism, market demand of timber and non-timber products, and benefits to smallholder farmers through incentive policies on afforestation and allocation of forestland for farmers (co-management of forests). However, a number of potential barriers and risks were discussed. There is a certain trade-off between afforestation and land use for agricultural production. Additionally, without proper policy guidance, the most prominent afforestation practice of acacia monoculture may lead to soil degradation. Thus, both forest quality and forest cover would be of equal importance. Also, benefits of smallholder farmers should be part of the policy making process. Besides, uncertainties such as fluctuation of market demand and prices of timber products and PES threshold per hectare might influence motivation for adoption of local community members. Co-benefits include ecosystem services and eco-tourism industry development, particularly for protective forests.

For **Agroforestry**, incentive policy, carbon market demand and donor-funded projects were stated as the main drivers for scaling this LMT. Market risks from monoculture of a single crop might promote a transition toward agroforestry (intercropping) practices. Such transition is affordable for smallholder farmers. Nonetheless, there are a number of barriers to replicating agroforestry. Farmers have limited awareness about long-term benefits of agroforestry. Their limited understanding and/or limited access to technical guidelines for adoption of agroforestry. Their concern of reduced productivity of main commodity crops within the system may hinder adoption of agroforestry practices. Despite the stated co-benefits of diversified livelihoods from the agroforestry systems, there are still a number of uncertainties and risks. For example, upfront investment costs for initial setup of agroforestry systems are rather high, which are not affordable by resource-poor farmers. Lack of young labourers in rural areas might hinder adoption of the labour-intensive agroforestry practices. Finally, market demand of monoculture crop (e.g. durian for the Chinese market) would hamper the LMT adoption. To overcome such barriers and risks, government commitments, international cooperation and recognition of agroforestry as a beneficial system (via national policy) together with accessible technical guidelines will be essential.

Biochar has recently been interested by the governments and private sector companies in the region. Opportunities for scaling up biochar include: government commitments and incentive policies, and new technology to produce reduced emission biochar (compared to the conventional open burning of rice husks). However, there are some barriers to adoption and replication of biochar such as expensive prices, slow impact on soil properties and fertility. Moreover, unintended impact occurred in Indonesia (e.g. deforestation) due cutting forest trees for producing biochar. Co-benefits include: partial replacement of fertilizer input (NPK) for crops, utilization of agricultural byproducts as biochar producing materials, etc. Having said that, there would be a gradual progress of biochar adoption due to limited evidence of the actual benefits of biochar on soil health and crop yields, and therefore low market demand.

Climate-smart rice production was another LMT of interest among the participants since rice is among the most popular agricultural crops in the region. While the benefits are evident through reduced emission and input costs, and water saving, continuing awareness campaign in accordance with technology transfer for behaviour change are required.

Finally, **mangrove management** was stated with multiple benefits of high carbon storage, improved biodiversity and climate change adaptation. However, some barriers comprise limited awareness of local

community members, lack of technical guidelines for effective production and management. Mangroves are also highly vulnerable to tidal waves. Incentive policy, capacity building and commitments of both government and local communities are critical in replicating this LMT.

Table 3: Summary of Climate Ambition evaluation by Stakeholder Group 2 for chosen LMTs according to key issues, enablers and/or barriers

LMTs	Scaling options	Uncertainty and Risks	Co-benefits	Ambition	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market demand for timber and non-timber products; Policy support, including a long-term policy to improve forest quality; Benefits from the sustainable forest management models. Payment of ecosystem services (PES) mechanism; Co-management by the government and local communities. <p>Barriers of opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The price of PES could be not competitive e.g., Vietnam. Ownership: Forestland is managed by the government, so a benefit sharing mechanism could be useful to ensure other stakeholders' benefits 	<p>Uncertainty and Risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forestry fire; Small farmers' benefits are not considered in policy making; Carbon market may experience fluctuating prices; Trade-off between forestry quality vs. forest cover: current monoculture of acacia leads to reduce soil quality, etc. Competition with agricultural land due to afforestation; Uncertain market demand on timber products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Eco-tourism industry development; Enhanced biodiversity and ecosystem services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognition of all aspects: biodiversity; management, sustainability, etc. Planting without tending and maintaining the forest. 	
Agroforestry	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial options: Financial assistance from the government; donor-funded projects; Carbon markets Affordable for smallholder farmers (in case of transition from the monocropping systems); <p>Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited understanding of technology and guidance Farmers' limited awareness: Traditional preference for monocropping over the long- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High investment costs for establishing new agroforestry systems (particularly on sloping land). Insufficient agricultural labour and predominated by the elder (due to migration of young labourers to big cities and industrial zones). Criteria from different countries (e.g., China requires monocropping on durian). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient use of labour. Diversification of livelihoods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognitions of agroforestry production as a beneficial system (national policy); government commitments; finance support Easy to adopt leads to large scale replication. Regional cooperation; 	

	<p>term benefits of agroforestry, coupled with concerns that agroforestry may decrease productivity, restricts land adoption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low price of crops in the intercropping systems. • Long production cycle vs. immediate needs of poor farmers. 				
Biochar	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralised policy; incentives for farmers; creating demand of biochar • Technology to produce reduced emission biochar • Gov's commitment & policy to promote adoption and produce standard guidelines. • Incentives for farmer adoption • <p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive prices: not instant effectiveness of biochar on soil properties and the expensive costs leads to low adoption • cutting forest trees to produce biochar (deforestation) (Indonesia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to best use of biomass • Limited motivation due to slow impact of biochar on soil properties; no improvement on crop yield. • Biochar's is in its early stage (not affordable for farmers without subsidy). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced NPK use. • Reduce deforestation. • Enhance biodiversity. • Potential use of byproducts for producing biochar, e.g., bio-pesticides • Carbon market pricing -> affordable for farmers • Incorporating agricultural waste-derived biochar into agroforestry systems for circular agriculture and enhanced soil fertility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production vs. need in some countries. • Market/demand side (carbon removal) is critical. • Balanced use of biochar, organic and chemical fertilizers -> boost this LMT adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow progress: step by step approach -> scaling will be increased gradually. • Need time for proven effectiveness
Mangroves	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More carbon storage; but difficult to maintain. • Community-based management. • Large area for adoption of this LMT. <p>Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited awareness of local people; • Require commitment of both government and local communities, having incentives for mangrove management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly vulnerable to tidal waves • Lack of technology for production and management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon storage • Biodiversity • Climate change adaptation. 		

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Rice Fields</p>	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct seeding (reduced labour). • Efficient use of water resource ; • NDCs drive the change: most countries care about rice production. <p>Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to enhance awareness and capacity building for farmers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low information on field-level management. • Unavailability of technology • At the pilot stage, difficult to replicate in large scale due to limited awareness; require behavioural change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change adaptation • Water/soil management • Cost reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machinery production • Direct seeding • Land levelling 	
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3.1.3 Breakout Group 3

Participants discussed scaling up afforestation with a focus on empowering local communities as land stewards. Barriers included governance issues (ministerial conflicts, policy disjuncture), unsustainable ambitions, and business model limitations. Community empowerment, appropriate native species selection, bridging the policy-implementation gap, and addressing underdeveloped business models were deemed crucial. The uncontrollable carbon market, monocropping trends, and climate change-induced hazards posed risks to afforestation. The participants also raised the need to separate intrinsic and external co-benefits, avoiding emission double counting. Likewise highlighted are the long-term co-benefits of afforestation, linking biodiversity and human health. Managed with local communities, afforestation was seen as enhancing their economic benefits.

Overcoming barriers to scaling agroforestry involves addressing the complexity of its management, especially for farmers accustomed to monoculture. Ecological education and the documentation of tacit knowledge on sustainable land practices, natural ingredients, and traditional medicine are essential to navigate this. The opportunities lie in intercropping and multi-cropping, not confined to rural areas but extending to urban landscapes by incorporating urban farms. Despite facing challenges from natural hazards and perceived economic risks, agroforestry offers diverse yields that can mitigate uncertainties. Multi cropping, though economically risky, proves more resilient in the long term against hazards and pests while enhancing soil quality. Participants emphasized the importance of a high-ambition scenario, highlighting the potential loss of certain food products without increased efforts. Strategies include seed and sapling conservation, financial support for farmers to allow land rest and boost sequestration, and education on optimal fund utilization. The vision for 2050 includes local seed storage facilities and integrating urban food production into the concept of smart cities.

To advance Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), substantial investment in research and technology is imperative for its upscaling, given its current immaturity. The development and upscaling of BECCS require robust policies or standards, emphasizing the centrality of partnerships between research institutes and the public and private sectors. Despite the high scalability potential, risks include technology failures and geographic limitations depending on bioenergy source availability. Forest fires and illegal land use expansion for bioenergy crops also pose concerns. Job creation is anticipated, with a suggestion to establish a social fund from profits made from the technologies. While there is potential for trading sequestered carbon in the uncertain carbon market, it also entails risks. Research on bioresource diversification is essential for sustainable supply chains, emphasizing an ecosystem approach to bioenergy. High ambitions involve enhancing carbon sequestration and reducing emissions through BECCS, requiring a shift in mindset toward energy generation without burning.

Addressing challenges in sustainable agriculture requires tackling issues such as soil degradation, geographical limitations, and unsustainable post-harvest land practices, including burning. Emissions from agricultural production and the need for climate-resilient crop varieties and systems add complexity. Climate change-induced risks, like altered weather patterns and extreme events, further challenge agricultural practices. However, agricultural lands can act as buffers for natural forests and wildlife corridors. Beyond environmental benefits, agriculture ensures food supplies, fostering self-sufficiency for growers. Prioritizing agricultural education, particularly for young people, especially women, is crucial to scale up. High ambitions in sustainable agriculture focus on reducing carbon footprints and diversifying

staple foods locally. The integration of AI and satellite technology for monitoring and evaluation is proposed, emphasizing the attraction of a younger workforce to the agriculture sector.

Table 4: Summary of Climate Ambition evaluation by Stakeholder Group 3 for chosen LMTs according to key issues, enablers and/or barriers

LMTs	Scaling options	Uncertainty and Risks	Co-benefits	Ambition	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empowerment of local communities <p>Appropriate selection of native species</p> <p>Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of ministerial integration Disjuncture between national and regional policy Low level of meaningful stakeholder engagement Unsustainable and unrealistic ambition <p>Underdeveloped business model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly uncontrollable carbon market Afforestation could involve increased monocropping rather than a biodiverse forest <p>Natural hazards and man-made threat</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity and health <p>Increased economic benefit for local people</p>	<p>High ambitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rational and sustainable investment Enabling policy environment Shift in mindset Reduced focus on GDP as a measure of well-being <p>Cooperation among farmers to collectively carry out planned agriculture</p> <p>Needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local investment and bottom-up engagement at all levels <p>Informed decision for planned agriculture</p>	<p>Between the present and 2050, sustainable forest management to limit forest leakage should be underway to allow for forest restoration. In 2100, an integrated relationship between people and nature will be necessary for human survival.</p>
Agroforestry	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Herbs and medicine, as well as wild food, can offer opportunities for scaling up Cities can also be involved in incorporating urban farm into the landscape <p>Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry requires complicated management <p>Ecological education should be in place to overcome the barrier</p>	<p>While mixed food production can provide diverse yield, it may appear risky for farmers who are used to planting in a market-oriented manner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yielding food and medicine Making the land more resistant to hazards/pests <p>Soil enhancement</p>	<p>High ambitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In situ and ex-situ conservation of food plants <p>Financial support for farmers to rest their land and not cultivate to increase sequestration and forest restoration</p>	<p>By 2050, local seed storage facilities will be available for food plants. The idea of a smart city should also incorporate urban food production.</p>

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Agriculture</p>	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate resilience crop varieties and systems such as cropping calendar and rotational practice <p>Barrier:</p> <p>Degrading soil quality, unsustainable post-harvest land management (e.g. burning)</p> <p>Low enrolment in education related to farming</p>	<p>Climate viability and extreme weather events</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving as a buffer for natural forest and wildlife corridors <p>Providing food supplies, which can enable self-sufficiency for growers</p>	<p>High ambitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowering carbon footprint from agriculture • Diversifying staple food for each locality <p>AI and Satellite technology for monitoring and evaluation should be incorporated into farming practices while also attracting a younger workforce into the agriculture sector.</p>	
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">BECCS</p>	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More investment in research and technology • Robust policy or standard to govern the development of BECCS • The partnership between research institutes <p>Public and private sector</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology failures • Technology applicability • Forest fires <p>Illegal land use expansion and exploitation for bioenergy crops</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job creation <p>The potential gain from trading the sequestered carbon in the carbon market, but the market is currently highly uncertain</p>	<p>High ambitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem approach to bioenergy • More research on how to grow plants and adapt to ambition scenario <p>Enhanced carbon sequestration and lower carbon emission using BECCS</p>	<p>Research and shift in mindset: how to generate energy without burning</p>

3.2 Regional engagement

Include a cleaned-up matrix for each breakout group and briefly explain (avoid too much text and focus especially on the matrix to keep it concise). Note that each matrix can be one page (probably in landscape layout), leaving one page for explanation.

After discussing the LMTs and the barriers and opportunities as well as the risk to their scaling, workshop participants were now invited to discuss how increased regional cooperation and coordination could drive LMT scaling at the regional level. This exercise was mainly influenced by the ideas of several decades of social- and political science research (especially in the context of studies of the European Union and its functioning) that argue that cooperation, as well as economic and political integration, are usually beneficial for the scaling of technologies and multilateral trade in products. Integration is said to contribute to the market building (Orcalli 2017), allows for the pooling of resources and efficient allocation, strengthens the exchange of knowledge (Bößner et al. 2020) and is generally thought of as beneficial for prosperity (de Bruijn, Kox, and Lejour 2008; Moravcsik 2005; Mion and Ponattu 2019). Therefore, this exercise asked participants to envision how stronger regional cooperation and integration might help the adoption of LMTs. From a methodological point of view, the organisation team had to strike a balance between not biasing the participants too much while at the same time providing enough guidance on what the research team meant by regional cooperation and integration and which kind of qualifiers (or indicators) could be used to measure or assess regional cooperation and integration. In the end, participants were provided with three broad categories of integration and cooperation qualifiers, namely 'economic integration and harmonisation', 'formal governance mechanisms' and 'research cooperation and technology transfer', with each category containing several sub-qualifiers (which, however, were not revealed to the participants in order to let them come up with their own qualifiers).

3.2.1 Breakout Group 1

The qualifier proposed by Group 1 when it comes to economic integration and harmonisation was a carbon crediting mechanism that benefits developers and local communities through bilateral carbon credit markets which is based on Paris Agreement Article 6.4. This qualifier can boost the adoption of LMT by providing positive compensation or discount on tax from cross-border agreement, particularly led by government and private sector collaboration. Implementing this qualifier requires strong government involvement and addressing issues such as the lack of regulation and national sovereignty concerns. Key actors for implementation include governments, private sectors in the region.

Participants then discussed qualifiers that could drive LMT uptake regionally when it comes to regional governance mechanisms. One measure discussed were regional quality standards. By having regional quality standards in place, participants argued that this would reduce the risks for the private sector to buy into LMT development but would also increase the scalability of all LMTs. To implement regional quality standards, participants argued that those standards should be based on trustworthy research and on regular communication among involved actors. Governments should create mechanisms to gather insights of how such standards could be adopted and what to include, and businesses collaborating across borders could facilitate their implementation according to participants. Key actors who could drive the implementation of quality standards include regional organizations like ASEAN, large companies, Corporations involved in land-related activities, and financial institutes. While debating actors that could drive the adoption of quality standards, ASEAN's role was debated with some participants advocating for the body's functionality and direct impact on national government agendas while, others argued in favour

of private sector-driven initiatives on quality standards given ASEAN's perceived low efficiency and diverse interests. One participant highlighted the importance of recognizing the need for a minimal coalition for success and leveraging regional organizations like ASEAN to push the agenda forward.

For the category of 'Research Cooperation & Technology Transfer', participants identified network building as an important qualifier that could drive more regional cooperation on LMT implementation. Those (transnational) networks would advance LMTs by sharing best practices and experiences and by advancing regional research cooperation and partnerships with universities. Promoting collaboration within the business sector, participants stress avoiding competition but facilitate working among companies involved in the same supply chain. Via those networks, engagement with the scientific community and the private sector could be promoted, therefore utilizing scientific insights to drive LMT adoption. As a consensus, participants argued that technology transfer between countries would be needed and that this would apply to all LMTs. and one of the key element is to build up the practical knowledge and technology capacity at the community level. Participant suggested that facilitating technology transfer could be done through pilot projects or stakeholder engagement forums where people could learn from each another and from successfully implemented case studies. Participants called on the government to make funding available to implement such networks. Other key actors identified by participants to drive this technology and research cooperation were ministries, high-level university researchers, local communities, and private businesses. Participants also highlighted the need to include Community Based Organizations (CBOs) in those research and knowledge sharing networks and suggested to include them into those research networks. One risk identified was the role of private sector actors who could either drive LMT adoption (see points above) but could also obstruct progress on and within those research networks by imposing their agenda. Also, competitive advantage is often key for private sector players, and they might be reluctant to share their knowledge. Therefore, participants argued that research networks would need careful management, and instead of inviting business stakeholders from the whole value chain, compartmentalisation of research networks might mitigate the reluctance of the private sector (giving up 'company secrets' on smaller parts of the value chain might be more feasible and palatable for companies than overall sharing of knowhow and experience).

Table 5: Summary of Regional Engagement evaluation by **Stakeholder Group 1** for chosen LMTs according to key issues, enablers and/or barriers

	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier	What are the main barriers to this barrier? What is strengthening/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> carbon credit mechanism benefiting developers and local communities (Paris Agreement Article 6.4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible for all LMTs, the economic compensation benefits local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement positive compensation from the carbon credit mechanism leading by bilateral or regional carbon credit market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government Private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of regulation National sovereignty concern when implementing carbon credit mechanism 	
Formal mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional quality standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> will benefit all LMTs Quality standards also facilitate private-sector buy-in. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trustworthy research to guide the regional quality standards Governments collect information and viewpoints from the private sector, NGOs and different stakeholders to feed into the standards Regular communication between actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional organizations like ASEAN to enhance engagement Financial institutes offering low interest rate, such as Development banks, like ADB Finance actors, countries like Norway, which fund afforestation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diverging interests of the government Low efficiency of inter-government collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognize the necessity of a minimal coalition for success instead of relying on inter-governmental collaboration. Host countries of ASEAN have potential to push the agenda.
Research cooperation & technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional research and cooperation networks and partnership including a variety of stakeholders (science, civil society, private sector) Business sector collaboration networks to share knowledge and best practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible for all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foster cooperation and communication between a large group of stakeholders Implement pilot projects that could serve as a learning case study Compartmentalization and zoning in on specific issues might increase willingness of the private sector to participate and foster synergies (instead of competitive mindsets). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Related Ministries, researcher professors from high-level universities to provide guidance Local communities Private business actors (Note: avoid putting competition in the same room but compartmentalization) Researchers in the field provide guidance, including markets and targets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CBOs are not presented. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CBOs should be invited into the research network and form a CBO network The private sector's stakeholders use fora to obstruct stakeholders' agendas.

3.2.2 Breakout Group 2

Group two focused on trade, tax, and value chains as qualifying economic integration and harmonisation indicators. The participants emphasized the strong connection between LMTs and livelihoods, highlighting the importance of LMTs to benefit local communities, particularly those dependent on natural resources for their income. The discussion covered biochar products, given their market limitations in the region. The limitations of companies producing biochar added to the complexity of promoting its use and attracting more companies to work in this sector due to its profitability. The participants acknowledge that regional engagement, such as ASEAN, NGOs, Universities, Research institutes and private sectors, could play a critical role in driving the adoption of biochar. Since biochar was not prevalent compared to other LMTs in the region, such as agroforestry and rice cultivation, technical assistance and funding for joint research and capacity building were identified as essential elements to further encourage and support its adoption.

In related to Formal and Governance Mechanisms, participants highlighted the significance of policy coherence, regional collaboration, and coordination to foster the adoption of LMTs. Often time, existing policies are done in silos and only specific to certain sectors even though its' application affects many other sectors. Regulations concerning agriculture, forest commodities and trade/ industry not always aligned, and this is where a platform that consolidates initiative affecting LMTs to ensure effective coordination would be needed. Participants also discussed the importance to establish regional working groups as valuable strategy to promote the adoption of LMTs. However, they also recognized that existing working groups might already existed but lack of efficiency, unclear mandates from their respective countries, and not having decision-making authority. Hence, the participants proposed the formation of a working group with the capacity to mainstream recommendation into policy-making processes. Low capacity and limited resources were identified as barriers and to overcome these challenges; the group explored the potential for engaging with private sectors, capacity building and develop policies that incentives the adoption of LMTs.

Aligned with the recommendation on Governance Mechanism, participants emphasized the significance of regional network and collaborative programs to enhance research cooperation and facilitate technology transfer. This includes initiating new platforms or leveraging existing ones of regional research networks, universities partnerships, exchange programs, and joint research initiatives on relevant subjects. Participants discussed the need for more research and information related to biochar, especially with its limited availability and applicability in the region. Another important research focus was on rice, considering the commodity and relevant LMTs' importance to the region and its significant contribution to climate change due to its methane emission from traditional planting practices. Participants also discussed the importance of local communities to ensure they understand the value and co-benefits associated with specific LMTs. Beyond research networks and universities, the group also recommends unlocking the media's potential to disseminate information and raise awareness, particularly targeting a broader public audience.

Table 6: Summary of Regional Engagement evaluation by **Stakeholder Group 2** for chosen LMTs according to key issues, enablers and/or barriers

	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthening/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trade Tariff Transparent Value Chain Reduced tax for LMT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The market for Biochar will expand if there is a reduced trade tariff. Certification for agricultural products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional agreement to support these LMT implementations since most of them have transboundary effects and context. Credit exchange Standard certification for all products to ensure standard quality and best practices Blockchain and other technology to collect the data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ASEAN Council Private Sectors and other relevant companies NGOs, Universities, Research Institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The market for biochar is still small; hence, it is difficult for SMEs or other small-scale industries to gain profits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical assistance Micro loan for smallholder farmers
Formal governance mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting policies to promote LMTs Framework for partnership Inter-ministerial agreement and coordination. Policy coherence -> different policies related to biochar, Agri products, and trade/industry are often not aligned. Involving youth to raise awareness and also showcase job opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LMTs related to afforestation, agroforestry, and biochar These are three LMTs that can be overlapped, and with clear policy support (policy coherence), they can be managed better. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platform to gather all initiatives, to avoid working in silos and clarity on government agencies/institutions' roles and responsibilities Regional working groups to help promote and regulate the LMTs Mainstreaming working group recommendations in policy-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperatives Extension services not only in agriculture but across sectors Regional institutions and universities (e.g. AIT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low capacity and mostly the implementation still low scale Lack of resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private sector engagement The policy that promotes incentives Capacity building activities
Research cooperation and technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional research network University and exchange programme Joint research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biochar Rice field (methane reduction) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community practice Training and technology transfer Conference, hub, joint research Bilateral agreement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Institutions and Extension Network Provincial Governments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of seed funding to do research/cooperation Silos approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness campaign for consumer Research on valuation of LMTs

				<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Media Influencers• Consumers		<p>and understand its co-benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Government provides early investment
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3.2.3 Breakout Group 3

In terms of Economic Integration and Harmonization, qualifiers deemed beneficial especially for afforestation and biochar include carbon credit pricing, standardization of carbon pricing systems, carbon credit certification, and tax incentives, specifically rebates and subsidies. The concern is that the implementation of these qualifiers faces barriers such as fluctuating market conditions, economic valuation challenges, and the risk of double counting carbon credits. Solutions proposed include transparent reporting of carbon inventory in forms of open national inventories, UNFCCC harmonization about the targets, and streamlining the certifying processes. To facilitate implementation, the region needs more accredited laboratories to test biochar for carbon content. Additionally, a regional approach, akin to the ASEAN emission/trading scheme, is considered crucial. Key actors in the biochar sector include the International Biochar Institute's Thailand Biochar Academy. For Agroforestry, key players encompass financing/ventures, regional policy, certification bodies, as well as local/indigenous organizations.

Some qualifiers suggested to enhance Formal governance mechanisms involve Strengthening the LMTs components on ASEAN level by harmonizing knowledge on LMTs on regional level and ASEAN Ministerial forum in LMTs management. Agriculture, Agroforestry, and Afforestation are anticipated to benefit from these qualifiers, given their interconnectedness in land management and the high priority ASEAN countries place on afforestation. A proposed action involves countries agreeing to allocate a percentage of land for forest or agriculture, with a more regionally engaged approach incorporating the LMT agenda into existing Climate Change Working groups. Anticipated barriers include differing priorities and economic interests among countries, potentially impacting regional focus, and concerns about resource distribution and benefits, particularly for marginalized populations. To address these challenges, participants advocate for increased adoption of equity principles. Key enabling actors include international development and educational organizations such as the UN regional platform, G20, UN Global Compact, ASEAN working group, universities, EURAXESS, and the Mangrove initiative.

Facilitating effective research cooperation and technology transfer for all LMTs requires prioritizing knowledge sharing between countries, robust research funding, the establishment of a Capacity Building and Learning Center, and regional educational extension programs for agriculture. Additionally, a conference on soil carbon, digital, and spatial technology research is deemed crucial. Challenges in achieving this vision include navigating stakeholder collaboration and consensus-building, addressing an aging agricultural labour force along with a lack of replacements. A solution entails increased research investment within the ASEAN context, coupled with mechanisms to attract younger individuals to agriculture education and the creation of informal learning platforms. Engaging key actors such as NGOs (WWF, WCS, WINROCK, OXFAM, SNV), financing institutions (Acorn under Rabobank), and private companies like Nestle and other energy firms is essential to drive these initiatives forward.

Table 7: Summary of Regional Engagement evaluation by **Stakeholder Group 3** for chosen LMTs according to key issues, enablers and/or barriers

	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon credit pricing Carbon credit certification Standardization of carbon pricing system Tax incentives 	Afforestation and biochar (because according to the participant, IPCC reported biochar is the 5th most scalable CDR technology, currently in low supply with huge demand. It is thus attractive for investors)	<p>Medium engagement: more accredited laboratories in the region to test the biochar for carbon content and other parameters to qualify for carbon credits.</p> <p>High engagement: ASEAN emission/trading scheme</p>	Biochar: Thailand Biochar Academy Agroforestry: ADB, ADB Venture, GGGI, TGO, Chambers of Commerce, Board of Investment, NDC working group, ASEAN Secretariat, APRCM, AIPP, National banks, Samples of certificate: social carbon standard, gold standard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluctuating market conditions (pricing) Economic valuation Double counting of carbon credits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation of carbon market with transparent reporting of inventory Open national inventory UNFCCC harmonization about the target Minimization of chain of orders/processes
Formal governance mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening the LMTs components on ASEAN level <p>ASEAN Ministerial forum in LMTs management</p>	Agriculture, Agroforestry, Afforestation because these LMTs are interconnected in terms of land management. ASEAN countries put high priority for afforestation.	<p>Medium engagement: Countries should agree to allocate a percentage of land for forest or agriculture.</p> <p>High engagement: putting LMTs agenda in the existing Climate Change Working groups</p>	UN regional platform, G20, UN Global compact, ASEAN working group, universities, EURAXESS, Mangrove initiative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differing economic interests in each country <p>Competing interest about who should benefit from resources</p>	Adoption of equity principles
Research cooperation & technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge sharing between countries Research funding Capacity Building and Learning centres Regional educational extension for agriculture <p>Conference on soil carbon/digital/spatial technology research</p>	Important for all LMTs because these issues need multidisciplinary approach	<p>Medium engagement:</p> <p>More investment in research in ASEAN context</p> <p>High engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> School-vocation impact pathway More young people enrolling in agriculture <p>Informal learning platform for agriculture</p>	NGOs (WWF, WCS, WINROCK, OXFAM, SNV), Nestle, Acorn (under Rabo Bank), Energy companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working among stakeholder and building a consensus Aging farmers <p>Lack of labour replacement</p>	

3.3 Interactions and Linkages

Various interactions and linkages between the successful scaling up and implementation of LMTs were considered by the stakeholders. The relation between regional engagement and climate ambition were also discussed by stakeholders across different LMTs while other interactions were implied by the discussions in combination with background information and the modelling results for the region.

3.3.1 Breakout Group 1

Group 1 proposed that the interaction among LMTs is characterized by fairly well-connected relationships in many cases, based on the availability of land and biomass and the choices made. Biochar and biofuel focus on forestry and agricultural waste utilization, aligning with the shared goal of resource efficiency. In parallel, agroforestry and afforestation generate waste during the production process, complementing the production of biochar and biofuel. Increasing the digital identity of farmers is identified as a pivotal factor in ensuring effective benefits across all LMTs. Financially, biochar, and bioenergy production demonstrate profitability, while afforestation and agroforestry projects are more in need of blended financing models to provide essential support, resulting in a more balanced resource allocation. Furthermore, the health benefits derived from banning agricultural waste, and mitigating air pollution, contribute to the synergy among these LMTs. The collaborative efforts of these technologies contribute to a sustainable and integrated approach to land management.

3.3.2 Breakout Group 2

Group 2 identified a number of linkages and interactions that might suggest common approaches:

- The One health approach in production and management has wide applicability and might be applied across different LMTs, since it considers the health of people, animals and ecosystems that may all depend on common methods and priorities for use of land and biomass;
- Variations in the cost of implementation and financial support affect the adoption of each LMTs, since financing and administrative support for one LMT may crowd out another;
- NDC: conditional vs. unconditional may have impact on choice and the adoption level of the LMTs;
- Increase biochar may reduce the need for agrochemical inputs (NPK) and thereby have co-benefits for other LMTs and/or may free up these inputs for where they are more needed;
- Food security may be affected by deforestation on upland areas, which may also lead to reduced water resources for agriculture, thus constraining upscaling of other agricultural LMTs;
- Land ownership and tenure (government, private sector, community, individual HHs) may influence adoption of LMTs unevenly, as those occurring under existing ownership regimes (e.g. biochar) will normally be easier than those that require changes in ownership or tenure (e.g. new plantations or biomass sources for BECCS).

3.3.3 Breakout Group 3

During the regional workshop to discuss Southeast Asia, Group 3 focused on the interconnectedness among land mitigation technologies (LMTs), specifically agroforestry and forest management, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), and biochar. They highlighted that while BECCS lacks current implementation in the region, its future potential was acknowledged, emphasizing the need for creating an enabling environment. Biochar's role in reforestation and biodiversity protection through the utilization

of forestry and agricultural waste was discussed as aligning with resource efficiency goals. The group also pointed out the complementarity between agroforestry, afforestation, and biochar production, especially in waste management, enhancing biochar's production viability.

The discussion underscored the importance of digitalizing farmer identities to optimize benefits from these LMTs, suggesting that such technological adoption can bridge gaps between sustainable land management and operational efficiency. Financial aspects were also examined, indicating that while biochar and future BECCS projects might show profitability, afforestation and agroforestry require blended financing models to support their initial stages, aiming for a more equitable resource distribution.

Furthermore, the group discussed the broader environmental and health benefits, including the role of these LMTs in reducing air pollution and banning agricultural waste burning. This multifaceted approach underlines the synergy among the LMTs, presenting a comprehensive and sustainable framework for land management that not only addresses climate mitigation but also promotes biodiversity, resource efficiency, and community health benefits.

4 Comparison and synthesis: Narratives for climate ambition and regional engagement

The level of climate ambition (moderate vs. high) and the level of regional engagement (current, improved, and/or high) can be used to structure different narratives that describe a set of future pathways that are representative of stakeholder deliberations in conjunction with the physical and socio-economic conditions outlined in the background report alongside the constraints on internal consistency imposed by the modelling results. Four narratives were developed and are outlined below. One narrative applied the current level of regional engagement in achieving moderate climate ambition, two considered improved regional engagement alongside moderate climate ambition for LMTs, and one considered high regional engagement in achieving high climate ambition.

Table 8: Alternative Narratives for Southeast Asia according to climate ambition and regional engagement

	Climate Ambition		
Regional Engagement	<i>Baseline</i>	<i>Moderate ambition</i>	<i>High ambition</i>
<i>Current</i>	<i>N/A (taken as input)</i>	<i>Narrative A</i>	
<i>Improved</i>	<i>N/A (taken as input)</i>	<i>Narrative B, Narrative C</i>	
<i>High</i>	<i>N/A</i>		<i>Narrative D</i>

4.1 Narrative/Storyline A: biochar and bioenergy production is connected well with agroforestry and afforestation waste utilisation.

The first narrative emerging from the workshop discussions emphasizes the symbiotic relationship between biochar and bioenergy production with the utilization of waste from agroforestry and afforestation. This narrative underlines a circular economy approach where waste materials from agroforestry and afforestation are not viewed as mere byproducts but as valuable resources for biochar

and bioenergy production. The integration of these processes contributes to enhancing soil fertility through biochar, while simultaneously generating renewable energy, showcasing a model of sustainable land management that leverages synergies between different land mitigation technologies (LMTs).

This model not only addresses the challenge of waste management in agricultural and forestry operations but also contributes to carbon sequestration and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through biochar soil amendments and the production of clean energy. The approach exemplifies how interconnected LMTs can create multiple environmental benefits, including improved land productivity, biodiversity conservation, and resilience to climate change.

Furthermore, the narrative highlights the potential for creating new economic opportunities and fostering rural development. By integrating biochar and bioenergy production with agroforestry and afforestation practices, communities can benefit from diversified income streams, enhanced food security, and increased access to clean energy. This comprehensive approach to land management and waste utilization presents a forward-looking model for sustainable development in Southeast Asia, balancing ecological integrity with economic viability and social well-being.

4.2 Narrative/Storyline B: The enable environment for BECCS implementation can be created for in the next 10 years by connecting with existing LMTs.

The second storyline from the workshop discussions centres on creating an enabling environment for Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) implementation within the next decade, by leveraging synergies with existing biochar, bioenergy, and waste utilization practices in the Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector. This approach emphasizes the strategic integration of BECCS into the current landscape of sustainable land management, aiming to capitalize on the established infrastructure and knowledge base related to biochar production and bioenergy generation.

The narrative suggests that fostering a conducive environment for BECCS involves addressing technological, regulatory, and financial challenges, while simultaneously drawing on the strengths of biochar and bioenergy practices to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of carbon capture and storage technologies. This forward-looking perspective advocates for collaborative efforts among government, industry, and research institutions to develop policies, incentivize innovations, and mobilize investments that support the transition towards a low-carbon economy.

Furthermore, the storyline underscores the importance of holistic approaches that consider the lifecycle emissions, energy balances, and socio-economic impacts of integrating BECCS with biochar and bioenergy production. By focusing on waste utilization from the AFOLU sector, this narrative not only aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions but also promotes sustainable land management practices that enhance soil health, biodiversity, and rural livelihoods, contributing to the broader goals of climate change mitigation and sustainable development in Southeast Asia.

4.3 Narrative/Storyline C: Biodiversity protection with high ambitious of afforestation and agroforestry by scaling out best practices

The third storyline developed during the workshop focuses on enhancing biodiversity protection through ambitious afforestation and agroforestry projects, emphasizing the scaling out of best practices. This narrative recognizes the critical role of biodiversity in ensuring ecosystem resilience and the provision of

ecosystem services vital for human well-being and climate mitigation efforts. By adopting and expanding upon proven agroforestry and afforestation techniques, the strategy aims to create more diverse and sustainable landscapes that support a wide range of species, including those at risk of extinction.

Scaling out these best practices involves not only the replication of successful models across different regions but also the adaptation of these models to suit local ecological and socio-economic conditions. This approach ensures that afforestation and agroforestry projects contribute positively to local communities, offering economic benefits while preserving natural habitats. The emphasis on community involvement and indigenous knowledge in the planning and implementation phases is crucial for the success and sustainability of these initiatives.

Moreover, this storyline highlights the importance of integrated land management policies that support biodiversity conservation alongside climate mitigation and adaptation objectives. By fostering synergies between afforestation, agroforestry, and biodiversity protection, Southeast Asia can move towards a more holistic approach to environmental stewardship, ensuring that efforts to combat climate change also contribute to the preservation and enhancement of the region's rich biological diversity.

4.4 Narrative/Storyline D: high climate ambitious should be followed by high regional engagement to increase the implementation and knowledge transfer

The fourth storyline elaborates on the necessity for high climate ambition to be matched with high regional engagement, to boost implementation and facilitate knowledge transfer. This narrative underlines the importance of collaborative efforts across Southeast Asia, urging nations to not only set ambitious climate targets but also actively participate in regional initiatives that foster the sharing of insights, technologies, and best practices. Such engagement is crucial for overcoming the technical, financial, and policy barriers to effective climate action.

Emphasizing the role of knowledge transfer, the storyline advocates for the establishment of platforms and networks that enable the exchange of information and experiences related to land mitigation technologies and sustainable land management practices. This approach aims to accelerate the adoption of innovative solutions across the region, enhancing the capacity of countries to meet their climate objectives.

Finally, the narrative calls for strengthening partnerships between governments, the private sector, civil society, and international organizations. These collaborations are essential for mobilizing resources, driving technological advancements, and implementing effective policies that support the region's transition towards a more sustainable and climate-resilient future.

5 Limitations and Conclusions

Although the primary aim in this analysis is to present stakeholder perspectives on regional engagement for climate ambition for land-based mitigation in Southeast Asia, we used a storyline and simulation approach by relying on land/carbon modelling so that stakeholders could visualize climate ambition in quantitative terms. At the same time, we instructed participants to consider the modelling results as one of the inputs to the process. Other inputs included a background report on land use and mitigation in the ASEAN context, interview results, and framing presentations at the start of the workshop. A key reason for this multi-dimensional framing is that the modelling (simulation) was constrained in various ways since

only selected LMTs were covered and since the implementation of the LMTs is simulated through the particular features of these models that are based on land use transitions over time and do not capture economic relationships between land use, carbon flows and mitigation options. Therefore, a limitation in this approach is that the models need to be viewed not as realistic pathways for LMT implementation but as broad indicators of expected trends and changes in the physical systems. The insights of stakeholders along with interviews and background literatures thus provide the primary evidence for expectations on regional engagement and climate ambition while the modelling results provide some complementary framing on the physical constraints and opportunities for land-based mitigation in the region. Our conclusions reflect these limitations, and the resulting narratives (storylines) are generally independent of the simulation approach chosen taken here.

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7 Additional information: Workshop Agenda

08.30-09.00: Arrival, coffee, introductions

09.00-10.30 Part I: Introduction to the workshop

- Introduction to LANDMARC and LMTs
- Introduction to Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement framework
- LANDMARC modelling results and discussion
- Breakout group structure

10.30-10.45 Coffee break

10.45-12.30 Part II: Climate Ambition for LMTs

- Introduction to session
- Breakout group discussion on LMT portfolio

12.30-13.30 Lunch

13.30-15.15 Part III: Regional Engagement for scaling up LMTs

- Introduction to session
- Breakout group discussion on regional engagement for LMT implementation

15.15-15.30 Coffee break

15.30-17.00 Part IV: Synthesis

- Reporting from Breakout Groups
- Discussion on Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement
- Discussion on Regional Narratives or Storylines

17.00-17.30 Final remarks

18.00-19.30 Workshop dinner (restaurant at The Quarter Saladaeng by UHG Hotel)

ANNEX D5 - WORKSHOP REPORT FOR EUROPE

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Annex D5: Workshop report for Europe

LANDMARC Regional Workshop Results Report for Europe

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LANDMARC Regional Workshop Results Report for Europe

1 Introduction and Overview

1.1 Setting and participant profile

The European workshop of the LANDMARC project was held on October 24th, 2023 and was hybrid. In-person participants gathered at SEI Headquarters in Stockholm, while online participants joined through Microsoft Teams. The workshop lasted the whole day, following the format of all LANDMARC regional workshops. The participant profiles are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. European region workshop – Online and in person participation

Expertise	Country of expertise	Region of expertise	Participation	Sector	Gender
Agriculture	Germany	Global	Online	Public sector	Male
Agroforestry	Switzerland	EU	Online	Research	Female
Agriculture	Switzerland	Global	Online	Research	Male
CDR	Finland	EU	Online	Research	Female
Agroforestry	Netherlands	Netherlands	Online	NGO	Male
Peatland	Netherlands	Netherlands	Online	Public sector	Female
Forestry	Portugal	South Europe	Online	Research	Female
Soil, agriculture	Ukraine	Eastern Europe	In person	Research	Male
Biochar	Sweden	Sweden	In person	Consultancy	Female
BECCS	Sweden	Nordics	In person	Research	Male
BECCS, biochar	Sweden	Sweden	In person	Communications	Female

1.2 Regional focus

The European Union (EU) is central to the continent's development and leads global climate action, setting a goal to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 and advocating for global temperature increase limitation to 2°C above pre-industrial levels. Regulations like the European Climate Law bind the EU to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. Distinct in its role as a union under a common framework, the EU serves as a global example, with policies such as the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), allowing Member States to distribute emissions targets across sectors, including agriculture. The ESR is also crucial for balancing emissions, including in the Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry sector, measuring both CO₂ removals and emissions. Challenges in translating EU policies into Member State actions require effective coordination and dialogue, though.

Land-based mitigation technologies have received particular interest in the European context in recent years, with the focus being on how forest can be best managed and conserved, but also how new technologies, such as bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), can be scaled up and contribute to achieving climate targets and creating a new industry for global export. Furthermore, the geographical and climatic differences between the North and South of Europe create also an interesting contrast that requires dialogue and knowledge exchange in forums such as the LANDMARC-organized workshop.

1.3 Regional implications and expected results

The aim of characterising future development of LMTs was clarified among participants and no issues were identified prior to or the start of the workshop.

2 Regional Modelling Results

2.1 Assumptions for models

Afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, no-tillage, biochar, and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) were the LMTs modelled for the EU27. The assumptions and model parameters were reviewed and discussed among participants.

2.2 Overview on modelling results

Figure 1 summarizes results for the EU27 from the LandSHIFT model, showing absolute spatial allocation of the selected LMTs. In general, cropland in the region remains quite stable until 2050 with similar areas in all three scenarios. However, after 2050 the scenarios diverge, with the Reference and High ambition scenarios showing slightly decreasing cropland area and the Moderate ambition scenario showing a slight increase. The share of cropland allocated to bioenergy crops production steadily increases in the region in the Moderate and High ambition scenarios (used in the model for the BECCS and biochar), especially after 2050, while cropland for food decreases in all scenarios due to the assumed improvements in crop yields for food and the decreasing food production rates. This is because of the global nature of these models, that optimize land-use allocation from a global, and not regional, perspective. Therefore, parts of land use for food production currently in Europe successively move to other world regions where crop yields are more favourable.

Furthermore, pasture areas slightly decrease in all scenarios, while afforestation areas remain stable, representing only a much smaller share of the land areas in the EU region. No-tillage cropland area is the second largest land area after cropland in the analysis, steadily increasing until around 2040 (High ambition scenario) and 2100 (Moderate scenario), showing that no-tillage potential is not currently fully exploited in the EU. Afforestation remains relatively constant in the moderate and high emissions (LMT) scenarios, while the reference scenario experiences some deforestation followed by slight recovery. A significant portion of crops in the latter part of the century was allocated to bioenergy crops, particularly perennial ones unaffected by no-tillage practices, which was why the no-tillage curve experiences a steep drop in the second half of the century in the High ambition scenario.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 present a comparison of land use fraction and carbon on land differences between the Reference and the Moderate and High ambition scenarios, respectively. The carbon estimates were obtained by coupling the LPJ-Guess model to the results of the LandShift model, thus showing the implications of land use transitions over time with respect to the distribution of carbon in the terrestrial carbon pool. Differences are more accentuated in the comparison of the High ambition and Reference scenario.

Figure 1. LandSHIFT results for EU27 - spatial allocation of land over time.

Central Europe, especially some regions of France, as well as regions of South-eastern Spain and Eastern Europe (e.g. parts of Ukraine and Romania) show the biggest positive differences for the cases of cropland and natural land, while negative differences appear in North-western Spain and Eastern Europe (e.g. parts of Ukraine and Bulgaria) show negative differences. Pastureland, shows very few areas of slight positive differences in the Moderate and High ambition scenarios, e.g. in France, but in general is decreasing. BECCS is prominent in certain regions, primarily associated with agricultural practices, but it remains spatially limited, considering the models only assume crops as feedstock for biofuels to be used in such BECCS applications. In general, total carbon stored in Europe increases according to the LPJ-Guess model results, with carbon stored in vegetation being the primary contributor.

Figure 2. Carbon on land and land use fraction differences between the Reference Case and Moderate Ambition Case in 2095.

Figure 3. Land use fraction (top) and carbon on land (bottom) differences between the Reference Case and High Ambition Case in 2095.

2.3 Context for discussion and use of modeling results

The LANDMARC models assume a 40% increase in crop yields. This assumption was derived from MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM and was consistently applied to all scenarios. While some studies have proposed even higher yield increases, this figure was deliberately selected as a cautious estimate to simplify the modelling process. However, it's worth noting that such an optimistic projection for crop yields can significantly impact model results and may present accuracy challenges. Workshop participants challenged though the assumption for crop yields in Europe and indicated that even dietary changes would be needed to achieve necessary carbon emission reductions in that case.

Participants were also interested in understanding what type of feedstocks and carbon pools are included, e.g. whether roots are included as pools or only as soil organic matter. Indeed, in the models, roots are part of the vegetation cohort. Another point of discussion was whether temperature differences are considered in the model. The model simulates higher soil carbon turnover with higher temperatures. Yet, the current LPJ-Simulations were all driven with the same climate input.

Another comment was about handling forest management in the models. The currently used version of LPJ-Guess does not include forest management parameters and does not consider woody biomass as a source of negative emissions. Participants from Nordic countries especially highlighted the inclusion of woody biomass in the models as necessary for illustrating an accurate picture of this LMT's potential. The current results do not reflect the potential of BECCS using woody biomass, according to some participants.

A participant raised a question about bioCCU (Carbon Capture and Utilization) and biofuels, pointing out potential confusion in considering biofuels as a form of substitution in the models. Participants emphasized the potential for bioCCU to be linked to point sources of biogenic CO₂, e.g. from the pulp and paper industry, rather than using additional land for biomass crops. For example, NEGEM project scenarios are exploring BECCS from crop residues and it seems there is potential documented even within Europe.

Participants also emphasized the need to address double-counting issues when using both BECCS and soil carbon sequestration in the modelling. Biofuels are considered a substitution, BECCS is considered a carbon removal, however, different waste forms (woody biomass waste, agricultural waste, sludge etc.)

are not currently included, and would be interesting to include, according to the participants. Assigning vegetation areas to be different uses, i.e. removal or residue, can be challenging from a modelling perspective, though.

Furthermore, another discussion point from the Nordic perspective was regarding the model assumption of reducing agricultural land and allocating it to afforestation instead which is probably not realistic for Sweden and would complicate communication of these results to policy-makers. Additionally, the potential use of woody biomass in Combined Heat and Power plants was recommended to be included by workshop participants.

A key recommendation from workshop participants regarding the use and dissemination of LANDMARC modelling results was that the **assumptions on key values (e.g. crop yields), decisions on what types of feedstocks were included or not (e.g. exclusion of woody biomass and waste), and how removals and substitutions are handled (e.g. regarding biofuels)** in the models should be very clearly documented and communicated in order to **avoid misconceptions that would negatively affect the potential development of technologies and land-use management applications for climate change mitigation**. This involves transparent reporting regarding the model design and subsequently the final results.

3 Summary of Breakout Group Discussions

3.1 Climate Ambition

For better understanding what the climate ambition with LMTs can be, the participants were divided into breakout groups to characterise and discuss possible LMT portfolios for the European region. In this workshop, the discussion started with Afforestation and forest management as a common topic for all breakout groups, followed by agroforestry. Depending on the knowledge and the regional applicability, the participants had the opportunity to select two more LMTs to be discussed in the group. The following sections describe the results of these discussions.

3.1.1 Breakout Group 1

The fixed LMTs under discussion were afforestation and forest management, with limited knowledge of agroforestry leading to its exclusion from discussion. For the LMTs of free selection, BECCS and biochar were chosen for additional discussion. A summary is presented in Table 2.

The group stressed the importance of sustainable forest management practices over increasing forest land area. This involves promoting sustainably sourced wood products and incentivizing the preservation of trees, potentially through a negative emissions market. The group highlighted the necessity for differentiated EU forestry regulations tailored to the unique conditions of the Nordics. In Sweden and Finland, for example, the pulp and paper industries are key for forestry and support the goal of becoming a net sink of CO₂. Afforestation is a practice implemented for more than a hundred years in Sweden, and there are conflicts with EU policies in several areas of interest with relation to forest management.

Upscaling of afforestation and forest management as a carbon sink will be challenging. Data accessibility remains a barrier, especially for small farmers. Forest inventories and carbon stock assessments are prone to uncertainty and time-consuming, prompting the need for cost-effective inventory methodologies. Concerns were raised about the potential for double counting emissions and removals, impacting carbon emission inventories and stock assessments.

Workshop participants commented that defining how ambitious afforestation and forest management will be in the future is a difficult task, which is also quite uncertain. In the future, EU regulations will play a key role in how forestry will develop in the EU countries. A harmonized guidance for carbon accounting is needed to stimulate the market for carbon sinks across the region. Additionally, the group explored future possibilities for war-damaged soils, considering their potential transformation into new bioenergy crops, particularly if unsuitable for food production.

BECCS and biochar were discussed as well with a focus on the need to use forestry biomass residues for both technologies. Participants emphasized the need to avoid clustering both technologies together.

BECCS potential in the pulp and paper industry is large. Its benefits span from bioenergy production to the creation of a market for negative emissions. However, CO₂ emissions storage heavily relies on collaboration with other countries, notably Norway. In contrast, biochar, adaptable for small-scale applications, requires attention to the sustainable and ethical sourcing of residual biomass. Additionally, the residual residues used should have good quality to minimize additional energy input in the process. Ambition levels for both biochar and BECCS were said to be somewhat uncertain, but the group participants stressed that these technologies need to be in operation at full commercial scale before 2045.

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	Scaling options	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards	Co-benefits	Ambition (baseline, moderate, high)	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management <i>(Fixed by SEI)</i>	Not necessarily more forest area but sustainable management of forests and biomass supply. For existing forests, motivate not cutting down trees with new sources of income from a market for negative emissions.	Sweden's forestry cannot cover the emissions from other sectors. Discrepancies in data access (small vs. large farmers). Private forests – difficulties in state prescribing more forest planting (Ukraine). Forest inventories and carbon stocks. Soil carbon pools. Access to new technologies.	Value from wood and material efficiency (construction, bioenergy, bio-based material). Potential for more efficient usage of wood-based products. Higher carbon content and higher biodiversity. A balance between unmanaged and managed forests.	Unclear where and Europe stands in terms of afforestation and forest management. Difficult to know the ambition levels. A reasonable ambition for the region should be better management in the form of sections of forestland used for different purposes (e.g., one part of C sequestration, one part for biodiversity, etc).	Unlikely to have afforestation on cropland in Sweden and Finland. EU Regulation development is key to guide afforestation efforts according to the country. Regulations discouraging monocultures can shift forestry practices. EU level guidance for increasing carbon stock and accounting it. Soils affected by the war in Ukraine will take time to recover. It is unclear when recovery will occur and how they will be purposed. Possibly, war-damaged soil will be used for new forests and new bioenergy crops but not for food. In parallel, after the war the demand for woody products for construction may increase. However, this is uncertain.
Agroforestry <i>(Fixed by SEI, for each region)</i>	No expertise in the group, moved to the next topic.				
BECCS <i>(Selected by participants in each breakout group)</i>	Dependent on the negative emissions market. Definition of locations and contracts for storage. Storage is a limiting factor, dependent on international storage location availability.	No local storage for CCS, lack of a timeline for these Reliance on storage in Norway. Other countries with potential storage capabilities are mainly concerned for their own emissions and may not provide storage for other countries.	Heat and electricity production from biomass (bioenergy), plus CO ₂ is captured and stored, creating two new businesses.	Potential to sequester 10 to 20 Mt CO ₂ per year if storage in Norway is available.	Varying timescales for BECCS
Biochar <i>(Selected by participants)</i>	Wide scales can be produced by small and large-scale players. Forestry waste products can also be used for biochar.	Complex due to many technical aspects of biomass and energy requirements. Conservative estimates of biochar stability in soil.	Soil: increase of water holding capacity and nutrient storage. Increased yields, depending on where the biochar is used.		

3.1.2 Breakout Group 2

The experts discussed afforestation and forest management, as well as agroforestry. The third LMT, selected by participants, was cropland management. A summary of the discussion is provided in Table 3.

Afforestation and forest management were discussed with a focus on land availability. Concerns were raised regarding limited land availability for planting more forests, potential competition with other land uses, and the risk of monoculture forest management leading to a lack of crop diversity. The group assessed a low scalability of afforestation as an LMT in Europe. EU-level policy faces challenges, particularly concerning countries with significant forestry such as the Nordics. Additionally, the long-term carbon sequestration effects of forestry could only be accounted for when trees reach maturity, a situation that could be constrained by increasing fire risks. Despite this, the benefits of afforestation in biodiversity and the water cycle were noted to potentially outweigh CO₂ emissions mitigation benefits.

Agroforestry, on the other hand, was assessed as a scalable LMT for Europe, providing positive impacts on both farmers and farms. While its direct CO₂ mitigation effect may be modest, it offers various co-benefits including pest control, soil erosion prevention and fruit and timber production. Overcoming barriers to agroforestry implementation requires the creation and promotion of supportive policies, addressing knowledge and skill gaps in the agricultural sector, and incentivizing adoption, especially considering possible short-term yield losses.

Cropland management was assessed as an effective and scalable LMT, particularly when incorporating sustainability practices. These practices extend beyond organic agriculture and encompass regenerative and conservation agriculture, along with managing energy use and emissions associated with the crop. Concerns were raised about the sustainability of energy choices, specifically when selecting between energy sources based on efficiency. For example selecting between, solar energy and bioenergy from biomass. The need of using biomass waste for biofuel production was judged as indispensable in this context.

Uncertainties associated with cropland management primarily revolve around definitions and terminology such as regenerative and conservation agriculture. There is also a lack of systemic thinking about impacts in the agricultural sector, presenting an opportunity to raise awareness of non-CO₂ agricultural emissions. Policymaking is crucial to defining rules for agroforestry and incentivizing its implementation, as well as addressing uncertainties in cropland management practices.

Table 3. Climate ambition - Summary of Group 2 discussion

	Scaling options	Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards	Co-benefits	Ambition (baseline, moderate, high)	Timing: 2050 vs. 2100
Afforestation and forest management <i>(Fixed by SEI)</i>	Limited effect in the short term (when trees are small). Protect existing forests rather than expanding. Avoidance of deforestation is the main concern in Nordics. Increased afforestation shrinks land for agriculture.	Might emit more carbon from woody biomass than what is captured. Negative impacts on food security. Monoculture's lack of resilience to natural disasters. Additional emissions from transport of fuel crops.	Increased Biodiversity. Conservation of water cycle.	Higher ambition in specific European regions, e.g. the Nordics, with longer tradition in forestry sector management, but overall little impact on European ambition.	Long-term solution, little effect in the short term.
Agroforestry <i>(Fixed by SEI, for each region)</i>	Inclusion of agroforestry practices can be used as a farm brand differentiator against other farms. Carbon markets and carbon farming. Labelling and certifications. EU legislation for improved reforestation rates consider agroforestry.	The regulatory status of land. Absence of legislation. Low acceptance due to short-term yield loss. Minimal mitigation effect. Lack of policy push. Skills gap in farming vs. forestry	Fruit and timber production Pest control Conservation of Water cycle Eco-tourism Prevent soil erosion	Policy to de-risk and remove barriers to extend land share for agroforestry.	
Cropland management <i>(Selected by participants in each breakout group)</i>	Combination of land management techniques. Solar energy. Generation of biofuel with biomass waste.	No clear boundaries between regenerative and conservation agriculture. Future uncertainty of stocking density and carbon influxes Energy efficiency (biomass vs. solar PV).	Connecting crop, grassland and livestock. Nutrient balance. Pest control. Waste treatment and circular economy.		Agriculture sector emissions are not limited to only CO ₂ .

3.2 Regional Engagement

For the regional engagement discussions, the same breakout groups and the selected LMTs were kept. The following sections summarize the insights from the group participants on three fronts: economic integration and harmonisation, formal governance mechanisms, and research cooperation & technology transfer.

The European Union is different from other regions in world studied in the LANDMARC project. It has a common institutional framework and existing structures that allow EU Members to have more effective regional engagement compared to other regions. In this session, the suggestions for regional engagement leverage on these structures.

3.2.1 Breakout Group 1

As previously mentioned, the LMTs considered for this group were afforestation and forest management, BECCS and biochar. The participants delved into the economic integration aspects, particularly trading products from BECCS and biochar, highlighting the need for improved knowledge in afforestation and forest management. Table 4 presents the summary of the discussion. Products to be traded and carbon market standards were the selected qualifiers in the economic integration and harmonisation discussions. For BECCS, the trade of CO₂ emissions and their economic value compared to other technologies was brought upon given that the trade of emissions captured and stored after the bioenergy production represents a new source of income. The group emphasised the necessity of smaller pilot projects to demonstrate tangible energy production and carbon capture before scaling up, drawing parallels with the early expansion of wind-powered energy.

Carbon market standards and certification for the three LMTs were identified as crucial for influencing adoption. The absence of clear guidance on emission accounting at the European level prompted suggestions, including keeping these emissions within the Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector and incorporating them into national inventory reports. The participants advocated for a multi-policy approach to assess emissions mitigation from each technology and establish standards for sustainably sourced biomass, particularly for BECCS and biochar, calling for government involvement in policy creation.

Formal governance mechanisms for LMTs were seen as essential. For BECCS, it was highlighted that development relies on integrated working groups throughout the supply chain, including bilateral cooperation with other countries to establish conventions for CO₂ transport and storage. Collaboration between public and private sectors, as well as community involvement, was underscored for successful technology implementation, investment strategies, and effective communication.

Knowledge grounded on science was raised as an element needed for the scaling of the LMTs discussed. Policymaker decisions were emphasised to benefit from research and development partnerships, especially regarding afforestation and forest management, BECCS, and biochar. Stakeholders expressed the need for enhanced knowledge in shaping EU forest policies to avoid hindering the development of BECCS or biochar. Similarly, the participants raised the need to assess if the Swedish-led developments for BECCS could be suitable for other countries in Europe. If this is not the case, research partnerships are key to transferring knowledge for adapting the technology. Informed decision-making could also aid better communication of the risks and uncertainties associated with these technologies and inform better society.

LANDMARC Regional Workshop Report for Europe

Workshop Date: October 24th, 2023

Workshop Location: Stockholm

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	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products to be traded. 	BECCS: trade of CO2 emissions. Biochar: trade of material or energy.	Emission and carbon footprint accounting, price variability from voluntary market.	Government, municipalities BECCS: Industry Biochar: farmers.	Other product lines, trade outside of the EU. BECCS: Not yet profitable, transportation of CO2. Biochar: not enough voices supporting the technology.	Technology portfolio to avoid reliance on one option. Small pilots for making tangible first and then scaling up.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon market Certification / Standards. 	BECCS and biochar.	Emission accounting for the LULUCF sector, as part of inventory reports. Multi-policy approach.	Government.	Overlaps of national and corporate visions of carbon accounting.	Accounting separately for land and combustion emissions. Biomass sourcing traceability. Tax incentives – post-war carbon credits.
Formal governance mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working groups. 	BECCS: bi-lateral groups for agreements to scale.	Long-term governance. Marine pollution regulation on the transport of emissions (London Protocol).	Private-public stakeholders, government, researchers, policymakers.	Conditions for storage of emissions Local storage in Sweden Final cost uncertainty	Collaboration between private-public actors. Refrain from speculative visions Burden sharing within society
Research cooperation & technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research partnerships. 	Afforestation and reforestation, BECCS, and biochar.	Knowledge building and data. Avoid regulatory barriers in forestry that hinder BECCS.	Researchers, policymakers.	"Pushing away from the problem", i.e., how we might face problems if we rely in BECCS and this technology does not fulfil the goals/expectations. The suitability of BECCS in Sweden is different for the EU	Research partnerships Open-source data Knowledge campaigns for awareness-raising of risks and uncertainties and communication of technology options

3.2.2 Breakout Group 2

As previously mentioned, the LMTs considered for this group were afforestation and forest management, agroforestry and cropland management.

The economic integration and harmonisation discussion centred on the agricultural implications of implementing these LMTs. Beyond individual farmers, the group emphasised the need for a systemic change in the EU's agricultural supply chain to facilitate widespread LMT adoption. The existing subsidies favour large-scale operations and need restructuring to incentivise sustainable practices, focusing on the production process rather than scale or outcome. Restructuring subsidies to relieve initial costs for small-scale projects and promoting localised agriculture were proposed alternatives. In this way, farmers would not directly assume the initial costs, thus making small-scale projects profitable. According to the group, the global agriculture supply chains focusing on import/export need to be redesigned, and there are opportunities to do this at a regional level.

Certification and carbon credits were key topics, requiring clearer definitions for practices within these LMTs. Standardisation of concepts such as *regenerative* and *conservation* farming is deemed essential to prevent greenwashing. On the other hand, carbon credits were evaluated as complex to be applicable in agriculture due to imprecise measurement of carbon fluxes and focus on the outcome rather than on the process.

Market integration, monitoring, and localisation were identified as qualifiers for formal governance mechanisms. Sustainability concerns related to the origin of biomass and transportation controls for wood products were raised by participants. Effective governance at the European level was seen as contingent on improvements to current regulations and further integration of policy, knowledge, and markets.

The integration of forestry into agriculture emerged as a challenge, necessitating training for farmers in forestry practices. Participants stressed the urgency of translating theoretical knowledge into practical action in the field based on the identified benefits of these LMTs.

	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restructuring agriculture subsidies 	Agroforestry and cropland management	Farmers adopt LMTs, costs subsidized by CAP	Policy makers, research institutions	Measure of emissions capture and co-benefits	Reward process rather than scale or outcome
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restructuring agriculture supply chains 	Agroforestry and cropland management	Local supply chains	Policy makers	Difficult global system change	Regional marketing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certification 	Afforestation, agroforestry and cropland management	Standard definition of regenerative and conservation farming	Policy makers, research institutions, private sector	Green of labelling schemes and vague definitions	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon credits 	Not easily applicable to agriculture		Policy makers, research institutions, private sector		
Formal governance mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market integration and monitoring 	Afforestation, forest management	Tracking and control of wood transport	Policy makers, private sector		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localization 	Afforestation, agroforestry, cropland management	Breakdown of EU policy to local levels	Policy makers		
Research cooperation & technology transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research 	Agroforestry, afforestation	Filling the knowledge gap of carbon storage and stock	Research institutions	Quantification of carbon indicators and time-consuming research process	Long-term research, restructuring of funding opportunities
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education 	Agroforestry	Close the gap by educating farmers in forestry Experimental policy scheme	Policy makers		

3.3 Discussion on Interactions and Linkages

This section describes the different interactions and linkages between regional engagement and climate ambition, according to the discussions held with the stakeholders in the breakout groups.

3.3.1 Breakout Group 1

The participants of this group emphasised the necessity of utilising woody biomass waste as feedstock for implementing biochar or BECCS, critiquing the use of other biofuels in the modelling results presented at the beginning of the workshop. The emphasis on woody biomass aligns with the prevailing technological developments in Sweden, where substantial progress has been made for both biochar and BECCS. The discussion underscored the interconnectedness of forest management with the implementation of these technologies, introducing the potential for interdependence and competition of actors for woody biomass feedstock, thereby influencing scalability based on biomass utilization.

The ongoing BECCS pilot and future large-scale facilities in Sweden were recognised as potentially unsuitable for replication in other European regions. The replicability of BECCS in different European countries may necessitate additional efforts to adapt the technology to diverse local conditions. Challenges were highlighted concerning the interactions between BECCS and the EU Forest policy, with current regulations deemed incompatible with BECCS implementation in Finland and Sweden. Participants urged action to bridge these gaps through research partnerships and evidence-based policymaking.

To increase ambition for CO₂ emission mitigation, the group proposed that ambitious LMT implementation should encompass a variety of options. Each technology in the LANDMARC project operates uniquely with different time scales and emission mitigation potentials, making direct comparisons challenging. Financial aspects further complicate comparisons due to variations in investment and operation costs. The participants recommended encouraging countries to adopt a diversified LMT portfolio to avoid reliance on a single option.

Concerns were raised regarding potential overlaps in operation and accounting of mitigated and avoided carbon dioxide emissions through LMTs. These overlaps could impact national emissions inventories and carbon credit trading, leading to conflicts between national and corporate reporting. An example mentioned was a hypothetical situation in which companies state that products are carbon neutral and that those emissions would not contribute to national reporting.

3.3.2 Breakout Group 2

The group participants recognised the interconnectedness of afforestation, forest management, and agroforestry. While there was consensus that afforestation might face feasibility challenges across European countries due to limited land availability, there was a positive outlook on integrating trees into agriculture. The ambition of increasing the tree count in Europe was assessed as an enabler for agroforestry, beneficial for the water cycle and biodiversity.

Addressing knowledge gaps is crucial for expanding agroforestry, requiring additional efforts at a European regional level to educate farmers about forestry practices. However, the participants noted that farmer training alone might not be sufficient to boost acceptance of agroforestry. Agricultural policies promoting agroforestry were deemed essential to establish rules and incentives for increasing tree presence in agricultural lands. The participants recommended a more nuanced breakdown of European policy at local levels to align with the specific needs of farmers.

Regarding cropland management, participants highlighted that individual implementation of techniques is often ineffective, advocating for a combination of practices. Furthermore, a higher level of ambition can be attained through integrating agroforestry into cropland management. This synergistic approach was seen as a promising opportunity, offering emissions mitigation effects and numerous co-benefits for the agricultural sector.

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4 Comparison and synthesis

In this section we formulate narratives based on the workshop activities, as well as including as feasible and appropriate results from interviews and background research on the region conducted prior to the workshop. These narratives triangulate the information collected throughout these activities and present alternatives of how LMT scaling might develop in the future in the region.

4.1 Narrative/Storyline 1: Forests protection and forestry residues for BECCS

EU regulation has enabled the preservation of forests across the region, however increasing temperatures and limited forestry practices within the agricultural sector make more difficult managing wildfires.

Under current levels of regional engagement, the use of residual woody biomass is deemed necessary for the implementation of Bioenergy Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) across the European region. BECCS is considered as essential for achieving negative emissions Europe. Residual woody biomass has the potential to produce bioenergy and the capture and sequestration of carbon dioxide emissions. The expected removal of emissions under a scenario moderate ambition using BECCS would represent around 3 million tonnes CO₂-eq per year sequestered in Sweden by 2045, with additional commercial plants in other parts of Europe where discussions for the technology have been ongoing including Finland, Denmark and Germany. Energy utilities lead the use of BECCS across Europe and emission removals regulated in a negative emissions market, where countries and private actors are able to trade.

4.2 Narrative/Storyline 2: Ambitious scaling-up of BECCS and embracing agroforestry

Woody biomass waste is integrated into the development of BECCS across Europe with a notable higher ambition in the Nordics. The increased ambition leads to upscaling of BECCS in the energy sector able to remove more than 10 million tonnes of CO₂-eq per year. Sweden alone has the potential to remove approximately 10 million CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Additional efforts by other European nations add up to this number and contribute to emission removal in the region. Reaching this level is possible thanks to parallel efforts including the introduction of enabling policies for the use of forest residues, de-risking of investments, ensuring agreements withing Europe for underground storage of emissions, and enabling a market for negative emissions. The energy utilities continue to be in the lead of emission removal using BECCS and the pulp and paper sector use their own residues to enter the negative emission market. Pilot plants in the pulp and paper sector across Europe start to operate.

There is an increasing trend on the use of agroforestry practice for southern European nations where woody biomass residues is locally available. BECCS is not attractive for that region. Benefits of integrating agroforestry in agriculture and food production are acknowledged and are more common.

4.3 Narrative/Storyline 3: Improved forest management across Europe contributes to risk prevention and climate resilience

Forest management resumes a crucial role in emission reduction in Europe. Although European countries have explored the possibility of implementing afforestation across the continent, agreement has been reached that this strategy does not fit all countries due to space constraints and forest type variability (i.e., forests differ between the Iberian Peninsula, Eastern Europe, and Nordic regions). The EU and its Member States have been prompted to implement alternative strategies for carbon storage. The region has reached agreement of the need to prioritise forest management over afforestation. Ensuring effective carbon storage in trees and mitigating risks like fires and droughts becomes a primary focus. European countries,

as a result, actively promote forest management initiatives by creating training opportunities for farmers. This approach aims to bridge the knowledge gap between agriculture and forestry, fostering meaningful efforts across the continent. Industries reliant on forest resources express interest in participating in the negative emissions market. Notably, pulp and paper industries in the Nordics take a proactive step by deploying their own full scale BECCS facilities. This allows the pulp and paper industry to leverage residual woody biomass for both energy generation and carbon dioxide capture. The expanded use of BECCS in these industries increases the potential for technology transfer beyond the Nordic regions.

4.4 Narrative/Storyline 4: high ambition, high engagement Europe-wide commitment to enhance carbon removal in the energy, forestry and agriculture sectors

Europe has a high level of ambition and a robust engagement between countries in the region. The practise of agroforestry is commonly used by farmers, bringing positive effects to fire risk minimisation. Likewise, forest management gained a critical role through the continent and is prioritized. Forest products are used in a sustainable way meaning that woody biomass waste is also employed by different sectors for the production of energy and the removal of carbon dioxide emissions.

The recognition of agroforestry's substantial potential for tree conservation and carbon dioxide capture underscores the necessity for expansive certification schemes. Targets to the short and long terms are stated in Europe's regional roadmap for agroforestry implementation. Europe's leadership on agroforestry is fortified by regulatory measures pertaining to crop management, which seek to standardize practices like organic agriculture, reduced tillage, and conservation agriculture. Certification schemes play a pivotal role by endorsing farms that comply with these standards, solidifying agriculture's significant contribution with negative emissions to Europe's carbon inventories.

Simultaneously, policymakers in Europe recognize the need of evaluating with a separate lens the forestry sector in the Nordics. Legislative frameworks promoting the balanced use of wood resources and mandating the utilization of biomass residues are endorsed. These conditions allow BECCS to thrive both in the energy utility and in pulp and paper industries of the region.

5 Limitations, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Limitations of the storyline and simulation approach

The approach used in this workshop is based on a combination of the quantitative evidence available from land use and vegetation/carbon models, and the need to consider contextual information and the experience and expertise of stakeholders. The model results are not to be seen as predictions of likely results but rather as a quantitative story (simulation) that contributes to a qualitative story (narratives). The model permits some reflection on structural issues that may be more easily expressed numerically. It is neither expected nor required that the model results reflect future trends in any absolute terms but rather than they provide internal consistency across the overall driving factors and constraints. Therefore, in this case, the qualitative narratives can be viewed as the primary result of the overall exercise, which is a variation of the storyline and simulation approach. The approach is therefore not replicable in an easily comparative way, as only a small group of stakeholders was gathered and a different group could reach different conclusions. Nevertheless, the results offer useful reflections on the drivers of change in land use and carbon over time and on the relation between the physical evidence base and the actions taken to steer or guide those changes through economic, political, and social governance mechanisms.

5.2 Conclusions and recommendations

Both breakout groups reached a consensus on the limited applicability of afforestation in the European context, primarily due to land constraints. This shared perspective underscores the possible incompatibility of increased afforestation as a long-term option as carbon removal for Europe. Instead, the groups highlighted the importance of prioritizing forest management and agroforestry over afforestation. Afforestation or reforestation may not increase but forest conservation should be encouraged.

Agroforestry was favoured throughout the workshop but there is a gap of existing skills for its large-scale implementation. Training in forestry practices aimed to farmers is needed for an increased ambition of agroforestry across Europe. Expertise in both agriculture and forestry could have positive effects for food security, climate risk mitigation and carbon dioxide removals.

The actual potential of carbon removals and the current status of removals is uncertain. This comes across in agriculture as well as in other sectors, such as forestry. This workshop allowed the participants to reflect on the lack of clarity of the baselines for afforestation and reforestation from an emission accounting perspective. Europe needs to define these baselines at a regional level.

There is a gap on the accounting standards of carbon dioxide emission removals at the European level. There are opportunities to establish the rules for removals including sustainability requirements (i.e., biomass sourcing, agroforestry practices, forest management) and the operation systems for emission inventories including removals originated in the land use sector. These rules should also consider how removals can be traded within the European region.

There is uncertainty on the rules or the eventual creation of a carbon dioxide removal market. Standards and policy are essential to allow the trade of emission removals in the country and between countries in the European region.

Establishing narratives was a difficult task for the workshop participants. Giving future-looking indicators of the development of afforestation, agroforestry, BECCS and organic agriculture was a challenge, since it is difficult to mentally depart from the current situation and visualize long-term futures where land

management is completely transformed. Projections to 2030, 2050 or 2100 were mostly speculative, and based on incremental improvements. Nevertheless, it was agreed that it is difficult to create narratives without policies for carbon removals in the land use sector in place.

Policy recommendations

- Regulations and cooperation at European level exist, but further improvements to those regulations to integrate emission removal practices, as well as integration of policy, knowledge, and markets for LMTs are needed.
- The conditions of forestry in the Nordics are different from central and southern Europe. It is recommended that the current regulation on EU forestry should be flexible to recognize that forests in the region differ according to the country.
- Sustainable cropland and forest management practices, when combined, can be effective and scalable LMTs with mitigation effect as well as co-benefits.
- The creation of integrated working groups for policy creation and research is of great importance to ensure that policy roll-out targeting emission removals is based on science.

Limitations

Feedback by the workshop participants indicates that all model limitations should be carefully communicated so results are not generalized. The workshop participants recommended making clear that the results may not reflect the reality for technologies such as BECCS. The model is not using woody biomass waste as feedstock, yielding results that are in line with the real conditions for BECCS in Europe. If these model limitations are not clearly communicated, there is risk the current momentum and on-going development of BECCS in the European continent is challenged. The workshop participants recommended that for further work with the models the assumptions and limitations are stated as transparently as possible.

The region and LMTs of expertise of workshop attendees limited somehow the discussion. Given that there were not representatives for each country in Europe, the information shared in the workshop may have gaps, but nevertheless gives some overview of challenges common across all Member States.

6 Additional information

6.1 Agenda

October 24th, 2023

Stockholm, Sweden (and online)

- 08.30-09.00 Arrival, coffee, introductions
- 09.00-10.30 **Part I: Introduction to the workshop**
Introduction to LANDMARC and LMTs
Introduction to Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement framework
LANDMARC modelling results and discussion
Breakout group structure
- 10.30-10.45 *Coffee break*
- 10.45-12.30 **Part II: Climate Ambition for LMTs**
Introduction to session
Breakout group discussion on LMT portfolio
- 12.30-13.30 *Lunch*
- 13.30-15.15 **Part III: Regional Engagement for scaling up LMTs**
Introduction to session
Breakout group discussion on regional engagement for LMT implementation
- 15.15-15.30 *Coffee break*
- 15.30-16.15 **Part IV: Synthesis**
Reporting from Breakout Groups
Discussion on Climate Ambition and Regional Engagement
Discussion on Regional Narratives or Storylines
- 16.15-16.30 Final remarks + Brief Survey and Evaluation

ANNEX D6 - WORKSHOP REPORT FOR LATIN AMERICA

LANDMARC Regional Workshop Results Report for Latin America

1 Introduction and Overview (max 1 page)

1.1 Setting and participant profile

The regional workshop for Latin America was attended by 9 experts in forestry, conservation, sustainable forest management and biochar. Most of them were interviewed previously, which means that they were already engaged in the land use-based discussions for climate mitigation. The countries represented were Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru and covered the academic, business and government sectors.

The Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR) whose regional office is in Perú, the Institute for Conservation and Sustainable Development of the Amazon (IDESAM) from Brazil, the Federal University of Amazonas (UFAM) from Brazil, the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Research on Biological Resources from Colombia, the Palladium Group international private group with office in Colombia, Alliance Biodiversity International (CIAT) from Perú, the Ministry of Environment, Water and Ecological Transition of Ecuador and the Secretariat of Environment of Bogota D.C. were at the workshop.

1.2 Regional focus

For this workshop, the regional focus was on the Amazon biome, which includes 8 countries in South America (Brazil, Bolivia, Peru, Ecuador, Colombia, Venezuela, Guyana and Suriname), being the largest tropical rainforest in the world with more than 6 million square kilometers. This biome absorbs large amounts of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere—10-15% of annual GHG emissions (Moreno Rincón, 2023)—, which is critical for climate mitigation and human well-being. Additionally, this region contains a quarter of the planet's biodiversity, is the source of 20% of the world's freshwater, is home to more than 34 million people including around 400 indigenous peoples and local communities (Cancillería de Colombia, 2019). However, in recent years the capacity to mitigate climate change by being a carbon sink has been reversed due to the level of transformation of the ecosystem mainly due to deforestation and forest fires (Castilhos, 2021).

Analysts suggest that 13.2% of the original Amazon Forest has been lost (more than 85 million hectares). This is critical, not only for South America but for the world because of its water regulation capacity and key ecosystem services for human being. It is estimated that the point of no return or tipping point for the Amazon is when it becomes a drier ecosystem linked to disruptive rainfall patterns and more intense dry season. This tipping point could be triggered by the loss of 25% of the Amazon Forest (Finer & Mamani, 2022). The gradual degradation of the Amazon not only has serious consequences for the planet's climate, but also threatens the economic prosperity of the countries that share it (Gobierno de Colombia, 2023).

The Amazonian countries created a treaty to work together since 1978 after which they set up an intergovernmental organization that cooperates to promote sustainable development. The Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) is the only socio-environmental bloc in Latin America (OTCA, s. f.). In recent years, the Amazon has been at the center of political attention in the region linked to its level of transformation. Processes such as the [Pact of Leticia](#), signed by 7 Amazonian countries in 2019 to address deforestation and environmental crimes, and the Summit of Amazonian Presidents, called the Belém Summit in 2023, show the political interest and the need to define joint policies and actions. This

Summit meeting created a new agenda for the Amazon biome, based on science and traditional knowledge, and strengthens the role of ACTO.

In order to focus the analysis, four of the eight countries of the Amazon basin were selected for the Landmarc project and the stakeholder consultations: Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador and Peru.

1.3 Regional implications and expected results.

Briefly explain any specific issues that arose beforehand or were raised by stakeholders in the beginning of the workshop in terms of establishing the basis for the workshop exercises for this region. If no issues arising, then this section can be left blank.

2 Regional Modeling Results

2.1 Assumptions for models

The assumptions for the models are given in Deliverable 6.3 on the scaling scenarios/modeling.

2.2 Overview on modeling results

In summary, the stakeholders/experts consider that:

1. The model does not contemplate the potential of storage of the natural forest, its management and conservation to improve removal and storage, so large part of the Amazon basin is not represented. Experts stated that better management of natural forest improves greenhouse gas mitigation capacity. Forest management as a technology did not figure prominently in the model, so experts did not see Amazonian priorities and realities reflected in the model.
2. BECCS uptake in Latin America is very low; therefore, from the invited experts' point of view BECCS was not considered a priority technology for Latin America, even in the long term. Besides, *Miscanthus* is hardly available as an energy source in the region.
3. More promotion of technologies associated with forest management and sustainable use of biodiversity, forest and non-forest timber products that address causes of deforestation, the main threat in the Amazon basin, is the priority. The main threats to the Amazon forest, that are drivers of deforestation, are the illegal economies of gold mining, logging, land grabbing, coca production for drug trafficking, among others. In this way, finding economic alternatives and markets from the sustainable use of biodiversity is the priority.
4. Assumptions for agroforestry systems should be separated from those for agro-silvopastoral systems.

2.3 Context for discussion and use of modeling results

In the assumption of up to 75% reduction of agroforestry in 2100, the experts point out that "In agroforestry systems it cannot be assumed that the area needed in the future will be reduced because productivity does not increase, and it is not possible to reduce the area under crops (e.g. annual crops). This assumption is viable if it is made for agroforestry systems because the area destined for cattle raising can be reduced. In fact, crop productivity in agroforestry systems is lower than in monoculture systems, however, the total yield of the agroforestry system is higher. It is not feasible to think of reducing the area for crops in agroforestry systems if future demand remains the same or increases".

- Although the removal capacity of the Amazon rainforest is not so high due to its age, its storage capacity is huge. So, if deforestation is not controlled, the stored carbon will be released into the

atmosphere, exacerbating the climate change crisis. Maintaining this ecosystem service is crucial to prevent the Amazon from becoming a GHG emitting forest: in fact, it is necessary to promote better forest management to increase this carbon storage capacity. In general, workshop attendees identified gaps in the assumptions to reflect the natural forest management in Latin America, especially for the Amazon context. The failure to include natural forest management within the model was seen as a weakness in excluding the most important issue for Amazonian countries associated with controlling deforestation, promoting ecological restoration, biodiversity conservation and enhancing community livelihoods.

- A central theme in the discussion and interest of the attendees were the technologies most associated with biodiversity conservation such as natural forest management, ecological restoration of natural forests and its sustainable use (which is different from reforestation).
- Attendees did not identify BECCS as an interesting technology for Latin America, nor in the long term. Nor did they identify that the *Miscanthus* assumption applies to the region. Even though *Miscanthus* is a second-generation source of bioenergy it is originally from Asia and the priority in the Amazon is to restore the natural forest with native species, not exotic species. Biochar, although a slightly better-known technology, implemented at the level of research institutes and laboratories in the region, was also not much discussed in the workshop. Only one group included it due to the experience of an attendee.
- The priority in the region is not only climate change oriented, but multi-purpose technologies that address the relationship between nature and humans in a more systemic way are needed. Based on the complex context of the Amazon, its problems, needs and inhabitants, technologies such as nature-based solutions that promote both adaptation and mitigation to climate change, sustainable forest management and income generation for rural communities ensuring competitive and long-term value chains connected with high value markets are required.

3 Summary of Breakout Group Discussions

3.1 Climate Ambition

Breakout group 1:

This group prioritized afforestation, sustainable forest management and ecological restoration, agroforestry as LMTs of importance for the region. Attendees discussed these LMTs as a group, not separately.

Breakout group 2:

This group selected 3 subgroups of LMT for the discussion. The first one included the LMTs more related to biodiversity conservation: Natural forest management and ecological restoration – reforestation. The second one included the LMTs more related to commercial aspects: agroforestry, commercial reforestation – afforestation and some aspects of sustainable agriculture. The third one included biochar.

3.1.1 Breakout Group 1

<p>Key questions:</p> <p>LMTs</p>	<p>Scaling options (how to upscale – barriers and enablers)</p>	<p>Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards (note differences across LMTs – how to address them?)</p>	<p>Co-benefits (especially adaptation, biodiversity/ecosystems, livelihoods)</p>	<p>Ambition (baseline, moderate, high)</p> <p>The selected LMTs, one by one, will be discussed considering the various levels of ambition as per the model (baseline, moderate (RCP2.6), and high (RCP 1.9). What does the LMT implementation look like at various levels of ambition? Is LMT implementation possible at all levels of ambition?</p>	<p>Timing: 2050 vs. 2100</p> <p>How might the expected scale, risks, and co-benefits change between the two different time periods?</p>
<p>Afforestation, sustainable forest management and ecological restoration, agroforestry</p>	<p>Replicate success stories in the region associated with the sustainable use of Amazonian fruits and their connection to value chains and markets, e.g. AJE Group.</p> <p>It is necessary to facilitate the conditions for strengthening the restoration system (seedlings, services, equipment, logistics) and thus make financing effective.</p> <p>Overcome logistical challenges, availability of native seedlings, rural extension - technical assistance and clarity on land tenure.</p>	<p>Difficulty in establishing value chains and developing market demand for products from sustainable use of natural forest.</p>	<p>Community development. Conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.</p> <p>Sources of income, provided that the establishment of the value chain with non-timber forest products is ensured.</p> <p>Increase in the Human Development Index</p>	<p>To achieve implementation, it is necessary to put pressure on companies to implement more sustainable practices, but planning this transition is key. For example, the EU has planned its transition for 3 years so that large companies change from monoculture systems to more sustainable ones.</p> <p>Mitigation is important, but we are in the time of adaptation. Right now, adaptation and forest conservation are the most urgent actions in the Amazon region. The effects are no longer projected; they are being experienced by the ecosystem and its people</p>	<p>In the Arc of deforestation in Brazil, there is a major problem of public security and illegal economies (such as illegal mining and logging), which may delay the implementation of LMTs.</p>

3.1.2 Breakout Group 2

<p>Key questions:</p> <p>LMTs</p>	<p>Scaling options (how to upscale – barriers and enablers)</p>	<p>Uncertainty and Risks, including hazards (note differences across LMTs – how to address them?)</p>	<p>Co-benefits (especially adaptation, biodiversity/ecosystems, livelihoods)</p>	<p>Ambition (baseline, moderate, high)</p> <p>The selected LMTs, one by one, will be discussed considering the various levels of ambition as per the model (baseline, moderate (RCP2.6), and high (RCP 1.9). What does the LMT implementation look like at various levels of ambition? Is LMT implementation possible at all levels of ambition?</p>	<p>Timing: 2050 vs. 2100</p> <p>How might the expected scale, risks, and co-benefits change between the two different time periods?</p>
<p>Natural forest management and ecological restoration (emphasis on forest conservation and sustainable use)</p>	<p>The main threats to the forest are illegal and unsustainable economic activities. The causes of the threats need to be addressed to make the standing forest profitable—with proper management. The route to scaling up is economic; the bioeconomy needs to be promoted.</p> <p>It is necessary to generate regional forest management policies and standards for ecological restoration through best practices, rural extension and economic incentives under the umbrella of ACTO. Promote the bioeconomy and payment for environmental and ecosystem services.</p>	<p>The Amazon is huge and territorial logistics, connectivity and transport are deficient. There are no roads, the connection is by river or air and fuel is very expensive.</p> <p>Changing governments hinder continuity in policies.</p> <p>Regulations and standards are not always aligned with the environmental objectives of conservation and restoration policies.</p> <p>There are perverse incentives: To apply for some bank loans, it is more important for the land to be "cleared" or without forest suitable for livestock.</p> <p>Lack of availability of native tree planting material and technical assistance for management.</p>	<p>Conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.</p> <p>Well-being for communities: economic, cultural, social.</p> <p>Maintenance of income and quality of life. Nature tourism as a reliable source of income.</p> <p>Adaptation to climate change.</p>	<p>Countries' ambition is high to halt deforestation and improve the conservation and sustainable use of the Amazon. However, it is possible that deforestation will continue to increase if the right measures are not implemented.</p> <p>There are several elements that are not included in the model assumptions. For example, improved forest management is not considered, an alternative that can sequester more carbon. The model is restrictive as it is right now.</p>	<p>Looking at scenarios to 2100 is very uncertain. Analyses proposed at a shorter time range may be more useful, especially to influence policy making in the Amazon region.</p>
<p>Afforestation, agroforestry, sustainable agriculture (emphasis on commercial and sustainable use)</p>	<p>It is necessary to compete with illegal economies. In addition to economic profitability, the concept of well-being in general must be strengthened: security, mental health, health,</p>	<p>Organized and highly lucrative illegal activities (e.g. coca, illegal mining, arms) that may affect the implementation of any strategy, program, technology.</p>	<p>More research is needed to identify co-benefits of these technologies. For example, the Humboldt Institute is going to carry out research to analyze the co-benefits of the palm and</p>	<p>Silvopasture systems should be included as an option in the model. In silvopasture systems, the type of fodder is important. Depending on the species, the system can have a much higher impact on mitigation.</p>	

	<p>benefits for women, quality of life, cultural well-being. Communication campaigns to value welfare, modify aspirations in illegality (e.g., the lack of clear job opportunities in the bioeconomy sector may lead the economically active population to work on illegal sectors, given their economic returns in the very short term)</p> <p>It is necessary to organize value chains to supply markets in a sustainable and competitive way within the framework of the bioeconomy. It is essential to guarantee the profitability of the agroforestry system, taking into account the logistical difficulties in processing, value addition and accessing markets.</p> <p>The European regulation to ban the import of products derived from deforestation is an opportunity for joint action between countries (e.g., EU-Mercosur discussions on a joint agreement).</p>	<p>Low implementation of economic alternatives and value addition from sustainable forest use with minimal connection to markets.</p> <p>Technological barriers, low rural extension and technical assistance for agroforestry systems: shortage of planting material and standardized production systems.</p> <p>Production and economic strategies do not respond to areas with management priorities or threats of deforestation.</p> <p>Low internet access. Large economic and lifestyle gaps between urban and rural population.</p>	<p>rice systems in the Amazonian foothills.</p> <p>These technologies can strengthen the empowerment of women, as they own 30% of the land. It is necessary to improve the official registry and clarify land tenure.</p>	<p>An FAO study has highlighted that forest managed by indigenous communities has a lower level of deforestation than areas without indigenous communities (FAO, 2021).</p>	
<p>Biochar</p>	<p>It is necessary to develop the regulatory framework in the countries of the region, as well as to facilitate the development of markets: supply, demand and prices.</p>	<p>There are no regulations to facilitate the use and demand for biochar in Colombia and in Latin American countries in general.</p>	<p>In terms of cost-efficiency: the ratio of carbon captured per area is very high for Biochar. In addition, it lasts much longer in the soil, the release is slow due to the presence of pre-</p>		

	<p>The best one is biochar from wood, e.g. biochar from Brazil nuts in Peru.</p> <p>The discussion focused on the advantages of biochar. Some cases of research were mentioned and very few cases of implementation.</p> <p>In terms of implementation, the case of CENIPALMA and the palm sector in Colombia's Casanare Department was mentioned. However, there is a lack of market: there is no demand and its benefit beyond fertilisation is not clear.</p> <p>If it is to be scaled up, it requires an industrial size. Biochar with nutrient-dense feedstocks can generate better capture of polluting metals.</p>	<p>Logistical barrier: a stable, clean and separated organic source is needed. Barrier in cities: separation at source.</p> <p>In rural areas, facilities are needed and there is a challenge of scale: each producer has its waste, but there are few of them. It is important to see the system: 1) decentralised, where each farm makes its own biochar, 2) centralised, a large plant where everyone takes their waste and then collects their own biochar.</p>	<p>Columbian soil (known as 'tierra preta' in Spanish or 'terra preta' in Portuguese). The long lifetime of biochar in the soil is where its disruptive component resides.</p>		
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3.2 Regional Engagement

3.2.1 Breakout Group 1

Categories	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question
	Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?	Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?	How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?	Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)	What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?	How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?
Economic Integration and Harmonisation (includes trade, tariffs, standards/certification, carbon markets)	Carbon markets: piloting regional projects to ensure coherence and shared lessons learned. Regulatory framework that enables market-driven initiatives: for example, the Brazilian Emissions Reduction Market (MBRE), determined by the National Climate Change Policy (Law n. 12.187, 2009). The proposal would establish a mandatory emissions trading system (ETS) and could help the country meet its climate targets of reducing emissions by 50% below 2005 levels by 2030 and reaching climate neutrality by 2050.	Afforestation, reforestation, forest management / sustainable forest use, agroforestry	Political commitment Clear regulations Knowledge transfer Taxation - zero VAT for trade in non-timber products Tax benefits on income tax returns for producers of non-timber products Standardisation of rules and tariffs at regional level.	Companies specialised in structuring environmental investments. For example: Terrasos, which focuses on investments for biodiversity conservation. Regional bodies, such as Mercosur, can boost coordinated bioeconomy initiatives. Already successful companies with a bioeconomy portfolio, such as Brazil's Natura. Companies that have adopted PES schemes in their operation and projects, such as Brazil's AmBev.		Platform for market facilitation between countries Priority bioeconomy program in the Amazon region Definition of an economic, market and regulatory management body. For example, Malaysia with its bioeconomy agency.

				<p>Multilateral organisms, such as the Inter-American Development Bank</p> <p>National banks, such as BNDES (Brazilian Development Bank)</p>		
<p>Formal governance mechanisms (bilateral & interregional working groups/coordination bodies, agreements on land, forests etc., pooling of resources [regional funds])</p>	<p>Coordinated action: for instance, the creation of an Intergovernmental Scientific Technical Panel for the Amazon, as proposed in the Belém Declaration by ACTO Member Countries.</p> <p>Specialised funds for the Amazon, such as Norway and Germany's joint fund (called 'Amazon Fund', specific to the Brazilian Amazon)</p>	<p>Afforestation, reforestation, forest management / sustainable forest use, agroforestry</p>		<p>International partners, such as USAID South America Office, and get to know their strategic financing programmes</p> <p>Colombian Ministry of Environment and environmental ministries in other countries</p> <p>Other stakeholders to consider: ACTO, Natura, IADB</p>	<p>Bureaucracy in countries, even for information sharing.</p> <p>Policy short-termism: Changing political agendas change priorities.</p>	<p>Strengthen the role of the private sector in regional integration.</p> <p>Minimise the role of governments, given the high risk of changing agendas and priorities.</p> <p>NBS Brazil Alliance: carbon project developers and companies working together.</p> <p>'Network of networks' that bring together regional trade associations.</p> <p>Take advantage of international cooperation initiatives already taking place in the Amazon (UK, Germany, Norway).</p> <p>Broaden the participation of private and industrial associations in regional for a in the Amazon</p>

<p>Research cooperation & technology transfer (research partnerships, capacity building, networks etc.)</p>	<p>Capacity-building both at the local and regional levels: include rural extension, agroforestry initiatives; connect with countries' public agencies and ministries (e.g., agriculture and environment)</p> <p>Research partnerships/networks between research institutes in Amazon countries</p>	<p>Afforestation, reforestation, forest management / sustainable forest use, agroforestry</p>		<p>Agricultural research institutes, such as EMBRAPA in Brazil, targeting the productivity-focused agricultural sector.</p> <p>AGROSAVIA in Colombia and CIAT, seed development and agricultural productivity.</p> <p>Biodiversity research institutes such as the Humboldt Institute in Colombia: Centre for bio-business.</p> <p>Amazon Regional Observatory of the ACTO: ARO https://oraotca.org/pric/</p>	<p>Low technology transfer. Little rural extension and technical assistance, which are fundamental for cooperation.</p> <p>Research institutes such as CIAT/AGROSAVIA/EMBRAPA should direct their research and technologies towards sustainable practices and crops.</p> <p>Promote dialogue and cooperation between research institutes.</p>	<p>More funding is needed for the Amazon. There is also a need for more technology transfer in the region, cooperation and implementation of LMTs.</p> <p>It is necessary to share experiences of Amazonian management in the countries of the region.</p> <p>It is important to have a platform that allows cooperation and coordination across borders.</p>
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3.2.2 Breakout Group 2

Categories	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question	Prompt/Question
	<p>Which qualifier do you think is useful for LMT adoption? If so, how would a 'stronger' qualifier boost LMT adoption?</p>	<p>Which of the LMTs discussed in session 2 will benefit the most from this qualifier? Reasons why?</p>	<p>How to Implement this qualifier? Can we distinguish between medium and high engagement?</p>	<p>Key actors or institutions to implement this qualifier (note differences across LMTs)</p>	<p>What are the main barriers to strengthen/implementing this qualifier?</p>	<p>How can SHs overcome this barrier? What is needed?</p>
<p>Economic Integration and Harmonisation (includes trade, tariffs, standards/certification, carbon markets)</p>	<p>Ecological - green certifications and good production and harvesting practices for timber and non-timber forest products.</p>	<p>Natural forest management, ecological restoration and reforestation agroforestry.</p>	<p>Leverage ACTO as a generator of standards and best practices, independent platform for funding and support.</p>	<p>Regional and local governments are the biggest protagonists. Decentralisation is fundamental. For example, Brazil's Acre state, which borders</p>	<p>It is necessary to review the Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) of the countries in the region, as they have sometimes had negative effects. In the Peruvian Amazon, pine is</p>	<p>Facilitate the connection of producers with markets.</p> <p>Incentives for associativity.</p>

	<p>The new EU law banning the import of deforestation products from the EU (cattle, cocoa, coffee, palm oil, soya, rubber and timber) was mentioned as an opportunity and entry point to promote LMTs implementation.</p>		<p>Fostering a bioeconomy that generates income for communities from sustainable forest management is fundamental to implementing these technologies. It is necessary to facilitate the entrepreneurial and business environment for products from sustainable wild harvesting and production systems, as well as nature tourism.</p>	<p>Bolivia and Peru, is a global example in forest management.</p> <p>Companies and economic associations that produce and demand agroforestry, timber and non-timber forest products are needed.</p> <p>Improving the relationship between the Ministry of Agriculture (which regulates commercial forest plantations) and the Ministry of Environment (which regulates natural forest) is very important. The forest service in countries should be a merger and blend between the two.</p> <p>Forestry services or forestry agencies should conduct research and not just fulfil management tasks. The national environmental system in Colombia with regional environmental authorities (CARS) is highlighted, which according to the workshop attendees, performs a mix of research and management tasks.</p>	<p>bought from Chile, which generates an imbalance in international trade in the forest area. Trade of native species should be strengthened. Illegal timber trade is responsible for most of the forest damage.</p> <p>There are no strong forestry services in the Amazon countries. In Peru there is a forestry service, but it failed to unify the two sectors and became bureaucratized.</p> <p>Lack of connectivity: logistics, roads, flights between the regions. As a result, not much trade has happened because. Navigability needs to be promoted. There is a drought crisis in the Amazon right now and connectivity needs to be strengthened. Example of riverway: Manta - Manaus.</p> <p>It is essential to promote collective actions: associativity and business work in guilds.</p> <p>It is necessary to encourage marketing so that the producer sells timber and non-timber</p>	<p>Fair trade certificates, sustainable agriculture.</p> <p>Market intelligence and consolidation of value chains: collection centres, transport logistics, infrastructure and access to clients and consumers.</p> <p>Hubs that connect production and markets. Each country should provide market intelligence for timber and non-timber forest products from sustainable use.</p> <p>Develop domestic markets.</p> <p>Promote the legal timber pact (Colombian case).</p>
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					<p>forest products at a good and fair price.</p> <p>There are perverse regulations: it is necessary to prohibit and control according to the species and the danger. There must be a harmony between market trends and the rules that regulate.</p>	
<p>Formal governance mechanisms (bilateral & interregional working groups/coordination bodies, agreements on land, forests etc., pooling of resources [regional funds])</p>	<p>Working group such as the Latin American forestry commission led by FAO (which does not only work on forestry). FAO convenes every 2 years for each continent. Forestry representatives from each country, multilateral, includes Amazonian countries. There should also be working groups on food security and agriculture in this commission (COFLAC).</p> <p>Leticia Pact: emergency plan to halt deforestation. These meetings have also taken place within the framework of ACTO. CAN regional strategy: conservation, access to genetic resources, benefit sharing.</p>	<p>All: natural forest management, harvesting of timber and non-timber forest products, agroforestry, plantations.</p>	<p>There should be a closer relationship between ACTO and multilateral international organisations such as FAO, UNDP, UNEP, among others.</p> <p>The example of other ecosystems, such as high mountain ecosystems, could be followed: a Declaration of Andean mountain ecosystems will be drawn up among the Andean countries (which are also Amazonian) to standardise terms. Andean technical group, an initiative of the chancelleries. This would not be a problem in the Amazon basin.</p>	<p>Chancelleries</p> <p>Local and regional governments</p> <p>Businesses, community associations.</p> <p>Multilateral agencies: IADB, World Bank, CAF ACTO</p> <p>Multilateral organisations</p> <p>An independent actor is IUCN's Latin American regional office in Quito.</p>	<p>Communities can generate obstruction because they do not agree. No participation mechanisms.</p> <p>Escazu Agreement</p>	<p>Prior consultation mechanisms. Formulate long-term public policies, state policies.</p> <p>Efficient follow-up mechanisms. There are no state policies that last.</p> <p>Communicate with the territory: it is necessary to integrate national public policy with territorial and local public policy.</p>

<p>Research cooperation & technology transfer (research partnerships, capacity building, networks etc.)</p>	<p>Create a shared Amazon University with the countries of the region to strengthen research and knowledge transfer in technologies for mitigation, adaptation and conservation of biodiversity. For example, joint alliances such as the CAN University. Having a common Amazonian university can promote sustainability issues in agriculture, forest use, nature tourism, among others.</p>	<p>All: natural forest management, harvesting of timber and non-timber forest products, agroforestry, plantations.</p>	<p>Shared rural extension. Sharing of gene banks such as the Andean Integration System (SAI). Greater support for patents is needed.</p> <p>Sharing information and experiences such as the Brazilian programme "Living Pharmacy" with indigenous communities and women.</p> <p>Amazonian universities summit: ACTO scholarships between universities (like Erasmus) including research institutes, IICA, Sinchi.</p> <p>Exchanges of institutes, congresses. Information sharing, public information.</p> <p>Information flow and gene banks.</p>	<p>Universities and research institutes.</p> <p>In Peru there is the Peruvian Amazon Research Institute.</p> <p>EMBRAPA - Brazil, Agrosavia - Colombia. INPA - Brazil, SINCHI - Colombia.</p> <p>International partners and</p> <p>Ministries of Environment, Agriculture, Trade, Science.</p>	<p>Defining leadership and monitoring mechanisms</p>	<p>Participants mentioned some mechanisms of the Andean Community of Nations (CAN). For example, replicating the Andean Integration System (SAI). A Gene Bank could be created in Latin America. Also, a mechanism to allow the exchange of biological material in Latin America.</p> <p>LACFORGEN is a network. Replicate joint CAN actions, for example, Decision 391 on access to genetic resources.</p>
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3.3 Discussion on Interactions and Linkages

3.3.1 Breakout Group 1

To achieve effective climate action at the regional level, there must be linkages between regional engagement and climate ambition, and in the Amazon basin we find the following:

- Establishing a strong relationship between neighboring countries requires the appropriate internal functioning in each country, unfortunately, Latin American countries still have many unresolved difficulties at the subnational level that jeopardize regional relations. These difficulties are related to logistical problems, governance, establishment of value chains, among others.
- Despite the difficulties, it is imperative to manage regional engagement around climate change. Relationships, goals and common agreements must be developed at the regional level. To this end, it is crucial to align public policies among the countries of the Amazon Basin, aiming at goals and attacking problems specific to the region, such as deforestation and biodiversity loss.
- It is not enough to have policies aligned for an electoral period. One of the great fears of the experts is the temporality and the change of priorities in political agendas. Climate change requires a collaborative effort over an extended period of time, which goes beyond an electoral period and the bureaucracy of governments. Some experts propose limiting the participation of governments to avoid delays due to bureaucratic processes.
- Sharing knowledge, successful experiences and data in a transparent way allows for more forceful and expeditious climate actions, in addition to avoiding previously made mistakes.
- Finally, the experts recognize the effort made by ACTO for the Amazon Summit in 2023, however, they consider that another regional management organization is needed to accelerate regional commitment on regulatory, economic, and intergovernmental relations issues.

3.3.2 Breakout Group 2

The Amazon, due to its geographical condition, has logistical limitations that hinder the implementation and monitoring of climate strategies, conservation and sustainable use of the forest. The high costs of river and air transport, the lack of connectivity and other public services make joint interventions and actions difficult. Illegal economies, based on mining, logging, coca production, wildlife trafficking, among others, are market forces that are transforming the forest and hinder climate and sustainability actions.

On the one hand, within each country, the difficulty of getting to the field, to the territory, is evident and there is lack of implementation of environmental, agricultural or trade policies and strategies. There is disconnection between the national and territorial levels. On the other hand, there are uncoordinated actions between Amazon countries. In spite of all this, there are initiatives at the municipal level for sustainable management and cooperation between territories that are worth highlighting. Participants highlighted that the implementation of LMTs at the local level is much more challenging due to the conditions of the Amazon, which means that effective implementation is not guaranteed in the territory despite national guidelines.

Despite this, ACTO presents an opportunity for integration and joint commitment to reverse forest loss and implement new economies that promote conservation, sustainable use and climate action. To increase ambition in the implementation of LMT, the need for rural extension and technical assistance

mechanisms at the local level with communities and small producers was highlighted. Joint action and regional engagement can help to foster this: common best practices, guidelines, standards were mentioned.

In order to increase ambition in the implementation of LMTs, it is very important to generate forestry and non-timber forest products agencies, which currently do not exist or exist with various drawbacks and needs in some Amazonian countries. Similarly, it is essential to generate markets and facilitate access to them for small producers who are committed to agroforestry, timber and non-timber forest products with sustainable management practices, among other activities compatible with the conservation of the natural forest.

4 Comparison and synthesis

Compares the results across the groups and synthesizes into storylines/narratives that characterize how LMT scaling might develop in future in the region under different conditions and means, as per the different aspects or components (columns of the matrices). The table below shows the options.

Regional Engagement	Baseline	Moderate ambition	High ambition
Current	N/A (taken as input)	<p>Narrative 1: Illegal and unsustainable economies Perverse incentives and illegal economies dominate in the Amazon. These market forces are destroying the natural forest and its capacity to store carbon, generate ecosystem services for the planetary balance, material and non-material contributions to the indigenous and non-indigenous communities that inhabit the region.</p>	<p>Narrative 2: Successful pilots and experiences There are successful pilot experiences of natural forest management and agroforestry systems to recover deforested areas, but they are disjointed and lack sufficient scale. These pilots are not sustained over time and the strategies do not achieve effective forest management and effective mitigation and adaptation actions.</p>
Improved In general, for the selected LMTs moderate and high ambition showed very similar results, there are no major differences. Agroforestry, reforestation - ecological restoration, natural forest management showed almost the same performance.	N/A (taken as input)	<p>Narrative 3: Strengthening governance and funding. financing mechanisms and an effective governance mechanism led by ACTO and adhered to by the countries, an effective exchange of information and knowledge, regulation, and facilitation of the implementation of technologies is expected. This effective exchange is based on technological integration between research institutes with rural extension and technical assistance tools as well as agencies promoting sustainable forest management. Markets that meet the needs of communities are expected to be accessed through organized value chains. Greater commitment and concrete actions are needed in the Amazon for the transition.</p>	<p>Narrative 4: Deforestation in the Amazon has been reduced. Commitment within countries to institutional presence in the region has improved. Command and control Policies are more coordinated with social, environmental and economic policies in the region. Policies promote natural forest economies and economic, financial and science, technology and innovation (STI) instruments are being available to strengthen economic alternatives based on sustainable forest management, including timber, non-</p>

		Governments manage to strengthen their territorial presence and generate regional commitments to reduce vulnerability in the region.	timber forest products and nature tourism. Barriers of land tenure, financing and standardized norms must be resolved, so that private, academic and governmental actors can promote the adoption of LMTs, develop the market and value chains.
High	N/A	Narrative 5: Best practices and innovation: Standards and best practices for natural forest management, agroforestry systems, ecological restoration and forest and non-forest production. Technical assistance targeted at small producers through specialised agencies. Integration and sustainability agreements in the value chain, generation of value-added products to high-value markets, market intelligence for forest and non-forest products.	Narrative 6: Amazon bioeconomy: Deforestation has been controlled and minimised in this scenario. The bioeconomy is the predominant model in the Amazon, based on the sustainable use of the forest for value-added products and services for the food, cosmetics, pharmaceutical and nature tourism industries. LMT such as sustainable management of natural forests, ecological restoration and agroforestry systems predominates.

4.1 Narrative/Storyline A:

Strengthening governance and funding

With financing and effective governance mechanism led by ACTO and adhered to by the countries, exchange of information and knowledge, regulation, and facilitation of the implementation of technologies is expected. This effective exchange is based on technological integration between research institutes with rural extension and technical assistance tools as well as agencies promoting sustainable forest management. Markets that meet the needs of communities are expected to be accessed through organized value chains.

4.2 Narrative/Storyline B:

Deforestation in the Amazon has been reduced. Commitment within countries to institutional presence in the region has improved. Command and control Policies are more coordinated with social, environmental and economic policies in the region and the deforestation in the Amazon has been reduced. Policies promote natural forest economies with financial and science, technology and innovation (STI) instruments that are available to small producers and local enterprises and associations. Economic alternatives based on sustainable forest management, including timber, non-timber forest products and nature tourism are strengthened. Barriers of land tenure, financing and standardized norms are overcome. Private, academic and governmental actors promote the adoption of LMTs and develop markets and value chains.

4.3 Narrative/Storyline C:

Best practices and innovation:

Standards and best practices for natural forest management, agroforestry systems, ecological restoration and forest and non-forest production. Technical assistance targeted at small producers through specialised agencies. Integration and sustainability agreements in the value chain, generation of value-added products to high-value markets, market intelligence for forest and non-forest products.

4.4 Narrative/Storyline D:

Amazon bioeconomy:

Deforestation has been controlled and minimised in this scenario. The bioeconomy is the predominant model in the Amazon, based on the sustainable use of the forest for value-added products and services for the food, cosmetics, pharmaceutical and nature tourism industries. LMT such as sustainable management of natural forests, ecological restoration, biochar and agroforestry systems predominates. The welfare of rural populations has increased. The conservation of biodiversity and its sustainable use is profitable for people and companies, in this way the forest remains standing generating material and non-material benefits.

5 Limitations, Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Limitations of the storyline and simulation approach

- Armed conflicts over illegal economies prevent the institutional framework from reaching the territory. As has been the case in Colombia, state strategies have been mainly military and specific operations against deforestation are not enough to solve the problems (Paz Cardona, 2021).
- Countries do not coordinate command and control policies with instruments that stimulate new economies to generate value-added products from the region's biodiversity. Institutional changes that weaken environmental policies and the necessary coordination between agriculture, trade, science, technology and innovation and the environment in Amazonian countries.
- High costs to create specialized forestry agencies in the Amazon.
- Difficulties in technical and economic integration and cooperation between Amazonian countries that promote nature based solutions and LMTs.

- Difficulties in accessing markets and organizing competitive and sustainable value chains that facilitate economic alternatives and LMTs more attractive to the population. Difficulties to integrate large companies and small-scale producers, indigenous associations around value chains.
- Failures in generating bio economies that match illegal and unsustainable economies.

5.2 Conclusions and Recommendations

Given the importance of the Amazon for the planet and for the countries of South America, climate action in the Amazon is intimately linked to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and the well-being of the rural population. The technologies prioritized in this context are natural forest management, ecological restoration, reforestation with native species, agroforestry systems including the use of non-timber forest products. To achieve the effective implementation of these technologies, the profitability of the system must be ensured with bioeconomies that promote the conservation and sustainable use of the forest.

Currently, the main problem in the Amazon is deforestation, which is increasing and uncontrolled. The cause of deforestation is based on market forces that promote illicit and destructive economies. With the accelerated rate of natural forest loss, Amazonian countries are committed to halting deforestation in a coordinated manner. This goal implies many challenges in terms of policies, incentives, knowledge, cooperation, and funding, among others, within the countries and among them. More coordinated and coherent policies with the Amazonian context are needed. Similarly, more research, technological assistance, and rural extension to promote LMTs, nature-based solutions and more sustainable systems are needed. Finally, market conditions must be guaranteed so that the bioeconomy can emerge through competitive and sustainable value chains.

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7 Any additional information

The agenda that was used is provided here (in Spanish).

ANNEX D7 - REGIONAL-COUNTRY DEFINITIONS

ANNEX D7 – Region/Country definitions

ASEAN countries	East African Community (EAC)	Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO)	EU-27
Cambodia	DR Congo	Bolivia	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Republic of Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden
Laos	Tanzania	Peru	
Malaysia	Kenya	Ecuador	
Philippines	Burundi	Colombia	
Thailand	Rwanda	Brazil	
Vietnam	South Sudan	Venezuela	
Indonesia	Uganda	Guyana	
Brunei		Suriname	
Singapore		French Guyana	
Myanmar			

ANNEX E: BIG COUNTRY REPORTS

ANNEX E1: BRAZIL-BIG COUNTRY REPORT

ANNEX E2: CHINA- BIG COUNTRY REPORT

ANNEX E3: DR CONGO- BIG COUNTRY REPORT

ANNEX E1- BRAZIL-BIG COUNTRY REPORT

BRAZIL'S PATHWAY TOWARDS CLIMATE SUSTAINABILITY: LAND-BASED MITIGATION STRATEGIES IN THE AMAZON BASIN

Brazil is the largest greenhouse gas (GHG) emitter in the Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) region and it is the seventh largest emitter in the world, with a total share of 3.09%. However, its emissions have been decreasing—in 2010, Brazil generated 2.12 GtCO₂ eq, whereas in 2020 emissions dropped to 1.47 GtCO₂ eq. The 2023 update of Brazil's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the Paris Agreement, approved by the Interministerial Committee on Climate Change (CIM) and announced at the Climate Ambition Summit in September 2023, brings the country's climate ambition back to the level of the 2015 First NDC: 1.32 GtCO₂e emission levels (48% reduction) in GHG emissions by 2025; 1.20 GtCO₂e emission levels (53% reduction) in GHGs by 2030 (Política por Inteiro and Talanoa Institute, 2023) (Table 1).

NDC	National Communication	Baseline year	Targets ¹		Difference in relation to NDC, 2015/2016		Difference in relation to 2020 Update		Difference in relation to 2022 Update	
		2005	2025	2030	2025	2030	2025	2030	2025	2030
Original (NDC, 2015/2016)	Close to the Second	2.10	1.3 ² (-37%)	1.2 (-43%)						
First Update (NDC, 2020)	Third	2.84	1.79 (-37%)	1.62 (-43%)	+ 0.49 (increase the emissions, reduce ambition)	+ 0.42 (increase the emissions, reduce ambition)				
Second Update (NDC, 2022)	Fourth	2.56	1.61 (-37%)	1.28 (-50%)	+ 0.31 (increase the emissions, reduce ambition)	+ 0.08 (increase the emissions, reduce ambition)	-0.17	-0.34		
Third Update (NDC, 2023)	Fourth (supposed)	2.56	1.32 ³ (-48%)	1.20 (-53%)	0 (equalizes the emissions, no change of ambition)	0 (equalizes the emissions, no change of ambition)	-0.47	-0.42	-0.29	-0.08

Table 1. Brazil's NDC ambition overtime, source: Política por Inteiro and Talanoa Institute (2023)

The greatest potential for the Brazilian Amazon lies primarily in forest-related LMTs—such as forestation/afforestation, forest restoration, forest conservation, and forest management. Another developed LMT is sustainable agriculture which has been promoted by Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (EMBRAPA) through an effective strategy that the implementation of integrated production systems, known as “integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems” (ICLFS). These systems have demonstrated a positive impact on reducing GHG emissions in the Amazon biome, where carbon capture exceeds emissions. This is particularly significant given the pressures of expanding agriculture and cattle ranching, which often encroach upon the Amazon Biome, especially in the “Arc of Deforestation” area.

The opportunities for the development of LMTs in the Brazilian Amazon are many. One piece of positive news is that reforestation will be implemented on a significant part of the 82 million hectares where the land is net deforested between 1985 and 2020 (Mapbiomas 2021a). Through this action, the national GHG emissions can be reduced by 41% during the 2005-2010 period (de Azevedo and Angelo 2018)—deforestation remains one of the biggest challenges for effective climate mitigation technology in the Brazilian Amazon. Also, the first version of Brazil's NDC to the Paris Agreement aims to restore and reforest 12 million hectares of forests by 2030 (República Federativa do Brasil 2015, República Federativa do Brasil 2020). The law, Payment for Environmental Services (PES) (Law n. 14.119, 13 January 2021), to support financial scheme of LMT development has been enacted and is deemed a key step forward, providing possible sources and routes of funding to make climate change mitigation projects financially viable, especially with the focus on forest conservation combined with best practices in the agriculture sector. As a next step to active the final scheme, In October of 2023, the bill of Brazilian Emissions Reduction Market (MBRE) has been approved by the Senate Environment Committee ultimately based upon the National Climate Change Policy (Law n. 12.187, of

29 December 2009). The Bill proposes the creation of the Brazilian Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading System (SBCE), regulating the environment subject to the GHG emissions limitation regime and the allow the trading of assets concerning GHG emissions reduction or removals. If the bill be approved by the Brazilian Congress, the potential legislative device could have substantial positive implications both within the country and extending to the Amazon region. Furthermore, the upcoming COP 30, to be held in Belém, Brazil in 2025, will be crucial to advance discussions and commitments related to the Amazon. This event presents a unique opportunity to highlight the importance of implementing LMTs and sustainable practices in the Amazon region. It will provide a platform for stakeholders to exchange knowledge and experiences, ultimately contributing to positioning the Amazon region in global climate governance.

However, many contextual challenges are spotted in LMT' development in the Brazilian Amazon, one particular is that necessitating a shift from the perspective of scaling up from national to regional to a grounded scaling-up approach by adapting the LMTs to the local condition. The socio-economic condition in the Amazonian area is more challenging than the other areas with developed economy in Brazil and the key scaling up options in the country is ensuring sustainable sources of income for the Amazonian local communities and indigenous people when developing LMTs. The suggested options include provide technical assistance to produce sustainable forestry product, like how to produce non-timber forest products in the Amazon and technical support in monitoring the performance LMTs at the local level. With the localized development of LMTs, The regional scaling up can be expected as a consequence of the increased exchange of local experiences, generating the technical guidance with experience from local communities integrated.

Note: Additional information regarding the literature review and interviews is available upon request from the author.

ANNEX E2- CHINA- BIG COUNTRY REPORT

Prospects and challenges for land-based climate change mitigation in support of carbon dioxide removal in China

Summary:

Reducing greenhouse gas emissions from land and harnessing land's carbon sequestration potential have not been addressed in China to the same extent as climate mitigation in other sectors such as energy and industry. Where existing land use policies have effects on emissions or carbon sequestration, the majority of examined policies primarily feature indirect indicators or targets related to carbon sequestration. Consequently, the development of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) often occurs by default rather than as a deliberate outcome of policy design, as illustrated in this report. Among land use and ecosystem types, forestry has received the most attention in China for its contribution to carbon sequestration through afforestation, forest management, and forest restoration. This is reflected in the amount of policy documents, including China's nationally determined contribution (NDC), presenting plans, targets and indicators for the forestry sector. The 2022 launch of the Agriculture and Rural Areas Emission Reduction and Carbon Sequestration Implementation Plan demonstrates the intention to address the rising emissions and considerable sequestration potential in the agricultural sector. However, this is a recent development, and detailed indicators and targets on carbon sequestration are yet to be devised. Other currently underexploited opportunities for land carbon sequestration and emission reductions include land use management of grasslands and wetlands, as well as industrial applications such as biochar and bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS); although generally recognized for their carbon sequestration potential, these do not yet appear to be present in the Chinese climate change mitigation policy landscape. Their relevance is likely to increase as the area for wider forest expansion saturates. Increased attention for the emissions and sequestration potential from the land sectors will be necessary on China's decarbonization pathway and journey to reach net-zero by 2060. More focus on these sectors is expected in the future especially after China reaches its carbon peak, currently planned for 2030. This will entail improving policy frameworks, methodologies, incentives schemes, and implementation practices across land sectors. The restart of the China Certified Emission Reduction (CCER) trial scheme in 2023 is an example of an instrument that may further financing and implementation of LMTs, albeit currently largely limited to the forestry sector. While each LMT exhibits distinct advantages and development barriers, a common challenge across many LMTs is the absence of knowledge, technical readiness, and standardized procedures for implementation. Therefore, apart from policy support from the government, there is an opportunity for both domestic and international research institutes to contribute by enhancing capacity and sharing knowledge in this domain. Research is needed, for example, on how to incentivize farmers efficiently through policies with adequate subsidy strategies and support systems with training and technical assistance that facilitate the uptake of LMTs.

Note: Link to access the working paper: <https://www.sei.org/publications/land-climate-mitigation-china/>

ANNEX E3- DR CONGO- BIG COUNTRY REPORT

Policy Review of Congo's Carbon Quest: Opportunities and Challenges in Land-Based mitigation for Resilient climate pathways

Highlights

- Forests and peatland ecosystems provide the largest share of land-based mitigation.
- The policies and measures to protect the climate system against human-induced change must be appropriate for the specific conditions in DRC and should be integrated with national development programmes, considering that economic development is essential for adopting measures to address climate change.
- Promoting sustainable agricultural practices such as conservation agriculture and organic farming reduces emissions from land-use change and improves soil carbon storage.
- Collaboration between government agencies, civil society, the private sector, and the international community is essential to translating mitigation strategies into impactful action.
- Fragmentation and ineffective coordination among government institutions and stakeholders dealing with the different elements of agroforestry, leads to inefficiencies in financial resource use as well as duplication or poor attention to needed efforts.

Introduction

Land based mitigation strategies play a crucial role in building resilient climate pathways in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing the country's resilience to climate change (Mosnier et al. 2014). Endowed with vast rainforests, sprawling savannas, and a myriad of unique ecosystems, Congo faces an increasingly urgent challenge of the impacts of climate change (Inogwabini, (2014). As global temperatures rise and extreme weather events become more frequent, the DRC, like many countries in sub-Saharan Africa, grapples with the urgent need to address the impacts of a warming planet. Yet, within this challenge lies a unique opportunity of harnessing the country's natural assets and taking decisive steps toward building resilient climate pathways (Amani et al. 2022). The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) is a carbon-negative emitter with the capacity to absorb almost two-thirds of Africa's carbon emissions (Schwingshackl et al. 2022). DRC has the second biggest rainforest (Nevins and Heale, 2018). and tropical peatlands on the earth (Biddulph et al. 2021), serving as crucial sites for carbon sequestration and contributing to the reduction of net global carbon emissions.

This policy landscape review document offers a broad assessment of land use-based mitigation strategies, which serve as the cornerstone of the DRC's response to climate change. By implementing measures to decrease the release of greenhouse gases while simultaneously strengthening the nation's ability to cope with the consequences of climate change, these strategies offer a means to address environmental challenges and promote the country's sustainable development. The implementation of land-based mitigation strategies is crucial for the development of resilient climate pathways. These strategies involve the sustainable management of various land resources such as forests, agricultural lands, urban areas, and wetlands (Roe et al. 2021). Sustainable management of these resources effectively mitigates the adverse impacts of climate change (Schwingshackl et al. 2022). In the context of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), characterized by its exceptional biodiversity, expansive forests, and a population heavily reliant on the land for sustenance, the land-based mitigation technologies hold significant importance and practicality.

This document presents a concise overview of the distinct mitigation options that can be utilized in the specific circumstances of the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), emphasizing their capacity to not only reduce emissions but also contribute to wider national development goals. This brief examines the significant impact of sustainable agriculture, conservation of forests, afforestation, reforestation, and integrated landscape management in building a more resilient future for the nation. The brief highlights the importance of collaboration across governmental entities, civil society organizations, the commercial sector, and international stakeholders. It underscores the significance of partnerships, both at the national and international level, in assisting the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) in addressing climate change commitments and attaining its developmental goals. Collaboration between government agencies, civil society, the private sector, and the international community is critical for translating mitigation strategies into effective action.

Note: The full report is available upon request from the author.